

University of Fort Hare

DEPARTMENT OF PHILOSOPHY
FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

East London Campus:

Chris Hanani Building
Private Bag x7426, 45 Church Street
East London, 5201, RSA

Alice (Main) Campus:

New Arts Building
Private Bag x1314, King William's Town Road,
Alice, 5700, RSA

Tel: +27 (0) 43 704 7161 • Email: mmmange@ufh.ac.za

University of Fort Hare
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*Communal Personhood and Temporality:
Tsenay Serequeberhan, Kwasi Wiredu, and Henri Bergson on
Place, Time, and Becoming a Person*

Dr. Justin Sands

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Supervisor: Prof. A. Olivier

To Danelle Fourie

You are my inspiration, support, and the love of my life.

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- 2024** “Kwasi Wiredu’s Empirical Metaphysics: The Political Nature of Becoming and Understanding,” in *Philosophy & Theology: South African Perspectives*, Khegan Delpont, ed. (Eugene: University of Johannesburg Press). ISBN: 978-0-906785-00-3.
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- 2023** “Self-Realizing a Lived Existence in Service of Emancipation: Tsenay Serequeberhan’s Activist Hermeneutics,” *Acta Academia* 55:2, 30-49. <https://doi.org/10.38140/aa.v55i2.7732>.
- 2023** “Where Does Philosophy Begin when Rationality is Denied? Tsenay Serequeberhan’s Concept of a Lived Existence as a Means of Decolonizing Philosophy,” *Philosophy and Social Criticism*, 50:3; 1-12. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/01914537231203552>.
- 2023** “Communal Space, Communal Temporality: Kwasi Wiredu and Henri Bergson in Dialogue,” in *Phenomenology in an African Context: Contributions and Challenges*, Justin Sands, Abraham Olivier, M John Lamola, eds., (Albany: SUNY Press, 2023). ISBN: 9781438494876.

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- 2019** “Hermeneutics, History, and *D’où Parlez Vous?* Paul Ricoeur and Tsenay Serequeberhan on How to Engage African Philosophy from a Western Context.” *South African Journal of Philosophy* 38:4, 371-382, DOI: 10.1080/02580136.2019.1692534.

SUMMARY OF WORK

This work examines the relational nature of becoming a person, a community, and a place. By bringing together Tsenay Serequeberhan, Kwasi Wiredu, and Henri Bergson in conversation, it seeks to explore this relationship's concept of temporality, spatiality, and interpenetrative, relational sense of becoming. In so doing, its main argument is that a human becomes a person by engaging its community over time, and this engagement manifests itself in space. Through these historical-memorial negotiations, these entities transform space into particular places. The outcome of this is that the interplay between person, community, and worldhood is an intersubjective relationship that can be best described as a mutual, co-effected becoming between these entities.

Through its argumentation, this work teases out this thesis' implications and importance to hermeneutic phenomenology. The relational logic between these entities discloses how morally and politically laden the interplay is between persons, communities, and places: how each act and/or engagement between them confers information or meaning that comes with historico-cultural underpinnings which shape each, how each entity is understood and, in the case of persons and communities, how each entity understands itself in relation to other persons and communities.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Tsenay Serequeberhan:

- HAP:** *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy: Horizon and Discourse.* New York: Routledge, 2012.
- OH:** *Our Heritage: The Past in the Present of African-American and African Existence.* Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2000.
- CM:** *Contested Memory: Icons of the Occidental Tradition.* Trenton: Africa World Press, 2007.
- EH:** *Existence and Heritage: Hermeneutic Explorations in African and Continental Philosophy.* Albany: SUNY Press, 2015.

Kwasi Wiredu:

- CUP:** *Cultural Universals and Particulars: An African Perspective.* Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1996.

Henri Bergson:

- CE:** *Creative Evolution.* Translated by Arthur Mitchell. New York: The Modern Library, 1944.
- IM:** *Introduction to Metaphysics.* Translated by T.E. Hume. New York: The Knickerbocker Press, 1918.
- LMC:** *Laughter: An Essay on the Meaning of the Comic.* Translated by Cloudesley Bereton, Fred Rothwell. New York: MacMillan, 1913.
- MM:** *Matter and Memory.* Translated by Nancy Margaret Paul, W. Scott Palmer. New York: Zone Books, 1991.
- TFW:** *Time and Free Will: An Essay on the Immediate Data of Consciousness.* Translated by F.L. Pogson. Mineola: Dover Publications, 2001.
- TSMR:** *The Two Sources of Morality and Religion.* Translated by R. Ashley Audra, Cloudesley Bereton, W. Horsfall Carter. Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame Press, 1977.

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INTRODUCTION

1. Motivations

This book continues the research undertaken after my academic monograph, *Reasoning from Faith: Fundamental Theology in Merold Westphal's Philosophy of Religion*.¹ This previous book primarily focused on the Philosopher of Religion, Merold Westphal, and his approach to 'overcoming' Heidegger's onto-theological critique of metaphysics. Since this book's completion in 2015 (published in 2018), I have begun exploring where and how decolonial and African thought unveils presumptions and misconceptions in the Western philosophical tradition, and how these disclosures may likewise reveal new pathways to understanding and meaning-making.² In so doing, I have also explored how a hermeneutical approach provides an access point for academics from the Western tradition (such as myself) to engage African thought without 'recolonizing' it. Or, in short, how Western academics can engage African thought from an approach that neither dulls the latter's critiques nor disregards its contextual and internal logic, both of which the West often is wont to do. From this, I have found an important intersection between Western and African discourses, particularly within phenomenology, which concerns the nature of personhood and community in relation to our conceptualization of time.

Interestingly, this became not merely a project on understanding the interrelation between personhood, community, and place through spatio-temporality, but also a project on how a given philosophical method or methodology shapes one's findings on these topics/concepts. As such, it was by exploring the lived contextualities within African philosophy and decolonial thought that I found new hermeneutical methods and their methodologies which I believe

¹ Justin Sands, *Reasoning from Faith* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2018).

² See, for example: Justin Sands, "After Onto-Theology: What Lies beyond 'The End of Everything.'" *Religions*, 8:98 (2017), pp.1-24; Justin Sands, "Introducing Cardinal Cardijn's See—Judge—Act as an Interdisciplinary Method to Move Theory into Practice," *Religions*, 9:129 (2018), p. 1-10; Justin Sands, "Beginning with Property? Hegel and Unfolding Freedom in a South African Academic Context." *KOERS—Bulletin for Christian Scholarship*, 8:13 (2017), p. 1-7.

could massively aid philosophical thought, broadly construed and especially within the Western context.³ This work therefore does not directly address philosophical problems *per se*, it rather presents new pathways to configuring the problem(s) at hand and how a different methodological approach may yield better questions and thus better answers.

In other words, this work focuses on the ways in which we view philosophical problems rather than addressing a specific issue or critique, such as onto-theology in my prior theological and philosophy of religion publications. This is a foundational work in the sense that it addresses the core assumptions and how thinkers arrive at those assumptions via their training, historico-cultural background, and presumptions. In what follows I will unpack what I mean by these statements while orienting and setting a trajectory for reading the following work. I will begin by providing some background on how I arrived at my thesis and the question it seeks to answer. Then, I will detail my thesis and my method for arguing it, and why this method matters. Finally, I will give the reader an overview of this present work and my rationale for composing it as I did.

2. Orientations: Reading Serequeberhan, Wiredu, and Bergson

To argue my above thesis, I chose to bring three thinkers into conversation with each other: Tsenay Serequeberhan, Kwasi Wiredu, and Henri Bergson. Each thinker comes from a different discipline: Serequeberhan is a hermeneuticist who focuses on decolonization and hermeneutics in general, Wiredu is an analytically trained philosopher who explores his own Akan heritage's rationality to discover new pathways to understanding empiricism, and Henri Bergson is a psychologically trained philosopher who sought to describe the creative mobility of life and how this energetic mobility functions through engaging the worldhood in which it moves.

Serequeberhan is crucial for this work since his intertwined concepts of a lived existence and heritage provides a hermeneutical tension between understanding and action (i.e., theory and praxis). Within this tension lies a socio-historical reckoning of one's situatedness – the en-framing nature of this situatedness on one's thinking – and the performative aspect of this

³ Note that I use the term 'thought' throughout this Introduction for brevity and to indicate broadly the discourses within the humanities. This includes – but is not limited to – philosophy, theology, literature, anthropology, and sociology.

reckoning. Here, one cannot be individually ‘free’ of this situatedness, one needs to engage their community and its socio-historical (and cultural) contexts to proceed to previously undisclosed horizons of truth and emancipation. In short, one’s concept of truth is related to emancipation through the relationship between the individual’s awareness and the community’s awareness, and how this interpenetrative awarenesses are enacted in and through history.

I engage Kwasi Wiredu because he argues for a sense of personhood that is intimately connected to the concept of community and, from this, both personhood and community are inherently based upon morality and ethics. In short, the becoming of personhood and community is based upon the actions of both the individual and the actions of the individual’s community. This adds a dynamic, malleable character to concepts that are often explored separately.

Bergson’s importance to this conversation stems from his understanding of consciousness’ perception of phenomena and the interplay between spatializing this perception and the temporality born from this perception. This is, in short, the underlying concept of intuition and *duration* within Bergson’s work. In tandem with *duration*, Bergson’s *elan vital* is necessary for this project since it opens this project to engaging placial thinking – or the concept of place with its own contextualized meanings and significances – which also leads toward understanding the relationship between places and persons as well as communities.

Of course, these are oversimplifications of their work – there are scores of books and articles written about different facets of each respective thinker’s philosophy – but it does provide insight into the scope of this present work. Within the following chapters, I will primarily be focusing on the above aspects of each respective thinker, placing them ‘in conversation’ with a corresponding thinker’s ideas to disclose consensus and tensions between them. In doing so, I will show how these conversational relationships give rise to understanding the corresponding relationships within the concept in question: whether it is decolonizing thinking and communitarian personhood (subjectivity and agency), becoming’s epistemological and historico-memorial nature (temporality and the political), or the manifested, memorial nature of placiality (spatiality and its embodiment), each conversation

addresses a key aspect of the relational rationality between a person, their community, and the place in which each evolves or changes.

Note, however, that evolving does not entail ‘progress’ or some positive sense of ‘greater.’ As Bergson states, and as I will detail in the oncoming work, some evolutions do more harm to a species and possibly could lead to extinction.⁴ Although Wiredu will speak about the “intellectual coming of age of our species,” which implies a ‘good’ evolution, he recognizes that it must be guided towards this good lest it become an amalgam of ideologies bent on harming or eliminating ‘others’ to achieve a so-called ‘good.’⁵ Becoming or evolution, then, is an intellectual force and all three thinkers – in some form or another – are seeking to understand this development to enact more emancipatory futures. When they speak of these possibilities, they articulate them as finding new regions of truth or a fusion of horizons (Serequeberhan), finding mutual understanding between persons and communities (Wiredu), or seeking a means to better understand the way in which humanity comports itself to its worldhood and how societies function (Bergson). In all three cases, the notions of ‘better,’ ‘greater,’ or what have you, is not secured. Rather, *it is through understanding how this becoming happens that we are able to form more emancipatory, liberative futures; to find possibilities of flourishing heretofore undisclosed to human reason.*

Furthermore, when I speak of ‘morality’ in the following chapters I do not mean to imply ‘good’ and ‘bad,’ nor ‘virtuous’ and ‘evil.’ Rather, I argue that what I call Wiredu’s ‘moral anthropology’ is one in which each act (and thinking is included as an act) happens within some ‘where’ (i.e., time and one’s historico-cultural situatedness) and some ‘place’ (i.e., space and its sedimentary, political layers) and this has consequences, however benign or unknown. This is what makes a moral act.⁶ Wiredu argues that there are two “cultural universals,” meaning two characteristics which can be found within all human cultures: communication and “the Golden Rule.”⁷ By the ‘Golden Rule,’ Wiredu means some form of mutual respect

⁴ See: Chapter Three, pp. 59-65; Chapter Seven, pp. 164-171; Chapter Eight, pp. 179-185, 191-193, 198-200.

⁵ Kwasi Wiredu, “Identity as an Intellectual Problem,” in *Identity and the Politics of Scholarship in the Study of Religion*, Jose Cabazon and Sheila Greeve Daveny, eds. (Abingdon: Taylor & Francis Group, 2004), p. 224. See: Chapter Three, pp. 60-62; Chapter Nine, pp. 209-211; Chapter Ten, pp. 255-256.

⁶ See: Chapter Two, pp. 30-34, 36-40; Chapter Four, pp. 74-75, 83, 86-90.

⁷ See: Chapter Two, pp. 26, 39-40; Chapter Four, pp. 77-80, Chapter Ten, pp. 246-247. See also: Kwasi Wiredu, “Are There Cultural Universals?,” *This Monist*, (78:1, January 1995), pp. 61-62. See also *CUP*, pp. 56, 109-110; Kwasi Wiredu, “Moral Foundations of an African Culture,” in *Person and Community: Ghanaian Philosophical*

where one treats others as they want to be treated. Since humans are pack animals, they require this cultural universal to survive and, through that survival, they establish particular cultures.⁸ Consequently, and as I will argue later, this Golden Rule is a foundational morality which is conferred between humans via communication and, through this conference, particular articulations of it arise to become an essential aspect of a given culture.

What I have found challenging when writing about Serequeberhan, Wiredu, and Bergson is that many readers are quick to move to their reception – and thus secondary literature – rather than assessing my reading of the author. In peer review for articles written in preparation for this book, I would often get responses such as ‘this reading of Heidegger is flawed, either Serequeberhan or the author has made a mistake, see: Hubert Dreyfus or Rudolph Bernet,’ ‘this is incorrect, as D.A. Masolo reads Wiredu...,’ or ‘why does this author not address Deleuze and Guattari when discussing Bergson?’ Consequently, it is important to note that I have tried to read each author independently from their reception and have read secondary literature mainly to improve my understanding of their ideas. What this means is that my presentation of their work is my own and I only bring in secondary literature to either inform my reading or to discuss where others may disagree with my reading.

This is especially important when reading Serequeberhan, who argues that he is not “...particularly concerned with ‘understanding a thinker [Marx or Heidegger] in his own terms,’ but in exploring certain confluences in their thought ...what we hope to do is to mold and/or shape ‘Our Marx’ and ‘Our Heidegger,’ so as to press them into service in engaging the contemporary African situation.”⁹ In fact, Serequeberhan greatly diverges from others’ reading of Heidegger, as I detail in Chapter One where I give extensive footnotes to the ‘standard’ reading of Heideggerian concepts. I will accordingly do this in every chapter where I describe a given thinker and their specific concept, providing extensive footnotes for secondary literature as well as citations for where I derived my reading of said thinker and

Studies Vol. I, Kwasi Wiredu and Kwame Gyekye, eds. (Washington, DC: The Council for Research in Values and Philosophy, 1992), p. 198.

⁸ *CUP*, 25, 27; Chapter Two, p. 33; Chapter Four, pp. 83-85, 87; Chapter Six, p. 138.

⁹ *EH*, p. 101. Serequeberhan cites from: Martin Heidegger, *What is Called Thinking*, (New York: Harper & Row, 1968), p. 185; and Martin Heidegger, *An Introduction to Metaphysics* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 1977), p. 176.

concept. This also improves the accessibility of the following work, since I imagine that some readers will not be particularly familiar with all three thinkers.

3. Becoming and its Logical Implications

The most critical characteristic of this work is that *it is not a work of African philosophy per se*. I will detail why in the next section. But in short, given my own background as a White American, I do not feel comfortable writing directly within an African philosophical discourse given its fraught history with Western thinkers domesticating and/or silencing African authors. Rather, this work is a product of reading African thinkers and learning from them. As such, it is an *application* of their philosophies and their ideas. In my research, I found that African and decolonial thought addresses similar issues seen within Western philosophies, but the former does so from different perspectives. It often does so while being oppressed by the issue in question and by the Western philosophical ‘solution’ or ‘foundation’ to address said issue. Consequently, I read thinkers like Tsenay Serequeberhan and Kwasi Wiredu on their own terms and conditions while thinking about how their ideas and concepts could prove fruitful to ongoing concerns throughout philosophy and the humanities writ large.

The initial problem I sought to address was the arch-question, ‘*How does a human become a person by engaging its community over time and in a place through their historical-memorial negotiations and grounded in time?*’ This meant that I needed to address the issue of personhood, of the world in which one becomes a person, and the temporality of this becoming. I initially focused on personhood because it holds such importance within African thought and African Traditional Religions.¹⁰ However, after researching this issue it came to me that I needed to focus on how personhood, communities, and places are all becoming interrelatedly between each other.

Consequently, my research changed its focus towards understanding this becoming as such. To coalesce these questions into an approachable focus, I decided to enquire into ‘*How does becoming happen between persons, communities, and places? What is the fundamental nature of this becoming and what are its implications for each entity?*’ By refocusing the

¹⁰ See: Justin Sands, “Transforming the Conversation: What is Liberation and from What is it Liberating Us? A Critical Response to ‘Transforming Encounters and Critical Reflection: African Thought, Critical Theory, and Liberation Theology in Dialogue,’” *Religions*, 9:194 (2018), pp. 1-19.

question on becoming rather than on a single entity such as personhood, I was better able to understand the co-effected relationship between persons, their communities, and the places created by each. As such, I crafted the following baseline thesis:

A human becomes a person by engaging its community over time, and this engagement manifests itself in space and, through their historical-memorial negotiations, they transform this space into particular places. Therefore, the interplay between person, community, and worldhood is an intersubjective relationship that is of a becoming nature (i.e. temporality) which manifests itself (i.e. is spatial) in an enduring communalism that, at its heart, is political (i.e. is interpenetrative).

As I mention throughout the following work, the primary thesis that becoming a person happens through community and place is not necessarily a novel thesis unto itself.¹¹ However, by exploring the political, temporal, and spatial implications of this thesis I argue that we can craft new approaches to hermeneutics, and hermeneutic phenomenology in particular. In short, this thesis presents how a relational logic can possibly better represent the phenomenon of a perceiver's engagement with phenomena (meaning, other perceivers, other organisms, or inanimate objects). Through this different articulation, the hermeneutic phenomenologist may be able to better understand how this perception does not happen in silo, but rather is interrelated with being perceived whilst perceiving, with historico-cultural memories that can be both/either personal or communal, and with the environment in which it is perceived. As such, in my concluding essay to this work I argue that a relational hermeneutic phenomenology is possible and may be a strong pathway toward understanding meaning-making and its co-effected, always already and always ongoing nature.

4. 'D'où Parlez Vous?' and a Hermeneutics of Suspicion

As mentioned above, this is not a work of African philosophy since I do not think it is my place to enter into such discourse *per se*. Rather, it is a reception and application of African and decolonial thought which I think may contribute to several different philosophical discourses

¹¹ See: *Who Is an African? Race, Identity and Destiny in Post-apartheid South Africa*, Roderick R. Hewitt, Chammah J. Kaunda, eds. (Minneapolis: Fortress Academic Press). Note that I use terms like 'thesis,' 'method,' and so forth to maintain clarity. Given that this book has a metaphilosophical bent to it, I thought that doing so would aid the reader in following the book's various curvatures.

ongoing across the globe.¹² My attention to this matter is twofold: a concern about neo-colonizing African thought and an anticipation that my findings may have an impact within hermeneutic phenomenological discourses, especially within the Western context.

Concerning my reticence about inhabiting African discourses, Serequeberhan articulates well my apprehension when he notes that Continental and African philosophy “dialogue at a distance.”¹³ For one, this dialogue is typically asymmetrical; whereas African thinkers engage Western authors and concepts, there are very few Westerners who engage African thinkers. Serequeberhan even points to Levinas, who stated that “Europe, that’s the Bible and the Greeks,” and “everything else in the world must be *included* in this. I do not have any nostalgia for the exotic. For me Europe is central.”¹⁴ Here, you have the paragon 20th century philosopher of alterity demanding that the other must incorporate *itself* into Eurocentric values. It seems little has changed since Kant and Hegel’s beliefs that Africans lack the capability to even do philosophy – and I would add humanities writ large.¹⁵

Adjacent to this asymmetry is the concern of neo-colonization, or “Western Universalism” as Edwin Etieyibo calls it.¹⁶ What he means by this is how African thought is typically viewed from a Western lens and, consequently, the articulation of African ideas and concepts get rendered into a more “hospitable” or favourable Western description.¹⁷ In other words, it is not read in its own context and in its own right; the result of this is that certain ideas and concepts must be shoe horned into Western frameworks such as immanence and transcendence, or what have you, so that they make ‘sense’ to ‘others.’ Not only does this present a distorted reading of the subject in question, it also shaves off important aspects of an African thinker’s argument to adhere it to Western sensibilities. I cover this more

¹² Justin Sands, “Hermeneutics, History, and *d’où parlez vous?* Paul Ricoeur and Tsenay Serequeberhan on How to engage African Philosophy from a Western context,” *South African Journal of Philosophy*, (2019) 38:4, pp. 371-382.

¹³ *EH*, pp. 1, 44.

¹⁴ *EH*, p. 41; he is quoting Emmanuel Levinas from: Florian Rozter, *Conversations with French Philosophers* (New Jersey: Humanities Press, 1995), p. 63. Note that portions of this paragraph come from: Justin Sands, “John D. Caputo and Tsenay Serequeberhan in Conversation: Can A Radical Theologian Be A Lived Existence?” in *Diversity and Exclusion in Religion and Politics*, Whitney Lynn Harper, ed. (Oxfordshire: Routledge, 2026), *forthcoming*.

¹⁵ See: Marcién Towa, “*Propositions sur l’identité culturelle*,” *Présence Africaine*, no. 109, (1st Quarterly 1979), p. 84.

¹⁶ Edwin Etieyibo, “African Philosophy in the Eyes of the West,” *Phronimon*, 17:1 (2016), p. 84-103.

¹⁷ Etieyibo, “African Philosophy in the Eyes of the West,” p. 87.

thoroughly in Chapters One and Four, especially when discussing the critique of ethnophilosophy.¹⁸ For now, though, one can at least see the need for a specific hermeneutical approach to engage thinkers like Serequeberhan and Wiredu without stepping into these pitfalls.

Here, a thinker from a Western context such as myself needs be self-aware of their hermeneutic presumptions. Therefore, the first provisional step that a Western thinker should take when engaging African philosophy is to ask oneself Ricoeur's famous question: '*d'où parlez vous?*' – 'from where do you speak?' Ricoeur called this the standard hermeneutic question because it makes one encounter what comprises one's own context.¹⁹ According to Veldsman, Buitendag, Fourie, and Van Wyk this necessitates a thorough investigation of oneself:

'Where do we speak from?' entails an enquiry the following questions: Who are the 'we' that are doing the teaching and research. In what context(s) are we pursuing our teaching and research endeavours. What are we doing, how do we go about our pursuits, and why are those important to us? The answers to these questions – although not all of them will be addressed explicitly – give flesh (and blood) to the very basic hermeneutical questions: Who is saying what to whom, why, where and when.²⁰

It is a personal inventory and, when done thoroughly, it allows oneself to engage in a more transparent hermeneutics that recognizes its own limitations while also employing a constant suspicion to maintain those limitations. For the present issue at hand, this means that a Western thinker should recognize what their implicit and explicit contexts are, and what they are bringing to their dialogue with African philosophy. The first and foremost contextuality that a Western thinker brings into such a dialogue is a historical and imperial legacy: as Etieyibo argues, even if one is strongly against Western imperialism, they may still perpetuate

¹⁸ See: Chapter One, pp. 17-20; Chapter Three, pp. 66-68; Chapter Four, pp. 165-167; Chapter Ten, p. 262.

¹⁹ Portions of what follows come from: Justin Sands, "Hermeneutics, History, and *d'où parlez vous?* Paul Ricoeur and Tsenay Serequeberhan on How to engage African Philosophy from a Western context," *South African Journal of Philosophy* (2019) 38:4, pp. 371-382.

²⁰ Daniel P. Veldsman; Johan Buitendag; Willem Fourie; Tonya Van Wyk, "Finding an academic voice in post-apartheid South Africa: Systematic Theology at the University of Pretoria," *Verbum et Ecclesia* (2017) 38:4, suppl.2, p. 100.

its legacy through the critiques they employ, the verbiage and terminology that they use, and the framework in which they engage others.²¹

Being open to uncovering and then challenging these presuppositions thus becomes imperative to any dialogical or cross-contextual examination of thinkers such as Senghor, Fanon, or even Temples. In effect, engaging African philosophy through hermeneutics requires casting a double hermeneutics of suspicion: a first wave of suspicion, which comes from the African context, is necessary to uncover one's "Western" or "Eurocentric" contextual approach to the material; then a second wave of suspicion, which comes from the Western context, is necessary to maintain a transparency of one's biases. Yet still, one needs to say something after these suspicious movements, which is why I think bringing Serequeberhan and Ricoeur together in hermeneutical tension can help the phenomenologist recognise that adhering to the limits of their method also entails adhering to the limits of their context.

I find that a possible access point for understanding such a tension resides in the question of hermeneutical authority. Serequeberhan's embrace of Gadamer's effective-historical consciousness, and hence an appreciation of tradition, raises the question of power from the standpoint of both the text and the interpreter. This was Ricoeur's concern and the cause of his "little supplement" or critique of Gadamer. As Richard Kearney puts it:

[W]e are spoken to before we speak; we are posited in tradition before we posit tradition; we are situated before we are free to criticize this situation. Whence Gadamer's conclusion that the Enlightenment claim to neutral, ahistorical judgment, residing above all prejudice, is itself a prejudice. Hermeneutic understanding is auditory understanding: it listens to the truth claims of memory.²²

In short, those from the West need to step back, remember that their position is in a second naiveté, in the mode of as-if, and not only do they need to cast a hermeneutics of suspicion against the texts they read, as Serequeberhan does, but they also need to do so against themselves, as Ricoeur does. In this way, the hermeneutics of suspicion reminds one to be careful when they proclaim what is their historicity or tradition, and for whom it speaks.²³

²¹ Etieyibo, "African Philosophy in the Eyes of the West," p. 91.

²² Richard Kearney, *On Paul Ricoeur: The Owl of Minerva*, (Aldershot: Ashgate, 2004), p. 64.

²³ See: *OH*, pp. ix, 1-3, 37-39, 53-55.

Regarding this critique of tradition and authority, the next movement where I could see a connection between Serequeberhan and Ricoeur is in *Oneself as Another*. All too briefly, Ricoeur's exploration of selfhood and otherness argues that one must recognize that one is another self to others and therefore needs to reflect upon this before engaging with other selves. As he argues, "there needs to be a detour of reflection *by way of analysis*...The revelatory function recognized in *Dasein* not only does not seem to be a substitute for this objectifying detour, it appears to presuppose it or to require it."²⁴

Throughout his work, Ricoeur is fond of arguing that Heidegger's ontology takes the "short route" to understanding selfhood (*Dasein*), sameness and otherness, and being-in-the-world in general. Here, Ricoeur emphasizes self-reflection through hermeneutical detours. This may add a reflection of which source and for whom this source speaks. This is especially important when one considers the heavy emphasis Serequeberhan gives to the political nature of history and, ultimately, of hermeneutics. It may also open a dialogue concerning how he sees a hermeneutical engagement as essential to African liberation, lest this liberation fall into the logical trap highlighted by Fanon's *Wretched of the Earth*, where he locates that the "nationalized bourgeoisie" merely replaced the colonialist authorities after so-called "independence" and thus perpetuated the Eurocentric logic of dominance and power.²⁵

The next step after this personal inventory is to find a way in which one can move forward with the dialogue. I find that employing Paul Ricoeur's concept of a sympathetic imagination is this pathway. For Ricoeur, a sympathetic imagination is where one accepts that they cannot directly inhabit another person's context because they simply cannot shed their own context aside. Through the sympathetic imagination, Ricoeur argues that a descriptive understanding of consciousness requires an act of provisionally adopting the other's point of view. Doing so requires that one must sympathetically re-imagine the other's perspective as close as one can: "one does not 'feel' the motivations and intention of the other in their first naiveté; he 're-feels' them in their neutralized mode, in the mode of 'as-if.' It is in this sense that phenomenology is a re-enactment in sympathetic imagination."²⁶

²⁴ Paul Ricoeur, *Oneself as Another*, K Blamey, trans. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995), pp. 314, 317-318, emphasis Ricoeur's.

²⁵ Frantz Fanon, *The Wretched of the Earth*, Richard Philcox, trans. (New York: Grove Press, 2004), p. 100.

²⁶ Paul Ricoeur, *They Symbolism of Evil* (Boston: Beacon Press, 1972), p. 19.

As a second naiveté, one understands that the sympathetic imagination cannot directly access the other's point of view, that this re-imagining is colored by one's own prejudices and experiences. Furthermore, as Boyd Blundell puts it, "[w]hen reading hermeneutically, the goal is not to be without prejudices, which is impossible, but to be *transparent* about them ... A *hermeneutic* phenomenology recognizes that our presuppositions cannot be bracketed out completely and thus should be made transparent."²⁷

Ricoeur's sympathetic imagination reveals that I, as someone from the Western context, cannot speak on behalf of African peoples, nor can I dictate my findings as theirs. They are my own understandings gathered from my own context. Ricoeur's hermeneutic phenomenology allows someone like me to take on a position of the student, of the learner, whose inquiry into African thought is one of self-discovery. The signs and symbols take on a different perspective with this imagination, giving rise to different contexts of thought. Similarly, this hermeneutical approach may also allow African thinkers to maintain their own narrativity when engaging the West, thereby opening Western philosophy to a sharper critical engagement concerning its historical, violent encounters with African cultures through colonialism.

This is also why my initial focus is opening Western thought to other possibilities rather than merely investigating African philosophy. Therefore, through hermeneutically exploring African philosophy, one can seek to improve their understanding, bringing what they have learned from this encounter back to their own historico-cultural context. Following this, the Western thinker would not be dictating what African philosophy is or should be (i.e., give an internal critique), but would rather present different ideas, concepts, and critiques to their own, Western discourse. This, I find, would be an acceptable pathway to an inter-contextual – or one could say inter-sub-disciplinary – dialogue or conversation. Importantly, this is nothing new and philosophers often take this approach when in dialogue with other disciplines.

This is also why decolonization is another important aspect of this methodological recognition. Decolonial thought readily reminds us of how easy it can be to take the dominant

²⁷ Boyd Blundell, *Paul Ricoeur: Between Theology and Philosophy, Detour and Return* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2004), p. 10; emphasis Blundell's.

position – that of the West or whiteness – in the course of our investigations. I have found that engaging decolonial thinkers continually reminds myself that there is a certain hermeneutical tension that needs to be respected. Even though I cannot deny my own context, I can maintain a transparent vigilance which allows me to preserve the limits of hermeneutics.

Importantly, hermeneutic phenomenology also seeks to maintain a tension between a phenomenological rigor and that of interpretation.²⁸ Thus, there is a difficult balance between description and explanation or prescription. Ideally, one hermeneutically explores texts and symbols to arrive at a descriptive understanding. Whereas an *explanation* involves giving reasons for why something is, thereby taking the position of an advocate or prosecutor. Similarly, *prescription*, akin to ideology critique, involves giving directives to address an issue or problem, thereby speaking on behalf of the other whose perspective the phenomenologist has provisionally adopted. Decolonization often takes up the charge of prescription, but again, those from the Western context can only engage in any sort of prescription from within their own context and its limitations.

As David Kaplan argues, Ricoeur is fond of creating a “‘hermeneutic arc’ between opposites, a metaphor that suggests a mitigated version of mediation.”²⁹ He then details how Ricoeur’s hermeneutics create a mediated tension. Considering interpretation and prescription or ideology critique,³⁰ Kaplan argues that:

[I]n theory...hermeneutics and the critique of ideology are unreconcilable; in practice, the very activity of recovering a tradition within the horizon of anticipated understanding achieves the practical aim of both. Where theoretical mediations are impossible, practical mediations are not.³¹

In *Hermeneutics and the Human Sciences*, Ricoeur nuances the distinction between description and prescription in relation to the distance between the interpreter and the object, arguing that explanation is a “positive component of being for the text” and that it

²⁸ For example, see Richard Kearney’s diacritical hermeneutics: Richard Kearney, “What is Diacritical Hermeneutics?,” *Journal of Applied Hermeneutics* (December 10, 2011), p. 1–14.

²⁹ David Kaplan, “Paul Ricoeur’s Theory of Truth: From Phenomenology to Communicative Action,” in *Between Description and Interpretation: The Hermeneutic Turn in Phenomenology*, A. Wiercinski, ed. (Toronto: Hermeneutic Press, 2005), p. 83.

³⁰ This is particularly regarding Ricoeur’s debates with Habermas.

³¹ Kaplan, “Paul Ricoeur’s Theory of Truth,” p. 90.

“belongs to interpretation.”³² However, in *Oneself as Another*, he still maintains that a descriptive analysis can be possible in so far as one remains transparent about their prejudices when engaging in interpretation; this is what he often refers to as a “middle ground between the descriptive viewpoint” and the “prescriptive viewpoint.”³³

This tension, which mediates between these distinctions, holds two important implications: First, concerning one’s purpose and intentions when engaging African philosophy; Second, how we can place thinkers into dialogue or conversation. Concerning the first implication, a Western thinker’s focus when engaging African thought will be a matter of *descriptive interpretation*, which I find attempts, as best one can, to maintain a position of seeking an understanding by illustrating what one has learned about the issue at hand. A hermeneutics of suspicion helps maintain this descriptive analysis and it further allows one to take up the position of the student, a position of self-discovery. Yet, description can easily pass through to prescription, as we have seen above.

This hermeneutical tension is helpful when critiquing Western normativity, which can restrict Western philosophy’s engagement with other contexts. By placing one’s critical – and hence prescriptive – focus on one’s Western context, one can better engage African philosophy without dictating what it is or what it should be. Furthermore, this tension will help reveal the political and hermeneutical normativity of one’s understandings, which can aid philosophers from all contexts to more precise and accurate descriptions.

Preserving the tensions and limits of Ricoeur’s hermeneutical phenomenology implies that one cannot seek a universal, or foundational, philosophy. Rather, I believe that there is not one. For example, as a white, American male, my own research may conclude that we need to further explore how contemporary African philosophy can be integrated into a particular

³² Paul Ricoeur, *Hermeneutics and the Human Sciences*, J. B. Thompson ed. and trans. (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1981), p. 91.

³³ See: Ricoeur, *Oneself as Another*. In the third and fourth study (or chapters), Ricoeur critiques the semantic difference between description and explanation through questioning the difference between the concepts of “what” and “why” in relation to one’s intention. In the fifth study, Ricoeur (p. 114) proposes thusly: “Once the notion of narrative identity has been confronted with — and has, I believe, emerged victorious from — the puzzles and the paradoxes of personal identity, it will be possible to develop, in a less polemical and more constructive way, the thesis announced early on in the Introduction to this work, namely that narrative theory finds one of its major justifications in the role it plays as a middle ground between the descriptive viewpoint on action, to which we have confined ourselves until now, and the prescriptive viewpoint which will prevail in the studies that follow.”

methodology or discipline such as hermeneutic phenomenology, but if there is any prescription involved in my analysis, or a turn to action *pace* Ricoeur, it will be considerations on where Western philosophy must go to find better understandings.

5. 'In Conversation:' My Methodological Framework

I think that Ricoeur's hermeneutics – and his sympathetic imagination in particular – provides me with an avenue to proceed in arguing my thesis. Yet still, I think that my overall argument needs a structure which allows each author 'to speak' via my second naiveté which is why I employ the 'Conversational Method' to craft the narrative structure of this book. The Conversational Method comes from the Conversational School, which is located at the University of Calabar, Nigeria, with its adherence spread across the African continent. It is born out of the debates concerning so-called 'ethnophilosophy' and 'professional philosophy' within Africa, which we will cover in Chapter One, and the subsequent emerging decolonization movement within philosophy.³⁴ The overriding contextual concern that the Conversational approach takes up is a respect for the means by which African thought originates – such as through an oral culture, proverbs, or sagacity – and the need to systematize or in some way organize African thought into comprehensive and accessible ideas/concepts.³⁵

As such, Jonathan O. Chimakonam, one of the School's founders and advocates, describes the conversational method as:

A rigorous and critical philosophical engagement... on one another's thoughts where the opponent contests and the respondent defends the viability of such thoughts. In African philosophy, conversational philosophy may prioritize the issues concerning Africa. On the whole, it is a rigorous intellectual encounter between two sides called conversationalists; the one called *nwa-nju* or the inquirer who poses critical and confrontational questions to the other on the other's thoughts; and *nwa-nsa* or the responder who attempts to answer such questions either posed to him or to another at all. ... conversational philosophy is not wholly interested in

³⁴ David Attoe; Chukwueloka Simon Uduagwu, "Conversational Thinking as a New Methodological Option for African Philosophy," *Arumaruka: Journal of Conversational Thinking*, 3:1 (2023), pp. 10-13.

³⁵ Jonathan O. Chimakonam, "Conversational Philosophy as a New School of Thought in African Philosophy: A Conversation with Bruce Janz on the Concept of 'Philosophical Space'," *Online Journal of World Philosophies* (2015) 3, pp. 10-19. Note that the term 'conversational philosophy' is borrowed from Richard Rorty, *Philosophy as Cultural Politics* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007).

metaphilosophical questions as such. It is rather interested in substantive questions pertaining to different life-worlds and it engages each question at two levels, namely; at the level of place in which questions are raised and answers sought within the context of designate philosophical place or tradition... and at the level of space in which the concerns of a definite philosophical place or tradition are resonated in the questions and answers of other philosophical traditions ... the latter engenders intercultural and comparative thoughts in which the viability of the thoughts, concepts and methods of some philosophical places are contested and protested. The result of such contestations and protestations opens a new vista into ... the GET [Global Expansion of Thought].³⁶

What this entails is that two thinkers (or conversationalists, the *nwa-nju* and the *nwa-nsa*) engage in a discourse where each poses challenges or arguments to the other, eliciting a response. Through this discourse, each thinker respects the context of the other's while still engaging in their argument. Doing so requires one to both understand their own context (i.e., how to receive and understand the other's argument) and the context of their interlocutor (i.e., the other's context). To my mind, this reflects, but through its own means, Ricoeur's sympathetic imagination. There is a similarity within the Conversational Approach to how Ricoeur recognizes that one cannot engage without one's contextuality and how one must be transparent about this while also trying to 're-feel' or 'imagine' the context of what or whom one is engaging.

The Conversational School employs this method as a means for cross-contextual or comparative philosophical engagement.³⁷ It therefore is an ideal framework for me to bring Serequeberhan, Wiredu, and Bergson into discussion with each other given their disparate backgrounds. Although both may be called 'African philosophers,' it is important to remember that Serequeberhan is Eritrean and trained within continental philosophy, and that Wiredu is Akan (residing largely within Ghana) and is analytically trained. One cannot merely rely on their heritage as a baseline for dialogue, one must respect from where Serequeberhan and Wiredu speak, and how that 'where' shapes the content of their speech.

³⁶ Jonathan O. Chimakonam, Transforming the African philosophical place through conversations: An inquiry into the global expansion of thought (GET). *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 34(4), pp. 463-464.

³⁷ See: Jonathan O. Chimakonam, "Conversationalism as an Emerging Method of Thinking in and Beyond African Philosophy," *Acta Academia* 49:2 (2017), pp. 11-33.

To that end, a comparative philosophy is perpetually happening within African philosophy since there is no univocal tradition or prevailing theme throughout intellectual thought within the continent.³⁸ As a student once told me, “Dr. Sands, we’re African. We’re always thinking in translation!” This student’s jest rings true for two reasons: First, the dominance of colonial languages which are used within African thought; Second, the fact that even the borders of countries are arbitrarily (and colonially) defined with no regard to the culture or peoples within those borders.³⁹ The consequence of these facts is that there is no ‘African philosophy’ in the European sense – such as ‘French Phenomenology’ or ‘German Idealism’ – and it is itself in constant comparative discourses within its own field of intellectual space.⁴⁰

So, on the one hand, a Conversational Method is helpful in bringing contextual authors together in discourse since it is maintaining a vigilance of each author’s contextualities and perspectives. Furthermore, and on the other hand, I find that it is especially vital for this work since it does not strive for a synthesis where each thinker’s ideas as dialectically synthesized into a new idea (or concept). On this front, recalling its emergence out of the ethnophilosophy and professional philosophy debates, a Conversational approach recognizes how dialectical Western thought tends to be, and how this thought presses itself onto other cultures; especially when those cultures are trying to gather their heritage and understand it (but without assimilating it into a univocal ‘thing’ or philosophy).⁴¹

Knowing this, the Conversational approach does not necessarily seek a singular conclusion where one side either ‘wins’ the argument or where both sides are taken up by a third party

³⁸ See: Isaac E. Ukpokolo, ed. *Themes, Issues and Problems in African Philosophy* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017); Edwin Etieyibo, ed. *Method, Substance, and the Future of African Philosophy* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2018).

³⁹ See: Hellen Tilley, *Africa as a Living Laboratory: Empire, Development, and the Problem of Scientific Knowledge, 1870-1950* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2011); Ngũgĩ Wa Thiong’o *Decolonizing the Mind* (Harare: Zimbabwe Publishing House, 1981).

⁴⁰ See: Bruce Janz, *African Philosophy and Enactivist Cognition* (London: Bloomsbury, 2022).

⁴¹ See: Aribia David Attoe and Chukwueloka Simon Uduagwu “Conversational Thinking as a New Methodological Option for African Philosophy,” *Arumaruka: Journal of Conversational Thinking*, 3:1 (2023), pp. 1-24. As they state on page 12: “With the tension building between these two broad methods of doing philosophy, it is only natural that with regards to finding a method of doing African philosophy, one of two things would occur – a continuation of the methodological contestation between the two camps mentioned above [ethnophilosophy and universalist/professional philosophy] with the appearance of yet another method that still prostrates before any of the two camps and/or the cessation of hostilities via the emergence of a new method that addresses most of the overarching concerns of both camps. Such a method would thus become the final conclusion to the dialectical movement we spoke of, serving as the dominant method of contemporary African philosophy and essentialising what African philosophy is about.”

– the author bringing two thinkers into dialogue – to form a new idea or concept. Like Ricoeur’s acceptance of hermeneutic tensions, the Conversational Method seeks to identify consensus and dissensus between conversation partners. Yet it seeks not to dissolve these tensions but rather allows them to resonate against each other upon critical reflection.⁴² Doing so permits a thinker to engage and critically compare different philosophies or ideas/concepts while respecting their differences. For the Conversational School, this provides intellectual discourses with a hermeneutic rigor upon which more authentic, comparative reflections can be made.⁴³

This is crucial for my project since the conversations I present throughout this work disclose different perspectives which I think play off each other. I chose to bring a specific idea from one thinker in conversation with another thinker’s idea, and I chose these thinkers and ideas because I found resonance between them. Note that resonance includes both consensus and dissensus. It is through these resonances that I seek to understand the interplay between personhood, community, and place (or placiality) and how they all ‘become’ through each other. Since I do not think that they assimilate into a mass whole, but rather maintain their own ‘identity,’ I found that using a Conversational Method maintained a sense of rigor while giving a strong framework to engage each entity.

As a method, the Conversational approach thus serves two purposes for this work: First, it allows me to bring disparate authors together to discuss (or critically engage upon) a specific topic; Second, it allows those topics – personhood, community, and place – to be brought together to discuss the interplay between how they co-effect each other. This, I found, was a strongest framework for any study with this scope to be performed.

6. How to Read this Book

When I began writing, to my surprise I discovered how discursive this work became: each chapter seemed ‘to speak’ to another in ways I did not anticipate. To highlight this discovery, I decided to include references to other sections within different chapters so that readers can

⁴² Jonathan O. Chimakonam, “Conversationalism as an Emerging Method of Thinking in and beyond African Philosophy,” pp. 28-30.

⁴³ Fainos Mangena, “The Fallacy of Exclusion and the Promise of Conversational Philosophy in Africa,” in *Essays on Contemporary Issues in Africa*, Jonathan O. Chimakonam; Edwin Etieyibo; Ike Odimegwu, eds. (Cham: Springer, 2022), pp. 57-60.

see the interwoven nature of these ideas as I presented them. In this sense, the work reads as if it has the to-and-fro of an actual conversation: with an idea being discussed at a given moment, then moving to another idea, then returning to the previous idea only to take it up and engage it with a new idea. This may be inconsequential to some, but I thought it worthwhile to point out since the work maintains its focus and rigor while also allowing for recursions to appear throughout the text.

In addition to this, I found that three 'conversations' could be read in any order, and doing so might yield different interpretations of how all three coalesce into a singular work on becoming. Although I do not anticipate nor require readers to perform such an endeavour, it is interesting to note this as a happy surprise or *felix culpa* within the work itself.

More straightforwardly, this text is comprised of three conversations with corresponding authors in discourse with each other. The First Conversation is on the concept of existence and personhood. This conversation focuses on the becoming of a person, specifically on their sense subjectivity, agency, and relationship to their community. The first chapter is on Tsenay Serequeberhan's notion of a 'lived existence' and how this becomes a means for one to recognize the ways in which their thinking is conditioned by their environment; both their physical and cultural surroundings. The second chapter details Wiredu's notions of cultural universals and particulars, emphasizing how they articulate how one becomes a person through community. Here, one becomes a person through engaging others, whereby their sense of 'personhood' is a co-effected relationship between whom one thinks they are and how others receive them. Personhood, for Wiredu, is a dynamic identity that is constantly negotiating its sense of self within and through its engagement of others (and the culture that connects or relates one with others).

Chapters One and Two lead to a conversation between Serequeberhan's lived existence and Wiredu's moral anthropology, which comprises Chapter Three. Within this chapter, I address the issue of the agency and subjectivity of being a lived existence and/or person. This is important to understanding the becoming of personhood and/or a lived existence given that it details the responsibilities laden within both concepts and how that responsibility is enacted through one's community. In so doing, this conversation shows that an individual becomes part of the community in which they live while also becoming a 'themselves,' or a unique

individual with specific traits, interests, and so forth. The key component to this chapter is how responsibility – as articulated through either morality or the activism ‘lived’ through existence – brings the person into the community while that person also presses the community towards new possibilities. Possibilities which may be more emancipatory or liberating.

Chapter Four begins our next Conversation by exploring Wiredu’s ‘empiricism’ and its metaphysics. This is essentially an in-depth reading of Wiredu’s epistemology and how it functions within a communalist framework. Following his Akan heritage, Wiredu argues for a specific kind of empiricism which emphasizes encounter and engagement; without one or the other, then neither a person nor a community can come to an understanding of the concept at hand. Rather, it is through this empirical engagement where either persons or communities reach their understanding about the world. Another interesting component which will be discussed is how this empiricism and its metaphysics eschews any transcendent/immanent paradigm; in accordance with Wiredu’s point that all understanding is spatial, I will highlight the relational logic within this engagement-based epistemology. This leads to Chapter Five, where I critically engage Henri Bergson’s notions of intuition (as it relates to method) and *duration* (as it relates to temporality). Here, I begin to explore the temporal nature of becoming and its relational logic through *duration*. However, rather than a *reportage* of Bergson, I examine whether *duration* can be extrapolated to describe the temporal becoming within a community. I call this a *communal duration*, and I argue that it allows us to understand the politically and morally laden interchanges between persons and communities which happen within time.

This also raises the question of memory’s role in becoming a person and a community, which forms the basis of Conversation Two, Chapter Six. This chapter engages the ways in which becoming ‘happens’ within time and what that entails: namely, that one entity engages another and, through this engagement, they come to realize aspects of the other entity as well as possibly themselves. This engagement can be between a person and community, a community and community, or a person and their general environment. However, here, I focus mainly on the communalist relationship. The essential theme of this Conversation is to explore how time is just as imbued with political and moral effects as the engagement itself: one does not encounter another without their memories of past events (even events that do

not relate to what one is currently encountering) and those memories influence the ways in which one perceives this encounter, engages another through encounter, recollects this encounter, and how this encounter temporally happens.

This leads to Conversation Three, which explores the placiality of these encounters and the relational logic which allows us to designate space into specific places. Importantly, these places are saturated with meaning, which I examine in Chapter Seven through Serequeberhan's reading of Gadamerian prejudice and 'effected-historical consciousness.' This chapter articulates what Serequeberhan calls 'our heritage,' generally meaning what we come to understand as a historico-cultural situatedness. Through his own version of an 'activist hermeneutics,' I detail the ways in which a lived existence seeks a fusion of horizons by critically reappraising their culture and history and, in the process uncovering previously silenced voices or persons from within their culture. In this (re)discovery, one can critically reflect upon one's present culture, as one understands it, and press toward new horizons of possibility disclosed to them by recompositing their culture's history into a heritage. What Serequeberhan's 'heritage' and its activistic hermeneutics emphasizes is the underlying politics of an effected-historical consciousness. It is a process of one's understanding of oneself, one's community, and one's worldhood. A process that is always already political and thus moral since one comes to this ongoing understanding through a relational reckoning of one's historicity and whether that historicity is formed by oneself or pressed onto oneself by others.

In Chapter Eight, I investigate Bergson's notion of the *elan vital* to understand the interrelationship that happens within an environment, or the world at large. Here, my focus is on Bergson's description of evolution as a creative act of survival and how evolution can be understood as a creative interchange of energy within an environment. Furthermore, this describes how engagements with the environment comes with consequences – both for the one engaging and the environment that they engage – which further the relationality of this event. What this establishes is how we come to understand life within a relational logic and how life is constantly reacting to, or enacting upon, environments which become its habitat.

In Conversation Three, I bring Serequeberhan's historicity into conversation with Bergson's *elan vital* by exploring the concept of placiality, or placial thinking. Here, I explore how a space

becomes a place through the engagements which happen within that given area. Places, in short, are spaces which become laden with meaning and which in turn co-effect the persons and communities which engage it, and further layer said space with meaning. As places become ever more saturated with political and historical meanings, whether by humans or by other organisms, they begin to change and thus are likewise co-effected. This Conversation therefore examines how places are manifested and how they are co-related to persons and communities, thereby establishing a relationship (or relational logic) between the three.

This relationship becomes the basis for my final chapter, Chapter Ten, where I bring these conversations in conference with each other. Within this chapter, I review the relational logic which brings these three entities – person, community, and place – together and make engagements (and thus memories, histories, and temporalities) possible. After I detail this, I then explore the implications of my findings by describing the possibility of a relational hermeneutic phenomenology. Throughout all these chapters, I will touch upon how my findings impart insights into what I call a relational hermeneutic phenomenology, but here I describe its mechanics, its possibilities, and possible avenues to further develop it as a method of analysis. In so doing, I bring all three conversations to a pause, and hopefully not to an enclosure, for it is my hope that others take up these conversations – or perhaps present conversations that I have overlooked – in pursuit of better understanding how we, as persons, relate to our communities, to our environments, and how these relationships inform us of our sense of identity.

**CONVERSATION ONE: SEREQUEBERHAN AND WIREDU AND ON
EXISTENCE AND PERSONHOOD**

CHAPTER ONE:
SEREQUEBERHAN'S LIVED EXISTENCE:
WHERE DOES PHILOSOPHY BEGIN WHEN RATIONALITY IS DENIED?

1. Introduction

As mentioned in the Introduction, I use Serequeberhan, Wiredu, and Bergson to argue my primary thesis that a human becomes a person by engaging its community over time, and this engagement manifests itself in space and, through their historical-memorial negotiations, they transform this space into particular places. I do this by arguing that the nature between person, community, and world is an intersubjective relationship that is of a becoming nature (i.e., temporality) which manifests itself (i.e., is spatial) in an enduring communalism that, at its heart, is political (i.e., is interpenetrative). This argument for a politics of becoming, I find, provides a more robust foundation for the future of hermeneutic phenomenology.

To argue these concepts, we first need to know why it matters for philosophy to understand the politics of becoming and how it provides us with a more robust understanding of ourselves, our community, and the worlds built through our personal-communal negotiations. That is, we need to know more exactly what actual problem this thesis addresses and why it is important to philosophy and hermeneutic phenomenology in particular. As such, this chapter will explore Serequeberhan's understanding of 'lived existence' by addressing the question: *Where does philosophy begin, and where should it go, particularly when rationality has been historically denied?*

In broader terms, this chapter will explore how the historical and ongoing struggles of post-colonial Africa reveal questions about how one begins to think through their own self-understanding, recognizing their existence on their own terms. In so doing, it examines the problem of where to even begin philosophizing: where do we start considering personhood

and community when the larger (i.e., Western) philosophical tradition has denied or devastated these essential concepts for many throughout its dominance?

Serequeberhan's movement from interrogating thinking itself to developing the concept of a lived existence provides us a pathway to address this question. What is especially important for us at this juncture is how Serequeberhan appropriates Heidegger's relationship between thinking and being. Through this appropriation, I will argue that Serequeberhan's 'lived existence' emerges from oneself realizing their own existentiality in and through a world saturated with (post)colonial and imperial residues, pre-colonial legacies via traditional beliefs, and the need for Africans to engage a contemporary, globalized world. Afterward, I will then examine how Serequeberhan employs the concept of a lived existence to argue for what he sees as the foundational problem plaguing postcolonial African philosophy: when all these forces collide, where and when does one begin to understand themselves and this world?

Finally, I am not concerned with whether Serequeberhan's appropriations align with extant Heideggerian scholarship. My sole interest is to explore the development of Serequeberhan's concept of a lived existence, what he appropriates from Heidegger, and how this undergirds his larger project. This strategy follows Serequeberhan's approach to engaging European philosophy: "I am not, furthermore, particularly concerned with 'understanding a thinker [Marx or Heidegger] in his own terms,' but in exploring certain confluences in their thought ...what we hope to do is to mold and/or shape 'Our Marx' and 'Our Heidegger,' so as to press them into service in engaging the contemporary African situation."⁴⁴ I want to, in short, see what 'Serequeberhan's Heidegger' looks like and how he employs it.⁴⁵

2. The Historical Denial of Reason and Philosophy

As mentioned above, I argue that the fundamental, persistent question throughout Serequeberhan's writing is best summarized as 'where does philosophy begin and where should it go?' I find that this concern propels Serequeberhan's entire project, and his response

⁴⁴ *EH*, p. 101. Serequeberhan cites from: Martin Heidegger, *What is Called Thinking*, (New York: Harper & Row, 1968), p. 185; and Martin Heidegger, *An Introduction to Metaphysics* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 1977), p. 176.

⁴⁵ I will give extensive references for future research if someone wishes to undertake a comparative-critical critique of his Heidegger scholarship.

to this question reveals the challenges history and temporality present to personhood and community. It is important to remember, though, that Serequeberhan does this as a hermeneuticist and elides from the term ‘phenomenology.’⁴⁶ This will become important as we see how he appropriates Heidegger as shown below.

Historically, one could argue that what we call contemporary ‘African philosophy’ began in the mid-20th century.⁴⁷ However, its emergence has come with existential difficulties concerning what ‘type’ of philosophy it intends to be and what its relationship should be to the West, which has historically rejected even the existence of African reason.⁴⁸ It is a fundamental problem whereby Europeans rejected African rationality to the point that they believed Africans could never attempt to philosophize on their own.⁴⁹ This denial of intellect – and, by extension, this denial of civilization – often reveals itself through Christian missionaries who sought to evangelize the continent. Here, Placide Tempels’ *Bantu Philosophy* (1945) is the exemplar.⁵⁰ Tempels has been the subject of many critiques across decades and disciplines, and Bernard Matolino best summarizes how Tempels perpetuated, and even amplified, the West’s delegitimization of African thought:

Thus, Tempels in keeping with Hume and Levy-Bruhl, actually thinks that Africans are incapable of formulating and maintaining decent thought patterns that are equivalent to Western notions of thought. He concurs with the main claims of the

⁴⁶ Abraham Olivier, “Enframing and Transformation: Serequeberhan’s African Phenomenological Approach,” in *Phenomenology and Organisation Studies*, François-Xavier de Vaujany and Jeremy Aroles and Mar Pérezts, eds., (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2022), p. 537.

⁴⁷ Note that African philosophical thought stretches back to even Egyptian times and the Akan people, for example, developed their own philosophical approaches long before colonialism (as we shall cover via Wiredu). For more, see: Barry Hallen, *A Short History of African Philosophy* (Bloomsbury: Indiana University Press, 2002), and Anke Graness, “Writing the History of Philosophy in Africa: Where to Begin?” *Journal of African Cultural Studies* 28:2, 2016, pp 132-146.

⁴⁸ For a more summative account of the racist attitudes toward African rationality, see: Edwin Etieyibo, “African Philosophy in History, Context, and Contemporary Times,” in *Method, Substance, and the Future of African Philosophy*, Edwin Etieyibo, ed. (London: Palgrave Macmillan), pp. 14-19.

⁴⁹ See: Tsenay Serequeberhan, “The African Anti-Colonial Struggle: An Effort at Reclaiming History,” *Philosophia Africa* 6:1 (2003) pp. 47-58, especially 48-51. This has been well documented, but here are two key focal points: Georg W.F. Hegel, Michael John Petry, trans. *Philosophy of Nature, Part Two of the Encyclopaedia of Philosophical Sciences*, (London: George Allen and Unwin, 1970), p. 393; Georg W. F. Hegel, *Philosophy of History*, J Sibree trans. (Kitchener: Batoche Books, 2001) pp. 55-56, 82-85, 92-93.

⁵⁰ Placide Tempels, *Bantu Philosophy*, Margaret Read and A. Rubbens, trans. (Orlando: HBC Publishing 2010). Furthering my point, Emile Possoz’s “Preface” for the original publication openly reveals this colonial-missionary collaboration: “That is why this present work by the Revd. Fr. Tempels is destined to achieve so much good. It will mark a new epoch in the history of colonisation. Europe will only enhance its prestige by admitting, in the light of Fr. Tempels’ thought, its former ethnological mistakes” (Emile Possoz, “Preface,” in Tempels, *Bantu Philosophy*, p. 15).

naked version of philosophical racialism that the capacity to think is something that was ordained by nature and naturally denied the African.⁵¹

This legacy of denial and its consequences continue to haunt African philosophy (and African theology, for that matter).⁵² Lewis Gordon calls this an “epistemic closure,” which Benedetta Lanfranchi describes as “this idea of reason [which] necessarily forecloses encounters with other historical experiences, and has historically gone hand in hand with the negation of Africans’ and blacks’ humanity on an equal footing with that of western peoples.”⁵³ Serequeberhan, for his part, addresses this Eurocentric denial as a primary issue throughout his work.⁵⁴

This historic denial reveals the stakes in developing an ‘African philosophy.’ Consequently, the question of ‘where does philosophy begin and where should it go’ – or when and where do we begin to philosophize – is deeply political for Serequeberhan and for other African and Africana philosophers. The question itself comes with a contentious, fractured history of the West’s rejection of non-European rationality. Following Ngugi Wa Thiong’o, the question of African reason is a consequence of the colonized mind, the aftermath of a colonialism’s “cultural bomb,” where one’s own concept of self is taken away and replaced with a sense of inferiority and dependence upon the colonizer.⁵⁵ As we shall see below, reclaiming this sense of self becomes foundational to Serequeberhan’s concept of existence.

⁵¹ Bernard Matolino, “Tempel’s Philosophical Racialism,” *South African Journal of Philosophy* 30:3 (2011), p. 340.

⁵² From a contemporary theological perspective, see: Vuyani Vellem, “Un-Thinking the West: The Spirit of Doing Black Theology of Liberation in Decolonial Times,” *HTS Theological Studies* 73:3 (2017), pp. 1-9 but especially pp. 3-6; Pavol Barár, “Mission Amidst Ideologies: Ideology and Hegemony in *The Cape Town Commitment, Together Towards Life, Evangelii Gaudium, and Mission of the Orthodox Church in Today’s World*,” *Exchange* 48 (2019), pp.85-104, especially p. 103; Daryl Balia, ““True Lies””: American Missionary Sayings in South Africa,” *Black Theology*, 5:2 (July 2007), pp. 203-219 but especially p. 216;

⁵³ Lewis R. Gordon, *What Fanon Said. A Philosophical Introduction to His Life and Thought*, (New York: Fordham, 2015) p. 49; Bernadette Lanfranchi, “The Postcolonial Condition and its Possible Futures,” p. 189.

⁵⁴ One of Serequeberhan’s first articles, “The Idea of Colonialism in Hegel’s Philosophy of Right,” *International Philosophical Quarterly*, 29:3, no. 115, 1989, pp. 316-317, meticulously critiques Hegel’s racist employment of Africa to support/argue his concept of history and politics. Also, his critique of Kant’s racism runs throughout his work: Tsenay Serequeberhan, “Eurocentrism in Philosophy: The Case of Immanuel Kant,” *The Philosophical Forum*, 27:4, 1996, 333-356, pp. 301-318. My thesis and scope prevent us from exploring these texts in-depth, but they are great sources which elaborates upon Serequeberhan’s critique of Eurocentric philosophy.

⁵⁵ Ngugi Wa Thiong’o *Decolonizing the Mind: The Politics of Language in African Literature* (Harare, Zimbabwe, 1981), p. 3.

Our question of philosophizing, therefore, raises the problem of ‘*when does one have the agency to appreciate their own rationality?*’ ‘*When does one shed these denials and delusions and begin to think through their own standards of self-determination?*’ For Serequeberhan, this necessitates a historical self-reckoning within philosophy and how it addresses its subject matter.⁵⁶ Though it is quite typical for Western philosophers to say that we begin philosophy *in medias res* (in the midst of things), many use it to merely acknowledge the historical-temporal context of their work, only to quickly move on to whatever they actually want to explore. Within African philosophy, though, this question of where to begin is persistent: ‘it is not just that we are *in medias res*, but within who’s *in medias res*? Who decides when and where we are?’

We will see this as the core of the ‘ethnophilosophy’ and ‘professional philosophy’ debate below.⁵⁷ However, before we get to that issue, we need to see how Serequeberhan builds his hermeneutical framework to rebuke both sides to provide a different philosophical pathway. For him, the issue of ‘where to begin,’ is essential to philosophy and being *in medias res* is not a mere recognition of where we are, but also a necessary condition for realizing and acknowledging the temporality of our own existence. Realizing our own existence, in short, is the core through which we begin to think and, as such, it is also the compass which helps us navigate through our “own historicalness.”⁵⁸

Thus, in what follows, I first will consider the how a lived existence understands itself in relation to the world (via Heidegger) and how this understanding leads to “meditative” thinking and, by extension, to philosophizing. From this approach, Serequeberhan will eventually apply the concept of a lived existence to the African struggle for self-realization. Recognizing how one comes to their own self-understanding – and consequently knowing how to (hermeneutically) direct it – is imperative to discovering when to begin philosophizing, where philosophy should go, and about what one should philosophize.

⁵⁶ Tsenay Serequeberhan, “African Philosophy and the Practice of Resistance, *Journal of Philosophy: A Cross Disciplinary Study* 4:9 (2009), pp. 43-45. For a strong summary of issue, see: Ndumiso Dladla, “Contested Memory: Retrieving the Africanist (Liberatory) Conception of Non-Racialism,” *Theoria* 153, 64:4 (December 2017), pp. 101-103. For more on agency, see: Chapter Three, pp. 47-49, 52-57, 59, 65-69; Chapter Ten, pp. 247-249, 259-261.

⁵⁷ These concerns also are explored throughout the anthology: Abraham Olivier, M. John Lamola, Justin Sands, eds. *African Contributions to Phenomenology* (Albany: SUNY Press, 2023).

⁵⁸ *HAP*, p. 38.

3. Heidegger: From Thinking to Existence

One of Serequeberhan's earliest articles, "Heidegger and Gadamer: Thinking as 'Meditative' and as 'Effective-Historical Consciousness,'" addresses the concerns above through exploring when reflective thought begins for a person, and how that 'when' is the key historical operator for philosophical thinking.⁵⁹ The article reads as a young scholar's critical dialogue between Heidegger's understanding of meditative thinking over and above calculative thinking, and how Gadamer develops this further through his hermeneutics.⁶⁰ In short, there is little shaping of 'our Heidegger' or 'our Gadamer' in this article, but one can see from whence Serequeberhan's shaping begins. In a way, one can see Serequeberhan 'working through' Heidegger in this text, figuring out how Heidegger understands authentic thinking and existence (and where Gadamer surpasses Heidegger). Although Serequeberhan does engage Heidegger in later texts, he often does so in a truncated manner since his is an appropriative application of Heidegger in service to a larger project and never pretends to be a scholarly exegesis of Heidegger.⁶¹

That being said, Serequeberhan's "Heidegger and Gadamer" is solely focused on its titular thinkers. While he eventually sides with Gadamer's critique (and appropriation) of Heidegger at the end of the article, the text clearly shows Heidegger's impact upon Serequeberhan's notion of thinking's relationship to existence. Interestingly, though, Serequeberhan approaches Heidegger through *Discourse on Thinking* and *What is Called Thinking* rather than directly engaging *Being in Time*, which most Heidegger scholars are wont to do. This note will prove its importance once we begin to unpack what Serequeberhan appropriates from Heidegger (and also what he leaves behind).

⁵⁹ Tsenay Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer: Thinking as 'Meditative' and as 'Effective-Historical Consciousness,' *Man and World* 20 (1987), pp. 41-64.

⁶⁰ Serequeberhan draws upon the following texts to form his reading of Heidegger: Martin Heidegger, *What is Called Thinking*; Martin Heidegger, *Discourse on Thinking* (New York: Harper and Row, 1966); Martin Heidegger, *Basic Writings*, Farrell Krell, ed. (New York: Harper & Row, 1977). For Gadamer, Serequeberhan mainly focuses upon three works: Hans-Georg Gadamer, *Reason in the Age of Science* (Cambridge: The MIT Press, 1981); Hans-Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, W. Glenn-Doeppel, trans. (New York: Crossroad Pub. Company, 1982).

⁶¹ For example, in *EH*, written 28 years after "Heidegger and Gadamer," he writes a chapter about Heidegger but this time in dialogue with Marx and Aimé Césaire, and it is primarily about applying the concept of *chosification* (thingification) in relation to the postcolonial situation. He spends most of the dialogue showing how each thinker reinforces this concept/problem (pp. 99-101).

Serequeberhan primarily focuses on the notion that “calculative thought functions within a confined and predetermined area,” an area which has now become dominated by scientific reasoning, where “science in its everyday practice [is] concerned with the application of routinized methods.”⁶² Over and against this form of repetitive scientific-calculative reasoning, Heidegger emphasizes ‘disclosive projection’ whereby ‘meditative thinking’ can occur. Serequeberhan summarizes the connection between the two as “the thinking that actualizes concrete possibilities. The ‘meditative’ resolve is the concrete engagement in which possibilities are possibilized or opened up within the confines of a specific situation.” Continuing, Serequeberhan agrees with Heidegger, stating that what “our modern situation calls for ... [is] to open the space of possibilities [that calculative thought] restricts and dominates.”⁶³ Serequeberhan carries on with his description of Heidegger’s thinking as a critique of the current, scientific-calculative situation in which we find ourselves engaging the world. It is a situation whereby one must be called into questioning the presuppositions upon which we place ourselves within the world, those which occlude us from thinking about the meaning of Being itself and what that entails for our own being.⁶⁴

Serequeberhan’s distinction between calculative and meditative thought will be further explained below. In short, one could say that the distinction between calculative and meditative thinking is that the former is disinterested thinking that races from one aspect of its use of things to the next, while the latter is engaged thinking which reexamines the things themselves. The crucial point, for Serequeberhan, is that genuine thinking requires a deep and ongoing engagement with the issue at hand. One cannot passively stand by and ‘read’ or interpret the world; one must absorb its context and problemata through personal involvement.

One can see this through Serequeberhan’s emphasis on Heideggerian “releasement” (*Gelassenheit*) as a key to meditative thought, which Serequeberhan treats as deeply related to (and almost synonymous with) meditative thought.⁶⁵ Releasement, as it is expressed in this article, is related to meditative thought in that it opens oneself to the possibilities of

⁶² Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer,” p. 43.

⁶³ *Ibid.*, p. 44.

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*, pp. 46-48.

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 45.

thought and/or thinking. Most importantly, for Serequeberhan, is that this process requires action: “it is not a form of passivity” and is a “disposition in which one’s own subjective inclinations are curtailed; the situation (whatever it be) is allowed to unfold and one puts oneself at the *service* of this unfolding.”⁶⁶

In short, releasement, as Serequeberhan understands it, is about seeing beyond the utility of the world. Instead, one must allow the world to be itself and thus open itself up to you. For example, I must let the world open itself to me before I can understand the things within that world as they ‘are’ in and of themselves, rather than seeing what their ‘use value’ is to me or what their scientific-descriptive properties are. As a disposition, this is a ‘letting go’ of the hyper-technological way in which I calculatedly see the world in my everyday life. Afterward I can actively engage the world as it is, in all of its being.

For Serequeberhan, though, this active engagement departs from typical readings of Heidegger: where most see this as a “disinterested reflection,” he emphasizes the active, service-oriented aspect that inspires releasement.⁶⁷ This is perhaps why he maintains a hermeneutic posture rather than a phenomenological one, with the former allowing for a stronger, activist temperament and the latter being focused (at least in its Heideggerian strain) upon descriptive reflection. It also may be why he chooses to engage Heidegger’s concept of Being and being outside of *Being and Time* and Heidegger’s other, more phenomenologically oriented works: within the texts Serequeberhan engages, Heidegger’s emphasis is not on existentiality as such but is on thinking about thinking. Serequeberhan sees the probative value of Heidegger’s reflections to self-realization. Once he moves onto Gadamer, this self-realization becomes embedded in time and history through an ‘effective-historical consciousness,’ and, eventually, embedded through a shared history via the concept of heritage. One of the primary obstacles to this access or openness, for Serequeberhan via Heidegger, is the way in which ‘calculative’ thought forgets or outright ignores the way in which one’s recognition of their own being in the world, and the horizons and regions in which their existence in that world places them, prevents them from truly thinking or

⁶⁶ Ibid., p. 45.

⁶⁷ For a more standard reading of Heidegger’s releasement (*Gelassenheit*), see: Michael Inwood, *A Heidegger Dictionary* (London: Blackwell, 1999), pp. 116-118; I quote from p. 118.

conceptualizing broader than their own line of sight.⁶⁸ This is part and parcel of the everydayness of workaday life and science's routinized methods and calculative thinking.⁶⁹

However, the impression this leaves upon Serequeberhan is what concerns our present purpose. He appreciates how Heidegger's distinction between calculative and meditative thinking (via releasement) "serves to overcome the stringent limitations put on thought."⁷⁰ Looking ahead, Serequeberhan does not outright say that ethno- and professional philosophers are stuck in calculative thought with no access to meditative thinking à la Heidegger. However, as we shall see, his critique of the way each side philosophizes echoes his appreciation of Heidegger's critique of the 'stringent limitations' calculative thought places upon oneself. Briefly, even though he does not use the mechanics and terminology from "Heidegger and Gadamer," his critique of African philosophy *employs* the concepts he explores within it.

Going further and regarding where or when one begins philosophizing, Serequeberhan notes that it begins when one realizes themselves as beings – or more, exactly, realizes their own existential-experiential nature via their actual being, i.e., their *Dasein*. For Serequeberhan, he argues that, after this self-realization, one can begin to actualize their being in the world by opening themselves to and/or through that world.⁷¹ Recall above how he reads Heidegger as a cry for active participation, to put "oneself at the *service* of this unfolding."⁷² Hence, one's self-realization via *Dasein* is also a recognition that their existential-experiential nature is always already ongoing, which furthers through one's engagement with the world.⁷³ *Dasein's*

⁶⁸ Much has been written on Heidegger's critique of calculative thought and its problem for thinking and metaphysics. Resultantly, it would be too unwieldy to unpack it here, so in the text I am only relating it to how it informs Serequeberhan's thinking. For my review of Heidegger's notion of scientific-calculative thinking, see: Justin Sands, "Technical Filmmaking and Scientific Narratives: Has Science Overtaken Fiction in Recent Science Fiction? An Analysis of *Gravity*, *Interstellar*, and *The Martian*." *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 37:1 (2018), pp. 53-65; Justin Sands, "After Onto-Theology: What Lies beyond 'The End of Everything.'" *Religions*, 8:98 (2017), pp.1-24. See also the following texts which cantilever my own reading of Heidegger: For the relationship between existence, presence, and thinking, see: Jussi Backman, *Complicated Presence: Heidegger and the Postmetaphysical Unity of Being* Albany: SUNY Press, 2015) pp. 26-28, 88-90; for ek-sistence, *Dasein*, and thought, see: Miguel De Bestegui, *Thinking with Heidegger* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2003) pp. 5-6, 18-25, 40-46, 73.

⁶⁹ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 44; he restates this problem in *EH*, p. 105.

⁷⁰ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 44.

⁷¹ *Ibid.*, pp. 45-48. See also: Martin Heidegger, *Being and Time*, John Macquarrie & Edward Robinson, trans. (Oxford: Blackwell, 2001), pp. 67, 157-163.

⁷² Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 45.

⁷³ *Ibid.*, p. 46 From reading through his citations for both "Heidegger and Gadamer" and *EH*, I think he mostly gathers this from Heidegger, *Being and Time*, pp., 100, 164-167.

open, meditative engagement presents a world that is more reflexively engaging (and revelatory) than the mechanized and calculative sense of a world that far too often passes as everyday living.⁷⁴

Serequeberhan continues his description of Heidegger's concept of thinking in relation to *Dasein*, noting that "the ontological character of man as the *Da* of *Sein* is such that man is the opening in which the Being of beings is revealed. It is important to note here that, the conception of man as *Dasein* represents Heidegger's attempt to by-pass and go beyond the subject-object dichotomy, which originates in modern philosophy. *Human self-consciousness is thus understood as being immanent in the totality in which it finds itself.*"⁷⁵ *Dasein*, for Serequeberhan, finds itself being-in-the-world and it is this world which one opens oneself to and fully engages.⁷⁶ This engagement reveals new understandings to the thinker about their own existence and their relationship to the world (and those within the world). If one steps back (*Schritt-zurück*) and recognizes their own being within and in relation to the world, then one's openness to this world can provoke a 'disclosure' (*aletheia*) or a revelatory moment where one can have access to truths that were previously obfuscated by the mundanity of everydayness and its calculative thinking.⁷⁷

Here, one can see an appropriation happening: Serequeberhan's reading of Heidegger's notion of thinking leads Serequeberhan to adopt the notion of releasement through meditative thought as a means of disclosing the truth about existence itself. It discloses one's true relationship to the world, how that relationship becomes distorted through calculative thinking, and how this openness to the world discloses a sense of truth that is always already ahead of oneself as the world 'worlds' (or moves on, persists, or continues). However, Serequeberhan also diverges from Heideggerian scholarship, and we can begin to see how this approach to thinking leads him to the compounded notion of a 'lived' 'existence:' 'lived,' here, imparts an active engagement with the world, rather than a modal one. Serequeberhan, contrariwise to typical Heideggerian readings, argues for *transformative* engagements, which opens the world up to oneself, and 'existence' imparts a sense of being in the world in order

⁷⁴ He also briefly covers this in *EH*, p. 109. See also: Heidegger, *Being and Time*, pp. 157-167, 264-269.

⁷⁵ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 47, emphasis mine.

⁷⁶ Serequeberhan also reiterates this, albeit with more focus on authenticity, in *EH*, pp. 106-107.

⁷⁷ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," pp. 48-49. In *EH*, p. 105, Serequeberhan also speaks upon this, albeit with a focus on his concept of lived existence.

to, reflexively and in an activist manner, change the world through what it has disclosed unto oneself. As we change this world, we move closer towards 'truth' and 'authenticity,' terms which Serequeberhan interestingly leaves vague except that they are part of *Dasein's* self-actualizing of all its possibilities.⁷⁸ Recall again, that Serequeberhan never calls himself or says that he is employing a phenomenology, let alone a Heideggerian phenomenology. Here, we see the headwaters of what he takes from Heidegger and, if you will, what he is willing to 'let go.'

Notably, Serequeberhan maintains this view of how thinking unfolds through *Dasein* throughout his career. For instance, in *Existence and Heritage*, he states: "But because *Dasein* is the 'there' of being, or the lived existence in and through which being shows itself, the human situation and the question of being are intimately intertwined in a privileged manner. For *Sein*, always and necessarily, is disclosed only in and through the openness (i.e., the lived actuality of human existence) made possible by human involvement in the world of care and concern." As he continues his description, he notes that this involvement with the world, as seen through an analysis of *Dasein*, "is exclusively focused on human life in its everyday 'concrete' actuation" which necessitates "a reflection on the lived 'average everydayness' of quotidian life."⁷⁹

Returning to "Heidegger and Gadamer," Serequeberhan states that "resolute 'releasement' is the disposition or 'comportment' that allows man to disclose beings in their Being, and hence become the avenue for the coming forth of truth. It is the actualization of the possibilities of human *Dasein*."⁸⁰ As mentioned above, truth, understood as disclosure (*aletheia*), comes forth to one when they begin to understand their own being, again in

⁷⁸ Or at least I find it opaque and obscured by Serequeberhan's ultimate motivations: in this article, to elevate Gadamer over Heidegger; in his *oeuvre*, to emphasize the activist nature of a lived existence. On Pages 46-48 of "Heidegger and Gadamer," Serequeberhan delves into the regionality of disclosure and truth, ultimately deciding that 'moving-into-nearness' [to truth, what is being disclosed] is the indwelling releasement of man (*ek-sistence*) to the 'region' which for Heidegger constitutes philosophic thinking in its proper vocation." This, to me at least, diverges from the typical Heideggerian notion of truth and *aletheia*, given its emphasis on activist participation, which he emphasizes later on through 'ek-sistence' as a means for self-actualization. See: Inwood, *A Heidegger Dictionary*, pp. 13-15

⁷⁹ *EH*, p. 100, 106.

⁸⁰ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 48; He cites "On the Essence of Truth" from Heidegger, *Basic Writings*, p. 129.

relation to Being itself and to being-in-the-world.⁸¹ However, truth is, in many ways, inaccessible and always moving further as the world unfolds, or 'worlds.' For Serequeberhan, this is why one must be an active participant, even though releasement is often understood as 'a letting go.'⁸² Contrariwise, Serequeberhan reads this as a means by which one can actively seek truth through meditative thought by a releasement from the calculative and confining ways in which one engages and describes the world around themselves. It is a disposition, then, rather than a mere practice, meaning that it is a mode of living rather than something someone does. As Serequeberhan states:

[Heidegger] indicates that it is only thus that man approaches or goes 'near to and so at the same time remaining distant from that-which-regions.' This means that by resolute releasement man approaches or approximates 'that-which-regions' where truth abides. Yet man remains at a distance, for the 'region' or expanse is all around us and thus escapes our reach and cannot be definitely grasped. ... The 'nearness' towards which 'meditative' thought 'moves,' however, is like an all encompassing horizon that recedes and presents various vistas and possibilities as one moves on towards it. Understood in this manner, 'meditative' thought or 'releasement' is the situation in which man is utilized by the 'region' for the disclosure of truth. That is to say, 'moving-into-nearness' is the indwelling releasement of man (*ek-sistence*) to the 'region' which for Heidegger constitutes philosophic thinking in its proper vocation.⁸³

These statements are crucial to understanding Serequeberhan's work since he is so reliant upon the notion of existence (often restating it as *ek-sistence*).⁸⁴ To my mind, what appeals to Serequeberhan is twofold: First, that truly deep thinking (i.e., philosophizing) requires engagement with the world. It is not passive. *You* must open yourself to the world as it itself unfolds to you, and, likewise, as you open to your own self-understanding. Second, this form of thinking is not merely thinking itself; it is an *actualized existence*. *You* stand out (*ek-sistence*) from the world around you; *you* are an active agent who resolutely participates in this world despite what may come.

⁸¹ Ibid., p. 48; he cites Heidegger, *Discourse on Thinking*, p. 80-81, 89. Also, disclosure, as Serequeberhan articulates it, is when and where something is revealed to oneself, something closer to truth than others ('the they') may realize.

⁸² See: Michael Inwood, *A Heidegger Dictionary*, pp. 116-118.

⁸³ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 48. Albeit without direct quotations, Serequeberhan states this in relation to Heidegger's *Discourse on Thinking*.

⁸⁴ For example, see *HAP*, p. 20, where he summarizes what we have just explored and uses it to critique the complex problems that an 'African existence' has had for Europe itself – philosophically and politically.

Noteworthy is Serequeberhan's significant response to the question of what it means to be 'authentically rational,' or, moreover, 'authentically human,' at the beginning of *Existence and Heritage*:

As Martin Heidegger has emphatically noted, the root meaning of the word existence – or, as he puts it, *ek-sistence* – is a process of standing out. It is in an ambient – an expanse cleared, as in a forest clearing, by a concrete historical standing out – that encounters occur. Encounters thus always happen in a space, or a clearing, already established by the standing out of a concrete historical *ek-sistence* in which Otherness has been nullified or its encounter has been made possible. *In this sense, true Otherness – the radically Other – is that actuality (or actualities) which does not originate in the shared standing out that makes possible the space of our existence.* The radically Other does not partake of our sociopolitical space of existence, our *Sittlichkeit* or ethical life. This is an Otherness that has not been leveled off, or not completely, into the sameness of what could otherwise possibly be a risky affront to our lived *ek-sistence*, our Otherness. *Thus, being open to encounters, or to an encounter of Otherness, is risky, but could it also be the true, or root, sense of the “authentically human”? Could it be that this openness to what is dicey is a core aspect of what it means to exist, that is, to stand out – to be human?*⁸⁵ (Emphasis mine)

Therefore, for Serequeberhan, there is an essential link between 'authentic' thinking and existence. There is likewise an essential link *within* these ideas concerning agency and active participation.⁸⁶ From my reading, this concept of a lived existence remains consistent throughout his work.⁸⁷ Here, in "Heidegger and Gadamer," we can see him building from Heidegger's thesis about thinking to his own notion of the relationship between 'lived' and 'existence.' Again, it is important (and surprising) that Serequeberhan does this without ever really touching upon Heidegger's reading of existentialism or even the existentials found within *Being and Time*. Rather than take that route – and I attribute this to his appreciation (and eventual appropriation) of Gadamer, which I will discuss in Chapter Seven – Serequeberhan forges an existence which first and foremost questions the nature of thinking itself. Hence, why I chose to frame this chapter through the question of *Where does*

⁸⁵ *EH*, p. 2. Note that Serequeberhan leaves the notion of 'authenticity' rather vague.

⁸⁶ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 49. Summarizing Heidegger, Serequeberhan notes "thinking as 'meditative' is understood as 'moving-into-nearness.' It is the situation in which man is used by the 'region' for the disclosure of truth." Serequeberhan reiterates this notion in *EH*, pp. 105-107, with a stronger emphasis on being with others.

⁸⁷ *OH* is an example of how he employs the same sense of existence, albeit through concept and not explicitly quoting Heidegger. See: *OH*, pp. xii and Chapter 1 (pp.1-13), where Serequeberhan engages Fanon's concept of 'zone de non-être.'

philosophy begin and where should it go, particularly when rationality has been historically denied? This is exactly where Serequeberhan begins his own journey.

As we shall see with the discussion between ethno- and professional philosophy regarding where African philosophy begins, Serequeberhan's notion of existence is essential: it begins when Africans truly (or perhaps 'authentically') recognize their existence within the world. It begins, according to Serequeberhan, when they *stand out* from their concrete historical worldliness and truly begin to think meditatively by actively opening themselves up to their possibilities within their world. This is when they act *not* as passive agents reflecting upon their situation, *but as active thinkers opening themselves up to reflective, meditative encounters which may disclose to them a greater sense of self-understanding of being-in-the-world and their own agency.*

For Serequeberhan, the post-colonial struggle itself is a call for Africans to bring out their own lived existence. 'Lived,' here, is vastly important: Serequeberhan argues that for Africans to fully comprehend (as well as overcome) their colonial past, they must rediscover their pre-colonial traditions but from a resolved, historical (i.e., a 'worldlyhood') disposition while also reckoning with their contemporary, politically fraught circumstances with all its postcolonial residues. Taken as a whole, this is what he calls Africa's heritage, and it becomes a prevailing theme throughout his work and engagement with existence via Heidegger.⁸⁸

It also becomes his critique of Heidegger and why he embraces Gadamer's hermeneutics, especially the concept of 'effective-historical consciousness.'⁸⁹ Heidegger's sense of existence holds a resoluteness to the world itself and to our own deaths. His concept of thinking and/or philosophizing presses one to constantly question their beliefs and their place within the world (or their worldhood). Fair enough. However, Serequeberhan agrees with Gadamer that Heidegger fails to consider that the historicity of that world matters much more than Heidegger acknowledges.⁹⁰ In a sense, Heidegger, like many so-called great thinkers before him, fails to question the world beyond his own Eurocentrism, that he "failed to actualize the

⁸⁸ You can find these sentiments in the Introductions to *HAP* and *EH*, and in his Preface to *OH*, p. ix.

⁸⁹ Throughout his work, Serequeberhan prefers this phrasing rather than *wirkungsgeschichtliches Bewusstsein*, or the English translation "historically-effected consciousness."

⁹⁰ *HAP*, p. 15.

veracity” of where and what a lived existence can and should question.⁹¹ That the world exists and puts *Dasein* into questioning its own existence is one thing; that the world has multivalent histories within which we live and through which we engage others is another:

Thus the hermeneutical effort becomes the site in which tradition is recognized in its autonomy and allowed to disclose itself within the horizon of the present. That is, the 'effective-historical consciousness' (the present as it arises out of tradition) is open to the past (tradition) and what it has to say. This posture allows the 'effective-historical consciousness' to recognize its own limitations, that is, its historicity and finitude. In this recognition the past is heard, understood and appropriated.⁹²

I will delve further into Serequeberhan’s critique of Heidegger in the concluding section of this chapter. For now, though, what is important to us is that we see the initial, theoretical-existential underpinning of Serequeberhan’s hermeneutic project: an active, engaging lived existence that opens itself to the world. An *ek-sistence* that stands out by actively participating in that world. In the next section, I will explore how one does this through both theirs and the world’s historicity. As we shall see, a lived existence goes hand-in-hand with one’s heritage, and engaging that heritage is from whence we begin to philosophize.

4. Missing the Point: Lived Existence Over and Against Ethno- and Professional Philosophy

Consider Serequeberhan’s *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy* (1994) as a case study where he employs this sense of existence. In sum, the book argues that both the so-called ethnophilosophers and professional philosophers are missing the point: their debate over which direction African philosophy should take fails to understand what it means to do philosophy on one’s own terms. Relating back to ‘when and where do we begin to philosophize,’ Serequeberhan finds that both sides lack a basic self-understanding of their project.⁹³ Moreover, and in opposing ways but arriving at the same place, they merely embody the Eurocentric ideals placed upon them.

As a case study, we should gather a stronger understanding of the debate between ethno- and professional philosophy and why it was (and sometimes still is) problematic to both

⁹¹ HAP, p. 4 See also: Olivier, “Enframing and Transformation: Reflections on Serequeberhan and Heidegger,” p. 548.

⁹² Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer,” p. 53.

⁹³ HAP, p. 32.

philosophy and the progress of the African intellectual tradition. After the publication of Tempels' *Bantu Philosophy* and, many would argue, John Mbiti's *African Religions and Philosophy* (1969), critics began questioning how African thought – its traditions, its rationalities, its cultures – were represented within academia.

Looking back on this era, Serequeberhan notes that these types of works seemingly tried to form a means by which one could recover African traditions in the wake of colonialism.⁹⁴ However, these recoveries only critically engage these traditions from a Western context, nor do they interrogate how these traditions could help serve the problems arising from post-colonialism. Rather, many focus on 'civilizing' Africans; meaning, rendering them more European, or at least viewed more favorably by Europeans. Indeed, several texts read like they were intended for – and to the advantage of – a Western audience and not actually written for Africans⁹⁵ For example, in *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy*, Serequeberhan devotes a strong portion of the book critiquing movements such as Leopold Senghor's *Négritude*, stating, "what does Senghor achieve from this model? He simply takes negative Eurocentric descriptions and presents them as positive Negrocentric manifestations of an ontological difference in and for the being of the Negro-African."⁹⁶ Serequeberhan later strengthens his critique against Senghor's *Négritude* and *Africanité*, noting that "Senghor's *Africanité* is a re-inscription of racist myths. ... Senghor constructs the being of the Negro out of what Europe belittles and rejects as inferior and defective. ... Senghor accepts, authenticates, and celebrates this inferiority."⁹⁷

This dispute raged on before Serequeberhan's time, and it especially came to a head with Paulin Hountondji's book, *African Philosophy: Myth and Reality* (1976). Hountondji was the first to dismissively label these prior approaches to African thought as "ethnophilosophy," arguing that it essentially works against the interests of Africans (note the sarcasm expressed throughout):

⁹⁴ HAP, pp. 2-3.

⁹⁵ Ngugi Wa Thiong'o has a similar critique against African literature, which he at times calls an "Afro-European" literary tradition, see: Ngugi, *Decolonizing the Mind*, pp. 5, 22, 26, 69-71. So also, Masolo in the first two chapters of *Self and Community in a Changing World*.

⁹⁶ HAP, p. 47.

⁹⁷ Tsenay, Serequeberhan, "The African Anti-Colonial Struggle: An Effort at Reclaiming History," pp. 50.

What does that mean in this context? Simply that contemporary African philosophy, inasmuch as it remains an ethnophilosophy, has been built up essentially *for a European public*. The African ethnophilosopher's discourse is not intended for Africans. It has not been produced for their benefit, and its authors understood that it would be challenged, if at all, not by Africans but by Europe alone. Unless, of course, the West expressed itself through Africans, as it knows so well how to do. In short, the African ethnophilosopher made himself the spokesman of All-Africa facing All-Europe at the imaginary rendezvous of give and take — from which we observe that 'Africanist' particularism goes hand in glove, *objectively*, with an abstract universalism, since the African intellectual who adopts it thereby expounds it, over the heads of his own people, in a mythical dialogue with his European colleagues, for the constitution of a 'civilization of the universal.'⁹⁸ (Emphasis Hountondji's)

In response, Hountondji proposed a different kind of a rigor, "professional philosophy," which hewed closer to the rational and foundational grounds one sees within 'traditional' or 'typical' philosophy.⁹⁹ That is, a philosophy which concerns itself with established issues of ontology, epistemology, etc., and approaches these concerns through an established, rationally comprehensive framework. Thus, for roughly 60 years (and some would say its legacy remains), African philosophy was couched between two opposing charges from within; some thinkers were charged with doing ethnophilosophy and, on the other side, others were charged with doing professional philosophy, which has Eurocentric problems of its own.¹⁰⁰ Professional philosophy, namely, gathers both its methodologies and its series of questions/issues from the West: ontology, for example, is often employed as a Western term, with Western assumptions, and with Western problemata attached to it. Thus, there is the question of what hidden, Western presuppositions professional philosophers tacitly accept when they go about their philosophical work. What gets assumed (or subsumed) within professional philosophy?

Serequeberhan argues that these questions reveal how professional philosophy also has an abstract universalism within its operation. He contends that professional philosophers act as

⁹⁸ Paulin Hountondji, *African Philosophy: Myth and Reality*, Henri Evans, trans. (Bloomington: Indiana UP, 1996) p. 45; see also: pp. 8-10.

⁹⁹ Hountondji, *African Philosophy: Myth and Reality*, pp. 8-10; Hountondji unpacks the meaning of this term throughout the book.

¹⁰⁰ Barry Hallen, "The Journey of African Philosophy" in *Method, Substance, and the Future of African Philosophy*, Edwin Etieyibo, ed. (London: Palgrave Macmillan), pp. 36-48. See also: Etieyibo, "African Philosophy in History, Context, and Contemporary Times," p. 20.

if “African philosophy is merely a ‘geographic designation’” where they can ignore the issues within Africa and can continue with their next commentary on whichever famous philosopher they favor.¹⁰¹ In short, for Serequeberhan, a professional philosopher only cares about Western philosophical issues – those ‘philosophically legitimate’ questions – and would rather sidestep the historical and intellectual denial of African rationality.

Rather than prove Eurocentric philosophers wrong about Africa’s so-called inability to do rational and philosophical thinking on African terms, the professional philosopher (perhaps subconsciously) accepts this Eurocentrism within their projects. Concerning professional philosophy’s adoption of Marxist thought, Serequeberhan was especially critical of how it adopted certain metaphysical presumptions.¹⁰² For example, Serequeberhan finds that Kwame Nkrumah’s use of Marxism “implicitly universalizes and surreptitiously – without even the semblance of an argument – assumes the historical ground of European modernity: that the ground of ‘scientific socialism’ is the universal ground on which and out of which economic questions *as such* are posed. Thus, the specific particularity of the African situation is relegated to oblivion.”¹⁰³ Going even further by commenting upon Hountondji’s approval and adoption of Nkrumah’s Marxism-Leninism, Serequeberhan arrives at the heart of the obliterated relegation:

[This] is nothing more than a futile attempt to square the proverbial circle, since to subscribe to Marx’s thought understood as “scientific socialism” or Marxism-Leninism, one necessarily subscribes to an evolutionary developmental metaphysics of history – historical materialism – that places Africa at the lowest rung of an evolutionary ladder of development and which fulfills its ‘objective’ and singular ‘human’ *telos* in the historic eventuation of European modernity. ¶ In such a perspective – given the metaphysical structure and logic of the discourse – one necessarily (good intentions notwithstanding!) subordinates Africa to Europe and ‘solves’ African problems by imposing European developmental ‘formulas,’ contrived and generated out of the singular historic experience of European modernity.¹⁰⁴

Serequeberhan spends much of *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy* critiquing both sides of the debate. His conclusion to these critiques is that both sides “share, in contrary ways, a

¹⁰¹ HAP, p. 12.

¹⁰² He especially focuses on Kwame Nkrumah in addition to Hountondji, see: HAP, p. 103.

¹⁰³ HAP, p. 34

¹⁰⁴ HAP, p 39.

dilapidating Eurocentric metaphysics.”¹⁰⁵ From this conclusion, though, he argues that the way to break this impasse is through a hermeneutics that recognizes its own existence and effective-historical consciousness.

Sticking with our focus on his sense of lived existence, though, Serequeberhan summarily finds the entire debate inauthentic – inauthentic to Africa and its heritage and inauthentic to philosophy – because each side has failed to understand their own existence on their own terms.¹⁰⁶ This is essentially the theme of the latter half of *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy* and it is carried on, in extensive detail, in both *Our Heritage* and *Existence and Heritage*. Throughout, Serequeberhan is especially critical of the ways in which postcolonial nations emerged out of colonialism only to become objects (or, subjugates) to their former colonizers.¹⁰⁷ Though placed in a precarious and nigh impossible situation by their colonizers, many postcolonial leaders lacked a fundamental understanding of *their own* existence and *their own* history through *their own* terms.¹⁰⁸ Consequently, this maintained the colonial apparatus that ensnared them into a system in which “the formerly colonized were *thingified*.”¹⁰⁹

Thingified, here, refers to the postcolonial position within the wider Eurocentric, globalized socio-economic system.¹¹⁰ I find, though, that it also correlates to Serequeberhan’s rejection of how the African philosophical debate was conducted: each side failed to philosophize on their own terms because they failed to recognize and understand their own lived existence. They are merely cogs within the larger, Eurocentric philosophical machine. Throughout his entire career, Serequeberhan employs the concept of a lived existence to articulate a way for

¹⁰⁵ HAP, p. 32.

¹⁰⁶ EH, pp. 92-93, 105-110.

¹⁰⁷ Even though most (if not all) the chapters in *OH* explore this theme in some way, see especially, pp. 53-58. For Serequeberhan’s critique of the inauthentic nature of these types of philosophizing, see: EH, pp. 91-93, 101-106.

¹⁰⁸ HAP, pp. 8-10, 82-89, 106-110.

¹⁰⁹ EH, pp. 99-101, 113. Though exploring this is beyond our scope, it is fascinating to see how Fanon is interwoven within these concepts. Clearly, Fanon influenced Serequeberhan, but there are specific aspects where they diverge. For me, this happens where Serequeberhan’s lived existence diverges from Fanon’s Sartrean-influenced existentialism and its ‘facticity’ of being Black, especially within *Black Skin, White Masks* Charles Lam Markmann, trans. (London: Pluto Press, 2008). For more, see: “Conclusion: Frantz Fanon, Thinking as Openness,” in EH, pp. 117-122.

¹¹⁰ Again, this critique runs throughout HAP. Also, it is a primary issue addressed in EH, specifically his critique against Levinas’ failure to legitimize the intellectual contributions of non-Europeans; seeing them as “all the rest,” pp. 39-50. It is furthermore essential within Serequeberhan’s reading of Frantz Fanon, as seen in OH, pp. 1-13. See: Chapter One, p. 7; Chapter Three, p. 56; Chapter Seven, pp. 166-168.

Africans (and others) to emerge out of these entrapments. This is clearly seen in his preface to *Our Heritage*:

Existence is always actualized in a specific and concrete heritage. ... Based on this we can say that that which exists is that which stands forth. A heritage, then, is the sedimented layering over time that is, the life of a community – of the actuality of existence, which in ‘standing forth’ does so necessarily in specific and determined ways and thus constitutes a heritage, a certain way of ‘being-in-the-world.’ And yet, to this day, most European thinkers write as if their heritage – the way their existence stands forth in being – is, for all that matters, coequal to existence as such! ¶ This book is an attempt to bypass this constricted view and think of the actuality of black existence – African American and African – in terms of a limited number of seminal questions and figures that have marked the character of our heritage, that is, the actuality of our ‘standing forth.’¹¹¹

One of the ways Serequeberhan prefers to show the importance of a lived existence to philosophy is by illustrating its meaning through those whose stories exemplify such an existence through their participation in the struggle for liberation. For example, in Chapter Four of *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy*, “The Liberation Struggle, Existence and Historicity,” he explores figures like Fanon, amongst others, who embody the concept of a lived existence through their intellectual pursuits and their struggle for liberation.¹¹² Serequeberhan’s exploration of these thinkers’ narratives runs throughout all of his works (for example, it is the primary theme of *Our Heritage*) and therefore it would be unmanageable to cover them all. I have therefore decided to explore the ways in which these narratives function as a concept within his philosophy rather than to detail how he reads each thinker.¹¹³

5. Final Analysis: Emerging Into A Lived Existence

Let us briefly step back by returning to our question, ‘Where does philosophy begin, and where should it go?’ For Serequeberhan, following Heidegger, beginning to philosophize requires two things: First, concerning engaging the world, one cannot be passive but must actively open themselves to the world and what it opens to them. The world must be able to ‘come’ to them as they open themselves to the world as it is. This is a necessary condition for

¹¹¹ *OH*, p. ix.

¹¹² *HAP*, pp. 87-116; *OH*, p. xiii.

¹¹³ See, for example: *HAP*, pp. 52, 57, 64-69, 74, 80-90, 99-102, 105-112. See also: Chapter Seven, 160-163.

meditative thought, a releasement from the somnambulist thinking that happens in everyday, calculative ponderance.

Second, this engagement is not merely a thought exercise but is part-and-parcel of an *actualized existence*. If I may condense two Heideggerian ideas, authentically thinking is integrated into ‘authentic being:’ actively thinking in a search for truth to disclose itself is integral to an authentic existence, and vice versa. As Serequeberhan reiterates often that a lived existence is one in which someone stands out (*ek-sistence*) from the everydayness of the world in which one finds themselves and, as such, one is an active agent who resolutely participates in this world in spite of what may come. Philosophy begins when one realizes their own being in relation to Being itself, which opens themselves to the possibility of truth, that is, the possibility of the disclosure of self-realization. Philosophy should go in search of this truth by actively engaging the world in which one finds oneself. Therefore, liberation/emancipation emerges through self-realization and actively engaging the world.¹¹⁴

Yet notice how quickly Serequeberhan moves from Heideggerian terminology – *Dasein*, releasement, meditative thought, etc. – toward the term lived existence. With a few exceptions, the only text in which Serequeberhan fully unpacks the Heideggerian mechanics behind lived existence are in “Heidegger and Gadamer,” one of his earliest articles. Consequently, I find that, although he is clearly indebted to Heidegger, the concept of a lived existence is Serequeberhan’s own. Though it carries a seed of Heideggerian thought within it – and Serequeberhan is quick to note this when introducing the concept – he employs it within his philosophy as a term that moves beyond Heidegger’s original ideas, and he does so in ways that more clearly connect with an effective-historical consciousness.

Accordingly, I will close our examination of Serequeberhan’s lived existence by emphasizing this appropriation and how it gains its own meaning and philosophical conceptualization. What is essential here is noticing this is the foundation of Serequeberhan’s hermeneutics. Hermeneutics begins as an active, engaging lived existence which opens itself to the world first through reflective, meditative thought. Though it speaks of existence, it is not an existentialism. Rather, it is an *ek-sistence* which stands out and actively engages that world,

¹¹⁴ OH, p. 74-76.

and does so through a process by which one can see the world as it is, that is, it allows a person to see things unto themselves, and it is from this realization that one can truly participate in changing that world. And again, he typically demonstrates this through exploring key African thinkers' historicity alongside (or in contrast to) their world's historicity.¹¹⁵

Serequeberhan adapts these narratives into a lived existence by noting that each thinker employs their own effective-historical consciousness to engage these histories, and that also of a larger, collective heritage.¹¹⁶ A lived existence goes hand-in-hand with one's history and one's heritage, and engaging that heritage is from whence one begins to philosophize. Serequeberhan makes this abundantly clear in the conclusion to *Our Heritage* when he states: "For human existence is always – and necessarily – actualized within the lived heritage of a specific tradition." He continues, stating that "it is in struggle – out of this recognition – that the imperious proclivities of European expansion have been curtailed. And in this process the formerly enslaved and colonized have carved out for themselves a human heritage."¹¹⁷

Importantly, Serequeberhan can only get so far with Heidegger; he can rely upon Heidegger for this notion of an active, self-aware (*Dasein*-like) existence, but the 'lived' part – with its horizontal infusion of histories – is problematic for Heidegger. Again, returning to "Heidegger and Gadamer," Serequeberhan spends just one section unpacking Heidegger's thinking as the rest of the text moves through Gadamer's improvement upon Heidegger. For example, in its closing section, Serequeberhan states that "Gadamer eloquently presents and makes more comprehensible the philosophic insights articulated by Heidegger."¹¹⁸ However, he also thinks that Gadamer "tames" or "domesticates" Heidegger's "concept of thought as "meditative."¹¹⁹ Recall from our review of thinking above that Serequeberhan appreciates the "'power of action and resolve' [that] are constitutive of 'meditative' thought."¹²⁰ Remember that, for Serequeberhan, thinking is not passive; it has to have an active engagement with the world. One cannot passively stand by and 'read' or interpret the world; one must absorb its

¹¹⁵ See: Serequeberhan, "The African Anti-Colonial Struggle;" as mentioned before, it is the primary theme of *OH* and this historical-narrative retrieval, particularly revolving around struggle, runs throughout his *oeuvre*.

¹¹⁶ *EH*, pp. 83-87, 94-96.

¹¹⁷ *OH*, pp. 74-75.

¹¹⁸ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 59.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 59.

¹²⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 61.

context and problemata. Resolving this ‘gap,’ as it were, between Heidegger’s ‘existence’ and Gadamer’s ‘historicity’ is where Serequeberhan finds a means to establish his concept of a lived existence.

Returning to Serequeberhan’s bold statement that we should “mold and/or shape ‘Our Marx and ‘Our Heidegger,’ so as to press them into service,” I think ‘Serequeberhan’s Heidegger’ is pressed in service to understand how an African philosophy is possible, where it should begin and where it should go.¹²¹ Yet this understanding should expand to philosophy questioning itself throughout the field. The theory behind how one ‘steps back’ (*Schritt-züruck*) to understand themselves and think authentically opens Serequeberhan to argue for an existence that not just ‘steps back’ *but also steps forward* – living within history so as to engage and change it. He does this through articulating the struggles of those who have done this – like Frantz Fanon, W.E.B. Dubois, Amilcar Cabral, amongst others – and how their existence is a *lived one*, one in which their struggles existentially and historically defined their lives and the histories which comprise their heritage.

Therefore, what we have explored in this chapter is the emergence of Serequeberhan’s concept of existence and its relationship to thinking itself. Philosophy, or philosophizing if you will, cannot even begin without understanding existence, for both Serequeberhan and Heidegger. How each articulates that existence – lived for Serequeberhan, *Dasein* for Heidegger – reveals much about their own impetus for where philosophy should go. For Heidegger, there are considerable debates concerning this issue, but for Serequeberhan, it abundantly is clear: it should go towards the struggle. It should go towards a socio-historical engagement with the world in process of liberation, or, rather, in process of giving others opportunities for a lived existence.

¹²¹ *EH*, p. 101. Serequeberhan cites from: Martin Heidegger, *What is Called Thinking*, p. 185; Martin Heidegger, *An Introduction to Metaphysics*, p. 176.

**CHAPTER TWO:
KWASI WIREDU'S MORAL ANTHROPOLOGY:
COMMUNITY AND THE BIRTH OF PERSONHOOD**

1. Introduction

Recall that Serequeberhan's 'lived existence' begins with a releasement from the everydayness of being in the world, where one can step back at a remove and think upon their own existence as well as existence itself. This initial step towards a lived existence at once allows a person to 'imagine' or realize themselves and the world that has shaped this selfhood, i.e., one's heritage. For Serequeberhan, this is a meditation upon the world and one's own place within it, which then spirals outward to an open engagement with that world in hopes of making it more just and liberating.

Wiredu brings a different contrasting notion through his genealogical analysis of communalism and how one becomes a person. For Wiredu, drawing upon his own Akan and Ghanian heritage, being a person is a qualitative achievement whereby personhood is bestowed upon a human being through their community.¹ One can also lose one's personhood if one fails to achieve certain moral obligations.² Importantly, though, when one loses their personhood it is not that the community condemns the individual as much as it is a recognition that someone is in moral danger. This emphasizes that the individual needs the community's help to restore themselves and reconcile whatever made them lose their personhood.³ In sum, Wiredu's notion of personhood is inherently moral and political since it

¹ Kwasi Wiredu, "Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa: Some Preliminaries concerning Communalism and Communitarianism," *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 27:4 (2008), p. 336.

² Kwasi Wiredu, "An Oral Philosophy of Personhood: Comments on Philosophy and Orality," *Research in African Literatures*, 40:1 (2009), p. 16

³ Michael Onyebuchi Eze, Thaddeus Metz, "Emergent issues in African Philosophy: A Dialogue with Kwasi Wiredu," *Philosophia Africana*, 17:2 (Winter, 2015/2016), p. 77.

is a status to be achieved and is not something biologically or metaphysically essential to being human.

Accordingly, Wiredu's moral anthropology spirals outward to encompass both an interpersonal ethics and a wider, communal (and eventually global) ethic through which he describes with a broad reading of the Golden Rule.⁴ Wiredu is not without his critics, but his communal notion of becoming a person questions some dominant Western notions of selfhood. In his view, these notions tend toward individualism or an isolated consciousness perceiving phenomena on its own as an existential-phenomenological presupposition and/or metaphysical concept.⁵ This chapter consequently teases out the embedded epistemic, political and moral implications within Wiredu's moral anthropology so that these critiques or contrasts can be plainly seen. This will open Wiredu to conversation with Serequeberhan concerning the relation between the agency of becoming a person through a community and how one can maintain a meditated lived existence. As we shall see in Chapter Three, this is within an always already political, communalist framework. The main question posed in that chapter will be, in short, although one may have become a person, have they truly *lived* (pace Serequeberhan) if they strictly follow Wiredu's moral imperatives?

For this chapter, though, I begin by reviewing Wiredu's philosophical method. Next, I will describe his personal-communal framework, leading to a penultimate section where I engage this framework's moral and political implications. In my final analysis, I will cover Wiredu's critics and, in so doing, I will present a few challenges that open Wiredu to conversation with Serequeberhan.

⁴ For Wiredu, the Golden Rule is essentially 'treat others as you would want to be treated.' He is extremely consistent on this point. See: Kwasi Wiredu, "Are There Cultural Universals?," *This Monist*, (78:1, January 1995), pp. 61-62. See also: *CUP*, pp. 56, 109-110; Kwasi Wiredu, "Moral Foundations of an African Culture," in *Person and Community: Ghanaian Philosophical Studies Vol. 1*, Kwasi Wiredu and Kwame Gyekye, eds. (Washington, DC: The Council for Research in Values and Philosophy, 1992), p. 198. For an overview, see: Barry Hallen, *Reading Wiredu* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, Kindle Edition, 2020), Ch. 5 "On Sympathetic Impartiality" (pp. 70-80).

⁵ Wiredu, "Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa," pp. 334-335. See also his critique of Western, adversarial (or multi-party) democracy: Kwasi Wiredu, "Democracy and Consensus in African Traditional Politics: A Plea for a Non-Party Polity," *The Centennial Review*, 39:1 (Winter, 1995), pp. 53-64 – note that this was revised in *CUP*.

2. Between Philosophical Worlds: Situating Wiredu's Methodology

It is important to recognize that, as Barry Hallen summarizes, Wiredu is an essayist, and there “is no book by him that provides a synoptic, comprehensive overview of his thought.”⁶ What this means for us is that, while conceptual threads are woven throughout his work, as an essayist, Wiredu covers various issues within ethics and political philosophy, the Analytic philosophical tradition, and African philosophy. Furthermore, like Serequeberhan, he began his career amidst the ethno- and professional philosophy debates. Yet, contrary to Serequeberhan who eschewed the debate as ‘en-framed’ (i.e., *Ge-stell*) within Western confines, Wiredu agrees with Hountondji that African philosophy must tightly hew to a “universally” compatible rational basis for its claims.⁷ Importantly, Wiredu believed that many ethnophilosophers were still in a “semi-anthropological paraphrase of African traditional beliefs” and that the way out of colonial entrapment was to form rational arguments that at once critically engage the West while employing/developing Africa’s indigenous rationalities and traditions.⁸ This process is what he eventually calls “conceptual decolonization.”⁹

Wiredu thus described himself as a philosopher who employed John Dewey’s “genetic method,” which entails a deep, empirical analysis of cultural mores and language.¹⁰ Through this, Wiredu performs a linguistic-cultural investigation of African Traditional Thought, which analytically challenges philosophies within both Western and African contexts.¹¹ For Wiredu, Dewey’s genetic method breaks open the conceptual canons of rationality so that one can

⁶ Hallen, *Reading Wiredu*. p. 2.

⁷ See: Chapters Three and Eight for Serequeberhan’s understanding of *Ge-stell*, CUP, pp. 136-138. One finds this especially in Wiredu’s critique of faith, see: Chapter Six, pp. 76-80; Chapter Six, pp. 135-141. See also: Kwasi Wiredu, “Identity as an Intellectual Problem,” in *Identity and the Politics of Scholarship in the Study of Religion*, Jose Cabazon and Sheila Greeve Daveny, eds. (Abingdon: Taylor & Francis Group, 2004), pp. 212.

⁸ Kwasi Wiredu, “On Defining African Philosophy,” in *African Philosophy: The Essential Readings*, Tsenay Serequeberhan, ed. (New York: Paragon House, 1991) p. 88. Note that Serequeberhan often quotes this passage.

⁹ This will be covered later, but Wiredu employs this notion often within his work. For an overview, see: CUP, Ch. 10, “The Need for Conceptual Decolonization in African Philosophy” (pp. 136-144); Wiredu, “Identity as an Intellectual Problem,” pp. 224-226.

¹⁰ Kwasi Wiredu, *Philosophy and an African Culture* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1980), pp. 164-165.

¹¹ Hallen, *Reading Wiredu*, p. 20.

further investigate the “patterns” that emerge from “our interaction with the environment;” meaning, both our physical and social environments.¹²

For those unfamiliar with John Dewey (1859-1952), he was a pragmatist who emphasized how thinking was not merely an abstract activity but, rather, a worldly, concrete action since thinking is always already bound to a given language. This language is built within the world, and its vocabulary and grammar are derived from concrete observations. This means that one’s cultural mores are built upon those observable experiences which are formed through one’s given language. Thus, a genetic method explores how these worldly linguistic-cultural constructs form ideas about the world: it investigates the ethics or governance through which those ideas are developed and employed within one’s society.¹³

This allows one to investigate not just knowledge as such but the epistemological-linguistic frameworks that deem certain things as knowledge and others as superstition, unsubstantiated claims, and so forth. For Wiredu, this allows him to analytically define the rationality of a given culture/community and how their truth claims are comparable to others through translation.¹⁴ Translation holds significant importance to Wiredu since the ability to translate ideas between different languages – though with some difficulty and the acceptance that certain ideas/phrases cannot be completely translatable – proves that there must be some ‘universals’ germane to all cultures.

Returning to Wiredu, the core aspect of his thinking is that he defines his Akan heritage and other African rationalities as a distinct and unique forms of empiricism, which he calls ‘empiricalism.’ For Wiredu, a primary issue with the Western gaze upon African rationalities is that it either finds it too abstract (i.e., supernatural) or too immanent, neither of which lends itself to authentic philosophical reflection.¹⁵ By immanent, he means that African rationalities have been force-fitted into Western frameworks such as immanence and transcendence rather than using their own terms and categories. Addressing these

¹² Kwasi Wiredu and Olusegun Oladipo, “Kwasi Wiredu: The Making of a Philosopher,” in *The Third Way in African Philosophy*, Olusegun Oladipo ed. (Ibadan: Hope Press, 2002) p. 331.

¹³ See: Hallen, *Reading Wiredu*, pp. 46-48.

¹⁴ In *Reading Wiredu*, Hallen gives an extensive account of Dewey’s influence on Wiredu throughout the text (pp. 20-25, 33-36).

¹⁵ Concerning the supernatural, see: Kwasi Wiredu, “How not to Compare African Traditional Thought with Western Thought,” in *Philosophy and African Culture* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009), pp. 46-47.

misconceptions, he notes that “the familiar claim is that African thinking is exhaustively empirical and innocent of metaphysical reflection. This is quite a severe misunderstanding. A mode of thinking can be both empirical and metaphysical, and I ... [argue] that traditional Akan metaphysics is an empirical metaphysic.”¹⁶ In defining empiricism, Wiredu states that it “is the adherence to the empirical imperative without the sensationalistic incoherencies of empiricism. It is the view which close attention to the conceptual intimations of my own culture renders the most plausible to me regarding the fundamental character of human knowledge.”¹⁷

I will further unpack these notions below. Moreover, in Chapter Four, I will review Wiredu’s reading of Akan metaphysics and further examine its incongruence to the Western, transcendent and immanent binary. For now, though, one can see that Wiredu’s philosophical approach is rather difficult to slot into any particular school (Western or African), which Barry Hallen argues is why many critiques against Wiredu are often misplaced or derived from poor reading.¹⁸ For example, some critique his conceptualization of Akan and African culture as being too utopic and say that he shaves off certain nuances to craft his own philosophical stance.¹⁹ Other critics engage whether his moral and political philosophies are viable or have enough decolonial impetus to create change, regardless of their fidelity to the Akan tradition.²⁰ For our purposes, I will touch upon these critiques in our penultimate section and final analysis.

¹⁶ Wiredu, “Empiricism: The Empirical Character of an African Philosophy,” in *Identity Meets Nationality: Voices from the Humanities*, Helen Lauer, Nana Abo Appiah Amfo, Jemima Asabea Anderson, eds. (Legon-Accra: Sub-Saharan Publishers, 2011) p. 22.

¹⁷ Wiredu, “Empiricism,” p. 33.

¹⁸ Hallen’s *Reading Wiredu* attempts something of a course correction on this matter. He goes at length to describe how Wiredu’s philosophy is fundamentally genetic and that Wiredu’s arch-project explores language, culture, and presents Akan philosophical understandings as a challenge to Western ideas (pp. 22-24, 30-32). Furthermore, Hallen (amongst others) argues that they appear to be keener on entrapping Wiredu within the decolonization’s ‘rejection’ of Analytic philosophy than they are in thoughtfully engaging his own work. See: Barry Hallen, “Book Review: Sanya Osha. *Kwasi Wiredu and Beyond: The Text, Writing and Thought in Africa*,” *African Studies Review*, 49 (2021), pp. 175-176.

¹⁹ See: Kwame Gyekye, “Person and Community in Akan Thought,” in *Person and Community: Ghanaian Philosophical Studies Vol. 1*, Kwasi Wiredu and Kwame Gyekye, eds. (Washington, DC: The Council for Research in Values and Philosophy, 1992), pp. 101-122; Motsamai Molefe, “A Critique of Kwasi Wiredu’s Humanism and Impartiality,” *Acta Academia*, 48:1 (2016), pp. 91-110.

²⁰ See: Bernard Matolino, “The Nature of Opposition in Kwasi Wiredu’s Democracy by Consensus,” *African Studies* 72:1 (April, 2013), pp. 138-153; Emmanuel Chukwudi Eze, “Democracy or Consensus? A Response to Wiredu,” *Postcolonial African Philosophy: A Critical Reader*, Emmanuel Chukwudi Eze, ed. (Cambridge:

With that said, it is crucial that we read Wiredu as a stand-alone thinker and not as an extension of Akan culture. Doing so will bring his notion of personhood as a status to be achieved into full relief and from this, we will see the hermeneutic and moral tensions that give rise to this status and whether a person can change their community – either through conceptual decolonization or otherwise.

3. Wiredu’s Moral Anthropology: How a Human Becomes a Person

I have found that D.A. Masolo articulates Wiredu’s notion of personhood best since he contrasts Wiredu with Kant’s classic notion of universalism to Wiredu’s notion of personhood. In so doing, details Wiredu’s critique of Western Universalism.²¹ Concerning the latter, Masolo shows how Wiredu’s approach is a direct critique against the ways in which particular notions of personhood, articulated from one culture to the next, are discarded by Western modernity or, at best, flattened out to become analogues to Western rationality.²² As Masolo argues, Kant arrives at a philosophical anthropology *after* his three famous critiques, whereas Wiredu inverts this and begins with an anthropology from which he then explores its implications.

Kant argues that the field of philosophy follows a certain linear path: first, it questions ‘What can I know?’ Then, ‘What ought I do?’ This moves it toward asking, ‘What can I hope for?’ This finally brings us to the question of, ‘What is man?’ Furthering this and quoting Kant, Masolo highlights how specific branches of philosophy address these issues: the first question is covered by metaphysics, the second by morality/ethics, the third by religion, and the fourth by anthropology.²³

Blackwell, 1997), pp. 313-323; Sanya Osha, *Kwasi Wiredu and Beyond: The Text, Writing, and Thought in Africa* (Dakar: CODESRIA, 2005).

²¹ See: Edwin Etieyibo, “African Philosophy in the eyes of the West,” *Phronimon*, 17:1 (2016), p. 84-103. For Western Universalism, see: Introduction, pp. viii-ix; Chapter Three, pp. 50-52; Chapter Four, pp. 73; Chapter pp. 262-263. In broad strokes, the term denotes how all philosophical rationalities or concepts must be force-fitted into a Western paradigm.

²² D.A. Masolo, *Self and Community in a Changing World* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2010), pp. 139-141, 149-154.

²³ D.A. Masolo, *Self and Community*, p. 137. He is quoting from: Immanuel Kant, *Logic*, Robert S Hartman and Wolfgang Schwarz, trans. (New York: Bobb-Merrill Co., 1974), p. 13. Note that I use the gendered ‘man’ above since this is how Masolo states it.

For Masolo, echoing Wiredu, starting with a metaphysics and then moving toward an anthropology unduly introduces presumptions onto what a person is.²⁴ Contrarywise, Wiredu's exploration of anthropology as 'first philosophy,' if you will, recognizes how one's rationality is shaped by what an individual knows about themselves within a particular society and how they conductively employ this knowledge within the world. Furthermore, Wiredu argues that metaphysics is not a universal foundation of reason from which one's self-understanding arises. Rather, self-understanding comes from an individual's sense of their own existence in relation to their community. As Masolo summarizes, it is a relationship that builds to a metaphysics through a shared culture:

While Kant starts with human nature as phenomenologically complete in its (metaphysical) constitution at least in the domain of understanding, Wiredu seeks to establish the view that such defining characteristics of being human are not endowed in humans by a force that exists outside an already existing environment of the deliberate actions of other humans, namely the socializing processes out of which the actualization of human capacities emerges. Thus, Wiredu argues, in an Aristotelian fashion, what makes humans humans cannot be their psychology, for this is an already-constituted aspect of them.²⁵

In sum, Wiredu is wary of any transcendental categories that endow oneself with identity. To begin with, being human is a biological fact. Wiredu even states (tongue in cheek yet matter-of-factly) that humans are merely "featherless bipeds dispersed over the surface of the world" and therefore self-understanding is a psycho-philosophical issue of the mind which develops through humans' social-empirical engagements with the world.²⁶ Remember that Wiredu is drawing upon what he calls an 'empiricism,' where one's potentiality for personhood and identity is constituted through concrete encounters, which then develop into a systematic framework of understanding (i.e., an empirical metaphysics built upon encounters that which are understood through culture and its given language/s). The mind is consequently always in the process of becoming, and, as we will see below, its endgame is achieving a strong, moral personhood that is esteemed from one featherless biped to another within communal-social relations. Concerning the issue of mind and its procurement of identity, Wiredu states:

²⁴ Ibid., p. 138.

²⁵ Ibid., p. 138.

²⁶ Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," p. 215. This is a play off of Plato's similar definition of humanity in his dialogues, particularly *The Statesman*.

We are born human beings by virtue of our biology and inherited potentials, but we become persons only by socialization. This is the process by which we not only develop the powers of our mind but also, more importantly, begin to have any sort of mind at all. In other words, we are not born with a mind that is a *tabula rasa* ... *Rather we are born with only the potential for one.* The acquisition, through suckling, nursing, and nurturing by parents or persons in loco parentis, of the gestured rudiments of language is the first hint of a baby's pretension to mind. Even this much is already heavily laden with culture, that is, with a certain particular way of becoming sensitive to 'the other' and subsequently cognizant of the self. In due course, one acquires a working command of a mother tongue.²⁷ (Emphasis mine)

From this, the resultant question becomes how can one explore identity and philosophical anthropology without outside categories, transcendental or otherwise? This is where Dewey's influence enters the picture. Wiredu argues that one can understand how identity and/or personhood are developed through a genetic exploration of linguistic-cultural norms. Furthermore, this approach shows that universal categories cannot describe personhood, and neither can culturally relativistic, particular rationalities. The fact that language and culture are translatable and can be learned shows some universals at play, but they are expressed in particular ways unique to the truth values of a given linguistic culture. As he states at the beginning of *Cultural Universals and Particulars*, "human beings cannot live by particulars or universals alone, but by some combination of both."²⁸

The way in which Wiredu connects the particulars and universals is through language. Following Dewey's genetic method (though not cited directly in this section of *Cultural Universals and Particulars*), Wiredu argues that communication is a biological necessity for humans to survive. He even goes as far as calling it "vital communications" because they are *sine qua non* for the human species' existence.²⁹ 'This is where to find food,' 'This is where to find shelter,' 'Beware of the predators over there;' all these communications are necessary for featherless bipeds to survive in an unstable, harmful environment. As he states, "the notion of different persons perceiving or apprehending the same entity presupposes a system of interpersonal correlation of inner experiences with external reality, which is inconceivable without communication."³⁰

²⁷ Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," p. 214.

²⁸ *CUP*, p. 9.

²⁹ *CUP*, p. 21.

³⁰ *CUP*, p. 19.

This communication, according to Wiredu, is an “evolutionary force” and the “cultural universal *par excellence*” which, in tandem with survival, establishes humans as social creatures.³¹ Formal languages, with sets of grammatical rules and vocabularies, evolve from rudimentary communications. Accordingly, these languages are the foundations of culture since each community expresses itself through language. Out of these cultures come a system of mores and/or ethics on how to conduct oneself within said community and, most importantly, these systems of governance become the means of knowledge creation. In sum, from survival to culturally produced knowledge, Wiredu locates that language, and its evolution, are how communities bind themselves together and hand down their own traditions to future generations. This happens somewhat instinctively: “Given a common language as a medium of communication, various things will be defined ... according to the semantical rules operative in the given language. ... speaking literally, it is not the community that does the defining [i.e., in a judicial, authoritative sense]; it is the individuals who do it, using rules developed in the community.”³²

Through this genealogical account of culture and anthropology, Wiredu argues that “a human being is a rule-following animal, and language is nothing but an arrangement of rules.”³³ These rules – either in grammar/syntax, ethics/culture, rationalities/epistemologies – become the structures by which both personhood and community co-develop. Subsequently, each community’s rules become the cultural particulars that arise from humanity’s universal, biological needs.

Masolo was right to contrast Wiredu with Kant because Wiredu’s rationality is not fixed nor endowed by the facticity of life itself. Wiredu argues that rationality and the development of the mind are themselves constructs to describe how a human being first survives and then develops their own sense of self within their community. This community frames this sense of self through its knowledge systems and morality, which is communicated through a particular language-culture that is taught hand or handed down. From my reading of Wiredu,

³¹ *CUP*, pp. 41, 28.

³² Wiredu, “Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa,” p. 338.

³³ *CUP*, pp. 25, 27.

this morality and its language-culture frames meaning and, eventually, epistemologies. As he summarizes:

[The capacity to be rational] has tremendous implications. It implies, for example, that we (human beings) are capable of learning from our experience of the environment and of adjusting, or trying to adjust, our behavior to the constraints of that experience. Now the environment is of two basic types. There is a natural and there is a social environment. The constraints of the natural environment arise from our contact with physical objects and forces [*Sands: i.e., empiricism*]. In terms of detail, different peoples react differently to the environment, but in basic essentials, there is only one human way of doing this. And that is the pursuit of survival and well-being through action on the basis of perception and inference [*Sands: i.e., meaning-making and epistemology*]. From the standpoint of cognitive biology, then, there is a basic way of being in the world. That is to say, there is a basic culture common to all human beings. ¶ There is another species-wide cultural commonality. It appertains to the conditions of the social environment. It is a necessary truth about human beings that they live in societies. But to live in a society is, in general, to have some conception of other selves in contrast to oneself [*Sands: i.e., personhood*]. At the minimum, this involves having a sense of one's own interests in relation to the interests of others. It involves also, beyond this, some sense of the need to harmonize these interests, which, by any account, are apt frequently to conflict. This need is the root of all morality. The rules for securing that minimum of harmony required by the survival of human community constitute morality in the strictest sense. In this sense, morality is the same for all humans. This, then, is a second element of unity in human nature and culture.³⁴

So far, communication as a biological and social necessity is clearly argued, but the issue of the moral implications of personhood needs more fleshing out. Wiredu argues that the Akan people (along with other African communities) endow others with personhood. Therefore, being a person requires an individual to be 'seen' or accepted by their community. This happens through social engagements when an individual achieves a good standing within their community through that community's morality. Though Wiredu does not give these examples, some analogues to Akan-African personhood can be seen in rituals such as Christian baptism or Jewish bar/bat mitzvahs; here, one becomes accepted into the community – essentially becoming 'one of us' – through performing a systematic ritual. Systematic, here, is imperative since each moral-social framework must have an impartial

³⁴ Kwasi Wiredu, "Reflections on Cultural Diversity," *Diogenes*, 52:1 (2005), p. 204.

basis: impartial in that it applies to all persons and is the foundation upon which morality is judged.³⁵

Wiredu also adds that this impartiality is constantly being negotiated between the person's own interests and their community's to consensually establish harmony. This allows a dynamism to individual morality – lest it become too rigid and *impersonal*, thereby creating drones and not living people – while also allowing morality to develop and change according to the needs of the person and a given society. Wiredu calls this negotiation a “sympathetic or better, empathetic impartiality” and nearly always equates it to the Gold Rule, or some analogue, where one ought to treat others as they want to be treated.³⁶

For now, we can see how empathetic impartiality sets the rules through which one becomes a person within a given community.³⁷ It gives individuals a baseline for understanding their role within the community by providing criteria for one to calibrate their actions. These criteria are derived through one's communal culture and its collective understanding. One can see this in rules or laws written by communities both in the political sphere (e.g., constitutions) as well as in the religious sphere (e.g., doctrine). In writing these, communities establish epistemologies and methodologies which decipher what is knowledge, superstition, trivia, and so forth.

Significantly and finally, cultural exchanges are possible since language can be translated. Moreover, one can also see the particularity of each culture since they require translation in the first place.³⁸ If they could not be translated then they could not be universal, nor could they be particular if they did not need translation. Rather, one needs both possibilities to understand how personhood and community establish harmonies. Crucially, one also needs them to understand how these featherless bipeds dispersed across the earth are the same species and how they communicatively and culturally self-identify.

³⁵ Wiredu, “Moral Foundations of an African Culture,” pp. 196-198.

³⁶ Wiredu, “Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa,” p. 334.

³⁷ *CUP*, p. 29.

³⁸ *CUP*, p. 25-26. Note that, in *Reading Wiredu*, Hallen sees this translatability issue as one of Wiredu's first philosophical inquiries, particularly in his earliest published works critiquing W.V.O. Quine and the Indeterminacy Thesis (pp. 33-50).

Thusly, I find that Wiredu's philosophical anthropology comes full circle: He begins by noting how communication is essential to the biological survival of the human species. This commutative survival evolves to develop a given culture by establishing languages. Consequently, a linguistically bound epistemological framework is crafted which, as a framework, is nothing but a set of rules. A given language-culture's rules help bind persons to a community through an (empathetic) impartial morality where a community judges individuals, bestowing upon them personhood. Seeking harmony, persons employ the same language-culture's morality to judge their community. Through this co-esteem between individual and community, a dynamic relationship evolves to develop concrete, empirical epistemologies through which they engage in self-reflection to further discover their world, and to evolve their moral sensibilities. As we shall explore further below, this morality is the basic capacity for a relational logic and its epistemology. Continuing here, though, this engagement with the world entails cross-cultural exchanges, which is only possible if there is a linguistic or communicative baseline. Thus, we arrive at a universal notion of what it is to be human and a culturally particular notion of what it means to be a person in a given society.

4. Wiredu's Conceptual Decolonization: The Implications of Personhood via Community

To my mind, the primary aspect at play within Wiredu's philosophy is his employment of relational logic. Since communication is needed for survival, and thus a conveyance of information from one human to another, the entire framework is based upon relationships between shared inferences and, eventually, shared language-cultures. Relational logic from the bottom to the top, his entire project emphasizes that anything known as 'fact' or 'knowledge' only becomes as such through communal acceptance. This consequently emphasizes the political and moral nature of not just personhood, but the epistemological framework through which personhood is understood.³⁹

Before we move forward, we need to address a problem that will arise throughout my engagement with Wiredu. I find that the typical cleavage between 'morality' and 'the political'

³⁹ Wiredu, *Philosophy and African Culture*, pp. 176-177. See also: Anke Graness, "African Philosophy," in *The Routledge Handbook of Philosophy of Relativism*, Martin Kusch, ed. (New York: Routledge, 2020), pp. 32-34; CUP, pp. 108-110.

that one sees in philosophy writ large is somewhat ambiguous in Wiredu's work. To be clear, there are multiple accounts within African moral philosophy and political philosophy which does make these distinctions, but they are beyond our scope since what I am trying to argue is that Wiredu's moral anthropology and its relational logic invites us to reconsider how we understand personhood, epistemology, and community. However, when Wiredu speaks of the political, he often is addressing actual politics such as democracy and its adversarial nature via political parties or he is critiquing the remains colonialism's global destruction.⁴⁰ When he speaks about morality, he does so within an anthropological and metaphysical register.

We will cover this below through his distinction between an ethic and ethics and his notion of conceptual decolonization. For now, though, the best I can read between these distinctions is that they are describing the same concept that each act (even thinking) is morally laden given that it happens within a political framework of impartial ethics. Here, morality and the political are relational and perhaps are different ways of describing the same event from two different sides: the personal (moral) and the communal (political). Conceivably, though, it might be the case where an act or event is always moral since it co-effects others, and said act is always political since it is assessed through a communally negotiated impartial ethics. Morality, then, is inherently political since it is always already being expressed and assessed through a given culture's mores, rules, and laws. Inversely, politics is inherently moral since it is an expression of a person or culture's beliefs and/or acts. This would make sense within Wiredu's conceptual decolonization, as described below. Then again, perhaps the distinction between morality and the political is one that cannot be made within Wiredu's reading of Akan metaphysics. Although Wiredu's differentiation between these two terms remains unresolved, for me at least, his moral anthropology still provides us with a convincing framework through which all acts, events, ideas, concepts, and cultures are relational and therefore co-effected.

Returning to this issue, consider the following illustration. Traditionally, one cannot be a father without a child to parent, and one cannot be a husband without a wife. Furthermore, one cannot be a 'man' without a shared network of references that designate proper

⁴⁰ One can see this throughout the entirety of *CUP*.

masculinity. Here, the designations of father, husband, and masculinity are related to both other persons (such as parenting a child) and to cultural-moral norms (such as obtaining the requirements for 'manliness'). There are impartial baselines to obtain these characteristics of one's personhood.

However, these norms and referents are constantly renegotiated: First, some fathers abandon their kids and are considered poor fathers or not even fathers at all, especially by their now-abandoned child. Also, someone else can take up the father's role (in loco parentis) and become the child's father without being biologically related. Second, many societies have renegotiated what a husband is. The obvious example is the recognition of same-sex marriages, but also, if one abuses their partner, then they may lose their privilege to be a husband either by divorce or force of law, the latter of which locates a certain impartiality where society steps in and legally removes the husband. Either way, the husband may have forfeited any rights and privileges of this social esteem. Finally, the concept of masculinity is constantly renegotiated within culture up to the point where the gendered notion of 'man' has changed, in the West at least, to a performative act (à la Judith Butler), and the moral acts that characterize 'good' masculinity have changed as well (as seen within the discourse on toxic masculinity). Throughout these examples of being a father, a husband, and a man, one can see how identity is not static: it is neither self-given nor arbitrarily endowed by the community. In both an individual and socially negotiated sense, these aspects of personhood relationally adhere to a network of referents that judge the behavior of the individual in question, which grants or denies them these characteristic identifiers. Ultimately, none of these aspects are self-endowed nor are they eternally situated; they are all dynamically relational.

Concerning translatability, different cultures have various notions of what is (or who can be) a father, a husband, or a man. The fact that we can notice these differences is itself a form of translation since we identify the existence of these characteristics without knowing the language or much about a given culture. Furthermore, and rightly or wrongly, the fact that we can judge another culture's impartial baselines of these characteristics furthers the point that they are indeed translatable. Perhaps to judge them, one needs to further investigate the roles these identifiers play within a given culture, but still, there is translatability at play. Conversely, the fact that we can notice different practices of fatherhood, marital

relationships, and masculinities across cultures means that we can also weigh and measure our own culture's practices. Through these cross-cultural exchanges, we can also evolve our own cultural notions by accepting certain principles from others. Or, contrariwise, we can condemn the practices of another culture's principles, rightly or wrongly but hopefully productively and in conversation with that culture. Either way, translatability always already holds a moral component since one culture is identifying its own practices in another culture's norms and this morality is politically expressed through its judgment of both its and the others' norms, regardless of whether it is implicit or explicit. Note that morality does not necessarily mean good or bad but simply means that there is a value-ethics at work in these intercultural translations and negotiations.

For Wiredu, the moral ideal for this translatability is exemplified in the Golden Rule; each culture has some form of this maxim.⁴¹ From this, cultures fashion an ethics and later a global ethics from which cultural exchanges may occur without each culture losing its own communal identity. For Wiredu, a global ethics binds all cultures together since our universal need for survival requires that we be social creatures who need to live in harmony with each other. The Golden Rule is imperative since it provides an impartial basis for social harmony. What gives a culture its own identity is how it particularly articulates and practices the Golden Rule, which he localizes as "an ethic."⁴² As Motsamai Molefe summarizes, for Wiredu "an ethic refers to subgroup-specific rules and/or norms for regulating human life in these groups; and ethics refers to the 'necessary laws for (all) human behaviour.' ... And, I might add, both are needed for a robust human life."⁴³

Here again, we see the universal and particular at play: an ethics maintains a fundamental universality which is tied to survival, and the ethic is the given praxis within a certain community. For Wiredu, this moves the moral aspect of translatability into a politics since cultures can debate, adopt, or impart their ethic to others since they share a basic ethics. From here, Wiredu often explores ranging notions, such as Consensual Democracy and the

⁴¹ Wiredu, "Are There Cultural Universals?," p. 60.

⁴² Kwasi Wiredu, "On the Idea of a Global Ethic," *Journal of Global Ethics*, 1:1 (June 2005), p. 46.

⁴³ Motsamai Molefe, "An African Perspective on the Partiality and Impartiality Debate: Insights from Kwasi Wiredu's Moral Philosophy," *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 36:4 (2017), p. 472. He is citing Wiredu from: "On the Idea of a Global Ethic," p. 45.

United Nations' Universal Declaration for Human Rights, topics that are beyond our scope.⁴⁴ For our purposes, this shows a relational logic at play that is at once moral and political. Whether locally or globally, the ultimate goal of this morality is to seek a harmonization, either between person and community or between one community and another.⁴⁵

Yet, what happens if people are forcefully initiated into an alien culture through events such as colonization? Here, the effects of such a miscarriage of morality amount to a severe estrangement between individuals and their respective communities, effectively severing this relational dynamic between them. Consequently, one's sense of personhood dissolves along with the communal fabric woven throughout each person.

This sentiment echoes Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's "cultural bomb" because colonialism devastated communities by severing people from their language, their heritage, and their sense of self.⁴⁶ Having been forced to take up Western norms such as the individualist concept of the self, the propositional nature of Western logic through Western languages, and the adversarial nature of governance (in its colonial, neoliberal capitalist, communist, and even democratic forms), a "colonial mentality" have been forced upon them.⁴⁷ They were conscripted to take up an identity – a persona – that severed them from their language-culture and, consequently, their sense of personhood. For Wiredu, this is especially true with Christian missionaries who devalued African Traditional Religions, bastardized or suppressed native languages, denied any cultural rationality beyond the West, and consequently denied African peoples of their own sense of personhood and community.⁴⁸

Though Wiredu does not reference Fanon, I find that Fanon's notion of the facticity of Blackness compliments Wiredu's reading of colonial personhood and its colonial mentality: stripped of relational identification, one is seen and called Black by an invading mindset. One loses themselves and resultantly, in Fanon's words, "little by little, putting out pseudopodia here and there, I secreted a race."⁴⁹ Moreover, when the colonized seek liberation – whether

⁴⁴ See also: Kwasi Wiredu, "Society and Democracy in Africa," *New Political Science*, 21:1 (1999), pp. 33-44; Kwasi Wiredu, "Democracy by Consensus: Some Conceptual Considerations," *Philosophical Papers* 30:3 (November 2001), pp. 227-244.

⁴⁵ Wiredu, "Society and Democracy in Africa," p. 35.

⁴⁶ Ngugi Wa Thiong'o, *Decolonizing the Mind*, p. 3.

⁴⁷ *CUP*, p. 4.

⁴⁸ *CUP*, p. 46-52.

⁴⁹ Franz Fanon, *Black Skin, White Masks*, p. 92.

in revolution or the post-colony – they do so through “white liberty and white justice; that is values secreted by [their] masters.”⁵⁰ The colonial mentality, for both Wiredu and Fanon, haunts the postcolonial situation in that what remains for the formerly colonized to rebuild their lives is the colonial artefacts used to subjugate them.⁵¹

Wiredu’s concerns about African philosophy follow a similar pattern in that he sees a lurking colonial mentality that haunts the entire enterprise. On the one hand, many ethnophilosophers present their retrievals in Western translations and fail to directly engage what they find. On the other hand, many professional philosophers fail to adequately consult their own traditions, and their work resultantly fails to achieve any resonance within their African context.⁵² Wiredu’s approach is what he calls a “conceptual decolonization,” where the point is not to fall completely to one side or the other but to disentangle mental colonization through a methodical self-awareness.⁵³ One cannot get rid of the legacy of the imperial West, and neither can one directly return to traditions that have forever been altered. Rather, one must live with a combination of what the West has imparted upon African cultures and what remains of those cultures’ traditions. As Wiredu summarizes:

...it is worth repeating that in [conceptual decolonization] there is no assumption that what comes from Africa is necessarily true, sound, profound et cetera. Much less, of course, should there be an over-valuation of what comes from the West. In fact, however, exactly such an overvaluation, at an apparently semi-conscious level, is the hallmark of that infelicity of the mind called the colonial mentality still afflicts us in African philosophy and other areas of African intellectual life. The cure for that mental condition, however, does not require the disavowal of all foreign sources of possible edification. It seems to me likely that any African synthesis for modern living will include indigenous and Western elements, as well as, perhaps, some from the East. There are good reasons for such catholicity.⁵⁴

⁵⁰ Fanon, *Black Skin, White Masks*, p. 172.

⁵¹ *CUP*, pp. 92-95, 142-144.

⁵² Godfrey Igwebuikwe Onah, “The Universal and the Particular in Wiredu’s Philosophy of Human Nature,” in *The Third Way in Philosophy: Essays in Honour of Kwasi Wiredu*, Olusegun Oladipo, ed. (Nigeria: Hope Publications, 2002) pp. 89-90.

⁵³ Kwasi Wiredu, “Conceptual Decolonization as an Imperative in Contemporary African Philosophy: Some Personal Reflections,” *Philosophies Africaines: Traversées des Expériences*, 36 (June 2002), pp. 54.

⁵⁴ Kwasi Wiredu, “Conceptual Decolonization as an Imperative in Contemporary African Philosophy: Some Personal Reflections,” pp. 54-55.

This recognition of the entanglements between various rationalities and their impact on communities and their cultures will be a crucial aspect of our conversation between Serequeberhan and Wiredu in Chapter Three. For now, though, what a conceptual decolonization does is locate the ways in which the “modes of conceptualization” have become inert, instrumental reasonings within African thought. However, rather than discarding Western conceptualizations, Africans may engage them through their “own reflective choices.”⁵⁵

What this means is that instrumental reasoning(s) become transparent and engageable for Africans writ large; they can choose to use Western concepts and methods such as phenomenology or democracy, but they do so with the self-awareness that it is a Western concept and that it comes with certain presuppositions attached that may need to be modified to fit said African thinker’s context. They therefore need to be translated from their Western context into an African context. Wiredu’s conceptual decolonization essentially employs his relational logic where, on this issue, the formerly colonized person is aware of the tensions between their traditional beliefs and the Western, post-colonial beliefs into which they were inculcated. Through this awareness, they do not have to choose one over the other but can use both to reckon with their own sense of personal identity, their own moral values, and their interlaced cultural context.

5. Final Analysis: Wiredu, His Critics, and Moral Anthropology as First Philosophy

Wiredu has been critiqued as an ethnophilosopher since he frequently references Akan traditional philosophy. Yet he has also been critiqued as a professional philosopher since he employs Analytical philosophy and often engages with issues within the Oxbridge tradition through which he was educated.⁵⁶ Furthermore, some thinkers like Sanya Osha find Wiredu’s approach to decolonization to be too closely attached to an “ethnocentric Western

⁵⁵ Wiredu, “Conceptual Decolonization,” p. 56.

⁵⁶ It should be noted that Wiredu prefers the ‘professional philosopher’ distinction albeit in a nuanced way: “Apart from anything else, some might conceivably regard much of the work I have done in Akan philosophy as ethnophilosophy. Be that as it may, I personally prefer to let the term ‘professional philosopher’ refer to anybody who gets paid to teach, and meditate on, philosophy. In this sense, the traditionalists too are generally professional philosophers.” This quote is from Kwasi Wiredu and Olusegun Oladipo, “Kwasi Wiredu: The Making of a Philosopher,” in *The Third Way in Philosophy: Essays in Honour of Kwasi Wiredu*, Olusegun Oladipo, ed. (Nigeria: Hope Publications, 2002) p. 336.

epistemology” to have the intellectual and political force to decolonize African life.⁵⁷ For Osha, this epistemology encapsulates a methodological problem in Wiredu’s conceptual decolonization, namely that his highly Analytic approach tries to bring African Traditional Thought to the forefront, but only as much as it gives evidence to an Analytic proof; it never goes beyond this to explore a deeper interrogation of the methodological and epistemological presumptions underlying its ideal.⁵⁸ Osha thus champions a decolonial approach closer to the Continental philosophical tradition. I bring this up to show how, in some ways, the ethno- and professional philosophy debate has been perhaps assumed into the Analytic-Continental philosophy debate. This is relevant since, *pace* Wiredu, there remains an entanglement between conceptual canons of thinking where the formerly colonized have an either/or decision forced upon them. One can especially see this in the aforementioned terminological difficulties in distinguishing between morality and the political.

Contrarily, and in partial defense of Wiredu, there could exist a space where one seeks a harmonization between decolonial projects: rather than picking one epistemological-methodological framework over another, one can find which best relates to their own personal and communal circumstances since neither will prove universally adequate for all the formerly colonized across the globe. Perhaps there is space for both. What Wiredu’s conceptual decolonization provides to his notion of communalism is the recognition that the damage of colonialism will not fade away. It is therefore a false choice to unreflectively decide between returning to a tradition that is forever altered or maintaining a Western mentality that is forever foreign. Language evolves and may recapture portions of its grammar and vocabulary, but it only does so through re-appropriation and not a wholesale rewrite of its own history, its own becoming.⁵⁹ So too does our sense of personhood evolve, and the formerly colonized should, according to Wiredu, recapture their traditions but can only

⁵⁷ Osha, *Kwasi Wiredu and Beyond*, p. vi.

⁵⁸ Osha, *Kwasi Wiredu and Beyond*, pp. 63-69. For similar critiques, see: Innocent Asouzu, *Ibuaru: The Heavy Burden of Philosophy - Beyond African Philosophy*, (Zurich: Lit Verlag, 2007); Msembe Edet, “A critique of Kwasi Wiredu and a Proposal for Conceptual Mandelanization in the Africa We Know,” in *Atuolu Omalu: Some Unanswered Questions in Contemporary African Philosophy*, Jonathan O. Chimakonam, ed. (Lanham: University Press of America, 2015), pp. 197–218. For a comprehensive review of these critiques, and a defense of Wiredu, see: Mary Carman, “A Defense of Wiredu’s project of Conceptual Decolonization,” *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 35:2 (2016), pp. 235-248.

⁵⁹ Consider, for example, the concept of a ‘dead language’ and what makes it ‘dead’ but still knowable and usable. Latin, here, is the exemplar in that it is essential to numerous Western and Subaltern legal systems.

authentically (or, in Sartrean terms, in good faith) do so as a re-appropriation that is self-aware of the historico-cultural situation at hand.

Thus, the best pathway to an authentic sense of personhood – authentic being broadly construed to apply to various circumstances – is to find a relational harmony between the individual and the community; knowing that the community is haunted by colonialism and recognizing what colonialism has denied oneself is essential to the personal-communal negotiation. In this sense, the agency of personhood is fully formed in that it directly confronts the colonial mentality perpetuated through the community and challenges the community to transform and decolonize itself by questioning its instrumental reasoning. Again, there is a relational dynamic at play here where individuals within their community (re)negotiate their community's ethic in pursuit of re-articulating their own idea of the Golden Rule or, differently said, their own ethics. It can do so through a reappraisal of the community's original language-culture, and the fact that these (re)negotiations carry a translatability with them means that they can negotiate what they wish to appropriate from other cultures, colonizing Western cultures included.

Though Wiredu's conceptual decolonization of the person and community may be benign for some, and I too wish it had more force and impetus to galvanize social justice movements, it is ultimately a philosophical anthropology and not a manifesto for change. What Wiredu's aims are, whether one agrees with him or not, is to provide the first philosophy *for effective change*, not to provide change itself. This will be further explored in Chapter Three but, for now, Wiredu limits his scope so that second, third, and further orders of philosophy may emerge. Or, returning to the counterpoint he takes against Kant, if there is going to be a decolonization, it needs to begin with the question 'What is a person?' before it attempts to liberate persons and communities.

**CHAPTER THREE:
THE AGENCY OF BECOMING:
SEREQUEBERHAN AND WIREDU ON PERSONHOOD AND COMMUNITY**

1. Introduction

The last two chapters have explored notions of how one opens themselves to realize previously unthought potentials and how one achieves personhood through communal engagement. In Serequeberhan's work, I explored how a lived existence opens oneself to think authentically for themselves – in short, to begin philosophizing – and doing so in pursuit of individual and collective liberation. Wiredu's notion of communal personhood revealed to us that one's sense of personhood is derived through the relational logic of epistemic and moral actions. Therefore, personhood is something obtained rather than self-given. Though in varying ways, both Serequeberhan and Wiredu speak of individuals as beings integrated within social and moral constructs. While this is clearly evident in Wiredu, I will cover Serequeberhan's notion of these constructs in-depth through his reading of Gadamer's 'effective-historical consciousness' in Chapter Seven.¹

Accordingly, in what follows, I will show how a conversation between these two thinkers establishes how one can become both authentic and a person without losing one's own subjectivity, agency, or relationship to one's community. To do that, though, I first must do some spadework to set the conversation. As such, the next two sections will provide some methodological considerations and examine the question of agency and subjectivity.

Afterward, I will begin the conversation by examining Serequeberhan's lived existence and how it opens a sense of subjective agency but also creates a tensive relationship with

¹ See also: Chapter One, pp. 9-10, 16, 20-23; Chapter Seven, pp. 157-161, 170-174; Chapter Nine, pp. 204-206, 228-229

communalist personhood. The penultimate section will further our query about the relationship between lived existence and personhood by arguing that Wiredu's moral anthropology is a foundational philosophical framework that should be seen as a philosophical platform through which concepts like Serequeberhan's can thrive.² By addressing these issues, we can see the full implications of bringing Serequeberhan and Wiredu into conversation concerning the agency of an individual's becoming. This will lead to my final analysis, where I propose that a communalist moral anthropology, through which lived existences arise, provides us with a stronger sense of how the concept of becoming is a co-generative act. If this co-generation is properly guided by those with a so-called lived existence within their own community, then that community builds solidarity, liberation, and a stronger sense of personal and communal determination.

2. Methodological Considerations

What I find important about Serequeberhan and Wiredu's notions of the individual is that they emphasize how one is an ongoing composition of experiences, histories, and actions. They also emphasize a relational logic through which one composes their identity through these concepts. As part of my thesis, I think bringing Serequeberhan and Wiredu into conversation clarifies the idea of how a human becomes a person through communal engagement, and, in so doing, they also show the crucial importance this has to philosophy writ large. On the whole, I think this gives us a stronger notion of an individual's relationship with phenomena than the often too abstract and bracketed notion of the self, which one sees within Western philosophy and especially in hermeneutic phenomenology.

To be fair, hermeneutic phenomenologists do bring this in through the notion of context, but there typically is an emphasis on specific aspects of the self: the religious self, the Black self, the self and the other, etc. The rest is often redacted so that the phenomenologist can examine their specific focus, and I find that this is sometimes reductive or that it allows hidden presuppositions to remain in their analysis.³ For instance, does the religious self's gender, race, and life history get considered when exploring said self's experience with religious

² Note that this will lead us to discussing Wiredu's empirical metaphysics in the next chapter.

³ Though scope and space prevent an extensive discussion on these concepts from a Western perspective, I found the following extremely helpful when orienting this chapter: Robert B Pippin, *The Persistence of Subjectivity: On the Kantian Aftermath* (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 2005).

phenomena? Are these ‘selves’ within phenomenology presumed to be white, male, and American/European unless otherwise stated? These are important questions, but this chapter cannot litigate the problematics of Western phenomenology; this is already well explored, and even a new critique of the Western self would require its own book.⁴ Rather, this chapter merely proposes a new pathway for hermeneutic phenomenology (and other disciplines) to broaden their analysis.

In so doing, I propose that bringing Serequeberhan and Wiredu into conversation reveals to us new possibilities for understanding humans as relational amalgamations of histories and cultures who are beings ‘on the way;’ they are human animals in the process of becoming unique persons within and through those histories and cultures. By focusing our analysis on seeing being human as a moral act – that is, one who is always engaging and changing those contexts – then we may find stronger ideas of what makes humans persons and what makes people communities.

However, bringing both thinkers together does present a major issue concerning the agency of an individual. This agency issue is rooted in the question of subjectivity – in both the political and phenomenological sense – given that communities place limitations on individuals while also providing them with possibilities of self-realization. For example, to Serequeberhan, one lives within an effective-historical consciousness which crafts one’s existence by simultaneously narrowing it to a specific historical worldview while also opening one to new possibilities once someone recognizes these limitations pressed upon them.⁵ For Wiredu, if the community esteems someone to personhood it is through that community’s specific knowledge systems, morals, and culture.⁶ Thus, one may ask, is Wiredu’s communitarianism more of a restraint of possibilities, and does Serequeberhan’s lived

⁴ Although there are myriad examples, see: *Self and Subjectivity*, Kim Atkins, ed. (Oxford: Blackwell, 2005); *Embodiment: Phenomenological, Religious and Deconstructive Views on Living and Dying*, Romana Fotiade, David Jasper, and Olivier Salazar-Ferrer, eds. (Burlington: Ashgate, 2014); *Understanding the Self and Others: Explorations in Intersubjectivity and Interobjectivity*, Gordon Sammut, Paul Daanen, and Fathali M. Moghaddam, eds. (Oxford: Routledge, 2013); Benedetta Giovanola, “Human Flourishing Beyond Economic Well-Being: The Contribution of Phenomenology Towards a ‘Richer’ Idea of Personhood,” *Analecta Husserliana Vol. C3*, Anna-Teresa Tymienicka, ed. (New York: Springer, 2010), pp. 339-354.

⁵ See: *HAP*, p. 26; Tsenay Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer: Thinking as ‘Meditative’ and as ‘Effective-Historical Consciousness,” pp. 55-56. As mentioned in Chapter Seven, pp. 156-159 (especially the footnotes), Serequeberhan is very consistent with his reading of Gadamer.

⁶ Kwasi Wiredu, “Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa,” p. 336. See also: Chapter Two, pp. 31-36, 38; Chapter Four, pp. 81-84; Chapter Five, pp. 101-102; Chapter Nine, pp. 236-239.

existence 'elevate' someone above this communalist personhood once someone recognizes how their community has delimited their possibilities? I do not think either is the case, but it needs to be fleshed out before I can adequately argue that the notion of someone becoming a person through community is a stronger hermeneutic phenomenological framework than the 'self-other' paradigm that the West normatively employs.

However, there is another issue that we cannot litigate here but is still crucially important: the notion of the self, person, or existential being is as strident as it is nebulous within contemporary African philosophy. One can see it throughout decolonial debates within the field, and it would be too unwieldy to give a comprehensive overview.⁷ In short, though, I would like to identify two primary branches within African philosophy concerning the concept of the individual: an existentialist one which hews closer to Fanon (amongst others), and a personable one which draws upon Afro-Communitarianism such as Ubuntu or collectivist ontologies similar to Wiredu's.⁸

Concerning the former, Frantz Fanon is its guiding influence, and accordingly thinkers employ existential phenomenologies and/or psychoanalyses to express the embodiment of Blackness and the consequences pressed upon Black persons.⁹ This branch is most prevalent in

⁷ Though not directly cited, the following works have influenced my reading of this philosophical landscape. For an understanding of the colonized subject and its relationship to emerging/rediscovery traditional rationalities, see: Michael Onyebuchi Eze, *Intellectual History in Contemporary South Africa* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010); for an understanding of the African political philosophy, or the politics of African philosophy, see: Ẹniḡlá Ànúolúwapó Şóyemí, "Doing African Political Philosophy from a Universalist Perspective," *Philos Forum*, 53 (2022), pp. 187-194; Abraham Olivier, "The Freedom of Facticity," *Religions* 9:110 (2018), pp. 1-15; Katrin Flikschuh, "Can I Choose to Be Who I Am Not?" *Angelaki* 24:2 (2019), pp. 78-91; M. John Lamola, "A Post-Sartrean Reflection on Being Black in the World: Reading Steve Biko through Slavoj Žižek," in *Phenomenology in an African Context*, Abraham Olivier, M. John Lamola, Justin Sands, eds. (Albany: SUNY Press, 2023), pp. 153-175; Kelebogile Mbebe and Thabang Dladla, "Blackness as a Conundrum for Phenomenology," *Phenomenology in an African Context*, Abraham Olivier, M. John Lamola, Justin Sands, eds. (Albany: SUNY Press, 2023), pp. 175-190.

⁸ See: Motsamai Molefe, "Relational Ethics and Partiality: A Critique of Thad Metz's 'Towards an African Moral Theory,'" *Theoria* 64:152 (2017), pp. 53-57; Jonathan O. Chimakonam and Victor C.A. Nweke, "Afro-Communitarianism and the Question of Rights," *Theoria* 65:4 (2018), pp. 78-99; Elvis Imafidon, Bernard Matolino, Lucky Uchenna Ogbonnaya, Ada Agada, Aribiah David Attoe, Fainos Mangena, and Edwin Etieyibo, "Are We Finished with the Ethnophilosophy Debate? A Multi-Perspective Conversation," *Filosofia Theoretica: Journal of African Philosophy, Culture, and Religions*, 8:2 (2019), pp. 111-137.

⁹ Concerning Fanon's legacy, Achille Mbembe and Gordon Lewis' work has been widely influential in shaping his current reception.

Broadly and summarily construed, Mbembe's work expands on Fanon by applying a deeper psychoanalysis to existentialism; see: Achille Mbembe, *Necropolitics*, Steven Corcoran, trans. (Durham: Duke UP, 2019); Achille Mbembe, "Fantz Fanon's Oeuvres: A Metamorphic Thought," *KNA: Journal of Contemporary African Art* 32 (2013) pp. 8-16); Schalk Gerber, "On the Phenomenology of a Shared World in Achille Mbembe," in *Phenomenology in an African Context*, pp. 249-269.

contemporary decolonial discourses and is the closest counterpoint to Serequeberhan even though he is not an existential phenomenologist. Concerning the latter, one typically sees thinkers teasing out the notion of personhood within Ubuntu and adjacent communitarian philosophies, often querying whether a person is a social-self or otherwise can only be understood as assimilated within the community.¹⁰ This, naturally, touches upon Wiredu's concept of personhood and will be explored further below.

However, my focus on this chapter is argumentative and not an overview of various problematics within Western and African philosophies. We therefore can only touch upon these debates when they prove relevant to understanding our interlocutors and when they reveal opportunities for Serequeberhan and Wiredu to converse.

Overall, I am presenting a conversation that proposes Serequeberhan's notion of lived existence provides radical subjective agency to Wiredu's concept of personhood. Consequently, I will argue that one develops one's character through communal engagements and, in so doing, one may develop critical reflections of their historico-cultural situatedness, or their effective-historical consciousness. This realization then provides them with a broader subjective sense of the world, which ultimately leads to a stronger agency. This work's central theme is the notion of becoming and its relational logic, and this chapter contributes to this theme by arguing that the concept of becoming – whether as a person, community, or place – necessitates active and self-reflective engagement. Each person should have their own agency, each community should have their own determination, and each place in turn has its own identity through the practical, concrete actions of persons and communities within time and space.

Gordon, on the other hand, often maintains more of Fanon's existentialism and phenomenology: Lewis Gordon: *Existential Africana: Understanding Africana Existential Thought* (New York: Routledge, 2000); Lewis Gordon, *Fanon and the Crisis of European Man: An Essay on Philosophy and the Human Sciences* (New York: Routledge, 1995).

¹⁰ Ifeanyi Menkiti, "On the Normative Conception of a Person," in *A Companion to African Philosophy*, Kwasi Wiredu, ed. (Oxford: Blackwell, 2006), pp. 328–230. Note that, in the same anthology, D.A. Masolo warns that "social self-identity should be kept separate from our canons of moral thinking" (p. 496). He further concludes that some communitarian ethics "calls for unquestioning conformism rather than encouraging critical discourse from members of society. But this too has been countered – again, by none other than Wiredu" (p. 496).

One final issue that must be addressed is Etieyibo's critique of Western Universalism.¹¹ Although mentioned in my Introduction, it is important to recall that his primary criticism against thinkers who engage African philosophy from outside its context is that they judge African philosophy from a Western lens, shaving off important cultural and intellectual concepts to 'fit' a Western perspective. Bypassing the long and contentious history of the concept of personhood within African philosophy tempts my analysis to craft a fusion of selfhood, which can be used for a specifically Western hermeneutic phenomenology. To prevent this, I will avoid synthesizing Serequeberhan and Wiredu, and instead, I will argue that a conversation between them gives rise to a notion of personhood unique in its own right. In short, this is not a dialectical enterprise. Moreover, before we can bring them into conversation, I will first explore how each understands the concepts of agency, subjectivity, and personhood. This will set up our conversation with the necessary intellectual and historical context for a stronger discussion.

3. Conceptual (Dis)entanglements: Agency, Subjectivity, and Personhood

Interestingly, the question of agency within African philosophy was first popularized within the methodological concerns Hountondji raised against ethnophilosophy. One of Hountondji's main critiques is that ethnophilosophers hold no responsibility or accountability for their truth claims: ethnophilosophers merely state what Africans allegedly believe but never try to rationally justify those beliefs. Wiredu holds a similar charge against certain African philosophies, which is why I think he chose to emphasize the rationality of Akan philosophy. From its religion, politics, personhood, and communal structure, Wiredu takes pains to show that Akan thought is rational throughout.¹² While I do not believe this is in direct response to Hountondji, there is an overlapping objective which is why I find it a great place to begin our discussion on the relationship between agency, subjectivity, and personhood.

¹¹ Etieyibo, "African Philosophy in the Eyes of the West," this theme runs throughout the article. See also: Introduction, pp. viii-ix; Chapter Two, pp. 31-36, 38; Chapter Three, pp. 47, 54-59, 62-63, 68-69; Chapter Ten, pp. 236-239.

¹² See: Introduction, pp. ii, Chapter Two, pp. 27-28, 33-34; Chapter Four, pp. 74-76, 77-80, 86-90; Chapter Six, pp. 127-129, 130-131, 135-140, 151.

Edmund Husserl was a primary influence on Hountondji, and one can see that he employed Husserlian subjectivity as a primary mechanism in his analysis. As Patrick Eldridge points out, for Hountondji, “philosophical responsibility is not a feeling of obligation for the subject but rather a way that the subject *produces itself, synthesizing its cognition and organizing its immanence, under the normative guidelines of transcendent objectivity*. Thus, Hountondji endorses Husserl’s infamous intellectualism, to the extent that he interprets this intellectualism as an ethics of self-effacement.”¹³ In short, when Hountondji sought to make professional philosophy argumentatively reliable, he made the subjective self take responsibility for its own truth claims and argumentations.¹⁴

According to Eldridge, Hountondji is arguing that it is both a rational necessity and an *ethical obligation* thinkers must undertake. The self – whether a philosopher or an everyday person – cannot appeal to tradition to make statements true. One must take responsibility so that their argument rationally can stand on its own two feet. However, this ‘self,’ with its own individual subjectivity for which it is responsible, carries with it presuppositions of what a self is and how a self renders its consciousness. This is the dilapidating Eurocentric metaphysics that Serequeberhan rejected, and it will be a critical piece to the conversation below.¹⁵

Regardless, Hountondji’s critique did spark a resurgence in engaging traditions to ground African philosophy, eventually leading to an over four decades old discussion on African moral theory. Although the ethno- and professional philosophy debate hovered over African philosophy like a dark cloud, thinkers like Mogobe Ramose, Kwame Nkrumah, Ifeanyi Menkiti, Kwame Gyekye, and Kwasi Wiredu began reconsidering Afro-communitarianism (or communalism) as a means to articulate African rationality through its own morals and culture.¹⁶ As I argue below, I think this is why Wiredu begins with a moral anthropology and then expand outward to other philosophical issues.

¹³ Patrick Eldridge, “Hountondji and Husserl: Subjectivity, Responsibility, and Phenomenology in the Critique of Ethnophilosophy,” in *African Phenomenology: Contributions and Challenges*, Abraham Olivier, M. John Lamola, Justin Sands, eds. (Albany: SUNY Press, 2023), p. 81-82, emphasis mine.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, pp. 80-88. See also: Paulin Hountondji, *The Struggle for Meaning*, John Conteh-Morgan, trans. (Athens: Ohio UP, 2002), pp. 27-29.

¹⁵ *HAP*, p. 32.

¹⁶ For a broad overview, see: *The Palgrave Handbook of African Social Ethics*, Nimi Wariboko, Toyin Falola, eds. (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2020).

Importantly, Afro-communitarianism is diversely expressed throughout Africa, but the moral theory of Ubuntu became a toehold in articulating the overlapping moral-theoretical foundations of African traditional cultures. In some places, it quickly became a focal point of studying African philosophy in general.¹⁷ However, as a focal point, it was the site of major debates on not just morality, but on how to approach African philosophy and especially how to develop it into a contemporary philosophy that addresses not just African concerns but those across contexts. The result of this is that Ubuntu, which up until then was mainly a cultural milieu, became a *philosophical* concept that needed (at times, Western) rational justification, often severing it from its cultural and historical roots.¹⁸ In short, for some, it became a philosophical construct to be mined and redefined rather than a way of life.

What matters to us is that, while many thinkers immediately explore the agency of communalism – that is, if a person holds any agency or are they at the whim of their people – the initial problem of agency lies within the philosophical description of the concept in question. Beginning with Serequeberhan, this was the inauthenticity within African philosophy: on the one side, thinkers appealed to tradition and did so unquestionably and without addressing said tradition’s internal logic; on the other side, thinkers appealed to a

¹⁷ This is largely due to the massive popularity – and accessibility – of Mogobe B. Ramose’s book, *African Philosophy Through Ubuntu* (Harare: Mond Books Publishers) which was originally published in 1999 but has had multiple reissues since. Naturally, Ramose was not the only thinker engaging Ubuntu, but this book was one of the first to break through various university curricula in the West and across Africa.

¹⁸ These fierce exchanges are why I have chosen to begin our section with the agency of philosophy before exploring the agency of persons. Again, Etieyibo’s critique of Western Universalism is an excellent example. He explicitly charges Thaddeus Metz as a Western Universalist given Metz’ reading of Ubuntu. In “African Philosophy in the Eyes of the West,” Etieyibo points out that Metz, after sifting through various translations of Ubuntu, defines it through the maxim that “an action is right just insofar as it produces harmony and reduces discord; an act is wrong to the extent that it fails to develop community” (pp. 86-87). From this, Etieyibo argues that Metz’ concerns with individual rights within Ubuntu *really had nothing to do with Ubuntu in the first place; the groundedness of the extrinsic value of persons was always within Ubuntu’s moral theory* (p. 95). So why did Metz miss it or feel the need to alter Ubuntu to ‘spotlight,’ if you will, the individual within a collectivist morality? Etieyibo contends that Metz has an ideological blind spot where the West’s emphasis on freedom and liberalism compels Metz to augment Ubuntu to fit within a Western framework (p. 92). Although not addressing Etieyibo’s article, Metz did give a response to critics who held similar concerns, see: Thaddeus Metz, “Motivation Towards an African Moral Theory,” *South African Journal of Philosophy* 26:4 (2007), pp. 331-335.

This shows the contentiousness within African philosophy concerning responsibility to both the philosophical tradition and to the concepts within that tradition. African subjectivity/agency, rooted in communal personhood, challenges Western assumptions of who a ‘person’ or ‘self’ is, and the rational responsibility of engaging Ubuntu or African philosophies must responsibly maintain these philosophies’ rationalities rather than grafting them onto existing, Western ones. Metz clearly believes he met this threshold, but others fiercely criticize him for not doing it enough.

Western rationality to make their work philosophically legitimate.¹⁹ The core issue was to what end and for whom: did either debate help everyday Africans? Was it even a debate *for* Africans?²⁰

Both Serequeberhan and Wiredu cross this impasse by using their own rational argumentations: for Serequeberhan, he shapes and molds European thought into his own philosophy in service of liberation; for Wiredu, he tasks himself with proving that Akan intellectualism is just as rigorous as any other philosophy and therefore can be a launching pad for a larger epistemic, cultural, and moral anthropology.²¹ Therefore, their notion of agency begins with the fact that their philosophies function on their own merits.

Emerging from this *philosophical* responsibility – or the obligations for those philosophizing – is the agency of the individual within the world. This is where each philosopher differs, and I believe that their methods are crucial to understanding their divergencies concerning agency and subjectivity. As we shall see, Serequeberhan’s hermeneutical approach raises questions about whether one can have true agency and authenticity within community. Contrastingly, Wiredu’s moral anthropology raises questions about whether one’s social obligations occludes one from truly enacting their own will and desires. These contrasts reveal how the subjectivity of individuals within both their philosophies are intertwined with an individual’s agency. Consequently, I will touch upon subjectivity when unpacking how their philosophical rationality (i.e., method) influences their perspective on individual agency.

Before transitioning to our interlocutors, it is important to recognize what is at stake: First, there is the philosopher’s own responsibility – and thus, the philosopher’s own agency – when examining a specific issue. This is important since no philosophy writes itself, it is literally subject to the author’s perspective. Therefore, a hermeneutics of suspicion is necessary, especially concerning the philosopher’s presentation and intent regarding the issue in question.

¹⁹ See: Introduction, pp. ix; Chapter One, pp. 17-20; Chapter Four, pp. 66-68; Chapter Seven, pp. 165-167; Chapter Ten, p. 262; *HAP*, p. 12; *EH*, pp. 92-93, 105-110.

²⁰ See: Chapter One, pp. 4-6, 19-21; *EH*, pp. 39-50, *OH*, pp. 1-13; *HAP*, pp. 87-116.

²¹ See: Chapter Two, pp. 30-36, 42-44; Chapter Four, pp. 73-75, 79, 89-91; Chapter Six, pp. 134, 141-143; Chapter Nine, pp. 206-207; Chapter Ten, pp. 240, 246-248.

Second, and specifically regarding African communalist philosophies, there are ongoing debates about the agency of individuals and how they become persons. As we have seen in Wiredu, this agency is expressed through one's moral acts and judged through one's community. This judgment and alignment with the community's moral code does not necessarily entail that an individual lacks agency, but it does reveal how agency within African philosophy (broadly understood) is framed through the perspective of the community. Hence the subjectivity of the moral agent is framed through their personal esteem and the esteem they have of their community (i.e., do they accept or reject their community's moral code and its internal logic?). For Wiredu, one can lose their personhood from their community, but this does not entail that they lost their agency, nor does it entail that they have gained or lost their subjective understanding of the world.²² We will unpack this in the final two sections of this chapter. In short, though, what this reveals is how personhood and community do not eliminate agency or subjectivity, but rather construes them as intertwined within moral-communal engagements. Although Serequeberhan's hermeneutics of agency and subjectivity may agree with these sentiments, his primary focus is on awakening oneself to a broader (subjective) reality of the world and its possibilities. However, both thinkers maintain that the individual has the ability to choose their actions, but those choices are always already entangled in a moral or social code(s) constructed either by the community or by wider, globalist forces.

In partial conclusion, then, what we see is a relational logic between agency and subjectivity: in either Serequeberhan's or Wiredu's case, one is responsible for their actions because they have the capacity to choose what they do. However, those choices are always defined through their community and its effective-historical consciousness; persons may not know what other options they have when they make a (moral) decision. According to Serequeberhan, when one authentically realizes their situatedness within history and culture, new possibilities arise; as do new responsibilities and obligations. According to Wiredu, building esteem within one's community opens them to new opportunities and their maturation likewise obliges them to take on new roles, accountabilities, and so forth. Finally, whether a lived existence or a 'great person,' the becoming of one's personhood is intimately related to the co-development of

²² See: Chapter Two, pp. 31-36, 38; Chapter Nine, pp. 236-239.

their agency and subjective understanding of the world: a person may become a person through other persons, but their capacity to define who they are and what they know – agency and subjectivity – is the interrelated, driving force of their becoming.

4. Subjective Agency: Serequeberhan's Lived Existence

Serequeberhan believes that we only begin to authentically think when we step back (*Schritt-zurück*) from the everydayness of life and its scientific-calculative rationality. When we begin to question thinking as a process of beingness, and how thinking about thinking releases us from the natural attitude of visioning the utility of things within the world. Accordingly, we then begin to see beyond the confined horizons given to us and discover possibilities heretofore unrecognized (or unrealized).²³ In short, he takes a Heideggerian approach to arrive at authentic thinking for oneself outside of the confines of the everydayness of one's current calculative and utilitarian culture. This allows one to "stand out" (*ek-sistence*) or, one could say, stand forth in front of their community and reveal to them the en-framed (*Ge-stell*) confinements of their current historical-cultural situation. A lived existence is, therefore, a liberated self-consciousness that carries with it an obligation to open others to authentic, liberating living.

I will cover in-depth how Serequeberhan engages Gadamer in Chapter Seven. In summary, though, Gadamer's effective-historical consciousness (*wirkungsgeschichtliches Bewusstsein*) is a concept through which Serequeberhan articulates how all human existences are within a socio-cultural environment embedded within history. It is:

...The hermeneutical encounter with tradition [which] is open to the tradition's claim on truth. In this encounter tradition/history (i.e., written or oral past) is not muffled but allowed to challenge the certainties of the present. The interpreter or philosopher in this situation – the embodiment of 'effective-historical consciousness' – is in a questioning and yet released disposition to that which the past holds in its independence and the autonomy of its possibilities.²⁴

²³ See: Introduction, p. iv-xxi; Chapter One, pp. 8-13, 16, 23; Chapter Six, pp. 131; Chapter Seven, pp. 157-163, 167, 169-170, 173; Chapter Nine, pp. 205, 218-220, 230, 236, 241; Chapter Ten, p. 246, 252, 258; Tsenay Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," pp. 48-49; *EH*, p. 105.

²⁴ *HAP*, p. 26. See also: *EH*, p. XII.

In short, an effective-historical consciousness is the socio-political, historical, and culturally normative constructs through which we subjectively understand the world. As articulated above, Serequeberhan sees that the philosopher (or authentic thinker) becomes self-aware of these constructs and must question them, albeit from an interpretive distance, so that they can truly investigate how these constructs reinforce certain truth claims. Through colonization and later globalization, the West's culture has become normative to nearly all persons within the world; we all live in the West or work for the West's needs/wants whether we realize it or not.²⁵ Concerning this latter portion of living *for* the West, Serequeberhan employs Marx to highlight how Africans and other postcolonial *subjects* have become "thingified" (*chosification*): they exist to supply the West with a labor force, secondary consumer markets, and – much like professional philosophy – must take up Western customs and mores to appear legitimate.²⁶

As 'things' crafted by and for the West, Serequeberhan notes that Africans diminish their own agency precisely due to them being both subjects of the West (similar to Micheal Onyebuchi Eze's concept of the "colonized subjectivity") and that their worldview is always already viewed through a Western perspective.²⁷ This is why Serequeberhan is so keen on emphasizing African(a) heritage: it shows a living culture that resists Western *subjugation* (i.e., subjectification, or thingification), and this heritage has its own heroes who possess their own existence, their own agency.²⁸ Again I will cover this more in-depth in Chapter Seven, but for now, what should be clear concerning agency and subjectivity is this: Serequeberhan's locates how one has been en-framed (*Ge-stell*) into a world or culture that is subject to others, thereby rendering one's life inauthentic to oneself.²⁹ This inauthentic beingness lacks its own agency given that one follows what they are told to do: what to wear, which job to take, who is their boss, and what is right and just. They never have a real choice. Contrarily, a lived existence actively resists this inauthenticity.

²⁵ *EH*, pp. 19-23, 28-29.

²⁶ See: CHAPTER Seven, pp. 166-168; see also: *EH*, p. 102.

²⁷ Micheal Onyebuchi Eze, *The Politics of History in Contemporary Africa* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010) p. 10; Eze deals with this issue throughout the book, but see especially: pp. 7, 13, 32-35, 104-112, 143-145.

²⁸ See: Chapter Ten, pp. 247-249, 259-261. Note that rediscovering this agency and subjectivity through heritage is the prevailing theme throughout his aptly entitled book, *OH*.

²⁹ *HAP*, p. 20-21, 24.

A lived existence recognizes this ensnarement and begins to authentically think for oneself; they see how they have become things in service to others, that the delimitations of their possibilities come through the suppression of their own culture (via effective-historical consciousness). Importantly, though, they do not merely recognize this and then, in a form of resoluteness or releasement, seek truth through what has been uncovered to them. Rather, they press forward and critically engage these ensnarements, disentangling them in pursuit of further realization (or truth) as well as the liberation of others who are likewise ensnared. I would go as far as to say that, for Serequeberhan, one cannot become a lived existence if they do nothing, they must press forward and run to the struggle:

What we take out and leave behind is thus sifted by a lived and constantly augmented heritage – instantiated in our ‘effective-historical consciousness’ – focused on the reciprocal enhancing of our shared existence. Thus, being open to the possible, in the actuality of the present, we solicit and call forth a new and shared world. ¶ In this, as in the past, we will invent. But this time around tempered by the surpassed pitfalls of what we have come to see as dead ends (Senghor’s *Africanité*, for example) and focused on solidarities – nurtured by mutual concerns – which have overcome the delusion of thinking that they possess, or that it is possible to possess, a foolproof system, *metaphysics*, to guard against the risks of inventing. This, then, is the treasured intellectual-political inheritance of humanity.³⁰ (Emphasis Serequeberhan’s)

Therefore, concerning agency and subjectivity, Serequeberhan’s hermeneutics is activist: one repossesses their agency as their perspective of the world widens to see how others have suppressed their historico-cultural experiences, *and then one does something about it*. Breaking it down, the ‘lived’ is one who activates theirs and others’ subjectivity, the ‘existence’ is one who stands out of one’s constraints in pursuit of guiding their activation which in turn reveals new possibilities or truths about the world (as seen in Gadamer’s fusion of horizons). “A new kind of thinking,” he urges, which is “attentive and open to the possible in that which *is*; a thinking engaged with, and directed by, one sole preoccupation: global solidarity in the common concerns that constitute our mutual humanity. ... a more inclusive

³⁰ *EH*, pp. 118-119. See: Chapter Seven, pp. 163, 168-170, where I further unpack the implications of this statement.

and more plausible story [i.e., narrative or history], sensitive to and aware of the differing hues that compose ‘our worldwide heritage.’”³¹

In my reading of Serequeberhan as a hermeneuticist, he does not explicitly venture into the phenomenological or materiality (i.e., critical theoretical or Sartrean existentialist) aspects of a lived existence; his work is more concerned with how one’s interpretation of the world informatively guides one’s life. As such, his notion of agency is tied to the subjective nature of interpretation. Hence, it is a subjective agency: one stands forth (*ek-sistence*), possessing their agency by realizing what type of world they live in and how it has subjectively framed their understanding of, and possibilities within, the world. As we shall see, this brings a new sensitivity and hue to Wiredu’s communalism and its reliance upon tradition.

5. Personhood and Community’s Responsibility to Reason: Wiredu’ Moral Anthropology

Serequeberhan often reads as an activist philosopher who possesses a sense of urgency in his work. Wiredu, however, is more reserved in the vein of trying to reassess the conditions of possibility for change by reorienting the trajectory of philosophy as an academic practice. Of course, both hold a wealth of theoretical and intellectual insights, they merely approach philosophy – and its possibility of a better life – from two different angles. These differing approaches are what makes bringing them into conversation important. To show how these approaches differ yet converge, I will begin with the broader implications of Wiredu’s philosophy and then will narrow it down to his concept of personhood and moral agency.

Wiredu’s conceptual decolonization is a great place to start this larger reading. As covered in Chapter Two, Wiredu argues that conceptual decolonization is the process through which one recognizes that they cannot return to pre-colonial Africa and reject all Western rationalities or constructs. Neither does one have to adopt a Western mindset and leave everything ‘African’ behind. Rather, one only needs to be aware of what they are taking up, if you will, and why they are doing so. This awareness means that conceptual decolonization

³¹ *EH*, p. 119. Serequeberhan is quoting Hans-Georg Gadamer, *Gadamer in Conversation*, R. E. Palmer, ed. and trans. (New Haven and London: Yale University Press, 2001), p. 54.

necessitates a *rational argumentation* for why one accepts, rejects, appropriates, and/or augments different aspects of African and Western culture.³²

Through conceptual decolonization, one can sense that Wiredu is calling for a critical assessment of the instrumental reasonings undergirding Western cultural dominance as well as a similar scrutiny for discarding Western ideas in the name of decolonization (or Africanization). Persons must be able to make their “own reflective choices” in the process of becoming who they want to be.³³ Given the current situation of most postcolonial communities – and echoing his summation of cultural universals and particulars – one’s worldview is neither Indigenous nor Western, but “some combination of both.”³⁴ What matters is that one consciously chooses which combination and has legitimate reasons for doing so. As he notes, conceptual decolonization:

...is a program for removing incongruous foreign conceptual accretions from indigenous thought materials through close attention to the vernacular [i.e., the language and its internal logic for a given culture/people]. The aim of the exercise is not necessarily to celebrate the indigenous conceptions when retrieved but rather to evaluate them critically and if possible to build upon them. Conceptual decolonization, then, does not amount to the indiscriminate rejection of foreign ideas or the automatic glorification of indigenous ones. ¶ Because the decolonizing procedure is critical in approach, it necessarily involves self-examination. There consequently develops in the decolonizing consciousness an interplay of identities.³⁵

Conceptual decolonization, then, requires rational agency where one chooses what to accept and reject of their culture. It also necessitates that, although one’s personhood is obtained through their community (and thus their culture’s) esteem, one can and does morally and epistemically choose what to accept or reject from that community. It also means that one can change their culture and thus community through conceptual decolonization. Finally, and bringing us full circle, Wiredu’s conceptual decolonization requires a constant self-critique in

³² Wiredu, “Conceptual Decolonization,” pp. 54-55; see also: Chapter Two, pp. 27-28, 37-42; where I expand upon this notion.

³³ Wiredu, “Conceptual Decolonization,” p. 56.

³⁴ *CUP*, p. 9. Note this is an appropriation of Wiredu’s words so it should be taken with some poetic or intellectual license. Also, this will become very important when I bring Wiredu’s empirical metaphysics into conversation with Bergson’s notion of spatio-temporality and memory in Chapter Six.

³⁵ Wiredu, “Identity as an Intellectual Problem,” p. 225

order for one's choice to be *their choice*, not one forced upon them by either Western or Indigenous ideologies.

Crucially, there is more to this process than decolonization; Wiredu is, in fact, arguing for a complete reorientation of *how we rationalize* and *why we rationalize*. If we were to ask, 'why do philosophy in the first place?,' Wiredu might respond that we do it to not just better understand ourselves or our world, but to *evolve* as human beings. This intellectual evolution creates better persons, communities, and, on an international level, better geopolitics.³⁶ His is a philosophy of becoming *tout court*, and to see this, we need to notice how conceptual decolonization is only a movement of his epistemic, cultural, and moral anthropology, but not its endgame.

Echoing Hountondji, Wiredu argues that philosophy – and decolonization in particular – needs to be both rational and philosophically *responsible* in its efforts: "Scholarship, as I have claimed, should be responsible, but responsible to what? Any Scholar is a native of some country. By virtue of this, she belongs to one culture or another. She also belongs to a race. This last is an identity that in some cases may come with a baggage of oppressive consequences."³⁷ This shows the subjective nature of philosophy, but it presses further: what role does subjectivity (one's country, race, etc.) play within that responsibility? If one is to be responsible for something, they are also responsible *from somewhere*.

One therefore holds a responsibility that is both particular and universal when philosophizing or thinking. On the particular side, it is a responsibility to one's culture or people. On the universal, it is a responsibility to all persons on the way to becoming a better humanity. We will touch upon the particular later, but concerning the universal, this responsibility leads to an "intercultural dialogue" which should be "a widespread pursuit among scholars and other leaders of opinion."³⁸ Such an intercultural dialogue would not merely lead to a decolonized people or philosophy, but the "*intellectual coming of age of our species*."³⁹ Crucially note this last part: Wiredu sees conceptual decolonization through the lens of intercultural dialogues

³⁶ For clarity, I want to emphasize this as an intellectual evolution. Wiredu is not concerned with the biological or physiological evolution of the human species.

³⁷ Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," p. 211.

³⁸ Ibid., p. 224.

³⁹ Ibid., p. 224.

and self-critical interrogations, all of which are philosophically (i.e., morally and thus epistemically) responsible for their communities and, if successful, this will allow our species – our humanity – to evolve or become something better than it already is.⁴⁰

In defense of critics like Sanya Osha who claim that Wiredu's conceptual decolonization is too abstract and analytical to provide real change, in Chapter Two I argued that Wiredu is presenting a philosophical framework through which widescale change – not just decolonization – would be possible; it is more a philosophical platform than a call to action.⁴¹ Conceptual decolonization is a *result* of his moral anthropology, but it is not the starting nor end point. Rather, he is describing an *evolutionary movement* within a moral anthropology that furthers not just a singular culture – or postcolonial cultures writ large – but the entire human race.

Although Wiredu is critical of Kant, his work often follows a similar trajectory in that it tries to establish what things are – or why things are what we say they are – before he goes about changing them.⁴² Recall that D.A. Masolo points this out when he notes that Wiredu's project is a radical inversion of Kant's.⁴³ Yet, like Kant, Wiredu is, in a sense, crafting a fundamental philosophy: beginning with asking 'why we are the same species,' he then goes on to query 'why we are persons,' then to 'why do we act the way that we do,' and finally to 'why we think what we do is good or bad.' I can imagine Wiredu arguing that we can begin the process of disentangling colonization only once we address these questions. Again, this is not fundamental for only decolonization, but for all personal and communal clashes.⁴⁴

Unfortunately, due to my scope and thesis, I have not had a chance to engage Wiredu's work on knowledge and relativism, but his argumentations on these matters are consistent with what I have noted above: intercultural dialogue reveals differences in rationalities, which opens possibilities for consensus building on truth claims, resulting in humanity evolving past

⁴⁰ In case it is not clear, Wiredu's use of 'species' is in relation to us being biologically human, and the evolution of our species is an intellectual one. He is not speaking about transhumanism nor any biological change.

⁴¹ Osha, *Kwasi Wiredu and Beyond*; Chapter Two, pp. 42-44.

⁴² See: Wiredu and Oladipo, "Kwasi Wiredu: The Making of a Philosopher," pp. 323-340.

⁴³ Masolo, *Self and Community in a Changing World*, pp. 139-141, 149-154.

⁴⁴ This is the primary thesis of Wiredu's "Identity as an Intellectual Problem." Note that I will cover Wiredu's empirical metaphysics in Chapter Four.

its disputations and often violent conflicts.⁴⁵ Again, notice how all of this focuses on moral responsibility as a medium of becoming: becoming better persons, better communities, better intercultural and international partners. Or, in Wiredu's parlance, a better species.

This is the broad picture of Wiredu's philosophy, and I will articulate its empirical and metaphysical implications in Chapter Four. What makes this fundamental philosophy, though, requires us to revisit 'the particular' aspect of his moral anthropology. I covered this in depth in Chapter Two, but a quick summary is that, for Wiredu, we are biologically human animals and, in order to survive as a species, we require two things: communication and moral principles, and from these two a fundamental logic and its sense of knowledge arises.⁴⁶ Regarding the moral principle, Wiredu argues that every community has some form of the Golden Rule of treating others as you wish to be treated.⁴⁷ Through communication and this moral pact, humans become a socially moral species: rudimentary communication of 'this is where to find food and shelter' alongside a mutual agreement to help one another allows the human species to survive. Eventually, this communication evolves and creates languages while simultaneously creating communities. This is where particularism arises: each language community forms its own identity through its collective linguistic and moral codes. Importantly, these codes co-effect one another since the internal logic within a given language reflects and influences the internal logic of its culture and morality.⁴⁸

Importantly, as linguistic cultures develop, they become self-critical. Here, they begin to reflect upon their community's internal logic and how it influences everyday life. This is where a culture epistemically evolves through their language and the values represented within that language. Resultantly, this culture has its own morality and rationality, both of which are interrelated: the culture begins to esteem certain acts – acknowledging them as morally good – and rewards people for performing them while in turn they begin to form reasonings for why those acts are morally good. This is how one obtains personhood: one gains esteem or

⁴⁵ For example, see: Kwasi Wiredu, "Canons of Conceptualization," *The Monist* 76:4 (1993), pp. 450-476; Kwasi Wiredu, "Knowledge, Truth, and Fallibility," in *The Concept of Knowledge: The Ankara Seminar*, Ioanna Kucaradi, Robert S. Cohen, eds. (Dordrecht: Springer Science & Business Media, 1995), pp. 137-153.

⁴⁶ Note that the next few paragraphs are summations from Chapter Two, pp. 26, 39-40. For more, see also: *CUP*, pp. 14-16; Wiredu, "Reflections on Cultural Diversity," p. 204.; Wiredu, "Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa," p. 334; Wiredu, "Are There Cultural Universals?," p. 60.

⁴⁷ Wiredu, "On the Idea of a Global Ethic," p. 46.

⁴⁸ *CUP*, pp. 25, 27.

approval within their community by following the moral and rational codes embedded within that culture and expressed through its language. However, because each individual within the community possesses their own rationality within that culture, they can also choose to critique or reject certain aspects of that culture.

A given culture thus follows a moral pact required for basic survival; individuals must ascribe to the moral code for it to be, in fact, a cultural construct. Again, as Wiredu notes, “it is not the community that does the defining [i.e., in a judicial, authoritative sense]; it is the individuals who do it, using rules developed in the community.”⁴⁹ Consequently, we can see how the individual and the community co-effect and even co-generate each other: the individual obtains esteem within the community and is acknowledged as a person by the community, and, simultaneously, the person keeps the community intact by consenting to the community’s cultural morality. “To adjust the interests of the individual,” Wiredu argues, “to those of the community is not to subordinate the one to the other. *The relationship is purely symmetrical.*”⁵⁰ You cannot have one without the other, and as the culture evolves and hands down its beliefs to other generations – thereby creating traditions and heritages – those generations change or develop that culture by critiquing or affirming certain aspects of their inherited culture.

Stepping back for a second, notice what is going on here specifically within this moral anthropology which I focus on: Wiredu is articulating an intellectual evolution of the human species from merely surviving to developing a thriving, ongoing culture with its own language, traditions, customs, mores, and heritage. When Wiredu calls communication an “evolutionary force” and the “cultural universal *par excellence*,” he seems to literally mean it.⁵¹ Communication is what allows humans to accept a moral pact; individuals could not agree upon the Golden Rule (however construed) if they could not communicate to each other what this pact entailed. Moreover, morally laden communication allows humans to evolve into persons since communication develops into a language with its own logic (i.e., knowledge or

⁴⁹ Wiredu, “Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa,” p. 338.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 334, emphasis mine.

⁵¹ *CUP*, pp. 41, 28.

epistemology).⁵² This allows the species to intellectually evolve, and as we have seen above, Wiredu does not think humanity's intellectual evolution has yet ended.

This evolution encompasses both personhood *and* community. The 'and' is important here since both concepts are symbiotically co-effective. Recall from Chapter Two where I argued that persons within communities are constantly renegotiating their concepts such as fatherhood, marriage, and masculinity. None of these are static concepts, and even the re-affirmation of what constitutes, say, a father, is a communally negotiated construct; here, at the risk of oversimplification, the community has either decided to consider other concepts or to reject them. Either way, there is still negotiation, and persons must engage each other to communally decide what their culture ultimately stands for and against. That is, persons within their community decide what is morally just.

What makes a community evolve, then, is this decision-making process, which is just another way to say it must have reasons for believing what it does. Of course, this is not always the case – as seen in Wiredu's critique of faith – but these irrational assents are potential sites of evolutionary development.⁵³ For Wiredu, every cultural construct must have a rational basis for being maintained or changed. Furthermore, echoing Hountondji, that rational basis justifies (rightly or wrongly) the person and/or community's beliefs. They are therefore responsible for their actions and justification precisely because they are the ones justifying them: whatever is accepted to be rationally just by the person or community affirms their actions, and that rationality – whether personal or communal – must be held accountable. The endgame of moral anthropology, then, is to deeply scrutinize the reasons or justifications of our beliefs and how these beliefs manifest themselves into actions. This is an ever going, evolving process and Wiredu hopes that it will evolve further in myriad, liberative ways.

A quick example of this is that European colonizers believed their actions to be just. They either rationally argued that they deserved the lands and peoples they enslaved, or they blindly held a belief that what they were doing was just and righteous. To my mind, a central problem for postcolonialism is that the colonizers (and my ancestry is a part of this group)

⁵² Wiredu, "Reflections on Cultural Diversity," p. 204.

⁵³ See: Chapter Four, pp. 73-75, 79, 89-91; Chapter Six, pp. 134, 141-143; *CUP*, pp. 48-52; Wiredu, "Reflections on Cultural Diversity," p. 126; Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," pp. 212-213.

were never held accountable nor responsible for the *rational justifications* of their acts, putting aside being held accountable for the acts themselves. One aim of decolonization, to me at least, is to hold the colonizer *rationally* accountable.

Wiredu's moral, and we should add, epistemic and cultural, anthropology affirms this need for accountability given that Wiredu argues persons and their communities are responsible for their reasonings and subsequent acts. But to what end? This returns us to the universal aspect of a moral anthropology: holding colonizing cultures accountable for their acts – which means critiquing their philosophies, religions, or other instruments of rational justification – is not just about reparations to the colonized but should, more importantly (for Wiredu), be in service of further evolving rationalities on a global scale. I think Wiredu would state the same about other atrocities committed across history, and what convinces me of this is that, for him, reason is inherently tied to morality: what does your thinking justify? What does your community stand for?

To quickly conclude, this 'moral reasoning' is a subjective agency in that the agent rationalizes their acts. An agent – be it a person or community – only evolves when they interrogate the reasons for their acts. They can either reform, reject, re-affirm, or replace their beliefs, but either way this is not just a rational decision, it also a moral one. For a person, this evolution should affect one's community (recall they are symbiotic), and for a community, this evolution should create better persons.

Finally, when philosophizing about concepts – such as what I am doing right now – one should be aware of their own subjective perspective of the issue at hand and how they are responsible for their argumentations and conclusions. From the philosopher, to the community, to the person, each holds a collective and symbiotic responsibility to each other. Therefore, each should hold the other accountable for their rationalized justifications.⁵⁴ According to Wiredu, if all of this is done well, then each co-effects and evolves the other. If done improperly, then one of the three must stand forth and hold the others accountable. This is where I think a lived existence thrives within moral anthropology.

⁵⁴ This is especially true for those philosophizing about another culture, or 'philosophizing in translation,' if you will.

6. Final Analysis: Philosophical Accountability Through Personhood and Community

Concerning this work's thesis, the aim of this chapter is to bring together Serequeberhan and Wiredu to describe how a human becomes a person by engaging their community, and how communities likewise evolve through this engagement. This conversation will eventually lead to the second and third aspects of my thesis, that these engagements temporally manifest themselves in space, and through their historical-memorial negotiations, they transform this space into particular places. As I mentioned at the beginning of this chapter, I think this notion of personhood and community is a fruitful paradigm for the future of hermeneutic phenomenology since it shows the relational logic between the two. This relationship shows how no self is an island unto itself, that it is a composite of the culture and effective-historical consciousness in which it resides.

Proving that a human becomes a person through community, and that communities are created through persons, was the clearest part of this chapter since this concept has been the bedrock for many cultures for centuries, if not millennia. However, what our conversation between Serequeberhan and Wiredu added to this argument – and why it was necessary to have the conversation in the first place – is that this should be the foundation for future hermeneutic phenomenologies.

The initial talking point of this conversation was the relationships between agency, subjectivity, and personhood. The issue at hand was whether communalism's personhood stripped the notion of agency away from individuals, making them assimilations of a greater whole. This has often been a misunderstanding of Afro-communitarianism, especially in Western circles, and one could imagine Serequeberhan's lived existence as a better alternative to a conceptual person who is a so-called derivative of their community.

I began by examining responsibility as a backdrop to address this. Through a quick detour into Hountondji and the ethnophilosophy debate, I argued that reason must be held accountable for its truth claims. Moreover, and perhaps more importantly, the philosopher must be held responsible for their rationalizations, and this is especially crucial given how European philosophers denied rationality to the colonized for centuries. As covered in Chapter One, this had dire consequences for all involved, and post-colonial communities are still trying to

grapple with the consequences. Thus, before we speak of the agent, self, or person, we must remember that we thinkers – the ones philosophizing – are the first point of subjectivity: our own assessments and rationalizations must first be held accountable before moving to any questioning of others' agency or selfhood or personhood. This reminds us of the remove, second naiveté, we have from our 'subjects' when we explore them, even if they come from our own culture.

I took this further through examining subjective agency. Both Serequeberhan and Wiredu accept the finite perspective of individuals, this is pretty standard for all philosophers. However, what Serequeberhan presents to us is an agent who, by becoming aware of their subjectivity, opens themselves to realizing how their perspective of the world is always already en-framed within their socio-historical construct. This awareness allows one to pull back and see their situatedness, and for the formerly colonized this is vital because then they can see the colonial residues which ensnare and confine their everyday life. As such, Serequeberhan's subjective agent opens themselves to a broader horizon of possibilities since they can see beyond this en-framed quotidian way of life. Though focused on formerly colonized persons, Serequeberhan's subjective agency is relevant to all persons, in my opinion, since it touches upon an inauthenticity that is just as relevant to the formerly colonized as it is to those who enjoy the privileges of the wealth gained by their former colonizing cultures. However, why Serequeberhan when we could simply gather this from reading Heidegger and Gadamer? What makes Serequeberhan significant in this discussion?

The answer is plain: Serequeberhan's subjective agent does not merely recognize their ensnarement, seek releasement from it, and open themselves to new regions of truth. No. Serequeberhan's subjective agent *is called to responsibility*: they must stand out, stand forth, and liberate themselves and others from these ensnarements in pursuit of more liberating, emancipatory lives. This is a lived existence: it is not merely a philosophical gesture of seeking an understanding of beingness through thinking about thinking. It is an active engagement that breaks the constricting lenses through which it once saw the world and does so to gaze upon a fusion of horizons which hold liberating possibilities.

A lived existence is a responsible existence. Its disposition is to run toward obfuscations and delimitations to clear them away so that other horizons can come onward. Thinking, standing

forth (*ek-sistence*), and self-realizing one's historico-cultural situatedness is not armchair philosophy for Serequeberhan. It is a call to action.

In contrast, Wiredu pulls even further back to provide a foundation for the future of philosophy. He does this through a moral anthropology which begins with the notion that a human is a biological animal, and personhood is something developed through the human species' impetus to survive. Humanity is a social species, and after survival is secured, it eventually seeks deeper ways of communicating and making life meaningful. This is always ongoing and, importantly, *evolving*. Evolution, here, is critical. He sees the movement from a human organism and its pack to a person and its community through a sense of becoming where what it means to be a person or a community co-develops as each seeks deeper understandings and knowledge of their ways of life (subjectivity), the moral consequences of their actions (agency), and the justifications of their actions (rationality).

What makes a person a person is not that the community likes them, but that an individual has evolved throughout their life to understand what it means to be a part of that community. As such, they learn the internal, moral, and thus epistemic logic of their community, and they can seek to reform, reject, re-affirm, or replace the moral and epistemic beliefs of their community. Thus, as rational agents, the more esteem they have within their community – and the more they understand the moral logic of their community – the greater the responsibility a person obtains. They are not just endowed with personhood; their community entrusts them with the imperative to help guide and direct the community. As Wiredu argues, both personhood and community must be held accountable to each other for what their culture justifies. This is the burden of rationality: are yours and your culture's beliefs just? If we follow the logic, will we find that either is rationalizing injustice? Through such inquiries, Wiredu argues, we intellectually evolve as a species.

But often such questioning falls on deaf ears or, as we have seen through the justification of colonialism, such rationalities are not held accountable. This, I find, is where Wiredu's personhood finds itself becoming Serequeberhan's lived existence: If someone or a culture is held unaccountable for their actions, or their justification for their actions is a gimmicked rationality, then a person must stand forth and demand moral responsibility. This begins with oneself recognizing their own situatedness – and perhaps complicity – in this oppressive

ideology or culture, but after one recognizes this, they must run to the struggle. They must point out hypocrisy, criticize the moral abuse and its justification (or lack thereof), and seek a pathway beyond the enslavement of not just themselves but the oppression of others as well. Wiredu argues that the community esteems one with personhood, meaning that the community holds one accountable for their actions (again, morality), and also that a person – especially those in great esteem – must do the same for their community. A lived existence embodies this obligation since its self-recognition of its own en-framing compels it to break the borders encapsulating itself and others so that all can seek a more liberative future.

Furthermore, as we shall see in Chapter Seven when I explore the implications of Serequeberhan's effective-historical consciousness, the result of this liberative movement is a fusion of horizons that reveals heretofore unknown possibilities. Is this not an evolution in its own way? The difference between Wiredu's evolving culture and Serequeberhan's is operational: Wiredu seeks a new foundation that holds everyone – philosophers, everyday persons, all communities, international governing bodies – more accountable through its molding and shaping of an evolutionary morality; Serequeberhan seeks to hold everyone more accountable by 'freeing,' if you will, people from their present circumstances. I would argue that Wiredu takes the long view, trying to reorient philosophy towards more accountability whereas Serequeberhan seeks accountability in the here and now. Obviously, they are concerned with both issues – Wiredu does not take a blind eye toward contemporary oppression, and Serequeberhan is far from a myopic thinker – but when we bring their approaches into conversation, we find that they address a person's agency and subjectivity from the perspective of accountability.

A more just philosophy, then, is one that is more epistemically and morally responsible for its claims. I think that the best way hermeneutic phenomenology can take up this responsibility is to base its analysis and interpretation on the relational logic that comprises personhood. Here, one cannot brush aside race, gender, nationality, and so forth, to find a hermeneutic analysis of how a given phenomenon provides meaning. Of course, this makes hermeneutic phenomenology less of an exact science, to quip on Husserl, given that the concept of analyzing 'a self' is much easier than 'a person.' 'A self' is the conceptualization of a thought experiment since it removes all those aforementioned identifiers, let alone their relationship and esteem within the community. In short, everything that makes a person a person. Even if

the analyst takes all these things into account, they do so as context and not as a composition of the subject – or person/self – at the heart of the analysis.

What the personhood and community dynamic offers hermeneutic phenomenology is a new insight into understanding meaning-making, culture, and human behavior. Through its relational logic, one can better grasp how interrelated subjectivity and agency are and how these limitations can be cries for freedom or possibilities for creativity; not all limitations are bad. Furthermore, Serequeberhan's notion of a lived existence and its effective-historical consciousness allows researchers to continue exploring issues pertaining to existentialism, embodiment, the colonized subject, and so forth. It only heightens the awareness of whose interpretation the researcher is examining, and whose beingness is under questioning. Finally, the concepts of 'personhood and community' and 'a lived existence' have a dirtiness to them. Meaning, neither can be fathomed in a vacuum but must be presumed to be real human beings with real stakes and consequences. This latter possible contribution returns us to the first part of this conversation: if you recognize the stakes involved in your research, then you are more liable to be responsible or be held accountable for your research.

If a human being becomes a person by engaging their community, and a lived existence is a person who realizes the constructs and potential ensnarements which constricted their existential constitution, then hermeneutic phenomenology should further explore how these interrelations operate. I still maintain that hermeneutic phenomenology must remain a descriptive enterprise, which is *sine qua non* for all phenomenology. Yet if it pursues these avenues, then what it retrieves may be bountiful: perhaps a better realization of the human condition as a thinking animal, or a better recognition of the role interpretation plays in morality and encountering others, or, ultimately, a better appreciation for what makes us ourselves, which is an interplay of personal and communal experiences.

**CONVERSATION TWO: WIREDU AND BERGSON ON SPACE, MEMORY,
AND TIME**

CHAPTER FOUR:
WIREDU'S EMPIRICAL METAPHYSICS:
THE POLITICAL NATURE OF BECOMING AND UNDERSTANDING

1. Introduction

As I covered in Chapter Two, my focus on Kwasi Wiredu is on his moral anthropology. That chapter examined Wiredu's argument that there are some cultural universals – namely, the need to communicate and a fundamental 'Golden Rule' morality – which then is expressed through cultural particulars such as language and mores and norms. The key to this moral anthropology is that personhood is a status to be achieved which is given through the community's esteem of an individual's actions and, consequently, their character. Although the idea that 'one becoming a person through community' is a widely explored African moral concept, I am concerned about how it often gets 'cogitized' in translation. I find that far too often, its ontological elements – what makes a being a *human* being – get repackaged into a Western framework. Consequently, this present chapter is pivotal for our exploration on how African philosophers like Serequeberhan and Wiredu need to be understood through their own terms before being brought into conversation with Western philosophy, and especially Western phenomenology.

Take, for example, the concept of Ubuntu, which in Zulu is spoken as '*umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu*,' and literally translates as 'a person is a person through others.' Ubuntu is translated/practiced differently across multiple Southern African languages and cultural communities, but it is often rendered into English as 'I am because we are.' Note the contra-Cartesianism at play here: rather than 'I think therefore I am' (*cogito ergo sum*), we have 'I am because we are' (*ego sum quia sumus*). Though this may be a well-intentioned way to convey African philosophy, in its translation it creates a dichotomy to (or worse, a dialectic

with) Western notions of the self and ontology.¹ For one, note how ‘I am because we are’ lacks any linkage to thought or self-reflection – this is why I provided cantilevering Latin translations to make the issue clear. To me, this translation of Ubuntu into English further reveals the West’s complicity in historically denying African rationality. It is subtle, but its subtext speaks volumes.

Given that Ubuntu has a wide-ranging and developing scholarship on its own, it is too unwieldy for our scope to explore it further.² I raise it here because, although Wiredu’s moral anthropology does not fall under Ubuntu, it shares the same communalist ethos and relational logic. What this brief discourse on Ubuntu shows is how difficult it can be to ‘translate’ African thought into Western frameworks, especially given that these frameworks’ language and structure are built from fundamental metaphysical concepts and presumptions.

Wiredu notices this and urges caution when comparing African thought to Western philosophies.³ Moreover, as Edwin Etieyibo argues, when trying to bring African philosophy *into* a Western discourse, one side typically needs adaptation/modification, and that burden is often placed upon African philosophy. This is what he calls a “Western Universalism,” whereby the West still dictates how far and how much African philosophy is allowed into the discourse.⁴ This is also why Tsenay Serequeberhan states that African Philosophy and Continental Philosophy typically “dialogue at a distance,” where Continental philosophy engages African philosophy so as long as it is useful to Continental philosophy’s projects.⁵ Here, the West’s discourses often pick and choose what they like within African philosophy,

¹ For more, see: Uchenna Okeja, “Justification of Moral Norms in African Philosophy,” in *Method, Substance, and the Future of African Philosophy*, Edwin Etieyibo, ed. (London: Palgrave MacMillan, 2018), pp. 213-220.

² I covered this more in-depth Chapter Three, pp. 48-52. For another perspective of Ubuntu as philosophy and an argument for developing a stronger moral-philosophical foundation to African philosophy, see: Aribiah David Attoe, *Groundwork for a New Kind of African Metaphysics*, (Cham: Palgrave MacMillan, 2022), pp. 65-73. For Ubuntu’s role as a relational ethics, and the implications thereof, see: Thaddeus Metz, “Towards an African Moral Theory (Revised),” in *Themes, Issues and Problems in African Philosophy*, Isaac Ukpokolo, ed. (Cham: Palgrave MacMillan, 2017), pp. 105-112; Anke Granness, “Concepts of Justice in Africa: Present and Past,” in *Themes, Issues and Problems in African Philosophy*, Isaac Ukpokolo, ed. (Cham: Palgrave MacMillan, 2017), pp. 310-315.

³ Wiredu, “Reflections on Cultural Diversity,” pp. 118-121.

⁴ Edwin Etieyibo, “African Philosophy in The Eyes of the West,” p. 87. Note that Etieyibo’s critique is against Metz’s reading of Ubuntu, which relates to the issues mentioned throughout this Chapter’s Introduction. See also: Introduction, pp. viii-ix.

⁵ *EH*, Chapter 2.

neutering these concepts from their broader implications. It is a hermeneutics of appropriation rather than a stout encounter.

Covalently, Wiredu also argues that one must consider all aspects of an African philosophy before they can adequately engage it. Concerning his own work, one cannot fully grasp the consequences of a moral anthropology unless they accept its metaphysical implications: if personhood is acquired through engagement with others, and one discovers who they are through these engagements, then it also follows that one discovers the world itself – in both a concrete and metaphorical sense – through these engagements. Hence, Wiredu emphasizes that the Akan's moral anthropology follows an "empirical metaphysic," which holds an empirically social epistemology.⁶ If one's personhood is always already becoming through engagements with the world, then one's sense of the world – what it is and what it could be – is likewise always already becoming. This is why Wiredu calls for a *conceptual* decolonization which entails a broader, psychological, and ideological examination. He calls for this paradigm shift since merely rejecting anything colonial requires a rational negotiation of what makes it colonial, whether it is beneficial to the community despite its colonial genealogy, and whether it has already been embedded into the given community's ethical-empirical self-understanding.⁷

This is also why he consistently criticizes the Western view of African persons as being overtly spiritual or superstitious. For him, shoehorning Akan philosophy into a Western paradigm is problematic because it requires one to dissect it into foreign categories, often mistaking differences of degree for differences of kind (and vice versa). This resonates with the issue I raised in Chapter Two between the terms morality and the political. For another example, Wiredu argues that spirituality and materiality are alien concepts to the Akan, stating that "not only is the notion of the spiritual unintelligible within [Akan thought and culture] ... it also is objectively a very problematic one."⁸ He then carries on showing that it is problematic because it skews the relationship the Akan have to God, to their ancestors, and to their community. Thus, many concepts in Western discourses such as spirituality are "not a

⁶ Wiredu, "Empiricism: The Empirical Character of an African Philosophy," p. 22.

⁷ Wiredu, "An Oral Philosophy of Personhood: Comments on Philosophy and Orality," p. 9. See also: *CUP*, pp. 137, 142-143; Chapter Six, pp. 127-129, 141-146.

⁸ *CUP*, p. 55.

universal feature of human thinking,” which subsequently reveals how they are not philosophically innocent. What this means for us is that if one is to explore African philosophies and religions, then one must be hermeneutically self-suspicious with how they employ Western terminologies and concepts that are beholden to specific intellectual assumptions.⁹

In what follows, I will keep this in mind as I investigate the political nature of Wiredu’s empirical metaphysics. What I will emphasize throughout is how his moral anthropology *builds to* a metaphysics that is always already moral (and accordingly always already political). This builds off the notion covered in Chapter Three, where I articulated how this moral anthropology is an intellectual evolution of the human species.¹⁰ To begin our exploration of the metaphysics which arises through this anthropology, I will first show how Wiredu’s critique of faith is really a critique of anti-rationality. Through this critique, Wiredu solidifies that the Akan’s metaphysics is neither spiritual nor divine in any way; it is a purely rational framework of understanding. Once this is made clear, I will then describe Wiredu’s reading of the Akan’s empirical metaphysics, highlighting how its basis on concrete encounters with other people and the world eschews a transcendent/immanent (or supernatural/natural) paradigm. Of greater significance is that, for Wiredu, an empirical metaphysics is entirely spatial: it is based upon both experience and the capability of forming ideas from these experiences. This displays how Wiredu’s metaphysics avoids abstraction or speculative rationality; everything is spatialized, even metaphor, and even then, it cannot be described as purely immanent.

Finally, we will unpack the way in which this moral, spatialized, empirical metaphysics entails an always already becoming of a moral-political nature and what it means to both a person and their community. This links our present study to our conversation in Chapter Three, and sets up Chapter Six’s conversation with Henri Bergson’s notion of *duration*, where Bergson provides insight into the temporal nature of this spatialized becoming. Complimentarily, Wiredu’s moral anthropology and empirical metaphysics further bring *duration* into a political

⁹ *CUP*, p. 55.

¹⁰ See Chapter Three, pp. 59-65.

register, revealing how the becoming of *duration* is always already socialized and, on this basis, our concepts of space and time hold a morally political component at their core.

2. Wiredu's Rationality Over and Against 'Faith'

Wiredu has consistently been critical of the concept of faith and, by extension, the Western distinctions of supernatural/natural and the religious/secular. From my reading, I think his critique stems from his frustration with the ways the West (especially missionaries) renders African thought as overly emotional, overly spiritual, and overly superstitious, all of which leads the West to declare African thought as not sufficiently rational. This concern runs similarly to Serequeberhan's complete dismissal of *Africanté* and *Negritude*.¹¹ Furthermore, Wiredu's critique carves a space where African rationality can be understood through its own distinctions.

Wiredu's critique holds vast decolonial implications while emphasizing a key philosophical point: the Akan (and other African traditions) simply do not have these distinctions, and the West problematically imposes these categories upon African culture, distorting these cultures in the process. For example, Wiredu argues that Christian missionaries bastardized the Akan language to delegitimize the Akan's intellectual heritage and to convert them.¹² In missionary circles, this bastardization was justified through the notion of *praeparatio evangelica*, or the belief that God had predisposed Africans to Christianity due to their overtly spiritual nature.¹³

One can see this in his early, highly influential article, "How Not to Compare African Traditional Thought with Western Thought."¹⁴ Here, Wiredu emphasizes how African Traditional Thought – often construed as primitive religion – is contrasted with Western science and reasoning. "Nevertheless," he argues sarcastically, "since [African] traditional thought is inferior to modern science-oriented thought in some obvious and important respects, some Western liberals have apparently had to think hard to protect themselves

¹¹ See: Chapter 1, pp. 17-18.

¹² *CUP*, p. 52.

¹³ James Kombo, "The Trinity in Africa," *Journal of Reformed Theology*, 3 (2009), p. 128. Note that Kombo gathers this from his reading of John Mbiti, *African Religions and Philosophy* (London: Heinemann, 1969), p. 39; John Mbiti, *Introduction to African Religion* (London: Heinemann, 1975) p. 44.

¹⁴ Kwasi Wiredu, "How Not to Compare African Traditional Thought with Western Thought," in *Transition*, 75/76 (1997), pp. 320-327.

against conceiving of Africans as intellectually inferior.”¹⁵ He continues by lamenting how African traditions are delimited to “spectacles of otherwise enlightened Africans” and how the West tends to see these acts as “superstitious” and not recognizing “the content of a belief,” seeing it rather as a “mode of entertainment.”¹⁶

Where the West views African witchcraft as superstitious, what they surmise is an irrational spectacle for their own amusement bereft of serious reflection. However, Wiredu is keen to point out the hypocrisy in all this: there are people who proudly propret to be witches in London; superstition runs rampant throughout Western society; Westerners too pray for rain and for good harvests. The list goes on, and how is any of this at all different from African praxis?¹⁷ And finally, the West neglects that there are plenty of Africans who use rationality throughout their daily lives, which cannot be relegated to an accessory of their consciousness. Rather, it is germane to their own sense of being.

Consequently, Wiredu argues that “the truth, then, is that rational knowledge is not the preserve of the modern West, nor is superstition a peculiarity of the African peoples.”¹⁸ What this article advances, and what Wiredu will expand upon throughout his work, is that superstition, religion, or ‘faith’ construed in whichever sense can only be cross-culturally compared with corresponding counterparts, and one cannot delimit African culture to the realm of the spiritual as so many Western thinkers so often do.¹⁹ More to the point, Wiredu’s critique aims to remove faith from the conversation between African and Western philosophy, lest one falls into the stereotype that Africans are too superstitious to be rationally serious.²⁰

This is why he begins with a moral anthropology which expands to an empirical metaphysics rather than the other way around, which is typically how Western philosophies present their larger claims. Some may disagree with this reading of Wiredu, but I find it valid and sound because Wiredu’s description of the Akan’s empirical metaphysics arises from the cultural universals of communication (language) and the Golden Rule (morality). These universals

¹⁵ Ibid., p. 321.

¹⁶ Ibid., p. 321.

¹⁷ Ibid., p. 322.

¹⁸ Ibid., p. 322.

¹⁹ *CUP*, pp. 48-52.

²⁰ Wiredu, “How Not to Compare African Traditional Thought,” p. 326.

come first and then they develop particular metaphysics for particular cultures. Otherwise, Wiredu would be stating that the Akan's empirical metaphysics is a *universal metaphysics* for all persons and communities.

Pressing on, Wiredu also finds no need to generate or explain African philosophy on the West's terms since presenting his Akan philosophy in a Western fashion would strip from it all nuance and intellectual force. Therefore, dispensing with the concept of faith – removing it from philosophical consideration – allows him to place African rationality as the focal point of any dialogue with Western thought. Africa's *intellectual* beliefs become the center of consideration rather than being ancillary to Africa's religious beliefs, the latter of which the West does not understand yet nonetheless fixates upon.

This being the case, Wiredu's definition of faith holds some peculiar details and needs to be read in full. Note how, although he allows space for a self-reflective practice of faith, his definition emphasizes an unthinking adherence to dogmatism:

The word 'faith' can be used in various senses. ... [in the way I employ it, I mean that] *what is believed by faith is, by virtue of that fact, inaccessible to rational evaluation. Accordingly, there can be no discussion with non-believers.* ¶ There is another complication. Religious dogmatists (of the anti-rational variety) are apt to maintain the dependence of morality on religion. The notion of what is morally right now comes to mean what is willed by the God in whom the particular believer believes. *The combination of anti-rational faith with this divine-command view of morality can lead to imperiously held views, not only about how abysmally wrong-headed non-conformers are, but also about how ungodly and unregenerate they are.* ... Given [that they believe their morality is God-given] they will hold their beliefs very strongly; indeed, with uncompromising inflexibility. ¶ ... Clearly, so long as such beliefs hold sway among their proprietors, there can be no chance of a dialogue. *The reason is that dialogue presupposes the fallibility of all its participants.* Consequently, if such beliefs should happen to function even as undertones of political dispute, the difficulties of conflict resolution are multiplied a thousand-fold. The only ray of hope that one espies in this matter is owing to the fact that in some dogmatic religions ... there are some devotees who do not entertain their beliefs in an anti-rational manner. *They appear outnumbered,* but, since time is infinite, such believers might, perhaps, come some day to outnumber their more faith-based partners in piety by the power of rational education.²¹ (Emphasis mine)

²¹ Wiredu, "Reflections on Cultural Diversity," p. 126.

Wiredu often references this notion of faith within his works, but not as openly as does above.²² On the one hand, it is quite problematic that Wiredu establishes his own definition of faith without serious consideration or investigation into the way in which the concept of faith operates in various theologies and philosophies of religion.²³ This makes him liable for creating a strawman against faith, particularly when emphasizing its so-called unquestioning nature. In a sense, his critique against the unthinking, stereotypical rendering of African Traditional Thought could likewise be placed against him and his definition of faith. Furthermore, numerous theologians across cultures, traditions, and generations likewise critique the fundamentalist faith Wiredu highlights, and they do so to emphasize the ‘pro-rational,’ open faith he espouses. In short, Wiredu is picking low-hanging fruit here, neglecting rich, cross-cultural traditions of theological and philosophical reflections on the concept of faith.²⁴

On the other hand, granting Wiredu some reprieve, I find that what he is really critiquing is not religion *per se*, but unquestioning anti-rationalities and their dogmatic ideologies. Note that his moral anthropology argues that ethical personhood is inherently rational. ‘Faith,’ therefore, becomes a means for him to critique an irrational – or blindly applied – morality that enters society under the guise of religious dogma and/or ideology. Contrarily, though his morality is impartial, it is empathetic and therefore is fundamentally rational: it holds to a moral standard of conduct, yet one’s actions are weighed and judged – hence reasonably considered – against that standard.²⁵

Importantly, while he will often attribute it to religion, secular institutions and their frameworks are not immune to unthinking dogmatism and irrationality. Their problematics arise through a susceptibility towards ideologies divorced from reason. So crafted, they employ a similar unthinking, instrumental reasoning which relies upon a set of unquestionable values for their moral-social acts and beliefs:

²² See: Kwasi Wiredu, “Truth and Dialogue,” in *Cultures. Conflict, Analysis, Dialogue*, Christian Kanzian and Edmund Runggaldier, SJ; eds. (Boston: De Gruyter, 2007), p. 127; Kwasi Wiredu, “Identity as an Intellectual Problem,” p. 212; Kwasi Wiredu, *Philosophy and African Culture*, p. 28, p. 169 fn. 22.

²³ Motsamai Molefe offers the strongest critique I have seen against this throughout his article, “A Critique of Kwasi Wiredu’s Humanism and Impartiality.” See also: Chapter Six, pp. 135-141, where I revisit Wiredu’s concept of faith.

²⁴ Note that I am speaking solely about the concept of faith, here, and not the concept of religion.

²⁵ Wiredu, “Society and Democracy in Africa,” pp. 35-36.

*A man pushing a doctrinaire line does not in the standard case say, 'I know that the policy I am pursuing is not reasonable but I don't care.' What usually happens is that his sensitivity to observation and reasoning is dulled by emotion; his perception is distorted and consequently he honestly regards his line as the best.*²⁶ (Emphasis mine)

What this critique of faith and/or dogmatism means for us is that Wiredu is intent on showing the empirical nature of morality and thus the rational theory of mind which crafts an Akan empirical metaphysics. As Finomo Julia Awajiusuk puts it, for Wiredu, “African morality is not founded on religion but on rational reflection as to what is conducive to human welfare. African traditional ethics is thus based on natural light of reason with conscience playing a central role.”²⁷ Remember that personhood is something one acquires through social esteem, it is communally awarded and not merely given. Even being ‘someone’ requires rational consensus. If it is true that being a person is socially rational, which necessitates an empirical encounter between person and community, then it follows that understanding the world is likewise fundamentally social and, accordingly, fundamentally empirical.

Thus, for Wiredu, we arrive at a bottom-up metaphysics: First, we require communication and a foundational ‘golden rule’ (however socially construed) to survive. Then, once survival is secured, we develop a shared language through which we develop a shared culture. Within that shared culture, we develop personal esteem through others whilst reflexively giving that to others as well. Then, from this shared culture and its moral encounter with the outer, concrete world, we develop a sense of this world and the way in which it works together (whether in harmony or discord). Finally, this sense becomes a metaphysics in the way that it helps further organize our moral-social encounters and our own sense of personhood as we interact with others and the world at large.

In the next section, I will lay this out in detail. For now, though, notice how intent Wiredu is on the rational nature of this metaphysics: he is not arguing that there is no God (for indeed the Akan believe in a God), but rather is stressing that one cannot rely upon an unthinking ideology for moral or personal comfort. Not only is one’s view of the world at stake but so is one’s own personality. This amplifies the consequences of an empirical metaphysics.

²⁶ Wiredu, *Philosophy and African Culture*, p. 177.

²⁷ Finomo Julia Awajiusuk, “Reflections on African Ethics: A Case For Cultural Relativism,” *Ciências da Religião: história e sociedade*, 12:1, p. 41.

3. Wiredu's Empirical Metaphysics

At this juncture, it is important to remember that what follows will be Wiredu's reading of Akan metaphysics, not a definitive account of Akan thought itself.²⁸ That being said, Wiredu sees the Akan as "a highly metaphysical people in that they are very curious about concepts such as God, human personality, destiny, free will, causation. But they are preeminently empirical in their intellectual orientation."²⁹ The primary difference to Western cultures lies within this relation to experience (hence his emphasis on the empirical). The implications of this concern what could be called God and how that God 'operates,' if you will, within the universe. As Wiredu explains:

In radical contrast, the Akan Supreme Being is a kind of cosmic architect, a fashioner of the world order, who occupies the apex of the same hierarchy of being which accommodates, in its intermediate ranges, the ancestors and living mortals, and, in its lower reaches, animals, plants, and inanimate objects. *This universe of being is ontologically homogenous. In other words, everything that exists exists in exactly the same sense as everything else. And this sense is empirical, broadly speaking.* In the Akan language to exist is *wo ho*, which, in literal translation, means 'to be at some place.' There is no equivalent, in Akan, of the existential 'to be' or 'is' of English, and there is no way of pretending in that medium to be speaking of the existence of something which is not in space. *This locative connotation of the Akan concept of existence is irreducible except metaphorically.* Thus you might speak of there existing an explanation of something ... without incurring any obligation of special specification, because an explanation is not an object in any but a metaphorical sense, and to a metaphorical object corresponds only a metaphorical kind of space. *The same applies to so-called abstract entities. In the Akan conceptual framework, then, existence is spatial. Now, since whatever transcendence means in this context, it implies existence beyond space, it follows that talk of any transcendent being is not just false but unintelligible from an Akan point of view.*³⁰ (Emphasis mine)

We will return to this lengthy quote in Chapter Six to unpack its notion of becoming in and through space.³¹ For now, note how, while there is an implied hierarchy of being, each entity exists in the same fashion as every other being. The hierarchy is crafted through esteem or status rather than anything ontologically pre-ordained: God exists in just the same sense as

²⁸ For his primary critics, amongst other examples, Kwasi Wiredu, Kwame Gyekye, eds.; *Personhood and Community: Ghanaian Philosophical Studies, Vol. I* (Washington DC: The Council for Research in Values and Philosophy, 1992). Wiredu addresses many of these critiques in the final chapter of *CUP*.

²⁹ *CUP*, p. 87.

³⁰ *CUP*, pp. 49-50.

³¹ See: Chapter Six, pp. 128-131.

an ant and in the same realm of space as an ant, where each occupies a specific space and time. Though God or an ant may hold different social statuses, their ontological and spatial status remains the same.

Moreover, as part of being in this same sense of space and time, both God and the ant are subject to the same rules: the Akan adhere to an “inherent law-likeness of reality. And the crucial consideration is that God’s relationship with the rest of the universe, that is, the world, is also conceived to be inherently law-like. ... Divine law-likeness *only* ensures that there will be no arbitrary interferences in the course of the world-process.”³² Wiredu explains that this is why the Akan do not appeal to God for intervention since God is not supernatural to the law-likeness of the world; the supernatural/natural dichotomy “has no place in the Akan system of thought.”³³

This means that even metaphorical notions accord to concrete experiences. There is no abstraction. This entails, for Wiredu, that the ‘concrete’ nature from which these ideas are derived maintains their ‘concreteness,’ or physicality. What this means is that Akan metaphysics is entirely spatial: it does not separate contemplation about the world from the physical nature of the world itself. It rejects any transcendental categorization of the principles of knowledge, as one may see in Kantian metaphysics. Every concept reflected upon in the Akan worldview corresponds to the concrete experiences within the world; one cannot hypothesize the world to reflect upon the world since even metaphors exist in a form of metaphorical space.

What holds this empirical metaphysics together, then, are two key concepts: First, that metaphysics cannot be done alone nor through inward introspection. Metaphysical contemplation must be done through reflecting upon shared (i.e., relational) experiences, whereby these reflections are socially negotiated to reach a consensus about the world. Second, for these experiences to happen, they must happen in a given space for them to be concrete. Accordingly, one’s reflection upon those experiences cannot divorce said experiences from their spatialized nature. Doing so would negate their concrete actuality (or the possibility of them being actualized) and move them into an abstract realm accessible

³² *CUP*, p. 50, emphasis Wiredu’s.

³³ *CUP*, p. 51, emphasis mine.

only to the individual. This negation destroys the social-empirical nature of the concept/experience in question.³⁴

Returning to this notion of ‘law-likeness,’ recall that Wiredu states that “a human being is a rule-following animal, and language is nothing but an arrangement of rules.”³⁵ Accordingly, when thinking about the world and/or cosmology, Wiredu argues that the Akan hold that everything has its explanation: “*biribiara wo nenkyerease* – a kind of principle of sufficient reason.”³⁶ This explanation is found in the order of the world, but a lingering concern is from whence this explanation comes? I argue that Wiredu sees the origins of this explanation emerge out of the universal, vital forces he locates within basic human survival.

Going back to Wiredu’s cultural universals – communication and the ‘Golden Rule’ – we find Wiredu describing how communication builds a language through referents between things/events that become words out of which vocabulary, syntax, and grammar arise. Furthermore, morality happens through relational interaction, establishing ethical/moral standards, i.e., an empathetic impartiality. Wiredu’s general theory of language, part and parcel with his general theory of morality, is built through experiences and interchanges between persons.

These interchanges create a relational and social network whereby explanations for the unknown are negotiated in the same way in which one struggles to describe – or a community struggles to judge or understand – an event. As these networks evolve within a community, an explanation of both that community’s purpose and the meaning of (and order to) the world likewise evolves. This follows with the notion of an intellectual evolution, as described in Chapter Three.³⁷ For our present purposes, though, this is what makes his empirical metaphysics always already moral and political: it is socially vital to the sustenance of the community and is always already being socially negotiated as the community encounters

³⁴ This negation, or divorce between the social reflection and empirical experience, is the great contrast between Akan metaphysics and Western metaphysics. As mentioned above, this contrast often gets rendered out when translating African thought into Western paradigms. This is why many perceive Africans to be overtly spiritual people when their worldviews are, in fact, incongruent to the supernatural/natural paradigm altogether. Moreover, addressing Akan metaphysics as a purely immanent metaphysics is likewise a problem since it denudes Akan metaphysics’ social – and thus morally political – nature.

³⁵ *CUP*, p. 24.

³⁶ *CUP*, p. 50.

³⁷ See: Chapter Three, pp. 59-65.

other communities and the world at large. These events build an explanation of, and give meaning to, the world order. In other words, they build *upwards* to a metaphysics.

What makes this exceptional from a Western metaphysics – whether religious or secular – is not the lack of an appeal to God, any transcendent *a priori*, or to an abstract idealism. Rather, it is the fact that speculative reasoning is never a consideration. In technical language, speculative reasoning, in the Kantian/Hegelian sense at least, is a philosophical notion of thinking about thought itself (i.e., infinite reason), and this would literally be ‘none sense’ due to the pure fact that it never practically relates to the here-and-now of the person or community participating in the reflection upon the issue at hand.³⁸ If a thought cannot be construed by, or corresponded to, an experiential sensation, then it holds no sense whatsoever to think it.

Moreover, speculative reasoning’s solitary introspection would be ‘none sense’ due to its ignorance of the fact that all the content of our thinking comes through engagements –

³⁸ For more on speculative reasoning, see: Justin Sands, “The Concept of *Aufhebung* in the Thought of Merold Westphal: Appropriation and Recontextualization,” *International Journal of Philosophy and Theology* (June 2015) p. 3 fn. 13. What I mean by speculative reasoning is as follows. Note how its determination to open reason to pure abstraction or infinite reason is vastly contrarian to Wiredu’s empirical metaphysics:

In *The Encyclopaedia Logic*, Hegel distinguishes infinite reason from the finite reason that dominated philosophy prior to Kant. This finite form of reasoning had not yet understood what reason could or could not do (which is why Kant’s critique of reason was so important for Hegel), and thus took for granted that one could reason about things-in-themselves with no attention to their predicates or relation to other things (EL §26–27). ‘The presupposition of the older metaphysics,’ Hegel summarizes, ‘was that of the naïve belief generally, namely, that thinking grasps what things are in-themselves, that things only are what they genuinely are when they are [captured] in thought’ (EL §28Z). In this manner, older metaphysics took up ‘the abstract determinations of thought immediately,’ which allowed the thinker to consider these predicates – these attachments to the thing-in-itself under consideration – as a part of what makes the thing a thing, what makes it ‘true’ as a thing in relation to the thinker (EL §28Z).

In contrast, speculative thought after Kant opens the thing in question to be considered from an ‘infinite form of reason’ by expressing that the thing in question has certain qualities that cannot ‘be brought to consciousness through what is finite;’ i.e., the thinker cannot fully bring about the abstract qualities of the thing in question through rationalization (EL §28Z). Infinite thinking thus turns inward toward speculation, and sublates this acknowledgment of finite thinking, accepting its limitations – what reason can and cannot do – while also cancelling these limitations in respect to finite thinking’s naiveté (that it can think of things-in-themselves), which allows the thinker to proceed toward an infinite speculation of the thing in itself. In this way, one transitions from thinking about things-in-themselves to thinking about thinking, which thus makes this an infinite form of thinking for Hegel: there is no limiting opposition when one is thinking about thinking since no object stands over against cognition as that which is not-cognition. Thus, Hegel states: ‘Infinite or speculative thinking, on the contrary [to finite thinking’s restriction to determinations], makes determinations likewise, but, in determining, in limiting, it sublates this defect again. Infinity must not be interpreted as an abstract, ever-receding beyond’ but in a simple manner of negation of limitation while cognizant of those limitations (EL §28Z). Quotes are from: Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, *Encyclopedia Logic: Part I of the Encyclopedia of Philosophical Sciences with the Zusätze*. T. F. Geraets, W. A. Suchting, and H. W. Harris, trans. (Indianapolis: Hackett Publishing, 1991).

through sensory experiences – with the people and the world in which we inhabit. We cannot survive in the world alone, *pace* Wiredu; we thusly cannot think about the world alone. We must always remember that we live in communion with others – whether harmoniously or discordantly – and that communion always already imparts our notions about the space in which we live.

Finally, just as an empirical metaphysic refuses abstraction, and therefore cannot be stereotyped as overtly supernatural or transcendent, it likewise cannot be confused as overly immanent. Nor can it be understood as a remixed Lockean-style *Weltanschauung*. Remember that empirical, for Wiredu, is not merely an existential ideal but entails the capacity for critically reflecting upon experience. Empirical, here, means not just the experience but the *capability to contemplate experience*. Importantly, this capability reflexively allows one to think or reflect upon previous, present, and future experiences in their becoming a person within community. I mentioned this Chapter Two, but it bears repeating:

In other words, we are not born with a mind that is a tabula rasa, as the seventeenth-century British empiricist philosopher John Locke suggested. *Rather we are born with only the potential for one*. The acquisition, through suckling, nursing, and nurturing by parents or persons in loco parentis, of the gestured rudiments of language is the first hint of a baby's pretension to mind. *Even this much is already heavily laden with culture, that is, with a certain particular way of becoming sensitive to "the other" and subsequently cognizant of the self.*³⁹ (Emphasis mine)

Sure, the Akan are curious about God, nature, and events unknown, but their curiosity flows through the practical, pragmatic functioning they experience within the world; the capacity for mind is met with their reception of the culture which nurtures them. Furthering this, the laws through which they experience the world also dictate the way in which the Akan understand that world and, consequently, the way in which they morally engage that world. Again, it is a bottom-up metaphysics: from the potentiality of forming fundamental, vital exchanges to culture and moral norms, to exploring the questions of both the mundane and cosmos, Wiredu's empirical metaphysics is one in which its practitioners need to go out into the world to find their sense of themselves and their world.

³⁹ Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," p. 214.

Stepping back for a second, one sees how this connects our conversation in Chapter Three, where I highlighted the evolutionary aspects of Wiredu's subjective agency. The endgame, for Wiredu, is to see the world find consensus and harmonize (or reconcile) discord, particularly concerning violence. In that chapter, I noted how it begins with a relationship between an individual and their community, and that it spirals outward to engage the world at large which includes other communities. His empirical metaphysics holds the same moral imperative to evolve intellectually the human species. Resultantly, as we come to know more about other persons in our lives, other cultures/worlds, and even the cosmos, that knowledge comes with a moral responsibility since it all arrives through experience or, better said, engagements.

Again, for Wiredu, all engagements or acts are moral – be they benign decisions or important ones – and thus all of knowledge and especially the rational ordering of knowledge – i.e., metaphysics writ large – must be moral as well: we weigh and judge not just what we have learned, but how we have learned (e.g., ethical experimentations), and how we use what we have learned (e.g., did explorers discover new continents to colonize and enslave persons, or to better understand the vast scope of Earth?).

This evolution is therefore a moral unfolding on both a personal and communal level. Finding one's sense of the world and, in tandem, finding one's personhood or character entails a sense of becoming. Again, one *becomes* a person through their engagements with their community, and a community *becomes* itself through interpersonal interactions and external encounters with the world in which they find themselves. From the above, we now understand the way in which an empirical metaphysics develops from a socio-political rationality which individuals employ to not only find understanding or meaning from worldly events, but also to understand their own moral character. This rationality thus guides one on their path to becoming a person, but, through its metaphysical nature, there appears to be larger concerns involved beyond one's personhood. This is what I will explore in the section.

4. The Relational Implications of a Moral Anthropology and its Empirical Metaphysics

What I have detailed above is how Wiredu's moral anthropology is not just communal in the sense of personhood and community, but also communal in the sense that its metaphysics is socialized. For the latter, a thing only becomes worthy of contemplation in relation to other things in and through the space we all cohabitate. This section will touch upon what I find to

be the lynchpin that binds Wiredu's philosophy: a relational or consensual logic that is necessarily moral and political.

Wiredu argues that humanity is a rule-following species that seeks order to the world. Furthermore, as we have seen in his metaphysics, throughout these developments humanity creates meaning in and through its survival. It makes sense, then, that his reading of the Akan's empirical metaphysics establishes a set of rules for contemplation and even has its own principle of sufficient reason (*'biribiara wo nenkyerease'*).

What I find interesting is that these rules – from who is a person to what is God – are both co-developed and co-effective. One can only form a language with others. One can only bestow personhood (let alone acquire it) through others. And finally, one can only find meaning in the world through a socialized and logical inference of signs and symbols. Each aspect cannot be done in silo, nothing can be understood or be fundamentally comprehensible without community.

Moreover, nothing develops or changes without encounter. This is why spatiality is so fundamental to Wiredu's empirical metaphysics: if a fundamental order is to be applied to the world, then it can only be applied so far as there is a *shared experience of the world*. Empirical experience is required for two reasons: First, something must happen for it to be shared. Second, for something to be meaningful it must be understood in relation to other things/events.

Concerning the first requirement, since there is no divine revelation or anything beyond the world itself, then something must have happened for it to be shared. The happening of the event takes place within the world – in time and space – which means that the event can be comprehended by others since they presumably have similar baseline referents. Even if it is a brand-new experience, it can be logically broken down by the community in accordance with what they already believe; this makes the event comprehensible and, more importantly, incorporable into that community's understanding of the world. In so doing, an evolutionary co-development occurs in their notion of how the world works – what is possible and impossible – and changes in tandem with their comprehension of the new experience in question. This co-development has a knock-on effect in that it may reorient their notions of other concepts, objects, and even laws.

Concerning the second requirement, for anything to generate meaning, it must do so in relation to others' experiences. Even in the realm of metaphor or concept, if one is to convey their thoughts, they must employ a shared language – or, more importantly, a shared sensibility – so that it is understood by others. There must be referents for others to grasp, and those references are derived from shared experiences. It is only thus that someone can share their beliefs with others. One can experience something alone, sure, but its meaningfulness expands when that experience is taught to others whilst others share their own experience in turn. In conversation or, more technically, through social negotiations, a community comes to understand the world in which they live and the meaning of life within that world. If something 'otherworldly' happens, then it changes as these social negotiations carry on throughout generations. It does not matter what one experiences, if they share it and it is received by the community, then the community judges it through their remembrance of past experiences to arrive at an understanding of the situation and event at hand.

This second requirement adds moral and political weight to Wiredu's empirical metaphysics in that *understanding the world and its order is a communal effort*. This requires what I have called social negotiations, but what Wiredu refers to as consensus building.⁴⁰ Wiredu argues that societies work best when they accept a consensus-based approach to social negotiations. This entails that, while not everyone will be in absolute agreement, they can come to terms with some key ideas/concepts, which not only provide social cohesion but also further the moral prerogatives of the community. There is variance of opinion, but an agreement on fundamental or essential ideas helps perpetuate the community's existence.

Regarding Wiredu's empirical metaphysics, what his notion of consensus informs us of is that beliefs not only require a symbolic/linguistic community of referents to be expressed, but they also require a social community of persons to be shared and understood. Far too often rationality – especially within Western philosophy – is adversarial in nature, where 'the best idea wins.' Yet, who picks the 'best idea' and is it always the correct one? Moreover, adversarial rationality has silenced the voices of the marginalized in pursuit of a *self-assured* sense of progress. A progress that often becomes an unthinking, unquestionable ideology. As

⁴⁰ CUP, pp. 8-9, 106, 120, 143-144, and especially 163-164, 184-186.

such, adversarial rationality often fails its primary function as a mode of thought and its impetus as a moral component for social cohesion and progress.

A detour is in order to make these implications clearer and to connect them to Wiredu's wider philosophy. Scope and space prohibit us from delving too deeply into Wiredu's critique of democracy and his advocacy of a consensual democracy, but his rationale for a consensual democracy can be helpful in unpacking how these social negotiations work. For Wiredu, Western democracy essentially is combative.⁴¹ He finds that Western democracies function on an oppositional model whereby the entire citizenry's notion of what is morally right for their society is placed into competition. This 'winner takes all' form of governance is innately confrontational and, at times, can even inhibit the moral-social growth of a community by its sheer competitive design.⁴²

Consider, for instance, how voting for a smaller party's candidate is often derided as a wasted vote since that candidate has no chance of winning. Compounding the matter, it could even be seen as helping the party least representative of your views since you have effectively taken away a vote from the party who best represents your views. In contrast, Wiredu advocates for a democracy by consensus, where communities come together to form a general agreement.⁴³ Again, agreement is not in totality but in conversation with other points of view: people arrive at the best path forward through what they agree upon and not against what they disagree with. The point of consensus is not to dissolve dissent, thereby creating a univocal vision of governance, but to remove the belligerence one sees in adversarial democracies when the winning party often dominates and silences the losing party, thereby marginalizing them and creating more and more resentment.⁴⁴

Conversely, a moral anthropology which develops an empirical metaphysics in pursuit of understanding its own moral progress finds its purpose through social consensus. Derived from the core needs of human survival, then to how humans become persons, and eventually to how societies form cultures, a moral anthropology dovetails back to question the 'hows'

⁴¹ Kwasi Wiredu, "Democracy by Consensus: Some Conceptual Considerations," pp. 230-231.

⁴² Wiredu, "Democracy by Consensus," pp. 228-229, *CUP*, pp. 178-179. See also: Danelle Fourie, Justin Sands, "Adversarial Democracy and the Flattening of Choice: A Marcusean Analysis of Sen's Capability Theory's Reliance Upon Universal Democracy as a Means for Overcoming Inequality," *Open Philosophy*, 5 (2022), pp. 675-688.

⁴³ Wiredu, "Democracy by Consensus," pp. 237-238.

⁴⁴ *CUP*, p 175, 179.

along this journey: how did we become persons? How did we become a society? Now that we know new things about the world – which has changed the way in which we think the world works (e.g., the ‘laws’ of the universe) – how does that change the meaning of not just our own life but the meaning of our community?

Importantly, these questions, asked through Wiredu’s framework, are asymptotic and keep evolving. Contrary to an adversarial culture, there is no best idea, or personal best, or award for the best community, but rather constant evolution such that good persons can always become better persons, good communities better ones, and similarly good encounters with the environment or other cultures can become better encounters. If, however, they become worse, then one can rationally trace back to where everything went wrong. It has this power to do so since nothing is unquestionable; nothing is held by ‘faith’ in Wiredu’s sense of the term (however problematic it may be).

One could say, in sum, that Wiredu is at once critiquing Western rationality and its various anti-rationalities whilst proclaiming another way to display how we are not alone in our reasoning. We are not alone in our expressions about the universe. We have others to contemplate with and against, and the whole enterprise of thinking is communal. Optimistic, it very much is, but it is a good distance away from the idealism which subjugated his continent and its people. From bottom-up to full circle, his moral anthropology declares a metaphysics that is moral before it situates itself amongst the stars, amongst the cosmos, and the meaning of cohabitating this planet. This morality, though, is socially negotiated, therefore it nakedly recognizes that it too can be co-opted for ill-gotten means. The question becomes, then, what society should we negotiate?

5. Final Analysis: Who do We Want to Be? What Society Do We Want to Have?

For the thesis of this work, it is not my place to dictate or imagine an ideal society. I hardly think Wiredu would even appreciate such a task given that it would disinvite future generations from the discussion. What I have done in this chapter is explore the metaphysical implications of Wiredu’s moral anthropology and how they may present threads to weave a communion between worldviews. I did not have the scope and space to explore in-depth his notions of an ethic and ethics, which I touched upon in Chapter Two, but one can see how they do fold into a larger project of a communal, consensus-based ethic for African

communities and beyond.⁴⁵ Furthermore, others have covered his debates about these ambitions.⁴⁶

What this chapter sought to do was to connect his notion of personhood through community to his larger metaphysics, and what it unpacked is the empirical and spatial nature of this metaphysics. It is not a static metaphysics, nor is it one grounded upon God or some other self-legitimizing entity, as seen in Heidegger's critique of the onto-theological construction of metaphysics which I previously covered via Serequeberhan. I sought to show the moralized and political nature of Wiredu's empirical metaphysics, which rejects any and all unthinking, anti-rational ideologues to make itself viable.

However, there is a danger here. Humans are well too capable of transforming anything into an unthinking ideology. Wiredu's empirical metaphysics is not immune to this: the consensus of a people can still agree upon war, even genocide. We should be mindful of this without dismissing Wiredu's metaphysics out of hand.

Why? Because Wiredu's empirical metaphysics, if meaningful to those who adhere to it, openly states that it is in the hands of the people – incumbent upon the people – to find order and harmony in the world according to the rules and order of the world. This is why he believes that the Golden Rule is fundamental to uniting humanity. It is also a fundamentally political rule, which undergirds this empirical metaphysics. As a bottom-up metaphysics, its epistemology is beholden to the morality it exhibits. Although Wiredu's concept of personhood through community holds this morality, it is up to both the person and the community to express that morality as they see it unfold, in the here and now, in the spatiality of existence, and not in the clouds or skies which move at the will of a select few.

⁴⁵ See: Chapter Two, pp. 30-32, 37-40.

⁴⁶ For an overview, see: Barry Hallen, *Reading Wiredu*, pp. 70-80; See also: Kwame Gyekye, "Person and Community in Akan Thought," pp. 101-122; Motsamai Molefe, "A Critique of Kwasi Wiredu's Humanism and Impartiality," pp. 91-110; Motsamai Molefe, "An African Perspective on the Partiality and Impartiality Debate: Insights from Kwasi Wiredu's Moral Philosophy," pp. 470-482.

CHAPTER FIVE:

WHERE IS THE 'WE' IN TIME?

BERGSON, 'CHRONOPOLITICS,' AND THE POSSIBILITY OF *COMMUNAL DURATION*

1. Introduction and Orientation(s)

Throughout this work I have emphasized the socio-political nature of concepts such as personhood and community. Following this, I likewise will argue that, though often presumed as a neutral concept in many Western intellectual investigations, time is always already political. Historicity and/or historical context often carries this political weight – in phenomenology, for example, time often is examined as if it were in a vacuum or that there is a fundamental temporality prior to any political machinations – yet this fails to recognize its conditional privileges to Western worldviews.¹ We shall see this in my critique of Bergson, but in sum, though many phenomenologists conclude that 'we are time itself,' I beggar to ask, '*where is the 'we' in this temporality?*'

Though, of course, these thinkers use 'we' as shorthand for 'the self,' I think that this shorthand reveals a glaring lacuna concerning how time is not experienced alone (even if that which is being perceived is an object and not another self). I will address this lacuna by engaging and critiquing, or perhaps adapting, Henri Bergson's notions of intuition, *duration*, and memory. Through my critique, I will emphasize how Bergson points us to a relational logic between time and memory which reveals to us the socially mediated nature of experience and its construal of time. Or, more succinctly, the chronopolitics of time and memory.

¹ See: Heath Massey, *The Origin of Time: Heidegger and Bergson*, (Albany: SUNY, 2015), pp. 140-144, 165-167; James Gilbert-Walsh, "The Concept of Time: Archaic Perplexity in Bergson and Heidegger," *Human Studies*, 22 (2010) pp. 175-181. Note that Massey essentially argues that, while Heidegger initially dismisses Bergson, he eventually moves closer to Bergsonian *duration* than many may realize. Gilbert-Walsh argues something similar, albeit with more emphasis on them being antipodes rather than parallels to each other.

This, I argue, shows us that temporality must be first understood as a shared experience before one can perform a phenomenological reduction or explore how the Cartesian ego renders meaning through time. The result of this will be a stronger hermeneutical framework for phenomenology. Though this chapter will only deal with temporality, the next chapter's conversation between Wiredu and Bergson will bring spatiality into the discussion. The final three chapters – on Serequeberhan, Bergson, and then a conversation between them – will allow us to explore how individuals and communities, time and space, and historicity interlace through politics.

Since unpacking Bergson's philosophy can become unwieldy, this chapter will only cover three aspects: his method of intuition, and his concepts of *duration* and memory. Although I recognize that Bergson first explored time and space *and then* went to memory, I think that this is both the most approachable way to understand Bergson and is a better integration of Bergson into my project. Furthermore, like my treatment of Wiredu and Serequeberhan, I will read Bergson as a stand-alone thinker and not in relation to Heidegger, Deleuze, or whether Bergsonian philosophy is a proper phenomenology, all of which have become primary discussions within the field.

After describing Bergson's philosophy in the second section, my third section will follow Leonard Lawler's insight into the Cartesian-like "loneliness" within Bergson's philosophy.² Intuition is a deeply introspective method that comes with the disadvantage of not being able to see how *duration* overlooks the political nature of its inquiries. In short, it lacks the always already socialized nature of our experiences and memories; when he wrote *Time and Free Will*, *Matter and Memory*, and *Introduction to Metaphysics*, he was not primarily concerned with the political nature of any of the issues/concepts/arguments with which he engages.

Therefore, in line with a step-by-step approach to bringing Bergson into our larger conversation, I will read his work as a developmental process that ultimately leads to a politics. Note that, for Bergson, 'politics' is the correct term since it is not a morality *per se*, which causes friction between Wiredu and Bergson. This will be explored further in the next chapter, but is important to remember when reading what follows.

² Leonard Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, (New York: Bloomsbury, 2003), pp. 68-70.

For our present purposes, though, I find that his intuitive method of understanding time and memory via *duration* articulates a sterilized notion of the mind prior to any socio-political engagement, as if one first needs to realize how they experience life before one can engage the questions life presents. My claim, which I will unfold via Lawler and later through chronopolitics, will be that this isolated inward approach fools itself into thinking it can fully understand ‘pure memory’ or hold a decontaminated temporality, two issues that need resolution prior to any future engagement with Bergson.

This is not a mere oversight given the deep wounds created by time’s hegemonically political history, which will be the focus of my fourth section. Charles Mills’s “chronopolitics” will be my starting point since Mills uncovers the politicization of temporality and how these politics never go away; they cannot merely be bracketed out.³ Mills thus opens an avenue to hermeneutically retrieve the experience of colonial time throughout Africa, which I will do through a brief detour via Keletso Atkins’s history of the temporal clashes between the Zulu and the early British settlers of the Natal Colony.⁴ This history shows how temporality – both as an experiential and conceptual issue – became a massive obstacle for imperial subjugation as well as a subtle weapon of resistance. Through this retrieval, I will close this section by looking at Anthony Monteiro’s call for temporality to be re-examined from a decolonial and African(a) point of view: the philosophical question of *Being Black* – as seen through W.E.B. De Bois and Frantz Fanon – often employs a temporal framework foreign to the culture and thus consciousness of Black persons. In De Bois’ case, this is part and parcel of a double consciousness; in Fanon’s, it is essential to his elaboration on the facticity of Blackness.⁵ The purpose of this section, again, is to argue that if phenomenology or any other philosophy aims to understand temporality unto itself, it needs to understand the politics through which time unfolds; one cannot approach time as if it is *sub speci aeterni* or, in Bergson’s case, *sub speci durationis*.⁶

³ Charles W Mills, “The Chronopolitics of Racial Time,” *Time & Society*, 29:2 (2020), 297-317.

⁴ Keletso E Atkins, *The Moon is Dead! Give Us Our Money! The Cultural Origins of an African Work Ethic, Natal, South Africa, 1843-1900* (Portsmouth: Heinemann, 1993).

⁵ Unpacking the temporal issues within De Bois and Fanon would be a monograph – if not years long project – unto itself. Thus, in this section I will stick with Monteiro’s argument for succinctness and because he is one of the few thinkers, at least from my extensive research, to directly address this problem.

⁶ *CM*, p. 151.

In my final analysis, I will answer the question of *'where is the 'we' in 'we are time itself?'* by returning to Bergson's concept of memory. Perhaps pushing Bergson further beyond his initial intentions, I find that chronopolitics can resolve the issues of Bergson's isolated introspection via what I call a *communal duration*; that is, a shared sense of *duration* through a mediated – and therefore socio-political – sense of memory. At this stage, I am merely proposing this concept and will develop it throughout my reading of Bergson within this work.

Regarding this chapter, though, I will initiate my proposal through John Mbiti's concept of 'African time.'⁷ Though often critiqued, Mbiti's notion of time relies heavily on memory, which I will show is where historicity, culture, and a politics can enter *duration's* relational logic between the perceiver and the perceived. In short, just as *duration* 'frees' temporality from its metaphorical and quantized spatializations, a chronopolitics' shared experience of temporality – that one does not perceive time by oneself but within a world of shared perceptions of time – likewise 'frees' *duration* from its loneliness. The conclusion is that the concept of a *communal duration* allows the 'we' of 'we are time itself' to be phenomenologically explored and conversant with African notions of becoming, of memory, and Africa's various concepts of historicity.

2. Bergson's Intuition, *Duration*, and Memory

Henri Bergson's *modus operandi* is the vivacious mobility of life; he always emphasizes movement, and especially creative mobility. It is even the bedrock of his enduring critique of the static (neo-)Kantian positivism of his day.⁸ Whether in *Time and Free Will* or later in *Creative Evolution*, Bergson sought to break free from the compulsion to quantify and categorize (and therefore isolate) faculties of the mind and body, as well as issues pertaining to culture and nature. This is why his argumentations often employ – albeit with critique and some distance – psychology, evolutionary science, and sociology rather than the philosophical canon. He reads, at times, as if he is not doing philosophy because he often critiques academic philosophy (i.e., professional philosophy, *pace* Serequeberhan) for misdirecting human

⁷ John Mbiti, *African Philosophy and Religion* (Garden City: Anchor Books, 1970).

⁸ Susan Guerlac, *Thinking in Time: An Introduction to Henri Bergson* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2006), pp. 21, 27-29.

understanding – especially its influence on science – through its faulty fundamental presuppositions of what reasoning is and how to go about doing it.

This is where intuition as a method enters the picture: what Bergson attempts is an application of what we know about the world from scientific discourses to arrive at a philosophy, which is a mode of living rather than a ‘philosophy of the book.’ As we will see with Lawler, Bergson does not quite arrive at his destination but does point the way forward.

While it is a philosophical method that holds a phenomenological register, for Bergson, intuition is more of a modality of life that brought its practitioner into a deeper understanding of life itself. It at times ‘feels’ more like a spiritual exercise than a mere philosophical approach.⁹ As such, intuition is a method which reveals how metaphysics is possible while also showing how said metaphysics enhances creative mobility rather than mollifying mobility. It does so by first addressing the way in which critics of metaphysics (especially Kant) misunderstand that knowing/understanding is a mixture between analysis and intuition.¹⁰ As Lawler summarizes:

Bergson makes the distinction between analysis and intuition along the line of inside and outside. Analysis remains outside the thing; it consists in turning about the thing and adopting viewpoints of the thing. ... The Turning about aims at taking the thing apart, at division and complexity; it is ‘analysis’ in the literal sense.¹¹

This analysis, though, is always incomplete since it requires rendering a given thing into referential symbols, which are then abstracted to connect elements of one thing to another via synthesis. In so doing, analysts deceive themselves when they think these dissections and observations imply that they have mastery and command over the thing itself. For Bergson, it is rather obvious why Kant and other philosophers believed that metaphysics was impossible: they were working with an incomplete comprehension of the mind’s capability. Again, creativity and mobility of life underpin Bergson’s work: metaphysics *was* impossible

⁹ Idella J Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution: The Moral Philosophy of Henri Bergson* (The Hague: Springer, 1970), pp. 12-13, 32-35.

¹⁰ *MM*, p. 189. Note that I will be citing *MM* rather than *The Creative Mind* even though most of my secondary authors cite the latter.

¹¹ Leonard Lawler, “An Introduction into Bergson’s ‘Introduction to Metaphysics,’” in *Bergson and Phenomenology*, Micheal R. Kelly, ed. (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), p. 27.

for Kant, but that is because Kant failed to see that a metaphysics entailed more than analytic knowledge; it required another skill set, which Bergson articulates as intuition.¹²

What analysis lacks intuition supplies. Intuition seeks to go ‘inside’ the thing to understand how it operates within its own internal mechanics. Intuition has this capability due to its inherent sympathy towards the thing in question. As Bergson summarizes:

It follows from this that an absolute could only be given in an *intuition*, whilst everything else falls within the province of *analysis*. By intuition is meant the kind of *intellectual sympathy* by which one places oneself within an object in order to coincide with what is unique in it and consequently inexpressible. Analysis, on the contrary, is the operation which reduces the object to elements already known, that is, to elements common both to it and other objects. To analyze, therefore, is to express a thing as a function of something other than itself. All analysis is thus a translation, a development into symbols, a representation taken from successive points of view from which we note as many resemblances as possible between the new object which we are studying and others which we believe we know already. ...¶ If there exists any means of possessing a reality absolutely instead of knowing it relatively, of placing oneself within it instead of looking at it from outside points of view, of having the intuition instead of making the analysis: in short, of seizing it without any expression, translation, or symbolic representation – metaphysics is that means. *Metaphysics, then, is the science which claims to dispense with symbols.*¹³ (Emphasis Bergson’s)

Bergson links intuition with our senses and instinct, which we will cover further in Chapter Eight.¹⁴ In short, and for now, Bergson sees that the interrelation between intuition and intelligence is one in which the utility of the former becomes articulated through mental effort within the latter.¹⁵ This utility is what makes intuition – and later the recognition of *duration* – so difficult to grasp. The mind is bent toward survival and navigating through the world; in so doing (and as we shall see below), it needs to focus on matters at hand rather than the reality rendered through the mind.¹⁶ Action comes too easily for us, and at times thinking does as well.¹⁷ What makes intuition a philosophical method, then, is the way in which it articulates how one can think without this daily functioning to sense, feel, and

¹² *IM*, pp. 81-85.

¹³ *IM*, pp. 7, 9.

¹⁴ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 178, 185-190, 192-197, 200-203.

¹⁵ Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, p. 64.

¹⁶ *CE*, pp. 77-80, 102-106.

¹⁷ See Bergson’s critique of Kant in *IM*, pp. 80-91.

recognize reality as one is penetrating it through time and, finally, as reality unfolds through this penetration.¹⁸ As Bergson summarizes the difficulty of intuition, it is, in a way, an intellectual violence to oneself:

But the truth is that our intelligence can follow the opposite method. It can place itself within the mobile reality, and adopt its ceaselessly changing direction; in short, can grasp it by means of that *intellectual sympathy* which we call intuition. This is extremely difficult. The mind has to do violence to itself, has to reverse the direction of the operation by which it habitually thinks, has perpetually to revise, or rather to recast, all its categories. But in this way it will attain to fluid concepts, capable of following reality in all its sinuosities and of adopting the very movement of the inward life of things. Only thus will a progressive philosophy be built up, freed from the disputes which arise between the various schools, and able to solve its problems naturally, because it will be released from the artificial expression in terms of which such problems are posited. To philosophize, therefore, is to invert the habitual direction of the work of thought.¹⁹ (Emphasis Bergson's)

The benefit of this violence, though, is that it reveals a greater freedom or mobility of life. This mobility is directly linked to *duration* and to memory.²⁰ However, before we proceed, we need to grasp what Bergson means by sympathy. Bergson notes that one first develops sympathy through a "self-sympathy," meaning that one begins to understand the nature of looking within things by looking within oneself.²¹

He gives raising and lowering one's arm as a key example: when I do this, I can observe physical and locational changes of my arm's movement, which would be an analysis from *outside* the arm. Doing so 'translates' my arm's movement to referent symbols, which renders it intellectually coherent. However, if I focus instead on how this movement makes me *feel* – as a bodily function that I do not intellectualize but sense and possibly emote through – then I have adopted a different point of view. As Lawler summarizes, "I am 'sympathizing' with the object which in this case is my own arm."²²

¹⁸ Note that 'daily functioning' is not Heideggerian everydayness or the phenomenological 'natural attitude,' but there are commonalities between these concepts.

¹⁹ *IM*, p. 70.

²⁰ William G Barnard, *Living Consciousness: The Metaphysical Vision of Henri Bergson* (Albany: SUNY Press, 2011), p. 128, emphasis Barnard's.

²¹ *IM*, p. 6-8.

²² Lawler, "Introduction to Bergson's 'Introduction to Metaphysics,'" p. 28.

Inner self-sympathy is then expanded outwardly through an *intellectual sympathy*, where one performs “a kind of intellectual expansion, within the thing studied: in short, a passage from reality to concepts and no longer from concepts to reality.”²³ This entails that one must shift their focus or concentration away from the exterior properties of the thing in question and seek a harmonious attunement with the thing’s interior complexity: one must refrain from their own analysis of the thing and focus on how the thing becomes itself through its own terms and conditions. What this means, according to Hanne Jacobs and Trevor Perri, is that “intuition can only overcome the workings of the intellect by looking for what is immediately given *in* our natural perception, since though ‘Intellect has detached itself from a vastly wider reality, ... there has never been a clean cut between the two; and all around conceptual thought there remains an indistinct fringe which recalls its origin.’”²⁴

I find that Bergsonian intuition is better seen in action than comprehensively summarized. Furthermore, Bergson articulates the method first when describing his notion of *duration* as both a sense of the temporal but also as a cognitive reality of one’s creative freedom. Therefore, we will now turn our attention to describing *duration* and memory to round out our understanding of Bergson. Unfortunately, given its divergence from Western canonical philosophy, there is no clear, succinct definition of *duration*, especially Bergson’s usage of the term. Consequently, we will have to see how duration unfolds throughout Bergson’s work before arriving at what it is and why it matters.

Bergson initially presents *duration* by critiquing two debates: first through free will versus determinism, and then disputes between monists and dualists.²⁵ For Bergson, these debates are connected by the way in which philosophers analytically render the relation between the body and consciousness into mechanized processes.²⁶ I imagine that Bergson chose to engage

²³ *IM*, p. 55.

²⁴ Hanne Jacobs and Trevor Perri, “Intuition and Freedom: Bergson, Husserl and the Movement of Philosophy,” in *Bergson and Phenomenology*, Micheal R. Kelly, ed. (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), p. 108. They are quoting Bergson from *CE*, p. 193. Emphasis Bergson’s

²⁵ Note that I present a similar, albeit more simplified, description of Bergsonian *duration* in: Justin Sands, “Communal Space, Communal Temporality: Kwasi Wiredu and Henri Bergson in Dialogue,” in *Phenomenology in an African Context: Contributions and Challenges*, Abraham Olivier, M John Lamola, and Justin Sands, eds. (Albany: SUNY Press, 2023), pp. 285-304.

²⁶ Note how similar Serequeberhan’s critique of the ethno- and professional philosophy employs a similar critique: both sides are manifestations of what Heidegger called *Ge-stell* (en-framing) within a worldview out of which they cannot rationalize.

in these debates since each demonstrates how calculative reasoning frames consciousness – from its temporality to its contents – in terms of rank and number. Subsequently, this quantized version of consciousness employs spatial representations that eventually transcend metaphor and become the perception of consciousness itself.²⁷

Determinism, for example, employs ‘decision trees’ to spatially render the cause of an event or to predict future outcomes. Here, the metaphorical mechanism of time-*lines* of decision-making gets transposed onto, and mistaken for, the concept itself. Importantly, one can see Bergson’s critique of analysis is at work here: by analyzing from outside the thing, they (mis)translate it by linking it with metaphors, which overdetermine their comprehension of the thing in question. In this debate, they confuse a spatialized construct of time as a line of decisions made (or not made) for the temporality *within* which decisions are made: “But by invading the series of our psychic states, by introducing space into our perception of *duration*, it corrupts at its very source our feeling of outer and inner change, of movement, and of freedom. Hence ... the problem of free will.”²⁸ In short, the problem of free will is not whether our decisions are determined but *how we perceive our decisions* by dissecting them through spatial metaphors rather than intuiting them as a creative flow of continual living events. “All of the difficulties of the problem and the problem itself,” he summarizes, “arise from the desire to endow *duration* with the same attributes as extensity [i.e., space], to interpret a succession by a simultaneity, and to express the idea of freedom in a language into which it is obviously untranslatable.”²⁹

We will cover the problem of spatialization more in Chapter Six, but foreshadowing a bit, one can see that the problem Bergson has with spatialized metaphors correlates with his problem of analysis: both seek not to sympathetically intuit the thing within itself because they are fine with limiting their understanding to the dissection of representations of the thing and with translating (via metaphor) its observable parts to other things.³⁰ This is especially true of abstract concepts whose representations are often spatial metaphors. From this, his concerns

²⁷ *MM*, pp. 24-27; *TF*, pp. 4-7, 85-92. See also: Guerlac, *Thinking in Time*, pp. 50-60, 110-15. Beyond spatial metaphors, note how temporal metaphors have taken on a consumerist tone through phrases like ‘time is money,’ ‘time is wasted,’ or ‘time is running out.’ All these phrases see time as a commodity and influence how we ‘use our time wisely.’

²⁸ *MM*, p. 74.

²⁹ *TFW*, p. 221.

³⁰ See: Chapter Six, pp. 145-149.

are that we use metaphor – which is derived from our experiences – to describe not just what we perceive but how we perceive it: philosophy and science, he observes, seem “particularly concerned to prove that we perceive things through the medium of certain forms, borrowed from our own constitution.”³¹ This causes confusion regarding differences in *kind* (i.e., category), forsaking that they really are differences in *degree*. It is a perceptual confusion not just in rank and number or how we order our perceptions – where quantitative thinking resides – but also a confusion of how our faculties of perception work. *In short, the description of perception becomes mistaken with the means of perception.*

Furthermore, quantification infects our perception of materiality, where we attempt to sever the relationship between our perception of a thing and the thing itself.³² Hence, the question of monism or dualism: separating our consciousness from materiality ignores how our perception of the thing is at play within the thing itself and how we draw our perception out of the thing without recognizing how perception and materiality are interpenetrative.³³ This confusion between perception and materiality subsequently misses how consciousness functions as a product of responding to stimuli. Moreover, these responses create emotions or ideas that relationally effect what consciousness perceives, which implies a sympathetic bond between the perceiver and the perceived.³⁴

For a clarifying example, let us return to the one I used to describe Wiredu’s notion of personhood from Chapter Two. Consider how being called a father corresponds to having a child and vice versa. Here, one can see how each person – the father and child – can be considered ‘outside stimuli’ for the other and how each’s esteem of this relationship can and does affect the other. Their relationship is not one of objectification but one of sympathetic interaction and co-generation since each’s action is in relation to the other (such as a father who disciplines their child) and builds an emotional bond with the other. For instance, if the father’s discipline is abusive, then this changes both the child’s relationship with their father and their own emotional sense of identity. As I move toward the important role that memory plays in Bergson’s analysis, keep this relationship in mind. Notably, Bergson is discussing

³¹ *TFW*, p. 222.

³² *MM*, pp. 23-28.

³³ *MM*, pp. 50, 68, 78-79.

³⁴ *MM*, p. 139.

stimuli in general and not the problem of other selves, but one can see within this illustration the co-generative nature of perception which he is describing.

Continuing, Bergson argues that perception breaks down phenomena into images upon which consciousness can project meanings and understandings. Critically, breaking up perception into images is necessary for daily life and is a part of consciousness seeking an understanding of its world; without it, one would be constantly exhausted and unable to process anything. Thus, the concept of images is something that brings analysis and intuition together: “by ‘image’ we mean a certain existence which is more than which the idealist calls a *representation*, but less than that which the realist calls a *thing* – an existence placed halfway between the ‘thing’ and the ‘representation.’”³⁵

The concept of images shows that Bergson is not against analysis *tout court*. Far from it, much of his work is an analysis of the philosophy and science of his time. It is mainly that, even though we employ intuition in our everyday lives, redacting it from our intellectual efforts leaves us with mere representations of the world and of ourselves; it cannot go further. We need both analysis and intuition to move from experience of phenomena to making sense of it, and we do so through breaking phenomena down into images. Sole analysis would leave us with mere representations, and sole intuition would leave us with only an instinctive, sympathetic reaction to the thing.³⁶ Through both, we can employ images to break down the constant onslaught of phenomenal perceptions and make sense of the world. As William G Barnard describes it:

Bergson argues that, from the time of our birth, we have had to work hard in order to successfully create a meaningful and manageable world out of the sensory data that cascades in and through us. In order to not be overwhelmed, in order to function, it is crucial that our senses and our brain carve out certain clearly defined zones of stability in the flux of universal becoming. We are forced to create order by screening out vast amounts of sensory and mental information that pours into us.³⁷

³⁵ *MM*, p. 7, emphasis Bergson’s.

³⁶ *CE*, pp. 193-196. See especially: p. 193: “The *Ammophila*, no doubt, discerns but a very little of that force, just what concerns itself; but at least it discerns it from within, quite otherwise than by a process of knowledge – by an intuition (*lived* rather than *represented*), which is probably like what we call divining sympathy.” Emphasis Bergson’s.

³⁷ Barnard, *Living Consciousness*, p. 10.

Perception, here, is a matter of focus: focus is typically described as fixating upon a thing, but it also works in the opposite direction where other objects are negated (blurred out, erased, discarded) to bring the thing in question into contrast with its surroundings. “My perception,” Bergson argues, “contracts into a single moment of my *duration* that which, taken in itself, spreads over an incalculable number of moments.”³⁸ Elena Fell summarizes this as the “mind, able to contract in what is our present multitude of events and conceive them in their connection with each other, is able to join them in a meaningful unity.”³⁹

This may be necessary for basic survival since it allows us to make sense of the world while being within the world. Science, for example, relies upon the ability to categorize and dissect, thereby giving us greater understandings of the world and of ourselves. Yet the consequence of only relying upon the representation of the thing is that it confuses distinction for reality (the latter of which we get through the image of the thing that the scientist dissects).

We therefore have a problem with emphasizing the separation of things and their representation to us: it comes at the cost of understanding that these entities stand in relation to other entities via a fluid succession of phenomena. We neglect that each phenomenon is interconnected and interpenetrated through our perceiving, which renders each phenomenal perception a representation rather than a fully formed image constructed by our consciousness.

Contrariwise, *duration* allows the perceiver to recognize the co-penetrative nature of perception: the perceiver sympathetically enters into that which they perceive, thereby revealing the fluid and creative relationship between them, which entails that that which is perceived also penetrates the perceiver, thereby creating memories, emotions, ideas, ect. Bergson is essentially arguing that we do not merely observe the thing in question; we *play* with it. Our perception of one thing is made real to us through its successive images, and this flow of imagery is always already in relation to other things that we intuitively imagine (whether they are being readily perceived or remembered). Therefore, our reception of each thing influences other things, which composes a sense of reality.

³⁸ *MM*, p. 208

³⁹ Elena Fell, *Duration, Temporality, Self: Prospects for the Future of Bergsonism* (New York: Peter Lang, 2012), p. 37.

In short, through what he calls *duration*, our reception sympathetically penetrates the thing received, sympathizing with its creative life (whether an object or organism) as it in turn does the same to us. This is where *duration* gathers its co-penetrative understanding of the mobility of life: this co-penetration through images received and given endows one to see that reality is the energetic mobility of life through precepting what the world presents to us. This mobility is where Bergson often locates the “rhythm” of *duration* since it ebbs and flows, moving about as we perceive/interact with the world around us.⁴⁰ The resulting clarity is how time, expressed as *duration*, is a *qualitative multiplicity* of images rather than a quantitative, mechanistic, successive progression of representations.⁴¹

We forget this when we seek to grasp a totalized concept of a thing, putting it in stasis and neutering its creative mobility (i.e., its qualitative multiplicities). When we dissect the world into singular representations and only reconstitute these representations – their name, properties, etc. – to what we can analyze or ‘rationally’ understand, we forsake our intuitive relationship to what we perceive and our co-effective interactions with it. When doing so, our aperture becomes too narrow, and thus, we ignore the flow of life, that is *duration*.

His favorite illustration of this qualitative multiplicity is a melody: recall a melody and think of how it forms in your mind.⁴² What makes a melody is the relation between tones and how they build off each other to create a cohesive, holistic ‘thing.’ Now, think of how meanings such as sadness or happiness are developed as the melody changes. Note how this is not just about tonality but also rhythm. Also, note that you are *remembering* this melody: you are recalling an auditory experience, and if you have heard this melody several times (a favorite song, perhaps), then the meaning of this melody is associated with other memories and those memories’ meanings (maybe it was played at a wedding or funeral). Finally, imagine this melody written out on sheet music: sure, this representation could make the music easily identifiable and replicable; it could be used to delve into the mathematical theory behind the melody and what makes it ‘work.’ While this may be valuable in some respects, it completely removes the meaning-making from the melody itself. It is as if the melody was a cadaver handed over for autopsy.

⁴⁰ *MM*, pp. 204-206.

⁴¹ *MM*, pp. 65-69.

⁴² To name just a few key examples see: *MM*, pp. 116-118, *CM* pp. 18-19, 82-83, 149-150, 173-175, 179.

Barnard gives a similar example by watching a film.⁴³ Whereas one can quantify this by saying, 'I watched a two-hour movie,' *duration* allows one to describe how the film stays with you long after its viewing. *Duration* describes not just the direct viewing of the film but how you thought about it afterward, how you compared it to other films, how you referenced the film in conversations, how others shared their own recollections of the film, and how references to the film may take on a persona completely outside the film's context through memes or jokes. *Duration*, then, would not *just* describe the two-hour runtime; it describes how your 'time' with the film continues through your experience of the film and how this experience's influence is so expansive. In effect, *duration* describes how you *live with the film*. Importantly, each experience you live with the film is novel and irreplicable; experiences build off one another and cannot be repeated.⁴⁴ Bergson would describe this as how "several conscious states are organized into a whole, permeate one another, [and] gradually gain a richer content."⁴⁵ Through the rhythm of these experiences – how they overlap, interlace, and play off of one another – the film changes in quality and/or meaning.

Both the melody and film analogies – as well as the father-son relationship above – deeply rely upon one's memory. Memory is consequently foundational to *duration* since, without it, one could not parse the onslaught of stimuli to make the world comprehensible, nor could one engage the images of reality since there would be no way for one to *relate* to the stimuli/events one encounters. However, Bergsonian memory is not a mere recollection, as a part of *duration*, it too is a qualitative multiplicity.

Bergson describes this through the analogy of the cone of memory.⁴⁶ However, I find this analogy clumsy given that, as an illustrative representation of a dynamic movement within consciousness, its static figuration can misconstrue what Bergson is trying to say about memory.⁴⁷ To prevent this, I will describe Bergsonian memory in my own terms but will refer back to the cone of memory for accuracy and to relate my work to other scholars.

⁴³ Barnard, *Living Consciousness*, pp. 31-32.

⁴⁴ Note that this will be important when we bring Bergson into conversation with Serequeberhan's heritage in Chapter Nine.

⁴⁵ *TFW*, p. 122.

⁴⁶ *MM*, pp. 151, 162.

⁴⁷ I am not alone on this, see: Barnard, *Living Consciousness*, p. 158; David Addyman, "Bergson's Matter and Memory: From Time to Space," in *Understanding Bergson, Understanding Modernism*, Paul Ardoin, S.E. Gontarski, and Laci Mattison, eds. (New York: Bloomsbury, 2012), pp. 27-28, 31.

For Bergson, there is a point where consciousness immediately intersects with reality, that is, with the world as we know it. Yet this intersection is a constant present that has already passed once we recognize it.⁴⁸ Therefore, to respond to an ever-moving present, we break it down through images and interact with those through our memories. However, memory is not 'linear,' nor is it a simple storehouse from which we recall experiences, and Bergson differentiates memory into two different, yet interlacing, types: habit memory and true memory.⁴⁹

Habit memory is our basic reactions to the world through movements that we unthinkingly do and instinctively recall. This can be both responsive motor-functioning habits – such as moving your lips to make sounds – and/or interactive habits – such as speaking without thinking about which language you use.⁵⁰ These habit memories, for Bergson, are utilitarian in nature since they allow “us to adapt ourselves to the present situation; through it, the actions to which we are subject prolong themselves into reactions that are ... more or less appropriate.”⁵¹ Their utility, importantly, is what brings true memory into practical interaction with the present moment.

True memory is where what one could call our 'emotional memories' reside. They are images of moments in our lives, but they are inoperable until they need to be connected to the situation at hand (and the right memory needs to be engaged at the right moment).⁵² I may remember my first time watching my favorite film, *Cool Hand Luke*, but of what use is it to me while I am writing this chapter? As images of experience, true memory mainly functions as consciousness' recollection of itself in prior moments and thus it primarily resides as a nebula of images waiting to be recalled but not currently active in consciousness' engagement with the present.

In this way, true memories at first seem regressive since they may appear to go backward in time and dissolve; for example, the older I get, the less I may remember exact quotes from

⁴⁸ *MM*, p. 150.

⁴⁹ Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, p. 39; *MM*, p. 151.

⁵⁰ Pete A.Y. Gunter, "A Criticism of Sartre's Concept of Time," in *Bergson and Phenomenology*, Micheal R. Kelly, ed. (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), p. 144.

⁵¹ *MM*, p. 151.

⁵² *MM*, p. 151; As Bergson describes it, true memory "retains and ranges alongside each other all our states in the order in which they occur, leaving to each fact its place and not, like [habit memory], in an ever renewed present."

Cool Hand Luke or smaller plot points. According to Bergson, this dissolution is what he calls “pure memory” and is illustrated as the “base,” or widest part of ‘the cone.’⁵³ As pure memory, it holds neither the utilitarian/practical usage of habit memory nor the imaged recollection of true memory.⁵⁴ It is unconsciously there but not capable of producing effects nor images, hence why Bergson describes it as ‘pure,’ emphasizing its lack of utility and/or attachment.⁵⁵

And yet, pure memory is the key to how all of memory functions within *duration’s* engagement with reality: habit memory may hold the practical engagement of consciousness’ penetration into/through the ever-present reality, but it calls upon true memory’s experience to imagine and negotiate its engagement. As both are part of the same ‘cone’ and share the same ‘base’ via pure memory, they co-effect one another.⁵⁶ Symbiotically, true memory encapsulates and enacts one’s character by informing oneself of what one priorly knows of a given situation and what to do in it, but this information can only be enacted through habit memory. Both are needed to focus consciousness into a single image (the point of the cone), which interacts with the ever-moving present reality.⁵⁷

For example, when I am presented with a moral quandary, I recall prior (true) memories, but they can only be enacted through (habit) memories concerning how to speak, which language to speak, and so forth. Habit and true memories thus correspond to one another, from the point in which I engage the world to the expanse of my unconscious (i.e., pure memory). Like analysis and intuition, if one were to operate solely on pure habit memory, then their actions would be merely responses to stimuli without knowing why; if one were to operate solely on true memory, their consciousness would reside in a complete dream-like state.⁵⁸

Recall the illustration of the film and how one lives with the film through *duration*. Though one can easily say that their real-life actions based upon the film are an interweaving enaction

⁵³ *MM*, pp. 139-141.

⁵⁴ Barnard, pp. 156-158

⁵⁵ Guerlac, *Thinking in Time*, pp. 127-128.

⁵⁶ *MM*, pp. 152-153.

⁵⁷ Dustin Anderson, “Joyce’s *Matter and Memory*: Perception and Memory-Events in *Finnegans Wake*,” in *Understanding Bergson, Understanding Modernism*, Paul Ardoin, S.E. Gontarski, and Laci Mattison, eds. (New York: Bloomsbury, 2012), p. 183. See also: *MM*, pp. 231-235; Barnard, *Living Consciousness*, pp. 155-158, 163-196.

⁵⁸ *MM*, pp. 162-163.

of habit (acting) and recollection (true) of the film, one may ask, what made the film so important as to stay within one's consciousness? The answer lies in that the film 'spoke' to the person: it struck the person's core deep enough to provoke the need/want to further engage the film. When one asks why a film is important to them, they must focus – recall Fell's notion of focusing one's attention above – and here, memory has a telescopic effect.⁵⁹ By focusing on how or why a film matters to oneself, one must probe deep into themselves, which means not just looking at what they can recall but also how the film speaks to them on an 'unconscious level,' as it were. One can recognize that the film may bring up feelings and emotions that they cannot articulate but nonetheless feel.

Here, one is tightening the relationship between habit and true memories by relating their instrumentally habitual actions arising from the film to the images that made it meaningful; they are bringing the film *into picture*, if you will. Yet, importantly, the ineffability as to why they *sense* a compelling reason to do so comes from the unconscious 'pure' memories informing their holistic mental state. Without a pure memory, the present cannot be rendered into images, nor can habits be formed. Hence, pure memory's propulsion of all facets of memory and how it expresses itself through *duration*.

To close and round out our reading of Bergson, it is critical to note that Bergson's aim is not merely to describe temporality as such but to understand more thoroughly – and find a better description of – consciousness.⁶⁰ *Duration* describes the interlacing of consciousness, stimulus, reception, influence, and action: they are differences in degree and not in kind. Like all the factors that create a melody, while they can be parsed out or categorized, we must not forget that they are all multiplicities of cognitive intuition.

Duration thus allows for the holistic understanding of living time rather than separating life and the world from time (as one sees in subject-object metaphysical constructs). *Duration* shows the mobility of life through time and how we employ that mobility. *Duration*, finally, shows how time is not separated from the world – one does not access time, one lives time –

⁵⁹ *MM*, pp. 165, 169. See also: Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, p. 51.

⁶⁰ *MM*, p. 26; Bergson, *TFW*, pp. 223-231. As Guerlac points out, both books are extremely critical of Kantian metaphysics; Bergson "asks whether we do not unconsciously tend to construct our understanding of the inner world according to the forms borrowed from the way we view the external world" (*Thinking in Time*, p. 94).

and thus, it shows how time is a force: it is the mobility of consciousness through which it interpenetrates its world.

For now, before moving on, it is best to summarize *duration* and then quickly move to its logical implications:

- *Duration* is the mobility of consciousness' perception of its world.
- It employs two relationships – intuition and analysis, and habit and true memories – to break down stimuli into images, allowing consciousness to project meanings upon worldly events.
- This entails how one perceives stimuli as an interpenetrative event: intuition and true memory allow one to sympathetically enter said stimuli while opening oneself up to penetration; analysis and habit memories both inform and enact this opening up of oneself.
- This is where one's consciousness and said stimuli co-effect each other through successive memory: each imbues the other with meaning, endowing the other with ideas and emotions.
- This establishes meaning-making as a co-generative and inter-penetrative process that is ongoing, and, like a melody, it builds off prior events.
- Consciousness, through this movement of interplay, finds its freedom as it creates novel, meaningful understandings which in turn influence further events or interactions with/between stimuli.

The sheer fact that it requires so much unpacking and that many thinkers overlook the power of intuition makes it clear that one's recognition of *duration* in their daily life does not come easy. One could call *duration* a form of instrumental reasoning, as something that is always already happening in the background which makes the world real to us. Recognizing *duration*, then, is a matter of deep concentration. However, by recognizing that *duration* is always already happening, one can better understand what temporality 'is' and how one lives it.

It is not without its challenges, though. For one, like other phenomenological analysis, although *duration* does allow philosophers access to relating temporality to lived experience, it renders out politically laden contextualities to provide this access. *Duration*, again, does not come easily to us; we must step back and inwardly address how *duration* operates within our own consciousness via *self-sympathy*. This means that experience is still bracketed out as mere 'stimuli' to arrive at an understanding of *duration*, which crucially includes other persons.

In the next section, we will critique this redaction so that, in the final analysis, we can find a means to bring these experiences into our understanding of *duration* through its concept of memory and through a critique of the mediation required to obtain memories to experience *duration's* living mobility. Whether it is a melody or another person, there is a mediation involved, and though Bergsonian *duration* seeks not to mistake the mediated metaphor for the thing itself, a *communal duration* needs to recognize that this temporal mediation brings its own memories, meanings, and, in short, its own politics.

3. Problematic Consciousness: Bergson's "Loneliness"

Bergson sought a reorientation of thinking about how consciousness operates. However, his operation is interior: Bergson's concerns against philosophy begin with introspection, how thought comes too easily for us, and how this can create mechanized notions of ourselves and our world. What he sought to accomplish was a reorientation of our thinking and our philosophy. At times, he will even call this a conversion.⁶¹

As Leonard Lawler argues, Bergson begins with a Cartesian-like deep introspection so he can disentangle the relationship between spatialization and temporality. Consequently, he reveals how we mistake spatialized and metaphorical categorizations of our experiences to render an understanding of ourselves and our world.⁶² For this reason, amongst others, Lawler identifies Bergson as an immanent philosopher in contradistinction to so-called philosophers of transcendence who look externally to transcend their limited faculties of understanding. Lawler, here, labels Derrida and Levinas as transcendent counterpoints, with the former looking externally through language and the latter through the other. Lawler even mentions a "loneliness" in *Matter and Memory* due to its inward, introspective thrust to remove itself from the world to find a greater perception of that world.⁶³

We will cover Bergson's view of morality society in Chapter Eight when we review *Two Sources of Morality and Religion*. However, even when speaking of society and morality, there is still an individualistic loneliness to his work.⁶⁴ I mostly agree with Lawler that, concerning his

⁶¹ Bergson, *The Creative Mind*, p. 115.

⁶² Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, p. 62

⁶³ *Ibid.*, pp. 68-70.

⁶⁴ He mentions the mystic or the hero, for example, who opens closed societies to development, but it always seems to be an individual who does this and not society itself. So, even if he envisions a more humane, more

notion of *duration*, Bergson maintains a ‘loneliness’ whereby “a human community [i.e., a society] is a collectivity of free beings.”⁶⁵ However, and I will show below, I think there is room for expanding Bergsonian *duration* to encapsulate a community and its politics.

Yet in support of Lawler’s argument, I find that in his essay *Laughter*, Bergson speaks the most about the intimacy and shared relationships between conscious persons. But still, he individuates intelligence and speaks of a consciousness relating to another.⁶⁶ In so doing, he keeps the group at a distance from consciousness as such, as if selves come together, but their experiences only relate to one another and are not co-effective. This is strange given the interpenetration of images as he described it in his earlier work:

This intelligence, however, must always remain in touch with other intelligences. ... Laughter appears to stand in need of an echo [i.e. others, one cannot be isolated]. ...it is something which would fain be prolonged by reverberating from one to another, something beginning with a crash, to continue in successive rumblings, like thunder in a mountain. Still this reverberation cannot go on forever. It can travel as wide a circle as you please: the circle remains, none the less, a closed one. Our laughter is always the laughter of a group.⁶⁷

If we are to “perceive all things *sub specie durationis*,” as Bergson claims, then *duration* needs further expansion.⁶⁸ What Bergson means by this claim is that the deeper we “plunge into real *duration*” and “immerse ourselves in it,” the more we can “participate” in “an eternity of life,” the latter of which means the flowing of living energy within the world and how that energy is shared throughout the world.⁶⁹ Yet how can we do this if our participation is regulated by our own consciousness? Where did the interpenetration go, which opened the thing in question to me, the interchange between myself and what I perceive? I believe there is a pathway out of this, but it entails expanding upon *duration’s* meaning of qualitative

divine even, society, it begins individually and at a certain distance to (but not removal from) society. See: Chapter Eight, pp. 178, 198-203; Chapter Nine, pp. 206-207, 233-239.

⁶⁵ *TSMR*, p. 11; this is also a concept explored throughout the book.

⁶⁶ *LMC*, pp. 6-8, 16-17, 139-142. From my reading of Bergson, I gather that this essay is more a tangent from his primary work on consciousness and *duration*, although I know it holds great appreciation for others. Yet, when discussing *duration*, the *elan vital*, or his morality, scholars rarely mention *Laughter* and again, from my reading, I see why.

⁶⁷ *LMC*, pp. 6-7.

⁶⁸ *CM*, p. 151.

⁶⁹ *CM*, p. 185.

multiplicities and how those multiplicities build relationships. Within this arises a communal sense of *duration*, as I will argue in my final analysis.

Returning to Lawler, I think it is fair for him and others to place Bergson as an immanent philosopher within a Western paradigm, but this comes with great disadvantages. Most importantly, it overlooks that Bergson could be read outside of an immanent/transcendent framework. While some scholars may disagree, I think Bergsonian intuition, with its emphasis on interpenetration and co-generative meaning-making, places him within a *relational framework* that makes his thought excitingly comparative to African philosophy and decolonial thinking. Emphasizing intuition's relational logic (via intellectual sympathy) opens Bergson to engaging these discourses. To do so, though, one needs to develop a concept of politics or culture – something that thinkers like Wiredu, Serequeberhan, and even Mbiti as seen below, could possibly supplement.

Recall the illustration of the father and child, where each influences the other's perception of the world and their own identity. This may be described immanently, with each actant inherently growing their own identity through encountering 'outside stimuli.' Yet I think that this paternal concept is best described relationally where the interpenetrative nature of this engagement emphasizes a co-generation; it is not merely one thing gaining meaning through memory and event; both entities co-create meaning through their interplay, and this grows as each new instance builds upon prior memories. Although Bergson may not wish to explicitly go in this direction, I do not see anything, at least within *Time and Freewill* or *Matter and Memory*, that prevents it. Rather, I think that it supplies the keystone to bridge intuition and a politics. This is what I call, and will eventually articulate, as a *communal duration*.

Bergson argued that the task of philosophy is to concentrate harder to further pull back to the sense of *duration*. While Lawler describes Bergson's notion of intuition as an access point for this focus, for our purposes, what I find most interesting is that Bergson's critique of philosophy reveals how easily our perceptions can fool us through our logic (be it quantitative, individualistic, or propositional).⁷⁰ If one separates the world into representations to understand it, then it makes sense that this understanding would rely upon the same devising

⁷⁰ Ibid., pp. 63-69.

and parsing of ideas to render the world wholly intelligible.⁷¹ However, if consciousness' perception of phenomena is co-generative via intuition's intellectual sympathy, and it arrives at ideas/concepts through its interpenetration of images that constitute reality, then ideas develop through a social mediation of images. A mutually perceptual engagement with the world is therefore at play. In short, if the perceiver is sympathetically penetrating the perceived, and the perceived is doing the same thing, then why could they not co-develop an image of this mutually perceptive event that they both negotiate, play with, and exchange?

Remember that Bergson persistently proclaims that we mistake differences of degree for differences of kind. Here, degree can emphasize the relationality and shared sense of all our perceptions; though we are imaging one thing then another, we do not independently 'image' them from each other, nor are we the only ones 'imaging.' Contrariwise, when we categorize or separate by kind, we sever this relational comprehension and, therefore, attempt to make the world wholly intelligible, but solely to us and our standards (which will be a major issue when we get to chronopolitics below). Sure, categorization may have a purpose, but we must never mistake it as more than a mere slice of reality. We must be aware that the image of reality is dependent upon the interplay between memories and new experiences of phenomena, and importantly, not all of these memories and experiences are our own: some are handed down to us through stories or shared experiences. Though some may state that these stories are simulacra, given that they are not ours, *we make them ours when they shape our reality.*

For example, the Vietnam War ended a decade before I was born. However, films, music, and veterans' stories about Vietnam greatly influenced my understanding of the war's impact on USA's politics and its culture. Though these memories are not mine, they are images seared into my consciousness as if they were mine since they carried so much emotional weight between myself and my community. I know it would be foolish to *empathetically* state that I know what the Vietnam War was like – that is, to proclaim that my experiences correlate to those who actually experienced the war – but I can, via intuition, *sympathetically* sense what the war was like and asymmetrically place my own experiences in relation to those who

⁷¹ In this way, Bergson has a lot of common with, and was an influence on, Heidegger. See: Massey, *The Origin of Time*, pp. 87-89, 141-144, 212-213.

experienced the war, opening myself to understanding those persons while also recognizing how their experiences co-effect my own sense of the world. This sympathy brings me closer to feeling or sensing what others sense. Through this sympathy, I am more able to feel solidarity with my community concerning the horrors of war, an expression that unfolds and therefore mobilizes the world via *duration*. Yet, notice how this *duration* of the Vietnam War – that in some ways we are still living with it – is a shared recollection and experience: *it is a shared event where the community deposits images of the war within me and, in turn, my reactive interplay with those memories influences my community's life with the war.*

Returning to Bergson and Lawler, perhaps the entire immanent/transcendent debate has the same problematics as the free will/determinism and monism/dualism debates; it is a dispute that mischaracterizes differences in degree as differences in kind. It also raises questions between the 'self-other' debates within Western philosophy, since if both are co-generatively penetrating each other in this temporal exchange, then where does one begin and the other end?

If *duration* adequately describes the memorial fluidity of these co-generative engagements, then perhaps the notions of an individuatedly constituted 'self' and 'other' are more permeable than philosophers taking sides in these debates may think, which raises more questions about temporality's – and accordingly, memory's – political nature. This assertion will require further unpacking, and we will touch briefly upon it through chronopolitics and our final analysis. Moreover, we will delve deeper into them through our conversation between Bergson and Wiredu in the next chapter.

For now, though, one can at least provisionally agree that the logic behind Bergsonian *duration* does cast alongside decolonial thought a critique against Western philosophical constructs pertaining to the ways in which Western thought dissects and categorizes concepts in pursuit of understanding the world.⁷² In what follows, we will look at the political consequences of those dissections and will then return to Bergsonian *duration* to explore its

⁷² My argument Bergson that is best read through a relational logic will likely be controversial to some Bergson scholars, and I understand that it could be taken more as an appropriation ('Our Bergson,' in Serequeberhan's words) than an accurate depiction of Bergson's thinking. However, even if scholars reject my argument, I do not find that this would nullify placing Bergson into conversation with thinkers who employ a relational logic or communitarian worldview.

viability in light of Western temporality's mental colonization. From this, we will get to my point that *duration* requires a politics to fully articulate the creative mobility of oneself and of the world. That is, it must become a communal effort rather than a solely mental and introspective one.

4. Chronopolitics and the Problem of Western Temporalities

As stated in this chapter's introduction, the political nature of temporality is often reduced to 'context,' as if the concept in question could be studied in a phenomenological vacuum. My critique of this presumption comes from Charles Mills' concept of 'chronopolitics,' which I will describe below. Afterward, I will demonstrate the implications of Mills' findings through a hermeneutic retrieval of the Zulu-British clashes over divergent notions of temporality. After exploring the brutal fallout of these encounters and how they could be read through a chronopolitics, I will close this section by arguing for a new, or at least decolonial, reconceptualization of temporality. Thus, my final section will propose that *duration* and its inherent relation to memory could be a starting point for this reconceptualization through what I call a *communal duration*.

The concept of time – both the way in which we think of time and the way we 'use' it – is filled with trauma for the formerly enslaved or colonized. This trauma often lingers within the consciousness of the oppressed and can even be passed down through generations. Mills locates this trauma in what he calls the chronopolitics of racial time. As he argues, "if there is a geopolitics, a politics of space, then clearly there should also be a chronopolitics, a politics of time."⁷³ What he means by this is that the experience of time, and therefore our concept of time, is always laden with societal conditions and social structures. Time is not a neutral concept in that it is *employed* in socially conditioned ways that are burdened by political substructures.

Furthermore, this employment of time is typically Eurocentric and the consequence of Western imperialism. Consider how time often becomes a practical 'instrument' for industrial development and consumption: the need for the invention of Greenwich Mean Time (i.e., time zones) was to improve the train industry so that trains can arrive *on time*; daylight

⁷³ Mills, "The Chronopolitics of Racial Time," p. 298.

savings time – *where time literally shifts* – was purportedly implemented to increase work hours for agricultural laborers and other industries. Also note that the rest of the world was either forced to adopt these concepts via colonization or have done so that they can maintain business relationships with the West. Though Mills does not use these examples for chronopolitics, they do illustrate the instrumental, political nature of everyday time.

Returning to Mills, he states that chronopolitics “has to do with the multiple different ways in which power relations between groups – whether formally acknowledged in recognized systems of governance or not – affect both the *representations of the relations between these groups and the world*, in their specifically temporal aspect and the *material relation of these groups to the world*, in their specifically temporal dimension.”⁷⁴ Going further, Mills argues that “whose space it is depends in part on whose time it is, on which temporality, which version of time, can be established as hegemonic.”⁷⁵ I think this statement is best understood through the relationship between the colonizer’s temporality and how they brutally imposed it upon the colonized. To my mind, the Ugandan poet Okot p’Bitek makes this severely clear in this section of his *Song of Lawino*:

Time has become
My husband's master
It is my husband's husband.
My husband runs from place to place
Like a small boy,
He rushes without dignity...
I do not know
How to keep the white man's time.

[...]

You do not first look at the sun!...
In the wisdom of the Acoli
Time is not stupidly split up
Into seconds and minutes,
It does not flow
Like beer in a pot
That is sucked
Until it is finished...
It does not get finished...

⁷⁴ Ibid., p. 299, emphasis mine.

⁷⁵ Ibid., p. 301.

Like vegetables in the dish.⁷⁶

p'Bitek, in concert with Mills, points out that it was not merely the land or space that was colonized. Rather, those who were forced into labor, into colonial schools, and so forth had to adopt the colonizer's time, dismantling their own sense of communal identity in the process. This, to me, is one of the strongest examples of Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's notion of mental colonization that one can find.⁷⁷

Stepping back, one could possibly see Bergson thinking of these experiences as European metaphysics imparting its misconception of time onto the colonized. The Europeans' mistaken notion of time as something quantized and parsed out – mistaking the metaphor of time for time itself – was thus employed as a subjugating construct. However, though that reading may be true in some sense, I find it too facile since African communities had their own notion of temporality before Europeans came to their shores, and that temporality based itself not on parcels but on events, as seen in p'Bitek's poem. Moreover, there are still traces of African temporal culture that affect how Africans navigate life. On a consciousness level, many Africans have to express themselves through various temporalities, so it is not a mere imparting of one misconception of time onto a people, it is a forceful splintering of how their consciousness perceives and interpenetrates phenomena in their daily life and how they perceive themselves and their communities. Consequently, there is more happening here than an enforced transposition of Western time since the colonized were caught between two worlds.

Keletso Atkin's *The Moon is Dead! Give us Our Money!* demonstrates this dual-worldly entrapment through his historical account of the British colonization of Natal and the Zulu people. Atkins covers this account by focusing on the coerced labor practices introduced by the British. It is an excellent microcosmic account of colonization, but for our interests, I want

⁷⁶ Okot p'Bitek, *Song of Lawino* (London: Heinemann, 1984), p. 1. I first discovered this poem in Omari H. Kokole, "Time, Language, and the Oral Tradition: An African Perspective," in *Time in the Back Experience*, Joseph K Adjaye, ed. (London: Greenwood Press, 1994), p. 36. I only quote a few phrases to respect copyright permissions with poetry.

⁷⁷ Ngugi Wa Thiong'o, *Decolonizing the Mind*, p. 3.

to focus on what the British eventually labeled as “Kafir Time” (hereafter K— or KT) and the temporal disconnect between the colonizer and the colonized.⁷⁸

Since the British abolished slavery before they established the Natal colony in 1893 (present day KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa), they resorted to coerced labor, employing the colonized as workers with a monthly salary.⁷⁹ The British, though, saw Africans as “lazy,” and, as Atkins states, many British ‘employers’ (to use the term extremely loosely) complained that “Africans could not or would not fulfill the terms of their contracts, often absconding from service.”⁸⁰

However, there was more at stake here than merely leaving one’s post. Atkins goes on to state that the general exchange between labor and wages was not just a foreign concept to southern Africans, but when they did acquiesce and agree to work, the terms of this agreement were based on clock time and the Western calendar, both of which were incoherent to southern Africans. Southern Africans did not think in hours, days, or weeks, and the Western Gregorian calendar soon proved to be the biggest problem for both sides. “Put simply,” Atkins states, “time was at the nexus of the ‘[K—] labor problem.’ No sooner was a work agreement made than confusion arose from the disparate notions of the white employer and his African employee regarding the *computation of time*.”⁸¹ In sum, the European “units of measure did not accord with the African mode of temporal reckoning.”⁸²

The African mode of temporal reckoning, according to Atkins, was through the moon and the stars, along with seasonal changes.⁸³ One can see this as well in p’Bitek’s poem above where there was no hourly wage, workday, or what have you; when the work needed to be done, it was done. Moreover, one can see Mills’ chronopolitics happening in concrete reality: when the British settled Natal, they began enforcing their own units of measure – their own

⁷⁸ Note that “Kafir,” in its various spellings and renditions, is an extremely offensive word to South African Black and Coloured peoples. Acknowledging this, I will only refer to it through initials.

⁷⁹ Atkins, *The Moon is Dead*, pp. 26-28, 51-54, 61-69.

⁸⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 78.

⁸¹ *Ibid.*, p. 80, emphasis mine.

⁸² *Ibid.*, p. 80.

⁸³ *Ibid.*, p. 80.

temporal rationale – onto the people of that area.⁸⁴ Again, those who control the space control the time.

The Zulu or African resistance to this temporal imposition, perceived as lazy by their colonizers, was not just a temporal disagreement but a politically infused cognitive disassociation between the two worlds. One can see this in the fact that a month's wage for the British followed the Gregorian cycle and the Zulu followed a lunar cycle. Thus, on the 28th day, they would demand their payment and stop working. This became known as "the [K—] month," and eventually "KT."⁸⁵ "*inganga Ifile! Imali Yethu!*" they would demand, translating to "The moon is Dead! Give us Our Money!"⁸⁶

As Atkins notes further, this temporal disconnection created two simultaneous issues: on the one hand, the African laborers felt like they were being cheated, and on the other, European settlers initially feared a revolt, so they either capitulated or they would pay those who worked a full European month extra wages or gave them better jobs.⁸⁷ Once industrialization came to the colony, and with it non-agricultural labor, the colonizers enforced the European calendar with much more vigor. This was more easily accomplished since the urbanization of labor allowed them to further control the living arrangements of the laborers.⁸⁸ And again, those who control the space control the time.

Though we cannot cover the entirety of the temporal colonization of Africa and those within the African diaspora here, what Atkins reveals to us is that time is not abstract; it is even a matter of survival in the case of the colonized.⁸⁹ African temporality is a devastating casualty of colonialism's cultural bomb and one that would be nigh impossible to recover fully in light of our globalized economic context. However, thinkers like Anthony Monteiro, commenting

⁸⁴ Another strong example of this is the narrative by Gregory Pardlo, "Colored People's Time," *Callaloo* 39:2 (2016), pp. 361-371. Here, Pardlo gives an essayistic-narrative account of a similar temporal disconnect within the African-American Black experience.

⁸⁵ Atkins, *The Moon is Dead*, p. 81.

⁸⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 80.

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*, pp. 82-86.

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 89. For a similar account see: Alamin Mazrui, Lupenga Mphande, "Time and Labor in Colonial Africa: The Case of Kenya and Malawi," in *Time in the Black Experience*, Joseph K Adjaye, ed. (London: Greenwood Press, 1994), pp. 97-120.

⁸⁹ For more on African(a) temporality in light of colonization and the African Diaspora, see: Joseph K. Adjaye, ed., *Time in the Black Experience* (London: Greenwood Press, 1994), this is an essential read for further expansion within this area of study.

on Clarence J. Munford's *Race and Civilization: Rebirth of Black Rationality*, contends that time must be rethought and conceptually decolonized:

I argue that Munford is among those Africana historians striving to construct a new historiography of the African world. To do so, I suggest, requires a new understanding of Time, Being, and Space; one which recognizes the malleability not just of Space and Being, but also of Time.⁹⁰

Monteiro continues in his commentary by giving an archeology, of sorts, concerning both the ways in which Western ideologies have transformed African(a) persons' concepts of temporality which are needed to describe "the Multiple Determinations of African Being."⁹¹ Arguing this, he engages Du Bois' and Fanon's conceptualizations of Blackness – the former as a double consciousness (hence, multiple determinations), the latter as an existential facticity (hence, 'Blackness' or Being Black) – as an argument against the epistemologies and methodologies currently employed within academia at large. As we will cover with Serequeberhan throughout Chapter Seven, there is a *Ge-stell*, or en-framing, of the temporality of being. What it means to be African or Black in relation to the concept of being is a primary issue for numerous scholars thanks to De Bois, Fanon, or for that matter Steve Biko. However, as Monteiro argues, they neglect how the temporality of being itself is always already en-framed through a white, Eurocentric construct.

The endpoint, for Monteiro, is that the dynamic complexities which exist between African Time, Blackness, and being creates a "multiple determinativeness," which "expresses the existence of multiple possibilities" of a "heterarchical or multiple, rather than the hierarchical system of determinations and causations."⁹² In short, for African(a) persons – or all colonized persons, one could argue – the complex negotiations between one's own cultural temporality and that of globalized Eurocentric temporality is part and parcel of the complex negotiations concerning being Black in a Eurocentric world. Whether KT, or 'Colored People's Time,' or being trapped within a Eurocentric historical consciousness, temporality must be addressed

⁹⁰ Anthony Monteiro, "Time, Space and Race: On Clarence J. Munford's *Race and Civilization*," *The Black Scholar*, 34:3 (2004), p. 53. Note that his commentary is on Clarence J. Munford, *Race and Civilization: Rebirth of Black Centrality* (Trenton: Africa World Press, 2001). I recognize that there are more comprehensive texts which address these issues, I chose Monteiro's because he succinctly states them. An expansive overview of these issues would be unwieldy for my scope.

⁹¹ Anthony Monteiro, "Time, Space and Race," p. 61.

⁹² *Ibid.*, p. 61.

as an issue to one's beingness within the world. It cannot be abstracted or phenomenologically reduced as mere context since, for many in the subaltern world, perception is always already navigating within two worlds. Thus, to proceed with a more holistic description of meaning-making or understanding within the world, phenomenology must reconsider temporality.

Mills' chronopolitics launched this section's exploration into the colonized (or, for Mills, the African diasporic) experience of temporality. I then demonstrated this chronopolitics through Atkin's historiography of the Southern African people's clash with Eurocentric temporality, particularly through labor and industrialization. I ended by expanding the notion of navigating through two worlds or temporalities through Monteiro. Of course, there is more to this issue than could be covered in one section. What I sought to prove, though, is that time is not a neutral concept, and if we want to fully understand consciousness and how it relates to its world, then we must reckon with this historical and metaphysical baggage.

Now, though Bergson's Cartesian-like introspection into consciousness does not take this into account, it does not disqualify *duration* as a meaningful starting point. Moreover, as I shall argue below, there is a place to consider Monteiro's multiplicities within *duration*. The key factor is that the mechanics of understanding *duration* require a relational logic between the perceiver and the perceived: if we allow for that relationship to convey more than extensivity (i.e., space) and emphasize its creative action – allowing the perception to convey meaning whilst relying upon and building up other meanings during its perception – then we can access a notion of temporality which adequately addresses the historical baggage mediation carries within itself when one engages the world or other persons.

5. Final Analysis: *Communal Duration*, Memory, and the Politics of Temporality

The key facet that makes a *communal duration* possible is memory. Recall the examples of the father and child, 'living with a film,' or thinking of a melody. All these examples show how *duration* allows for a multiplicity of events with a heterogeneity of meanings within time. Yet, more crucial is that they all require memory to be capable of both cohering these events together (creating a unity of meaningful experience) and allowing their meanings to 'travel along,' if you will, from one event to another (creating an interplay between meaningful

experiences through living). *Duration's* interlacing between habit, true, and unconsciously pure memory may present us with an opportunity to express a *communal duration*; that is a *duration* which is a temporally shared, social experience.

Bergsonian analysis does not foreclose that we could analyze how one consciousness' interpretation (i.e., memorial recollection) of an event interplays with another consciousness' interpretation, thereby exploring each consciousness individually. However, I think it is more important to note that the interplay, or more clearly, *the mediation of the event itself* is always already laden with meaning and history. This entails that the interpenetration between consciousness and its perceived stimuli is never neutral and carries with it historical baggage.

A great example of this is my own identity when reading African philosophy: though I come to these thinkers with an open mind and critically engage the internal mechanics within their rationales and ideas/concepts, I cannot deny that my own historically-situated identity as a white, American male born in the American South (with all of its own history with slavery) influences my interplay or interpenetration with Serequeberhan's work. My memories are not just my own, they are politically colored by their socialized, sedimented layering within my consciousness. My findings when reading their work are not merely *me living with their text*, but also *their text living with me*. Each of my new publications on a given author has the possibility of changing how others read/live with that author's texts.

Therefore, when I publish on, say, Serequeberhan, he may read it and engage with me, and others may do the same. In a sense, through my interplay with Serequeberhan's work, he and I inter-penetrate each other's own understanding of the world and we do so through mediated temporality and through the memories we both carry and pass on to each other. We have, then, our own memorial sense of the ideas within the text, but we share them with each other.

Moreover, if he wrote the text in 1994, for example, then *duration* would explain how the multiplicities of temporal engagements co-effect each other since reading the text in 1994 would be different than reading it in 2024, and if you are reading this present text in 2034, then you are enjoying – or sharing in/with – this engagement. However far back they reach or however forward they go, these memories interlace, play with one another, and allow

oneself the mobility to comprehend the fluidity of creative and active engagements with the past whilst foretelling future engagements. Memory is crucial here, but it always already comes to us with socially mediated histories: that of Serequeberhan as the original author, me as the commentator, and you as the present reader.

This socialization of memory opens *duration* to politics or culture since *duration* requires social mediation(s) to relate one memory to another, to relate one state of mind to another, and to relate one consciousness to another. Though one withdraws or steps back to perceive the creative multiplicities of living time – here, of living with a text – one comes back to the world to continue living with that text amongst others who likewise live with that text (and will continue to live with new texts, perhaps those influenced by the original text).

Concerning the more serious matter of chronopolitics and the need to rethink Black beingness' temporal situation, a *communal duration* allows us to recognize the multiplicity of *being* Black in the world and navigate different concepts of temporality. Or, how concepts that comprise one's identity are never fixed, never past, but always already are present within the time through which one expresses one's identity. Though it is not my place to articulate what African or Black temporality is, I think *communal duration* presents various access points for further engagement.

In closing, though, it is through *communal duration's* concept of memory where the 'we' is welcomed within time. For if 'we are time itself,' we are not alone, nor is our life which is lived through our times. We always carry with us our multiple pasts which are narrated and historicized through our present and future actions. A *communal duration* thus opens us to a new expression of life since it allows us to reckon with the multiple histories (or interpretations) of past events and how those narratives co-generate our world, our own identity, and our relations to other peoples' images of their worlds as well as their own creative, mobility of living life.

This social mobility, expressed in and through *communal duration*, will allow us to see how the temporal 'becoming' of a person through community and the 'becoming' of a world through Wiredu's cosmology are always already relational and therefore political. From personhood to metaphysics, temporality is always already reminding us of the politics we

bring to discussion through our identities. For if *we* are time, then whatever we create through time, whether in concert or through conflict, is always already political: our ideas and concepts of who 'we' are as people, who 'we' are as organisms, who 'we' are as members of society, never cease to happen and thus continue the sedimented layering of human history.

CHAPTER SIX: THE COMMUNALITY OF BECOMING: WIREDU AND BERGSON IN CONVERSATION ON TIME AND SPACE

1. Introduction

Our last conversation between Serequeberhan and Wiredu in Chapter Three focused on exploring how a 'lived existence' may thrive within a communitarian framework. What I argued was that, while a person becomes a person through community, one may (or possibly should) realize their own character and the roles they play in this becoming. Through this self-realization, one can enact a lived existence in the process of liberating their community or changing problematic norms within their community. Yet they cannot do it alone, and they must be within the community to help guide it. The general point was that a communitarian framework does not lack agency, and it indeed needs persons to recognize their lived existence to change problematic situations, whether they be decolonial or in pursuit of a better communal sense of justice and/or liberation. Regardless of the context, the notion of personhood encapsulates the rich notion of one's character and one's relationship to one's community, where each person's heritage is shared. This, I argued, was a much more holistic approach to hermeneutic phenomenology than the 'self-other' paradigm and its variants.

A key aspect of engaging personhood on a phenomenological level is that it describes the process of becoming. I delved further into this becoming process in Chapter Four by exploring Kwasi Wiredu's cosmology. A moral anthropology extends further than interpersonal relationships, it communally and epistemically guides one's understanding of the world. Recall that, for Wiredu, this empirical metaphysics is an evolving process: it is not merely an abstract metaphysics but directly relates to the physical here-and-now of living. It is an ongoing understanding of the space we inhabit and how that space transforms through our environmentally bound encounters.

Moreover, Chapter Five's exploration of Bergson furthered this communal epistemology by arguing that memories guide our sense of temporality through *duration*. I pushed this even further by arguing for a *communal duration*, which acknowledges the socially mediated memories and experiences through which we live, teasing out the chronopolitics at play within the concept of temporality. Every chapter thus far has spoken about the phenomenon of becoming in some fashion: whether it is becoming a self-realized person, how one develops their personhood and character in relationship to their community, how one realizes what the world is and their situatedness within that world, and how one develops all of these aspects of character through a *communally durational* relationship between themselves, their community, and the world around them.

What is next is to understand how these 'becomings' co-generate within and through each other. Taken on their own accounts, one sees each concept as slices of life happening. This chapter examines how some of these slices are part of a larger whole. It does this by exploring the spatio-temporality of these becomings through a conversation between Wiredu and Bergson.

I will start the conversation by highlighting the consensus(es) between Wiredu's and Bergson's respective philosophical approaches. Concerning divergences, which will be the focus of Sections Three and Four, I will underline possibilities where each may help address a lacuna within the others' work; this will allow hermeneutic tensions to arise. I will first explore Wiredu to show how Bergsonian intuition and duration may provide Wiredu with a concept of temporality that helps to account for his notion of how one becomes a person or how a community develops. Then, in the penultimate section, I will do the same to Bergson by showing how Wiredu provides a deeper understanding of the spatial and socio-political nature of becoming. In my final analysis, I will bring these conversational elements together to propose a spatio-temporal framework that underpins my argument that a human becomes a person by engaging its community over time. Consequently, these engagements manifest themselves in space, and through their historical-memorial negotiations, they transform this space into particular places imbued with history and their own character.

In the oncoming chapters, I will finally engage the concept of place and how it is the historical, living creation of these engagements. Taken together, each of these points elevates the

relationship between person, community, and place, thereby creating a stronger, more holistic platform for hermeneutic phenomenology.

2. Methodological Considerations: Empiricism, Relational Logic, and Becoming

The primary consensus between Wiredu and Bergson is that they are, in their own way, empirical thinkers. Neither agrees with the standard approaches to empirical epistemologies, but both agree that one gathers meaning and understanding through lived encounters. This may seem like phenomenology's notion of existentialism but notice how each evades the typical existential parameters and rather focuses on becoming as a co-generative, relational act. For Wiredu, this is a biological and inculturation process, and for Bergson, it is a biological and psychological process.

I covered Wiredu's empiricism in Chapters Two and Four, but quickly reviewing it, his argument is that Akan rationality hews to an "empirical metaphysic" that relies upon engagement with the world and one's community.¹ He states that what makes this different from other empiricisms is that it focuses on the *capability* to understand through engagement and he does not see the human being as *tabula rasa*. Instead, he argues that a human being is always already born within a culture and, therefore, right from birth, is enculturated into a rational framework.² In short, the human being does not begin from nowhere; they are brought into a world that is already fashioned through language, morals, and culture.

This allows Wiredu to note that the cultural universals of communication and morality arise from biological, and thus communal, needs; not specifically personal ones.³ Notice how the individual, contrariwise to Western phenomenology, is not the focus of engagement. Rather, it is a relational empiricism since one does not encounter the world alone but through others and/or through an already-existing cultural framework.⁴ The cultural community comes

¹ Wiredu, "Empiricism: The Empirical Character of an African Philosophy," p. 22.

² Kwasi Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," p. 214.

³ See: Wiredu, "Reflections on Cultural Diversity."

⁴ More specifically, Wiredu defines empiricism as "the adherence to the empirical imperative without the sensationalistic incoherencies of empiricism. It is the view which close attention to the conceptual intimations of my own culture renders the most plausible to me regarding the fundamental character of human knowledge." From: Wiredu, "Empiricism," p. 33.

before the person who, although merely an organic human at birth, is already becoming a person as they are born into said community.

Finally, recall from Chapter Four that, for Wiredu, Akan thought is spatialized because all empirical encounters happen within space.⁵ Even when thinking abstractly, a metaphorical concept is given its metaphorical space to interact with other concepts.⁶ This is why he prefers arguing that language is a “transference” of ideas and concepts – which emblematically implies a physical exchange of content in acts of communication – rather than just being about symbolic recognition or inference.⁷ This spatial relationship between becoming a person within communal engagement will be proven important further below.

Bergson’s empiricism undergirds how one should engage the world through images, which requires both analysis and intuition. According to Bergson, Kant was right that we understand the world as objects appear to us, which allows us to analytically scrutinize these representations to gather understanding. In fact, Bergson relies upon empirical evidence throughout his writings. The twist, though, is that Bergson critiques Kantian empiricism for only using rational analysis for its engagement with phenomena. This is why merely employing analysis for rationality renders the world into representations rather than images. As Susan Guerlac notes, “Bergson turns the Kantian perspective inside out. He asks whether we do not unconsciously tend to construct our understanding of the inner world according to forms borrowed from the way we view the external world. ... It is the charge he makes against all those who would attempt to acquire scientific knowledge of the actual workings of inner life.”⁸ This is why Bergson thinks associationism – a form of psychology derived from Kantian and positivist philosophies that correlate the mind to outer experiences – misunderstands representations of the mind for the operations within the mind (i.e., the metaphor overtakes

⁵ See: *CUP*, pp. 49-50; Wiredu, “Empiricism,” p. 28; see also: Chapter Four, p. 81-83, 85-87.

⁶ *CUP*, p. 50.

⁷ In *CUP*, pp. 18-19, Wiredu qualifies his terms and explains “human communication is the transference of *thought content* from one person or group of persons to another person or groups of persons. The notion of ‘transference’ here will have to be interpreted metaphorical, as we shall see shortly [Sands: he argues for metaphor so that he can translate Akan thought to others, see *CUP*, p. 20]. On the realistic view [Sands: in the Akan mind], however its interpretation will have to be *impossibly literal*.” Emphasis mine. See also: *CUP*, pp. 49-50.

⁸ Susan Guerlac, in *Thinking in Time* (Ithica: Cornell UP, 2006), p. 94.

the concept).⁹ Moreover, his intuitive approach to rationally engaging the world allows for the possibility of metaphysics.¹⁰

As we covered in Chapter Five, analysis requires intuition's intellectual sympathy when one engages the phenomena as it appears to oneself.¹¹ Through intuition, one can sympathetically engage the object – trying to imagine the object's own sense of being, even if it is inanimate like a stone, as I will show below – and, in so doing, one likewise must open themselves to allow the object to enter into their own mind or sense of perception. This co-penetration between perceiver and perceived co-generates a more comprehensive idea of the object as it relates to whom is perceiving it (and vice versa). For Bergson, this furthers empirical inquiry beyond mere analytical representation and allows both the perceiver and the perceived to gain richer content of each other as entities intertwined in a sympathetic relationship.

For example, let us consider an encounter with a stone on a hike. Although the stone may be inert, I can sense the multibillion-year transformation that caused the stone to be at this specific moment where I am here to perceive it. I can then 'feel' or relate how my appearance to the stone opens me to a deeper understanding of my relationship to the earth; the stone may not become my friend, but it does give me a sense of the vast history of the earth and my relationship to it. In a way, intuition employed alongside analysis allows one to overcome the technological thinking where science treats the world as mere objects for use and mastery.¹² It also shows how *duration* opens my sense of possibilities within the world and how my interactions with(in) the world are a temporal flow of memories, ideas, and concepts through which I gather further understandings and relationships. The time it took for the stone to 'come to me' as well as the time it took for me 'to come to the stone' is intertwined and woven throughout our mutual encounter. As I recall the stone later, such as what I am doing now, the memory of this moment allows me to 'live with the stone,' if you will, which shows that our time with each other carries on.

⁹ *MM*, p. 134. This is a common critique throughout his work.

¹⁰ See: Chapter Five, pp. 96-98, 108.

¹¹ *MM*, pp. 7, 9.

¹² I raise this since, to me, this is very similar to Serequeberhan's reading of Heidegger's critique of scientific-calculative reasoning, see: Chapter One, pp. 8-10, 19; Chapter Three, pp. 55, Chapter Seven, pp. 161-167.

This, at the risk of oversimplification, is the heart of *duration* as a temporal mindset of how one encounters the world: we open ourselves to being sensed as we sense others through intuition, and we are then able to analyze this encounter by recalling other encounters (perhaps comparing this stone to ones I have seen elsewhere, or by beholding the stone's vast history). This recollection is an interplay between my habit memory (knowing what is a stone) and my true memory (recollecting other moments when I have encountered rock formations, my knowledge of geology, etc.), which allows me to develop a co-penetrative relationship between myself and the stone. Of course, inanimate objects may seem innocuous at first sight, but through *duration*, the mere experience of a stone can open panoplies of possible events or understandings.

Both Wiredu's and Bergson's empirical approaches consequently suggest a relational logic to comprehend how the world forms a person: either through the co-generative meaning-making between person and community or the co-generative meaning-making between the perceiver and the perceived. Though from different perspectives, I think we can see a consensus between Wiredu and Bergson on the relationality of empiricism or, for simplicity's sake, a 'relational empiricism.' Note especially that neither thinker employs an immanent/transcendent framework to articulate their positions. This leads to our next point of consensus.

Though one could haphazardly slot them in as 'purely immanent' thinkers, throughout my reading of their work, I think that this is a misrepresentation. Wiredu's argument is that the Akan are a purely spatial-thinking community, but the concept of immanence is not needed (and at worst, could be misleading) when describing their empirical metaphysic. Recall that even abstract or metaphorical thought entails an abstract or metaphorical space. Wiredu never calls the Akan immanent thinkers, and he often critiques Western writers for imposing their categories onto African Traditional thought to make it 'rational.'¹³ Akan rationality

¹³ Note that in *CUP*, Wiredu does employ the term 'immanent' when describing aspects of Akan culture, but this is done via analogy and not a designation of them being immanent thinkers. The closest he comes to calling Akan thinking immanent is on pp. 50-51, where Wiredu critiques the notion of divine interference within the world not because the divine is too transcendent or supernatural, but because "He is too immanently implicated in the nature and happening of things to have any explanatory value." Reading this section as a whole, it is clear to me that Wiredu is attempting to explain Akan thinking – in English no less – to a Western audience who misunderstand Akan 'religiosity.' There are other instances where Wiredu will use the word immanent, but it is always in process of describing Akan thought to others.

stands on its own and does not need Western philosophical terms to explain itself. To be fair, Wiredu does employ said terms such as ‘empiricism,’ but he always qualifies them, and often, they appear to be a means to describe Akan rationality to an outside audience rather than integral to the concept in question.¹⁴

Also, to be fair, Bergson may be considered to have a Cartesian-like “loneliness” or inwardness within his intuitive method and within *duration*.¹⁵ However, neither aspect needs the concept of immanence to be comprehensible or practical. In fact, Bergson argues that *duration* is better understood as a recognition of the flowing, vibrating energy that comprises the phenomena being perceived; we only break it down into images to make it comprehensible *to us*. The imaging of phenomena and the interplay of memory happen within a duration as the mind engages the world, and neither operation requires a plane of immanence nor the *noema* of transcendence.¹⁶

Finally, it is true that Bergsonian intuition makes metaphysics possible and likewise that Wiredu employs spatialized encounters to demonstrate Akan metaphysics, but it would be presumptuous for us to read either as a typical metaphysics that requires immanence/transcendence, transcendentals, or any adjacent concepts to operate.¹⁷ This is why I continually argue that both are employing a relational logic: the possibility of a metaphysics, for both, is an evolving relationship between shared ideas and experiences. Whether sharing happens within a community or within one’s own *duration* will create tension between the two, yet still, the relationality at play allows a wider horizontal concept, which can be called metaphysics. This process, or development, is stymied when placed into

¹⁴ See: Wiredu, “Identity as an Intellectual Problem,” pp. 216-218. Wiredu rebuffs A.G. F. Bello for critiquing Wiredu’s usage of Western terminology and Wiredu’s approach to bringing Akan thought into English in *CUP*, pp. 203-208. He is critiquing A.G. F. Bello, “Philosophy and an African Language,” *Quest: An African Journal of Philosophy*, 1:1 (June 1987), pp. 5-12.

Note, however, that he has been criticized for his use of translation and how, even when diligently explaining Akan thought through Akan language, some thinkers argue he slips back into a Western paradigm. See, for just one example: Godfrey Igwebuike Onah, “The Universal and Particular in Wiredu’s Philosophy of Human Nature,” in *The Third Way in African Philosophy: Essays in Honour of Kwasi Wiredu*, Olusegun Oladipo, ed. (Ibadan: Hope Publications, 2002), pp. 61-97, especially pp. 80-88.

¹⁵ Leonard Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, (New York: Bloomsbury, 2003), pp. 68-70. See also: Chapter Five, p. 110-112; Mary Carman, “A Defence of Wiredu’s Project of Conceptual Decolonisation,” *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 35:2 (2016), pp. 235-248.

¹⁶ Bergson describes this notion of ‘flowing’ through simultaneity in *DS*, pp. 52-53. We will delve further into his notion of energy in Chapter Eight, yet Bergson summarizes this notion well in his essay “Life and Consciousness,” *CE*, pp. 3-36.

¹⁷ See: Chapter Four, pp. 75, 83, 85; Chapter Five, pp. 110-112, 114.

rigid categorical analysis, an analysis that either ignores that the Akan do not need Western concepts to articulate their worldview or an analysis that ignores the intuition needed for *duration*.

One may also think of Wiredu and Bergson as dualistic thinkers given that both employ binary or dual concepts within their method: for Wiredu, it is communication and morality, and for Bergson, it is intuition and analysis.¹⁸ However, this is wrong given that neither thinker sees these concepts as oppositional nor as either/or propositions: they are not pitting one against the other, nor are they saying that one can be analyzed without the other. Moreover, it is not a dialectic since there is no real synthesis arising within the concepts in question. Wiredu notes this well in his argument that one cannot live by cultural universals or particulars alone but “by some combination of both.”¹⁹ These universals need development, then, and it is “by virtue of our biology and inherited potentials” that human beings – these featherless bipeds strewn across the earth – can grow into something collectively larger: a community.²⁰ His two universals, then, are only descriptions of how the human species survives and, in that survival, builds concepts and ideas through a culture or a heritage, to use Serequeberhan’s words. As a social species, a human cannot survive without others, and that survival is actuated through communication and a basic morality. One can only ‘separate’ either concept for intellectual scrutiny, but one cannot pit them against each other, nor synthesize them, nor live without both.²¹

Bergson critiques the notion of reasoning by analysis alone, but he is just as critical of reasoning solely by intuition. Doing the former merely creates representations of the world; performing the latter would disengage one from the world altogether.²² Rather, it is through

¹⁸ One could add impartiality and partiality when it comes to Wiredu, or an ‘ethic’ and an ‘ethics.’ However, these concepts are born out of the cultural universals mentioned above.

¹⁹ *CUP*, p. 9.

²⁰ Kwasi Wiredu, “Identity as an Intellectual Problem,” p. 215

²¹ See: Chapter Two, pp. 32 Chapter Three, pp. 59; In *Self and Community* DA Masolo adroitly points this out in his reading of Wiredu, see: pp. 138-154.

²² It is beyond my scope to argue this further, but to me, this is where sole reliance upon pure memory or intuition intersect since neither are actuated engagements with the world but are passive receptions of the world, either in remembering things past (pure memory) or in solely sympathizing with the world yet without truly engaging the world (intuition). See: *MM*, 152-153; See also: Paul Douglas, “Bergson, Vitalism, and Modernist Literature,” in *Understanding Bergson, Understanding Modernism*, Paul Ardoin, S.E. Gontarski, and Laci Mattison, eds. (New York: Bloomsbury, 2012), pp. 107-109; Leonard Lawler, “Intuition and Duration: An Introduction to Bergson’s ‘Introduction to Metaphysics,’” in *Bergson and Phenomenology*, Micheal R. Kelly, ed. (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), pp. 26-28.

both that one can more sufficiently comprehend the *duration* of the world as it is happening.²³ Yes, there are two components to *duration*, but they are interrelated and co-dependent; recall that Bergson argues that we live within *duration* even if we do not know it. We glimpse *duration* and see the vital mobility of life by recognizing the images created through intuition and analysis, as well as the memories at play when bringing these mental efforts together to sense what is being perceived.²⁴

This is why I find that relationality is a much more accurate and succinct way to describe their logic. Neither thinker 'separates' the world or concepts thereof into distinct components that can exist on their own; they would argue that it may be helpful to understand one component to examine its function within our thinking and everyday life, but such an examination is always already interrelated to the other component. Bergson's analysis of memory is helpful in this way: he begins with how memory functions through both habit and true memory, yet he shows that neither can sufficiently explain the picture of memory without the other. He furthermore argues that they interlace and have a telescopic effect when operative, allowing us to focus upon a specific memory that is functionally important for the specific present moment.²⁵ Wiredu follows a similar path when describing how cultural particulars and universals, and ethical empathetic impartiality and partiality, can be individually examined, but neither can be understood without the other.²⁶

This relationality is key to understanding how a relational empiricism perpetually creates a metaphysics to come: it is an ongoing process and not the standard 'organizing principle' or 'foundation to understanding' one finds in traditional Western metaphysics. What is a metaphysics, for both thinkers, is a conditional process of becoming: whether it is becoming more self-aware, more attuned to the mobility of life, or becoming a pillar of the community, each thinker sees metaphysics as always reaching forward somewhat beyond our grasp. We

²³ See: Chapter Five, pp. 95-100, 109; *IM*, pp. 7, 9, 70, 81-85, 189; *MM*, pp. 7, 24-27; *TF*, pp 4-7, 85-92.

²⁴ Barnard, *Living Consciousness*, p. 10.

²⁵ *MM*, p. 166-169.

²⁶ See: Motsamai Molefe, "An African Perspective on the Partiality and Impartiality Debate," pp. 470-482; see especially, p. 470: "I submit that an under-explored exposition of Wiredu's distinction between what he calls an "ethic" and "ethics" promises to bridge the gap between partiality and impartiality ... My submission is that the element of ethic is congruent with partiality, and that of ethics with impartiality, and that both these facets are a function of human existence that is characterised by the duality of being part of the whole human family and also belonging to some subgroup."

may 'pause it' to reflect upon the given present, but only with an eye to the future-present or present-past.

I will not get into whether either's metaphysics overcomes Heidegger's critique of the onto-theological constitution of metaphysics; that argument would deserve its own investigation (perhaps even a book).²⁷ For now, I raise it only to show that if one were to scrutinize either's metaphysics, they must do it with the notion of mobility or vitality in mind. For both, it is through encountering the world – persons, communities, and places – that we gather a sense of what is the world. Bergson argues that if we engage *duration* to temporally experience the world, then our understanding of it constantly changes and lives with us as our memories carry on those temporal events. Wiredu finds that if we experience the world with awareness of how our communitarian, limited understanding of how the world works, then we can literally further expand our understanding of the world itself; we make space for new ideas in our mind, and we manifest those ideas when engaging others. This is why relational logic is key to fully recognizing the possibilities each thinker brings to us in their work: relationships carry on and develop, and a relational logic does likewise.

This leads us to our next sections, which explore how each thinker diverges from the other and how both may address lacunae within the others' thinking. I will first examine how Wiredu articulates when one becomes a person, then I will follow this with Bergson's description of where one becomes a person. In my final analysis, I will bring them into further conversation by exploring the direction and mobil(ies) of this becoming as it relates to personhood and community.

For Wiredu, his notion of becoming is clearly seen in how a human becomes a person through community. However, in describing this becoming, Wiredu is very apprehensive about whether the concept of faith has any role to play. He describes his moral anthropology and its cosmology (i.e., its metaphysics) purely on rational terms. As I noted in Chapter Four, I think he does this in response to the stereotype that Africans are overly supernatural. However, I think Bergsonian intuition may broaden Wiredu's cultural and moral anthropology and how it articulates the co-generative nature between person and community. Moreover,

²⁷ For Bergson, see: Heath Massey, *The Origin of Time: Heidegger and Bergson* (Albany: SUNY Press, 2015).

it further allows for the integration – or inculturation – of a lived existence, as discussed in our conversation between Serequeberhan and Wiredu in Chapter Three. Finally, when does this becoming happen? Or, more pointedly, what is the temporality of this becoming? As we shall see, Wiredu does not give a very clear answer to the temporal nature of becoming, and I think *duration* would address this.

3. Wiredu: When Does One Become a Person?

Wiredu is very apprehensive when it comes to the concept of faith. As stated before, he defines faith in his own unflattering terms. He argues that “what is believed by faith is, by virtue of that fact, inaccessible to rational evaluation” and, given that those with faith believe their information is God-given and thus infallible, “there can be no chance of dialogue” with those believers.²⁸ He does leave the door open for believers who are willing to accept the fallibility of their faith, though he does not recognize that most concepts of faith within religion readily accept that faith is anthropocentric, fallible, and uncertain.²⁹

I covered this at length in Chapter Four and argued that I find two primary reasons why he critiques faith in such a way: First, from a personal perspective, Wiredu is heavily concerned with the legacy of Africans being treated as overly spiritual or superstitious peoples. Second, from a philosophical perspective, Wiredu wants to demonstrate the inherent rationality of his Akan-based moral anthropology and its cosmology. However, I would now like to add a third reason to his critique of faith: Wiredu believes that faith severs dialogue between persons and communities.

The quotes above come from a section of his article, “Reflections on Cultural Diversity,” where he is setting the stage for how different cultures can dialogue or interact with each other. By setting aside a fundamentalist, rigidly dogmatic faith, Wiredu goes on to demonstrate how different types of moral reasoning can inform each other. Reason alone is the keystone to both dialogue and further developments of culture (or between cultures).³⁰ Through his

²⁸ Wiredu, “Reflections on Cultural Diversity,” p. 126.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 126.

³⁰ See: Chapter Two, pp. 27-30, 42-44, where I detail Wiredu’s relationship with analytic philosophy. See also: Barry Hallen, *Reading Wiredu*; Olusegun Oladipo, “Wiredu’s Idea of African Philosophy) in *The Third Way in African Philosophy: Essays in Honour of Kwasi Wiredu*, Olusegun Oladipo, ed. (Ibadan: Hope Publications, 2002), pp. 50-56.

adoption of Dewey's genetic method and its empirical analysis of culture through language, Wiredu crafts a philosophy that he thinks details how religion may operate within the mind, but merely as a cultural concept and not as a rationally informed epistemology.³¹ In a sense, whereas Kant denied reason to make room for faith, Wiredu goes a step further and denies theology – or any reasoned reflection on the divine or divine revelation – to progress philosophy. The progression of philosophy thus becomes the progression of community and inter-cultural dialogues.

I find that he does this at his own peril, though, given that he never provides an account as to why faith is a widely held – almost universally held – cultural concept and an epistemological one at that.³² He critiques religious faith but never replaces its moral and psychosocial vitality within the person or community. It is reason alone. Multiple African philosophers have critiqued Wiredu's notion of Akan reason – and, by extension, African reason – as being purely rational. For instance, Godfrey Igwebuike Onah argues that:

Wiredu's personal philosophy of human nature rejects two of the most fundamental principles in the Akan ontological concept of person, *okra* as an entity and the reality of God from whom *okra* is supposed to be directly derived. He is also sceptical [sic] about the actual nature of *sunsum*. Besides giving *okra* and *sunsum* a naturalist interpretation as quasimaterial entities, he criticises the hypothesis which regards *okra* as the principle of life. First, he observes that this hypothesis is based on the mistaken idea that every living being must have a principle of life. But if it were so, then the principle of life must itself be a living being and therefore must have its own principle of life ... *ad infinitum*. The problem is compounded by the postulation of the principle of life as an entity, which, according to Wiredu, is the result of the error of hypostasis. If rather than thinking of *okra* as an entity it was thought of as a concept, Wiredu thinks that the logical absurdity associated with the idea of an *okra*-entity would be avoided.³³

Onah then concludes that Wiredu “gives a rigorously this-worldly interpretation of Akan traditional philosophy” since parsing *okra* and *sunsum* (concepts that Onah and other Akan thinkers relate to spirit and/or one's spirituality) as “at most-quasi-material” entities or

³¹ Kwasi Wiredu, “What is Philosophy,” pp. 164-165; Hallen, *Reading Wiredu*, pp. 2, 20.

³² Scope and space preclude me from going in-depth on the way faith operates as an epistemology, but, for instance, see: Richard Kearney, *Anatheism*, (New York: Columbia UP, 2011); Colby Dickinson, *Haunted Words, Haunted Selves* (Eugene: Cascade Books, 2024); John D. Caputo, *Specters of God* (Bloomington: Indiana UP, 2023).

³³ Onah, “Wiredu's Philosophy of Human Nature,” p. 82.

properties would problematize Wiredu's emphasis on the material, spatiality of Akan cosmology.³⁴ It is not so much that Onah or others think Wiredu is completely wrong about Akan thought. It is rather that, by trying to hew to a purely rational thought – one that employs Akan logic but nonetheless excludes the spiritual aspects of the Akan – Wiredu may hold too much to his Analytic philosophical roots than he may realize.³⁵

This is also why I call his definition of faith a critique of fundamentalism rather than a complete description of the faith believed and practiced throughout various cultures and traditions.³⁶ However, if we look at Bergson's critique of analytic rationality and apply it to Wiredu's philosophy, we see an even larger gap left by excising faith as a form of rational reflection. From there, we can see where intuition may fill this gap without resorting to redefining the concept of faith on Wiredu's behalf.

As argued before, Wiredu's philosophy is one that is entirely spatial and his empirical metaphysics relies upon rationalizing encounters as they appear to us. This rationalization is an analysis of what has appeared to us, and it is reasoned through our own historico-cultural framework.³⁷ Recall that one of his arguments for a conceptual decolonization is so that African communities can reinvent or rediscover their own rational frameworks. Yet, according to Bergson, are not all these analyses of appearance mere representations of the event and thing in question?

To be clear, Wiredu does not argue that Akan cosmology must be universally held, but his principle of sufficient reason – "*biribiara wo nenkyerease*" – becomes a secret underpinning to his concept of cultural universals and his notion of inter-cultural dialogue.³⁸ However, even if we agree that Akan religion is solely rational and has no need for faith, not every culture

³⁴ Ibid., p. 82.

³⁵ Olusegun Oladipo explains this well in "Wiredu's Idea of African Philosophy," pp. 50-56. See again: Molefe, "A Critique of Kwasi Wiredu's Humanism and Impartiality." Of course, there are various other critiques, I am mainly sticking to the most relevant sources for concision and simplicity. Note that the constant reference to his Oxford and analytic training is a not-so-subtle critique of Wiredu's 'professional philosophy,' a debate we covered extensively throughout this dissertation.

³⁶ See: Chapter Four, pp. 76-80; see also Wiredu's response to Michael Onyebuchi Eze and Thaddeus Metz concerning religion: Michael Onyebuchi Eze, Thaddeus Metz, "Emergent Issues in Philosophy: A Dialogue with Kwasi Wiredu," *Philosophia Africana* 17:2 (Winter 2015-2016), pp. 79-80.

³⁷ For more on culture's role in rationality, see: Anke Graness, "Wiredu's Ethics of Consensus: A Model for a Global Ethics?," in *The Third Way in African Philosophy: Essays in Honour of Kwasi Wiredu*, Olusegun Oladipo, ed. (Ibadan: Hope Publications, 2002), pp. 259-262.

³⁸ CUP, p. 50.

defines faith as Wiredu does. If they must follow Wiredu's directives for inter-cultural dialogue, they may sever aspects of what they call reason but what Wiredu calls faith.³⁹

Furthermore, Wiredu's rationality arises from encountering other aspects of the world and then relating them back to prior encounters to arrive at an understanding of the matter at hand. In this way, his empirical metaphysics expands through future encounters happening in space, but each understanding of an event or thing is correlated to another event or thing. All these encounters set up a logic or rules for understanding since, as Wiredu argues, humanity is a "rule following animal, and language is nothing but an arrangement of rules."⁴⁰ This is associationism, albeit tacitly so, given that things encountered are always related to other things and not considered unto themselves. All the analytical rules are crafted by associating external events with internal, moral, and political ideals.

Faith, in many cultures, is often used to explain why there is something rather than nothing and why each given thing has a purpose unto itself. Faith may rely upon divine revelation – however construed – but it does have its own logical reflection and contribution to a given person's sense of understanding. Even Kant recognized a need to remedy this lacuna through his moral reasoning on transcendental idealism.⁴¹ However, given that there is no transcendence nor immanence within Wiredu's thinking, Wiredu's relational logic is trapped within a web of transference.

Analysis becomes the way to understand why this thing exists here, how it is like that thing over there, and how comparing each thing in question reveals how they exist together. However, this logic can never engage how a given thing exists unto itself. The benefit of this relational logic is that it emphasizes the socio-political nature of things – how no perception is without a history nor can be understood outside of the perceiver's own historico-cultural framework – but, as such, the thing is always already a physical *representation* of a person's socio-cultural understanding of the world. Perception and reasoning are always a transference of content or an economy of knowledge, leaving a given thing without its own

³⁹ Motsamai Molefe points this out in "A Critique of Wiredu's Humanism and Impartiality," *Acta Academia*, 48:1 (2016), pp. 100-101.

⁴⁰ *CUP*, p. 25.

⁴¹ See: Alison Laywine, *Kant's Early Metaphysics and the Origins of the Critical Philosophy* (Atascadero: Ridgeview, 1993), p. 1; Jordan Bell, Pamela Sue Anderson, *Kant and Theology* (New York: T&T Clark, 2010), pp. 23-25, 56-58, 59-64,

raison d'être. It is a representation of ideas and not the complete 'picture' or image of the thing itself, nor of the reality they encounter.

Perhaps this is where Bergsonian intuition may help: through intellectual sympathy, one moves past the appearance of the thing and how it relates to other things experienced and, thus, can enter into a relationship with the thing itself. Although I do not believe intuition is an analogue to faith, it does seem to fill the void of faith within Wiredu's logic. It may also be a way of crafting a philosophy of religion within Wiredu's thinking that sympathizes with the act and content of faith within culture, opening possibilities to understand how people think and see 'through the eyes of faith.' In such a way, it reopens the dialogues Wiredu argued were shut.

Moreover, this is not the first instance in which someone has suggested intuition as a supplement to Wiredu's philosophy. H. Odera Oruka proposed that Wiredu's overemphasis on logic excluded the intuitive nature of the mind:

I wish to include intuition and state that this is the most obvious of all cultural universals and yet the one least recognized and appreciated in philosophical dialogues and scientific inquiry. It is, therefore, not surprising that Prof. Wiredu has not thought it necessary to include in his list of cultural universals given that numerous others also exclude it.⁴²

Through exploring sage philosophy, Oruka defines intuition as "a form of mental skill which helps the mind to extrapolate from experience and come to establish an extra-statistical inductive truth, or it enables the mind to make a correct/plausible logical inference without any established or known rules of procedure."⁴³ Carrying on, he shows how sage philosophy within African traditions often arrives at truths but without an appeal to God, science, or logic. It is not a matter of purely inductive reasoning either; it is a matter of cohering experience with feeling or sensing what is happening around said experience:

Yet, the sayings are neither a matter of common sense nor a religious faith. But at the same time the sayings are earthly, i.e., empirical and logical enough that they do not give their author the color of one possessed by 'ghosts in machines.' *Still the sayings are*

⁴² H. Odera Oruka, "Cultural Fundamentals in Philosophy: Obstacles and Dialogues," in *The Concept of Knowledge: The Ankara Seminar*, Ioanna Kucuradi, Robert S. Cohen, eds. (Boston: Springer-Science & Business Media, BV, 1995), p. 170.

⁴³ Oruka, "Cultural Fundamentals in Philosophy," p. 171.

not fully amenable by the techniques available to science and logic. These two, science and logic, can verify intuitive claims, but they cannot disprove them. Yet, we should not confuse intuitive truths with the Kantian transcendental world of 'things in themselves.' Intuition is a truth of wisdom and wisdom is so far wisdom of this sensible world [sic].⁴⁴
(Emphasis mine)

For Oruka, intuition is related to wisdom and perception. It also shows that there is a place within Wiredu's cultural universals for something like wisdom-via-intuition to emerge. However, while Oruka's reading of intuition within or against Wiredu would make for a strong comparative philosophical project within African philosophy, for our present purposes, I will turn to Bergson's understanding of intuition as an alternative means of engaging the concept.

I do so not to make a Western-African philosophical dialogue but because I think Bergson's articulation of intuition as a distinct method of philosophy more closely relates to Wiredu's ultimate aim of understanding the world through a rational framework, however culturally bound. Moreover, Bergsonian intuition opens Wiredu's concept of becoming a *durational* temporality. Oruka provides us with an African culture's notion of intuition, which must be further explored, but for these reasons above, I think Bergson's methodological approach may prove more helpful for our present purposes, scope, and this work's primary thesis.

The way that Bergsonian intuition would operate within Wiredu's relational empiricism is that the perceiver critically acknowledges that what is being perceived is a spatial recognition, and that the relationship between said perceiver and thing is not merely the perceiver associating/relating the thing to other things. Rather, this recognition seeks to sympathize with the thing in question – opening the perceiver to imagine what it is like to be the thing being perceived by the perceiver at this moment – and how that thing came to be within the sightline of the perceiver (the thing's own history and life, if you will, up to its presentation to the perceiver). This opens Wiredu's relationality beyond a cultural construct of rules, language, and morality. To be sure, it does not take anything away from those aspects of his logic, but intuition allows that relationality to deepen one's appreciation of all things – from

⁴⁴ Oruka, "Cultural Fundamentals in Philosophy," p. 172. Note that, in the concluding section (p. 176-180), Oruka levies a similar critique of the Westernization within Wiredu's approach, also bringing up his Oxford or Analytic background as other critics have, and gently presses upon Wiredu to incorporate aspects like intuition – which can be found in not just sage philosophy but throughout African traditional beliefs – within his empiricism, ethics, and so forth.

persons to rocks – since it intellectually offers a movement of co-penetration between the perceiver and the perceived. This intellectual effort requires a trust, an open-endedness, that one often sees within different concepts of faith.

Moreover, intuition addresses the temporal question hidden within Wiredu's notion of becoming. When does one become a person? At what moment does one's notion of the world or universe expand to incorporate new ideas or knowledge? Wiredu is quite silent on this issue. I have only found one instance of this where Wiredu briefly discusses temporality, and it is when critiquing Kant's *a priori* construction of time and space. He notes that time is an "order of events" and that "time itself was conceived to be logically bound up with the notion of events."⁴⁵ His point in this text is to show the empirical nature of temporality, but he never goes further than this. Thus, he does not explore how memory and meaning-making are created through this ordering. Moreover, his metaphysics does not question the temporal relationality of objects in existence. It seems as if time, for Wiredu, is left unexamined beyond it being an empirical experience, which leaves me asking, 'how and when does this becoming happen?'⁴⁶

Bergsonian *duration* may be able to answer this question, but it would require intuition to be integrated into Wiredu's logic. This may stretch Akan rationality too far, or at least Wiredu's reading of his own culture, but I do not see anything preventing it. Especially given Oruka's commentary above. Intuition, as far as Bergson employs it, is merely a method of seeking an understanding of the perceptual interpenetrative relationship between two entities. It allows a space for one to sense or feel for the person or object one perceives, a co-penetration whereby each informs the other of their own sense of being. It would, therefore, open Wiredu's relational empiricism to engage the passion, emotion, and feelings of others, which can be rationally understood but not rationally *felt*. Or, following Oruka, experiences that science and logic can verify, but not disprove. Consequently, it opens a temporal sensation of emotion to Wiredu's concept of becoming.

⁴⁵ Kwasi Wiredu, "Empiricism," *Identity Meets Nationality: Voices from the Humanities*, Lauer, H., Appiah, N.A., Anderson, A.J.A. (eds). (Legon-Accra: Sub-Saharan Publishers, 2011), pp. 28-29.

⁴⁶ Portions of this paragraph come from: Justin Sands, "Communal Space, Communal Temporality: Kwasi Wiredu and Henri Bergson in Dialogue," *Phenomenology in an African Context: Contributions and Challenges*, Abraham Olivier, M. John Lamola, and Justin Sands, eds. (Albany: SUNY Press, 2023), p. 291.

It does this because of *duration's* inherent notion of memory as having a habitual and emotional component. Wiredu's principle of sufficient reason may explain why someone does something out of rules (or say, habits), but it can only explain why someone feels the way they do through associating one act with another. For example, if I am robbed and call the police rather than enacting vigilante justice, Wiredu would respond that this is part of my culture: there is a breach of the impartial rule to treat others as one wishes to be treated, and I result in my culture's process of remedying that breach. Wiredu would also respond that being robbed would change my character and how my community sees me: they may offer assistance and support, and the police are part of that communal structure, too.

However, Wiredu's logic can only associate my trauma of the event with other traumas; it can never allow others to 'feel' or sympathetically sense my pain; it can only causally describe that pain. When this affects my becoming or development as a person, it can describe the ordered events of my life but not how those events *still live within me* and perhaps even within my community. The latter is vastly important since some communities are perpetually haunted by traumatic events, as we have discussed with the residual and generational traumas of colonialism and social memory in Chapter Five.⁴⁷

Duration would allow a communal epistemology such as Wiredu's to see the successive temporal-memorial flow of events that comprise both an individual's personhood and a community's culture. There are events that continually live with a person, sometimes in an unconscious or pure memorial manner, that arise and inform how that person acts. Likewise, a heritage or culture is a *mélange* of shared memories and stories that informs a community of their customs, mores, and, yes, even religions. The empirical nature of moral anthropology – and even its cosmology – is, thus, not a linear progression of events. Although everything may be spatialized within Akan thinking, this space is not neatly ordered; it has layers of experiences sedimented and interlaced throughout each other (*pace* Serequeberhan's heritage).

Intuition would allow Wiredu to access experience outside of causal rationality while maintaining a relational logic of becoming. In so doing, it would also open *duration* to describe

⁴⁷ See: Chapter Five, pp. 115-121.

the temporal nature of this becoming and especially how it is not a successive or linear progression. Rather, through intuition, one can sympathize with others as they become, and through *duration*, one can experience the mobile vitality of another's becoming; one can even 'become' alongside, through, or with another person. Intuition would open Wiredu's relational empiricism to new possibilities while still keeping the spatialized, rational, and relatively bound within Wiredu's thinking. *Duration* would open Wiredu's thinking to reveal the layering of experiences that relate to each other as person and community co-generate their becoming.

At the moment, this may seem like a synthesis whereby I suggest sublimating Bergsonian thinking within Wiredu, but this is not my intention. My aim in this section was to address the representation and temporality problems within Wiredu's thinking and how Bergson may be able to address those issues without overtaking (or being synthesized into) Wiredu's project. In the next section, I will show how Wiredu may do the same with Bergson and, again, without overtaking Bergson's project. In my final analysis, I will show why keeping this as hermeneutic tensions – rather than a synthesis – is relevant. I will also describe how each thinker informs us of the spatio-temporal nature of becoming and how this can contribute to a more robust hermeneutic phenomenology.

4. Bergson: Where Does One Become a Person?

As mentioned in Chapter Four, one of Bergson's primary critiques against analysis and critical thinking is that scientists and philosophers mistake the metaphor for the concept.⁴⁸ In so doing, these concepts get quantized, and their misconceptions become overdetermined by spatial metaphors.⁴⁹ This creates massive problems with how we perceive the relationship between consciousness, the body, and the outside world. These critiques are why his first two major works, *Time and Free Will* and *Matter and Memory*, are focused on addressing issues of spatio-temporality.

⁴⁸ See: Chapter Four, p. 100-101, 110. Portions of the following paragraphs are reformulations from: Justin Sands, "Communal Space, Communal Temporality: Kwasi Wiredu and Henri Bergson in Dialogue," pp. 293-295, 300-302.

⁴⁹ *MM*, pp. 24-27; *TFW*, pp 4-7, 85-92; see also: Suzanne Guerlac, *Thinking in Time*, pp. 50-60, 110-115.

Time and Free Will finds the debate between liberationists and determinists to be defunct since they introduce “space into our perception,” which “corrupts at its very source our feeling of outer and inner change, of movement and of freedom. Hence ... the problem of free will.”⁵⁰ In short, the problem of free will is not whether our decisions are determined but *how we perceive our decisions* by cutting them into segments rather than as a flow of creative, successive events. “All of the difficulties of the problem and the problem itself,” Bergson summarizes, “arise from the desire to endow *duration* with the same attributes as extensity [i.e., space], to interpret a succession by a simultaneity, and to express the idea of freedom in a language into which it is obviously untranslatable.”⁵¹

The untranslatable, here, is what lies at the heart of the problem. Bergson finds that philosophy and science seem “particularly concerned to prove that we perceive things through the medium of certain forms, borrowed from our own constitution.”⁵² This is also the problem with monism and dualism, as seen in *Matter and Memory*. The problem is that the debate separates consciousness from materiality, ignoring how one’s perception of the thing in question is at play within the thing itself – as seen via intuition. We draw our perception out of the thing, and through *duration*, our perception of the thing and its own materiality becomes interpenetrative.⁵³

In both cases, the mediation or metaphor causes confusion regarding differences in kind (i.e., category), forsaking the notion that they are differences in *degree*. It is a perceptual confusion not just in rank and number or how we order our perceptions – where quantitative thinking resides – but also in how our faculties of perception work; the description of perception becomes confused with the means of perception itself. Going back to Guerlac, the problem is the faulty correlation between outer and inner experiences, where the outer experience (the spatialized metaphor) becomes the way in which one understands the inner experience (the perception of, and reaction to, the event at hand).

This critique of metaphor is heavily focused on the spatialization of consciousness and is seen throughout his *oeuvre*, especially in these two books. In short, this is the problem with

⁵⁰ *MM*, p. 74.

⁵¹ *TFW*, p. 221.

⁵² *TFW*, p. 222.

⁵³ *MM*, pp. 50, 68, 78-79.

representation: its metaphorical parsing of the world fails to sense the vitality of the world that it seeks to understand. Spatial overdetermination essentially forgoes intuition to create mere temporally bound representations of consciousness and/or materiality. Moreover, scientists and philosophers are happy with these representative quantifications, categorizations, and differences in kind rather than in degree, because these are easier to parse or scrutinize. Recall that, for Bergson, thinking comes too easily for us and to sense *duration* we must resist these representative impulses to spatialize and quantify everything.⁵⁴

However, as David Addyman notes, “one would not obviously look to Bergson for an account of space; even if one did, one would not immediately find a clear elaboration of the issue. ... Bergson’s critics – and even his admirers – have tended to recognize only one form of space – the ‘bad’ space of ‘spatialization.’”⁵⁵ Bergson’s intent is to have us recognize *duration* and its sense of the mobility of life, and to do so he must clear away poor representations, but he leaves underexamined the space in which this life vitalizes. If *one* were to seek to understand this mobility, then *duration* would allow them to do so; keeping images as moments of consciousness can adequately describe how an individual perceives events. However, if *we are to perceive life to collectively co-generate memories and cultures* – to live with movies, stones, and worldly events – then we must do so in an environment, in a ‘good space.’

This is where I think Wiredu may contribute to Bergsonian *duration* and flesh out a sense of *communal duration*, as argued in Chapter Six.⁵⁶ For Wiredu, space is social. This is inherent within his thinking; if communications are vital, and the world becomes demarcated through this communication – this is where to search for food, danger lurks over there – then the space of this world is socially imbued with meaning. Wiredu clearly states that, when it comes to space, anything like a Kantian *a priori* is a terminological contradiction:

Yet, even if it is granted that the notion of space is *a priori*, it does not follow that what the notion refers to can so much as be spoken of as being *a priori* or otherwise. ‘*A priori*’ applies to a mode of knowing, not a kind of entity or existent. If space is infinite, it may still be that the only way to conceive of it is through the notions of location or place and

⁵⁴ *IM*, pp. 80-91.

⁵⁵ David Addyman, “Bergson’s Matter and Memory: From Time to Space,” in *Understanding Bergson, Understanding Modernism*, Paul Ardoin, S.E. Gontarski, and Laci Mattison, eds. (London: Bloomsbury, 2013), pp. 24-25.

⁵⁶ See: Chapter Five, p. 121-126; Chapter Six, p. 145-150, 152.

of infinite extendibility, both of which are empirical. This is certainly how space is conceived in the Akan language.⁵⁷

Before I unpack this, let us quickly return to Lawler's comment that there is a loneliness in *Matter and Memory*. This observation is astute since it speaks to Bergson's approach as well as to his results. On the one hand, if the world comes to us too easily, and therefore we believe thinking comes to us too easily, then one must withdraw into a Cartesian-like meditation. It is not surprising, then, that such a hermetic withdrawal would render its findings for *a singular* consciousness; if one needs to turn within oneself to seek understanding then it seems fair to say that one finds only oneself. Again, this is why Lawler puts Bergson in opposition to Derrida and Levinas, two philosophers of alterity.

In contrast, Wiredu likewise seeks an understanding of life, but instead of a singular self, he finds that one needs others to survive, and this survival can only happen if there is communication between each other. Wiredu emphasizes the importance of a socially created world, and rather than withdrawing from it, he delves into it. It is as if Wiredu is responding to Bergson's critique, saying, 'the world may come too easily for us, but that is why it must be our first exploration! We must begin with an anthropology.'

Duration, for Bergson, is not just how a consciousness experiences phenomena and creates its world; it is also and foremost consciousness' mobile engagement with/in that world. In a sense, it describes the way in which *one is time* in terms of the vital flow of life and one's engagement with the world rather than describing one as living in a time or through a time. Moreover, recall that meaning-making happens when one's memories of prior events interlace with each new and oncoming event. Finally, our perception of phenomena is only rendered coherent when we break these perceptions down.⁵⁸ Yet, as argued in Chapter Five, Bergsonian *duration* only comes to the individual, and memories are articulated only in the singular.⁵⁹ A *communal duration*, though, would reveal how this mobile vitality of life is lived amongst and within others.

⁵⁷ Wiredu, "Empiricism," p. 28.

⁵⁸ Recall the notion of the image and how consciousness requires these images to allow us to make the experience of phenomena intelligible.

⁵⁹ See: Chapter Five, p. 101-103, 113, 121.

Through our exploration of collective memory, I argued that memory is both within oneself and also shared with others. It is passed down, carried forth, through various forms of *commemoration*: memorials, movies, songs, holidays, stories, and especially through a community's cultural norms and rules.

A chronopolitics is at play within time, and no proper notion of temporality can forget this: even if we excise the spatialized metaphors of time, we cannot remove the memories within time; as expressed through Bergsonian true memory and his notion of *duration*. Crucially, those metaphors actively memorialize this vital flow of life; as mentioned in Chapter Five, colonizers brought with them their own temporality, their own historico-cultural contexts, and obliterated the temporalities of the colonized.⁶⁰ A forgotten task of decolonization, as Anthony Monteiro notes, is not just to retrieve or revive these contexts but also their own notion of time and space.⁶¹

I proposed that this raises a problem for *duration* given its inward reflection upon time and space, which makes it a process for 'the self' while neglecting how the self does not retrieve nor recollect time in a vacuum. I proposed that true and pure memory – the former being events recalled and the latter being unconscious or forgotten recollections – possess a communal aspect; one never remembers alone. To quickly summarize, I noted how *duration's* interlacing between habit, true, and pure memory presents us with the notion of *communal duration*. *Communal duration* is the shared experience of events, recalled for the moment at hand as true memories are, or (and especially with trauma) that they lay quiet in a collective unconscious. As Idella Gallagher notes, Bergson's "theory of knowledge" (i.e., intuition and analysis) is inseparable from his "theory of life" (i.e., *duration*), and, if this is so, then there must be a point where both meet: that is, they both need to expand beyond an individual's *duration* of life and co-generate with others, with a community.⁶²

Thus, we arrive at space: there must be a place where this becoming happens, where this co-generation transforms and evolves. For, if the *elan vital* is a vital force permeating throughout all life (as will be further explored in Chapter Eight), it must permeate something, *somewhere*.

⁶⁰ See: Chapter Five, p. 119-121. As engaged in that Chapter, see also: Mills, "The Chronopolitics of Racial Time," pp. 297-317; Atkins, *The Moon is Dead! Give Us Our Money!*

⁶¹ Monteiro, "Time, Space and Race: On Clarence J. Munford's *Race and Civilization*," p. 53.

⁶² Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, pp. 39.

Bergson is quite clear that matter becomes reality through intuition and analysis revealing the perceived through *duration*. The issue then pivots to where *duration* occurs. In short, if *duration* is real, then there must also be *a medium in which it happens*. Space is where one interplays with phenomena whilst also being a phenomenon itself. Hence why we break it down into an image to make it intelligible in the first place. Here, in this medium, we not only experience the world; we build it as we create more and more memories and experiences.⁶³

In this way, we *create space* or, as Wiredu puts it, from out of our concrete experiences and designation of places, a conceptualization of infinite space arises; out of a 'here' and the designation of a 'there' and other 'theres' arises the notion of everywhere and/or anywhere. Rather than space being an *a priori*, we derive the abstract notion of space through our experience/creation of places. Recall that, for Wiredu, existence is empirically spatial, and to abstract entities, one correlates an abstract space; we first experience a place in order to render reflections of its infinite possibilities. Out of these infinite possibilities comes the notion that space can be infinite. Note that it is infinite not just in the sense of 'ever-expanding' but also in the sense of possibility, where anything can happen within space. Once it happens, it becomes a place and is, therefore, meaningful and concrete.

Yet we must negotiate places with others, it must be communicated to others what these places are, or more importantly, what they mean. Here, we begin to see not just the building of a particular culture but also how one's personality (à la Wiredu) is built within and alongside that culture. *Communal duration*, where each instance is interlaced with memory and the novelty of the current experience, can help us uncover the interplay between the self, their cultural society, and the places that both have co-generated.

Following Wiredu, this initially refers to vital communications, as in this is a place where you can find food, shelter, etc. Then these places build with meaning as they are experienced; places for shelter become villages, and places for food become markets. Through this evolution, knowledge is handed down and developed from one generation to the next.⁶⁴

⁶³ Although Bergson may dislike the notion of space being a medium, I do not think that this reading of him is too far off base. See: *MM*, 196-202.

⁶⁴ Wiredu, "Reflections on Cultural Diversity," p. 204; Wiredu, "Moral Foundations of an African Culture," pp. 196-198; *CUP*, pp. 25-26, 29.

Throughout this process, he reminds us that these memories and teachings develop cultures which in turn define individual personalities.

I think the same can be said for our places, and this cultural development of space is not something that is static; it is a living phenomenon that we experience. We do so not just when we enter into these places but also when we recollect them, assimilate them, or bring them into contrast with other places. In this sense, these places are co-generated in so far as our social and personal memory of them are maintained every time we recollect them. In contrast, and akin to the old practice of *damnatio memoriae*, a place can cease to be if it is completely forgotten. Finally, a place can be recontextualized as we discover its previous histor(ies).

Regarding Bergson's notion of memory and its importance to meaning-making, this raises the question of social memory. It is here that I think Wiredu may have something to contribute to Bergsonian *duration*, namely a culture which is carried through a *communal duration*. *Duration*, at least as expressed in his earlier works, lacks the capacity to maintain a sense of culture.⁶⁵ Perhaps one could argue that he does within *Two Sources of Morality and Religion*, which I will cover in-depth in Chapter Eight. Yet in *Two Sources*, he speaks more of 'society' in general – whether open or closed – and when he speaks of morality or politics, it is through a broad and evolutionary lens rather than as a socio-historical or communal one.

However, a *communal duration* endows memory with shared beliefs, ideas, concepts, and so forth. In the case of spatio-temporality, it allows the medium of experience to be incorporated into the experience itself. 'Bad space,' or the overdetermination of spatial metaphors, can be overcome through an intuitive understanding that the space in which an event occurs is just as important to the picture of the event as what that picture depicts. Space is thus incorporated into the degrees of sensation rather than a quantification of sense.

As I have argued throughout this work, and as I have shown above, one does not merely remember alone. Wiredu emphasizes that one is taught a culture, and through living within

⁶⁵ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 191-198, where I review Bergson's notion of political philosophy. In short, and as I will argue in Chapter Nine (pp. 220-223, 225-228, 231-233, 233-239), I find that Bergson reads morality and society through a broad, evolutionary perspective which, while important, can at times be too individualistic and introspective, as if he is thinking about the purpose of societies rather than the actual peoples and cultures which exist within them.

that culture, one changes this culture before passing it on to others. Through this, he articulates a culture as having a social memory. This social memory can be incorporated into *duration* via what I have described as a *communal duration*. It is also why I think understanding both Wiredu and Bergson through a relational logic is important: for both, there is a dynamic interplay between the self and its community (otherwise understood as phenomena), and through this play, they co-generate meaning by creating new memories. They also do this by reinterpreting prior memories as they redefine their relationships and pass these memories down through culture. Although Bergson begins by withdrawing from the world to better understand the *duration* of oneself within that world, he has not forgotten that the world exists. Rather, he has sought how one relates to this world by focusing on one's consciousness, which is the closest certainty one can have (again, very Cartesian).

What Bergson leaves underexplored is the other side of this equation. For Wiredu, his sense of becoming a person is entirely predicated upon memory: one not only takes up the characteristics of their personhood but is even designated as a person through their culture, and a culture requires an institutional, shared memory between selves. Moreover, these selves render their places with meaning and history through this shared memory.⁶⁶ That is, there is a *personal* (with all the implications of personhood) and a *cultural* memory of places. And these need to be negotiated through a politics. Again, I am not trying to synthesize the two, but perhaps Wiredu can point toward how Bergsonism can develop a good rendering of space, a social memory – a *cultural duration* – which could bridge the gap between Bergson's thinking on consciousness and on politics. It could also tease out his thinking on the issue of other selves, which is where a culture not only happens but is preserved through memory.

5. Final Analysis: The Direction and Mobility of Becoming

In our first conversation, I explored the relationship between subjectivity and agency. This conversation revealed that responsibility is what bound the concepts and what expanded their scope: when humans become persons through their community, it only happens when both the individual and the community have fulfilled their obligations to each other. If one were to become a lived existence, *pace* Serequeberhan, they do so in service of their

⁶⁶ *CUP*, pp. 159-167.

community and take up more responsibilities to guide and liberate their community. Furthermore, whether in Serequeberhan or Wiredu's philosophy, the ultimate aim is a liberation of entrapping frameworks of understanding and thus a realization of broader possibilities for persons and communities. Paraphrasing Serequeberhan, it is in pursuit of realizing new possibilities heretofore unknown to the community, and, to summarize Wiredu, it is in the process of intellectually evolving our species.

The issues that I focused on through our present conversation, and the previous two chapters, are when and where this becoming happens. Clearly, there is a co-development between person and community, or a lived existence and one's heritage, but in what arena does this development happen and when? I argued that Wiredu's moral anthropology provides the spatialization of this development through its focus on the empirical *capability* of humans to learn, to evolve: as one expands their moral reasoning, they also expand their horizons of both worldly knowledge and the expanse of the world. In short, their knowledge of the world co-develops with the expanse or extension of the world in which it now encounters.

Complimentarily, I argued that Bergson's *duration* clarifies the temporal nature of this becoming: it is not a linear progress, nor is it an analytically comprehensive succession of events; it is rather a deep sensation of grappling with how one's engagement with the world construes a mobile reality of that world. This mobility, expressed as *duration*, is the temporal gesture through which our memories and experiences influence our ever-ongoing presence within the present moment.

However, Wiredu and Bergson do not seamlessly form a cohesive notion of spatio-temporality. Wiredu's hyper-rationality cuts a sharp edge in that everything falls under a principle of sufficient reason of some kind (*biribiara wo nenkyerease*).⁶⁷ In response, I argued that perhaps the concept of intuition – whether through Oruka or Bergson – can supplement the knowledge production that Wiredu's philosophy does not take seriously. I chose Bergson since his articulation of intuition maintains Wiredu's emphasis on empiricism while presenting itself as rational. Whether that stands up to scrutiny is for readers to decide, but in my project, at least, it allows Wiredu's spatiality to round out two things that I found lacking in Bergson:

⁶⁷ *CUP*, p. 50.

an account of ‘good space’ and how to bring in shared memories through sites of interaction and events.

As Addyman points out above, Bergson lacks an account of ‘good space’ and this may be for the same reason that Wiredu lacks an account of ‘good faith:’ both thinkers are so focused on the battles they are fighting that they fail to present an alternative. However, granting some grace to both thinkers, one philosopher can only do so much.

Issues of establishing a spatio-temporality aside, that is the core of why I argue for a *communal duration*: neither Wiredu nor Bergson – or Serequeberhan for that matter – needs to philosophize alone. Every philosopher draws upon other thinkers (an institutional memory) in their work, just as every person draws upon their culture to navigate and understand the world. No one is alone; nothing is in silo. The same goes for our memories and our spatio-temporality; the more we share with each other, the more we learn about our world and the greater, ever more expansive it gets. If we harness the fact that no one is alone and we each come to one another with different characteristics that form our personhood, then we can open ourselves – either through communal dialogue via an empirical metaphysic, an intellectual sympathy via intuition, or some other means of openness – then we can actualize Serequeberhan’s philosophical dream:

...we will invent. But this time around tempered by the surpassed pitfalls of what we have come to see as dead ends ... and focused on solidarities – nurtured by mutual concerns – which have overcome the delusion of thinking that they possess, or that it is possible to possess, a foolproof system, *metaphysics*, to guard against the risks of inventing. This, then, is the treasured intellectual-political inheritance of humanity.⁶⁸

This is why I find no real need to ‘reconcile’ the contrasts or incongruencies between Wiredu and Bergson. There are tensions between these two thinkers, like the ‘dirtiness’ I highlighted between Serequeberhan and Wiredu in Chapter Three, our first conversation.

Concerning hermeneutic phenomenology as a method for future philosophy, it needs to be open to these tensions and see them as sites of creativity. It needs to accept the inexactitudes of life and the world which it is trying to describe. At times, one may need to employ the concept of ‘the self’ as well as personal-communal concepts of spatio-temporality to arrive at

⁶⁸ *EH*, pp. 118-119.

better understandings. There is a malleability, in other words, which is necessary for the method to thrive. The point is to demonstrate that hermeneutic phenomenology needs to create more pathways to understanding, and this present conversation demonstrates that the task is possible.

For me, I find that Wiredu and Bergson both point the way; Wiredu gives us the direction (space), and Bergson gives us the mobility (time). The question then becomes, what do we do with it? I think our first conversation answers this question: we pursue the evolution of our species, we pursue liberation – even if we are uncertain what liberation means at this point. What remains unclear, and what will be the focal point of our next conversation, is what happens to space and time in this becoming, in this co-development. This is where Serequeberhan and Bergson come into conversation regarding how, over time, space gets embedded with its own meaning and living history. It, too, becomes alive with heritage; it, too, grows and evolves.

**CONVERSATION THREE: SEREQUEBERHAN AND BERGSON ON POLITICS,
HISTORY, AND CREATION**

**CHAPTER SEVEN:
FROM GADAMER TO HERITAGE:
SEREQUEBERHAN'S ACTIVIST HERMENEUTICS**

1. Introduction

In Chapter One, I investigated Tsenay Serequeberhan's hermeneutical concept of existence. I found this an ideal opening to this work for reasons detailed in the chapter's Introduction, but essentially it was because his thinking shows the stakes involved within the question of personhood and existence. Therefore, following Serequeberhan's own approach, I began by detailing the ravaging impact of the West's imposition that Africans lacked a philosophical rationality. Importantly, this was not merely an account of colonialism's devastation. Rather, it revealed how Serequeberhan shapes his notion of existence *through* this devastation.

For Serequeberhan, where to begin when rationality has been historically and systematically denied to you is through a self-reflection of how this denial has shaped your own existence and those within your community. As he states in *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy*, "in [Heidegger's] deconstructing reading of the tradition of European metaphysics, starting from the lived ecstatic phenomenality of human life, Heidegger asserts – against the ossified and ossifying ontotheological conceptions of human existence – that human reality (*Dasein*) is not a present-at-hand substance or entity, but the lived fluidity/actuality of its own existence."¹ Or, as Serequeberhan continually highlights throughout his work, and with a perfect twist of irony, the starting point to overcoming others' denial of your ability to philosophize is to think meditatively about thinking itself. The resulting contemplation of your own existence and your own being-in-the-world can disclose to you heretofore unknown possibilities of your world. Therefore, you recognize your own existence in its full, concrete reality within the world.

¹ HAP, p. 20.

His concept of existence, as I pointed out, is neither existentialist (as in Fanon or Sartre) nor is it materialist (as in the Marxist-Leninist thinkers, which he pillories throughout his work). Rather, it hermeneutically begins with one's emerging self-realization of their own standing out (*ek-sistence*) from the world as-it-is (or comes to oneself). This allows one a space/clearing to both see one's place within history as it unfolds and also see beyond the horizons that were (post)colonially handed down to them.² From this vantage point, one begins to see a fusion of horizons and the possibilities of a lived existence contrary to what has been handed down to them.³ In that chapter, I focused solely on his concept of existence since it was both integral to my project's conversation on personhood and community and because it was never thoroughly examined within extant scholarship.

Complementarily, this chapter presents how Serequeberhan's hermeneutics does not attempt to overcome Eurocentrism and its ensnaring ideologies but rather accepts them as part and parcel of African(a) persons' heritage. Therefore, the aim is not to 'overcome' Eurocentrism as such, but to activistly pass through it – to debate it, disentangle it, decolonize it – in pursuit of uncovering other parts of one's heritage which Eurocentrism denied, overtook, or sought to colonize as their own. Serequeberhan argues that self-emancipation from these forces can only happen through this existential-historical realization and through engagement.⁴ Therefore, his method fundamentally holds a political impetus; he does not 'break method' by moving towards the prescriptive, which would be problematic for Western hermeneutical methods, which are based solely on descriptive interpretation.⁵ Remarkably, his method *is inherently prescriptive*, activist even.⁶

² *EH*, p. 2.

³ One could argue, following Heidegger, that it should be 'the possibilities of a lived existence contrariwise into which one has been thrown.' However, I chose 'handed down' here since it falls in line with Serequeberhan's reading of Heidegger and foreshadows his appreciation of Gadamerian 'tradition,' which Serequeberhan molds into his concept of heritage. It reveals how one's heritage is given to them through their community; it is a tradition, which, from its Latin roots, literally means handing down or over (*tradere*).

⁴ Tsenay Serequeberhan, "Philosophy in the Present Context of Africa," *Theoria*, 168:86, no. 3 (September 2021), pp. 32-33.

⁵ See Richard Kearney's work on Paul Ricoeur's hermeneutic phenomenology. For example, in *On Paul Ricoeur: The Owl of Minerva*, you will see how a cantilevering example, opposite Gadamer, whose hermeneutic operation is inherently descriptive. You can also see this in Kearney's own diacritical hermeneutics and in the authors whom both he and Ricoeur have influenced.

⁶ "Consciously and in a critical and rigorous manner," Serequeberhan argues, "[African Hermeneutics] will appropriate and add to the practical and engaged theoretic heritage of the African liberation struggle. In so doing, it will become a radical and emancipatory hermeneutic inventory of our post-colonial African inheritance." HAP, p. 115, emphasis mine.

I will start unpacking this argument by locating how Serequeberhan's tandem notions of existence and heritage inhabit a hermeneutic tension: as one's self-realization of one's own existence strengthens, so does their self-realization of the historical events that have shaped one's existence. I will then show how this is not a dialectic but a tension through revisiting Serequeberhan's usage of Heidegger's notion of *Ge-stell* (sometimes restated as 'en-framing,' or 'ensnaring' by Serequeberhan). This notion demonstrates that the process of becoming a lived existence is an ongoing reckoning between one's existence and one's heritage. Finally, rather than a typical conclusion, I demonstrate how this always already political hermeneutics is likewise always already activist through a brief case study of Serequeberhan's reading of Fanon. This open-ended conclusion shows how, once one sets upon the pathway of becoming a lived existence, one cannot merely stand back and remove the injustice within the world; one must run toward it in service of others' self-emancipation.

2. Existence and Historicity: A Hermeneutical Tension

To set our exploration, we must quickly return to Serequeberhan's notion of existence, which he molds and shapes within his hermeneutics. Although he states that Gadamer is an improvement upon Heidegger, he recognizes that "Gadamer tames or domesticates Heidegger's position" and that "Gadamer fails to bring out the element of resolute 'releasement' which is central to Heidegger's conception of thinking" and, by extension, Heidegger's concept of existence from which Serequeberhan appropriates.⁷ So, in a sense, what Serequeberhan's tandem notions of existence and heritage maintain Heidegger's resolve towards the world while also employing Gadamer's hermeneutics to open this world to new possibilities (i.e., new horizons). However, for Serequeberhan, remember that one does this to move towards the world itself, not merely to step back and let it open itself to *Dasein*; rather, actuation is essential for crafting an activist, prescriptive, and emancipatory hermeneutics.

Serequeberhan is remarkably consistent in his molding of Gadamer and focuses on three primary concepts: Gadamer's reappraisal of 'prejudice,' his notion of 'effective-historical consciousness' (*wirkungsgeschichtliches Bewusstsein*), and his concept of the 'fusion of

⁷ Tsenay Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer: Thinking as 'Meditative' and as 'Effective-Historical Consciousness,'" *Man and World*, 20:41-64 (1987), p. 59.

horizons.’ It is worthwhile discussing these in detail before moving forward so we can see how necessary heritage is to existence and why Serequeberhan cannot merely choose to be, say, a Gadamerian and must press beyond his influences to shape a new hermeneutics.

Concerning prejudice, what Serequeberhan appreciates is Gadamer’s view of shared pre-understandings we collectively hold “which are themselves not static but revisable – and indeed constantly revised – [and the] effects of this circular interplay” creates “an ongoing interpretative process.”⁸ As he states in “Heidegger and Gadamer,” “the consciousness saturated with history is not concerned with the methodical filtering out of pre-judgements, for it understands that it is only from *within the structure of prejudice that constitutes the present that the past and what it says can be heard.*”⁹ Clearly, Serequeberhan appreciates the historicity and pre-conditionality that Gadamerian prejudice acknowledges, but I also think one other slightly hidden admiration is that Gadamerian prejudice (and, broadly, the historicity of Gadamer’s epistemology) requires no Kantian transcendentals.¹⁰ There is no categorization of principles from which we can deduce one’s epistemic existence; we can only respect that one’s knowing and understanding of the world are inextricably linked to the historico-cultural world in which they were born.

This leads toward the notion of ‘effective-historical consciousness,’ which Serequeberhan describes as:

...The hermeneutical encounter with tradition [which] is open to the tradition’s claim on truth. In this encounter tradition/history (i.e., written or oral past) is not muffled but allowed to challenge the certainties of the present. The interpreter or philosopher in this situation – the embodiment of ‘effective-historical consciousness’ – is in a questioning and yet released disposition to that which the past holds in its independence and the autonomy of its possibilities.¹¹

⁸ *EH*, p. xii.

⁹ Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer,” pp. 55-56, emphasis mine.

¹⁰ See: *EH*, pp. 75-76, 84. Note that, on p. 47 of *EH*, Serequeberhan critiques Gadamer for praising Kant as the “greatest philosopher of all time,” but then goes on to show how this praise does not diminish Gadamer’s surpassing of Kantian transcendentals. Also, in *CM*, Serequeberhan, pp. 6-7; Tsenay Serequeberhan, “Eurocentrism in Philosophy, The Case for Immanuel Kant,” *The Philosophical Forum*, 27: 4 (1996), p. 336.

¹¹ *HAP*, p. 26. Serequeberhan is again very consistent with this reading of Gadamer, and he typically makes it the foundation of his projects, restating his definition either in the Introduction or initial chapter of his works. See, for example, in *EH*, p. XII, where he rearticulates this definition, albeit with less technical language.

The value he finds in this concept is its acceptance that each tradition has its own given truth claims. This opens further explorations of truth – individually and socially – by allowing for an interpretation of one’s own history while also establishing a conduit to engage others. “This ‘openness,’” Serequeberhan argues, “is thus the tangible stance of a seeking that consciously owns up to and is aware of its own finitude and specific distinctiveness.” Continuing, this allows a person who “incarnates” this stance “to concretely recognizing the partiality and/or flaws ... of his own historical heritage. It is this that institutes the space for the Other ... to be a possible, or imaginable, source for a *different*, or countervailing, truth.”¹²

In short, an ‘effective-historical consciousness’ is self-awareness of one’s own historicity and consequently their own finite perspective on the world. This allows them to recognize that they not only hold prejudices (which are essential to their own self-understanding) but that they can learn and appreciate others’ perspectives and others’ historicity. Prejudice and historical consciousness thus provide an opening for future possibilities, which Serequeberhan will eventually employ to craft a concept of a lived existence which can pass through the conditions of the historical present whilst crafting a more open, more liberated historical future.

This exposes one to possibilities heretofore unknown to oneself. Encountering others in this more appreciative (or, perhaps, more authentic) way “is the actuating of the ‘fusion of horizons’ in and through which the acuity of understanding occurs, or can occur, as it sieves/sifts that which it encounters.”¹³ He also welcomes the “risk” involved since it “lets the past speak” by one placing their truth claims in jeopardy through such an encounter.¹⁴ In summary, it allows one to appreciate how one’s own life is conditionally and historically situated. By accepting this and ‘letting go,’ being open to truly encounter otherness, one recognizes a “fusing of horizons” where one’s historicity is not static, not merely an object to

¹² *Eh*, p. 75. Serequeberhan quotes from Hans-Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, W. Glen-Doepel, trans. (New York: Crossroad, 1982), p. 238.

¹³ *Eh*, p. 80. Serequeberhan quotes from Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, p. 252. Recall that Serequeberhan often employs the word ‘authentic’ but vaguely defines it.

¹⁴ Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer,” p. 56. He repeats this appreciation of risk throughout his work, for example, see: *Eh*, pp. 79-81.

be studied, but is living and ongoing; it has possibilities (both good and bad) yet to be realized or actuated.¹⁵

Furthermore, knowing this gives one the ability to better understand other persons, the opportunity to reshape one's understanding of one's own past – things concealed, forgotten, or ignored – and, importantly, the impetus to actuate possibilities previously undisclosed to oneself. As Serequeberhan summarizes in *Existence and Heritage*, for Gadamer, “‘true experience is that of one's own historicity.’ It necessarily follows, then, that hermeneutical experience – *which is concerned with understanding that which is preserved and passed in and through a heritage* – in being, itself, within the realm of experience as such must exhibit its basic structure,” meaning its own historico-cultural situation.¹⁶ Continuing, he states that this structure “must harbor and tangibly reflect the finite/limited character of human experience. *The stance it takes toward the past and/or Other traditions is thus an effort not to assimilate but to comprehend that which it's own and/or Other traditions harbor and preserve.*”¹⁷

From the above, what we can surmise from Serequeberhan's Gadamer is that a more authentic historical future is possible through an honest engagement (or encounter) with one's and others' historico-cultural situation (i.e., the historicity that forms and shapes one's worldview or *Weltanschauung*). Furthermore, Serequeberhan values how Gadamer employs Heidegger's concept of the mind through the lens of a historical world upon which one's understanding of the world is constructed. The past is always ongoing; it cannot be dissolved into mere context or conditionality; *it is who we are* (or at least who we think we are). For Serequeberhan, this is the linkage between Heidegger's notion of *Dasein's* concrete and open relationship with the world and Gadamer's hermeneutics. Both are essential to recognizing the relationship between existence and one's own heritage. As he states at the end of “Heidegger and Gadamer:”

¹⁵ Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer,” p. 56: “...the past, in this consciousness, is not an object for the present to study; rather it is the background in which the present understands both itself and the tradition from which it arises.”

¹⁶ *Eh*, p. 89, emphasis mine. He cites Hegel from: Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, *Hegel's Science of Logic*, A.V. Miller, trans. (New York: Humanities Press, 1976), p. 321. See also: *Eh*, p. 85 for another fundamental summary of Serequeberhan's reading of Gadamer.

¹⁷ *Eh*, p. 90, emphasis mine.

In Heidegger's words; the 'effective-historical consciousness' (*Dasein* in concrete historical engagement) in being 'released' to the 'region,' is used by the 'region' in the disclosure of what it harbours. Which in this case is tradition as the historical horizon within which we live and think. The text or tradition uses the 'truly historical consciousness' to make itself heard. Thus thinking as 'meditative' or 'releasement' to the region, is the 'effective-historical consciousness' understood within the context of the problem-complex of hermeneutics.¹⁸

Notice how, for Serequeberhan's purposes, though each thinker divergently engages the finite nature of thinking and understanding, both ultimately arrive at the same end: they each describe aspects regarding the relationship between self-realizing one's existence and self-actualizing one's engagement with a historically situated/conditioned world. For Serequeberhan, most importantly, *this is not dialectical*. Rather, he is showing how inextricably linked an *ek-sistence* is for hermeneutically appreciating one's heritage:

Existence is always actualized in a specific and concrete heritage. Existence? The word derives from the Latin *existere*: *ex-*, out, plus *-sistere*, to cause to stand, set, place, to come forth, stand forth. Based on this we can say that that which exists is that which stands forth. A heritage, then, is the sedimented layering over time that is, the life of a community – of the actuality of existence, which in 'standing forth' does so necessarily in specific and determined ways and thus constitutes a heritage, a certain way of 'being-in-the-world.'¹⁹

For Serequeberhan, the lack of recognizing that existence is necessarily tied to heritage (or, put broadly, a historico-culturally conditioned hermeneutics) is what doomed the entho- and professional philosophy debates. They never realized, as we will detail below, how their debate was ensnared within a Eurocentric ideal of what philosophy is (and it is not). *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy* is the first lengthy test of his thesis, and his appropriation of Heidegger and Gadamer allows Serequeberhan to clear away "the dilapidating Eurocentric metaphysics," which he perceived to be the debate's fundamental problem.²⁰

¹⁸ Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 58.

¹⁹ *OH*, p. ix; see also: *EH*, pp. 1-2.

²⁰ *HAP*, p. 32. Note that, even though he was writing this in 1994, he continues this critique against particular forms of African philosophy throughout his career. See: *EH*, p. 53: "The critical deflation of this self-referential authority, the de-structive querying of its pretense, of its narcissistic metaphysics—the theoretic linchpin of colonialism and racism—is also a central preoccupation, the critique of Eurocentrism, of African/Africana philosophy. For, as argued above, the end of colonialism calls for a re-thinking of the pretense (i.e., ideas and concepts, the prejudices and presuppositions) that *authorized its practice*."

Interestingly, note that Serequeberhan uses two major thinkers within that European tradition (one of which was affiliated with the Nazi party, even) to critique his African colleagues and present a pathway forward. At first blush, this presents a contradiction, if not hypocrisy. However, it is also something of which he is well aware, and he even uses it to his advantage.²¹

What gives him license to employ such thinkers (and for others as well) is that he goes beyond merely criticizing or acknowledging his sources' Eurocentrism.²² Rather, he recognizes how all-encompassing Eurocentrism is to any contemporary philosophical discourse and, since it cannot be avoided, one must activistly pass through this Eurocentrism (*pace* Gadamer's risky engagement) in order to arrive at a disclosive, historically evolving truth about oneself and their concrete existence in the world (*pace* Heidegger's releasement and mediative thought):

...I begin with the candid recognition that Europe has *de facto* globalized itself. Thus its heritage is part of our lived Africanness, a heritage we share in as stepchildren. ... For we, contemporary Africans, are products of the world imaged in the semblance of Europe. Our present postcolonial world, in *effect*, is the uneasy *mélange* of those who engaged in the *mission civilatrice*, those who took up the 'White Man's burden' and produced *évolués* and *assimilados*.²³ (Emphasis Serequeberhan's)

This reminds me of the older debates concerning Heidegger's onto-theo-logical critique of metaphysics, where thinking is grounded upon an unquestionable ideal or god, which thus renders all knowledge through this lensing ideology. Therefore, one either accepts, rejects, or reformats knowledge to fit within the ossified, unquestionable ground of one's metaphysics.²⁴ The dilapidating metaphysics Serequeberhan critiques are Eurocentric and,

²¹ See, amongst multiple examples: *CM*, pp. XIII-XV, 46-54. See also: Abraham Olivier, "Enframing and Transformation: Serequeberhan's African Phenomenological Approach," in *Phenomenology and Organisation Studies*, François-Xavier de Vaujany and Jeremy Aroles and Mar Pérezts, eds., (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2022), pp. 538-540.

²² See, for instance, Ch. 2 of *EH*, "Continental and African Philosophy" (pp. 39-54) where he excoriates Levinas for his Eurocentrism, fundamentally undercutting both the myth of Levinas and problematizing Continental philosophy's myopic view of rationalities beyond its line of sight.

²³ *CM*, p. XIX; Note that much of *Contested Memory* explores untangling this metaphysical ensnarement. It is a critical, deconstruction of an 'icon' in European modernity – Kant, Hegel, and Marx – and Serequeberhan does this from a historical-critique of each respective author's assumption of reason and its underlying metaphysics. See: *CM*, pp. 12, 16-19, 112-113, 122-123, 141-143, 162-163.

²⁴ See: Martin Heidegger, "The Onto-Theo-Logical Constitution of Metaphysics, in *Identity and Difference*, Joan Stambaugh, trans. (New York: Harper & Row, 1969), pp. 42-74. For an overview of how philosophers and theologians have tried to overcome this problem, see: Justin Sands, "After Onto-Theology: What Lies Beyond the 'End of Everything,'" *Religions*, 8:5 (May, 2017), pp. 1-24.

much like philosophers and theologians who have tried to overcome onto-theo-logical metaphysics, African philosophy attempts to overcome Eurocentrism.

However, rather than overcoming this imperialized ideology, which is nigh impossible given its reach, Serequeberhan *accepts it* as part and parcel of his and others' African heritage.²⁵ Accordingly, it is about acknowledging it; not about overcoming it. It is about activistly passing through it and, in the process, accepting it critically as part of Africa's colonial heritage. Doing so within an existential-historical hermeneutics allows one the ability to critically recognize, reframe and deploy the influence of this historical factuality that construes their world. Furthermore, it provides them with the self-awareness (amongst other tools) to actuate their past, to rediscover, renew, reclaim, or reframe aspects of their history heretofore disclosed, colonized, denied, or otherwise debased.

One cannot be disinherited from one's past; one must critically accept it. According to Serequeberhan, through critical acceptance, one can rediscover their heritage in a new light, thus changing their present, their future, and their future-past through *realizing* these fusing of various horizons.²⁶ Through self-realizing their own existence within the vantage point from which they see these horizons, the world discloses new possibilities. His hermeneutics, then, is a process of thinking within a lived existence which, in short, 'knows itself.' A lived existence which emerges from this interrelation between *Dasein* and heritage, opening one to a broader horizon of possibilities beyond their previous recognition.²⁷ Therein lies the possibilities of self-emancipation from Eurocentrism.

²⁵ See also: Ndumiso Dladla, "Contested Memory: Retrieving the Africanist (Liberatory) Conception of Non-Racialism," *Theoria* 153, 64:4 (December, 2017), pp. 101-127. Therein, Dladla employs Serequeberhan's 'combative hermeneutics' as a means of critically interrogating Eurocentrism: "African philosophy understood as a liberatory or 'combative hermeneutics' (Serequeberhan 2009: 44) requires our re-reading of texts: a re-interpretation of history, of social practices and concepts which is grounded within the African experience. This approach is necessarily conscious of the violent ways in which Europe centred herself, and displaced, dominated, degraded and distorted all that which was not European and has been in contrast or conflict with Europe – as well as the way this process continues today (p. 102)."

²⁶ 'Future-past' here implies that one is always already reinterpreting their own historicity and that of their culture. As ongoing process, one reinvestigates their history and finds new interpretations and narratives of events, new ways of understanding how they arrived at who they currently are. The emerging discipline of critical fabulation is a terrific example of this, see: Saidiya Hartman, *Wayward Lives, Beautiful Experiments: Intimate Histories of Social Upheaval*, (New York: Norton, 2019).

²⁷ Note that this is *Dasein* according to Serequeberhan's appropriation of Heidegger, not necessarily Heidegger's own, rather distinctly rigid definition. I covered this in Chapter 1, but see also: *HAP*, p. 20.

3. En-Framing and Emancipation: The Fruitful Tension Between Existence and Heritage

I will further unpack the hermeneutical tension between existence and heritage later into this section. However, for now, it should be clear that Serequeberhan sees all philosophy as fundamentally hermeneutical.²⁸ Consequently, it is inherently political since it is from within our 'effective-historical consciousness' – a framework that is always already shaped by past and ongoing events – that we are able to think and philosophize. 'The political,' here, is key. What Serequeberhan does better than other hermeneuticists who likewise agree that hermeneutics is always already political is that he presses further: it must not be about merely recognizing bias or context within interpretation, as seen in Paul Ricoeur's *d'où parlez vous?*²⁹ Nor is it merely a hermeneutics of suspicion or decolonial critique, as seen in African philosophy, past and present. For Serequeberhan, a hermeneutics must also be willing to act as a guide to changing these political contexts through an interplay between one's own self-realization and one's critical examination of one's culture, history, and thus one's heritage.³⁰

For Serequeberhan, what postcolonial African philosophers did, knowingly or not, was forget how ensnared within Eurocentrism their own historico-cultural situation was. Concerning professional philosophy's embrace of Marxist-Leninist thought and politics as a means of liberation, Serequeberhan was especially polemical:

“[this is] nothing more than a futile attempt to square the proverbial circle since to subscribe Marx's thought understood as 'scientific socialism' or Marxism-Leninism, one necessarily subscribes an evolutionary developmental metaphysics of history – historical materialism – that places Africa at the lowest rung of the evolutionary ladder of development, which fulfills *its* 'objective' and singular 'human' *telos* in the historic eventuation of European modernity.”³¹ (Emphasis Serequeberhan's)

²⁸ See: Olivier, "Enframing and Transformation," p. 534.

²⁹ HAP, pp. 20-21. For a strong, African appraisal of this Western tradition, see especially: Ademola Kazeem Fayemi, "Hermeneutics in African Philosophy," *Filosofia Theoretica: Journal of African Philosophy, Culture, and Religions*, 5:2 (July-December, 2016), pp. 3-6. The text is mainly a *reportage* of the current state of hermeneutics within an African context, and note that on, pg. 8, Fayemi gives a very brief summation on Serequeberhan's emphasis on history within his hermeneutics.

³⁰ For others who are engaging hermeneutics and activism from a different yet at times overlapping perspective, see: Edwin Etieyibo, "African Philosophy in the Eyes of the West," pp. 84-103; Justin Sands, "Hermeneutics, History, and *d'où parlez vous?* Paul Ricoeur and Tsenay Serequeberhan on How to engage African Philosophy from a Western context", *South African Journal of Philosophy*, (2019) 38:4, pp. 371-382; Charles Mills, "The Chronopolitics of Racial Time," pp. 297-317.

³¹ HAP, p. 39.

In other words, replacing one Eurocentric ideal (Capitalism, which was part and parcel of colonialism) with another Eurocentric ideal (Marxism and its emphasis on a techno-utopian future) does nothing to emancipate Africa from its Eurocentrism.³² Though professional philosophers believe they have found a pathway to emancipation through critiquing the Eurocentric nature of ethnophilosophy, they either fail to see the ways in which their remedies mimic European ideals or ignore the problem altogether so as to be a part of the ‘professional’ conversation that is academic philosophy.³³

The question becomes, then, how do we reflect upon the historico-cultural ways in which our thinking is enclosed? If we are to activistly enact a self-reflection upon the ways in which the world shapes our thinking and our concretely real existence within that world, what resources do we have to recognize the borders which conceal possible horizons and potential pathways to self-emancipation? To answer this, Serequeberhan employs Heidegger’s notion of *Ge-stell*. Through the concept of *Ge-stell*, Serequeberhan sees a way to break through Eurocentrism’s epistemic closure, a closure that has globalized itself to become the lens through which all persons and cultures see and understand their world.³⁴

Note that Heidegger employs his concept of *Ge-stell* in his critique of technology to highlight how scientific-calculative thinking (and, subsequently, its onto-theological metaphysics) shapes our understanding of the world. Resultantly, it informs how we engage that world and how we employ concepts/items/persons within that world for our own ends.³⁵ It renders out the other possible understandings and meanings that these concepts/items/persons may have within themselves, placing them in a given situation, typically a situation used to one’s advantage or otherwise seen as scientific-calculative problemata to overcome so that one can achieve their endgame. Seen in a technocratic light, for example, a forest becomes timber, with all its possible beauty, ecology, and other promises for life rendered out. Persons become ‘human resources’ or ‘manpower’ – at its worst, ‘soldiers’ – which can be employed

³² *OH*, pp. 53-55.

³³ *OH*, pp. 1-3, 37-39.

³⁴ For more on epistemic closure, see: Chapter One, p. 5; Lewis R. Gordon, *What Fanon Said*, p. 49.

³⁵ Martin Heidegger, “The Question Concerning Technology,” in *The Question Concerning Technology and Other Essays*, W. Lovitt, trans. (1977, New York: Garland Publishing) pp. 3–35.

as means to an end for others.³⁶ Concerning other cultures, rather than seeing them through the possibilities of an authentic encounter, one sees them as competition or as potential human capital to employ and one's own service. In short, through the concept of *Ge-stell*, Heidegger locates how we shape or see the world to our advantage and the role that technology plays (be it a missile, a computer, or a pen) in this process.

Recall the quote above concerning Serequeberhan's worry about Marxist-Leninism's reliance upon development as the eventuation of European modernity, not emancipation from it. Here, one can see how this concern is integral to his hermeneutics:

To paraphrase Heidegger, 'development' is the global *Ge-stell* (en-framing) of modern technology playing itself out and being manifested as the perpetuation of European modernity's cultural and technological dominance of the Earth. It is this *Ge-stell* of European dominance, manifested as the 'neutrality' and 'objectivity' of science and technology, that Africa must overcome in order to reclaim and carve out the existential, historical space in which to ground its freedom.³⁷

Ge-stell functions as the intellectual operation through which metaphysics' onto-theological nature categorizes and shapes knowledge; effectively becoming the intellectual muscle, if you will, through which people justify the subjugation of the world into their own making. This includes persons, animals, and nature. Furthermore, according to Serequeberhan, it articulates the "thingification" of African persons: for centuries, Africans were seen merely as tools or commodities discovered by Europe, exploited for Europe, and this process continues to this day.³⁸ En-framing, therefore, describes how one situates nature and others as materials to master the world around them, intellectually justifying their actions, even at times fashioning them as theologically righteous or politically necessary (as seen in the concept of 'White man's burden').

In *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy*, Serequeberhan appropriates *Ge-stell* to illuminate how both ethno- and professional philosophers participated, and even propelled, this process: it was because they failed to see how their debates were always already en-framed

³⁶ For more see: Justin Sands, "Technical filmmaking and scientific narratives: Has science overtaken fiction in recent science fiction? An analysis of *Gravity*, *Interstellar*, and *The Martian*," *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 37:1, pp. 56-58.

³⁷ *HAP*, p. 40.

³⁸ We should also, by extension, include the United States and other Western countries in this analysis. *EH*, p. 101-116; *HAP*, pp. 68-73.

from within a Eurocentric notion of what is – and is not – philosophy. Furthermore, this oversight not only failed African intellectual thought but also enhanced Eurocentrism’s control over Africa and its people and cultures:

Seen from the perspective of Heidegger’s Being-question, and the grounding ontic-ontological destructive analysis that derives from it, the modern world is caught in the snare of the *Ge-stell* (en-framing) of modern technology. ... We too – the ex-colonial subjects of this ensnared and ensnaring Europe – suffer from this *Ge-stell*. But for us, this situation of en-framing is mediated, instituted, and imposed through the persistence of neocolonialism as the continued intrusion of European hegemony in present-day Africa.³⁹

In response to this crisis, he states that African philosophy needs a stronger grasp of its own historico-cultural situatedness. It needs a thoroughgoing historical-hermeneutical awareness, which he hopes to provide:

In this regard, the hermeneutics of contemporary African philosophy or African philosophical hermeneutics is a thinking of new beginnings born out of our political ‘emancipation’ and the historical and political crisis of European modernity – the long-awaited weakening, if not demise, of our subjugators. ... In other words, the philosophic discourse does not just happen; rather, it is the articulation of reflective concerns interior to a negativity arising out of the horizon of a specific cultural and historical totality within which it is located and framed.⁴⁰

In sum, Serequeberhan’s problem with much of mainstream postcolonial, African philosophy is that – whether from one side or the other – it unthinkingly always already reflected European ideals. Ethnophilosophers, knowingly or not, crafted their work in reflection of European rationality; often writing for a European audience, even. Professional philosophers did the same when they tried to present themselves as ‘real philosophers’ (i.e., professional academics) because they engaged in ‘traditional’ philosophical questions. However, it just so happened that this tradition was always European, whereby these philosophers treated Africa as a “geographic designation,” as if it were just south of France and not concerned with real, African-centric problems, contexts, and histories.⁴¹

³⁹ HAP, pp. 20-21.

⁴⁰ HAP, p. 24.

⁴¹ HAP, p. 5. Serequeberhan uses the disparaging phrase, ‘merely a geographic designation,’ against professional philosophers – especially Paulin Hountondji – throughout his work.

This, in and of itself, is not a new observation, and indeed it was a critique African philosophers charged against others often.⁴² Importantly, though, neither side could not do otherwise since they were always ensnared in a tacitly suffocating Eurocentric ideal of what is and is not philosophy, what stands as reason and rationality.

What is new, though, is that Serequeberhan shows that these philosophies *and* their critiques failed to recognize the ensnarement within which their debates were held. Through *Ge-stell* and, eventually, his tensive notions of existence and heritage, Serequeberhan hopes for a reckoning with this ensnarement, a detangling, if you will, of what it has done but without looking away from its destruction. One cannot ignore it; one cannot proceed as if it is over or try to go back to before it happened. One must critically accept it as part of their heritage. For Westerners, by the way, this means acknowledging one's complicity in this history: whether one was directly involved does not matter, all Westerners (especially white men, such as myself) have benefitted one way or the other from this Eurocentrism.

Returning to his analysis and critique, to my mind, it covalently folds into Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's sentiments in *Decolonizing the Mind*. Therein, Ngugi stresses that colonialism enforced a mindset whereby "it makes [the colonized] see their past as one wasteland of non-achievement ... Amidst this wasteland which it has created, imperialism [i.e., colonialism, Eurocentrism] presents itself as the cure and demands the dependent sing hymns of praise with the constant refrain: 'theft is holy.'" ⁴³ I think this coalesces with Serequeberhan's hermeneutics since his notion of a lived existence is one that is aware of this ensnarement, both its historical employment and its present operation. Furthermore, rather than forget it or otherwise attempt to jettison it from one's remembrance of the past, a lived existence directly confronts it – almost Dionysian-like à la Nietzsche – to reckon with what it has done, what it is doing, and how such a lived existence can move beyond it.

Recall that one cannot be disinherited from their heritage. The past will not pass, it lingers and shapes our thinking whether we recognize it or not. Here lies the hermeneutical tension between existence and heritage: they cannot be reconciled or synthesized, nor can they stand

⁴² See: Chapter One, pp. 16-20.

⁴³ Ngugi Wa Thiong'o, *Decolonizing the Mind*, p. 3. See also: Justin Sands, "Historical, Hermeneutical Awareness: Colonial, Postcolonial, and Decolonial Mentalities," in *Understanding Business Ethics in the South African Context*, Mark Rathbone, ed. (Pretoria: Van Schaik Publishers, 2020), pp. 120-136.

forth by themselves. *Ek-sistence*, standing forth, needs to understand the world upon which and through which it stands. *Ek-sistence* cannot fully realize its possibilities and take hold of its concrete reality (*Dasein*) as its own unless it reckons with its world and that world's history. Countervailingly, merely acknowledging the history of the world – say, as seen in typical historical-critical hermeneutics – is not enough to fully emancipate oneself from the ensnarement(s) within that history and the world created by/through that history. A decolonial critique, for example, is merely a description of what has happened and does nothing to liberate others unless it is pressed into service of liberation; that does not happen unless someone stands forth and makes a change in course.

This tension is necessary for both existence and heritage (as concepts and potentiates to enact a liberated reality). It also is necessary for any self-realization or communal-realization to bear any fruit: for Serequeberhan, we need people to stand forth to express their *ek-sistence*, and not look away from the past. Those who can do so will find new possibilities to change their and their communities' present circumstances.

Yet still, returning to the problem of overcoming Eurocentrism and its metaphysics, one could argue that we are merely replacing one frame for another, which is exactly what Serequeberhan critiques Hountondji and other professional philosophers of doing. However, the key is that a lived existence arises from the self-awareness of one's concrete reality (existence), the history which shaped it (heritage), and how one must press this in service toward a more emancipated future. Put this way; a lived existence opens new horizons, new possibilities, and new engagements with others. It opens new means of critical self-reflection and new pathways toward shaping a more emancipated culture.

It may be impossible not to fall into a *Ge-stell*, or to think outside of some organizing, epistemic principle (which, at its core, is a metaphysics). However, *knowing this*, and exploring the historicity through and by which we know this, gives us the possibility of choosing which organizing principle is the most liberating. In the future, new horizons may open with new principles chosen.

The imperative is who decides, and if one can decide for themselves. That is the emancipation: not from all organizing principles and their framing of knowledge, but from the

denial of choosing one's own path alongside their communities through which they historically share a heritage. It bears repeating again that, for Serequeberhan, this is his dream for African philosophy:

What we take out and leave behind is thus sifted by a lived and constantly augmented heritage – instantiated in our 'effective-historical consciousness' – focused on the reciprocal enhancing of our shared existence. Thus, being open to the possible, in the actuality of the present, we solicit and call forth a new and shared world. ¶ In this, as in the past, we will invent. But this time around tempered by the surpassed pitfalls of what we have come to see as dead ends (Senghor's *Africanité*, for example) and focused on solidarities – nurtured by mutual concerns – which have overcome the delusion of thinking that they possess, or that it is possible to possess, a foolproof system, *metaphysics*, to guard against the risks of inventing. This, then, is the treasured intellectual-political inheritance of humanity.⁴⁴ (Emphasis Serequeberhan's)

The pathway forward for a philosophy – African or otherwise – is thus not to ignore the racist sections of, say, Hegel or Heidegger, nor the intellectual misfires as he sees in *Africanité* or *Négritude*, but to directly confront them. For *all philosophers*, not just Africans, a lived existence that engages these historical problematics recognizes what has been denied to them: the more just, more open, and more honest regions of truth that these epistemic closures hid under such provisos as the *mission civilatrice*.

Through this, they also rediscover what has been given to them, albeit under the cover of darkness. Uncovering and/or rediscovering these regions is a revelation of pasts heretofore unknown to such a lived existence: stories of persons and communities – and their cultures and heritages – that reawaken new ideas, new appreciations, and new horizons through which they may engage the world.

4. A Concluding Case Study: Frantz Fanon's Lived Existence

Ultimately, this chapter explored three important things: First, one cannot merely disinherit oneself from one's own and one's culture's past; one cannot overcome history (or Eurocentrism) but they can critically deconstruct and uncover what it hides; what has been denied or concealed (or colonized) from oneself, particularly African(a) persons. Second, it shows how this operates from within and not from on high, or *sub specie aeterni*: one must

⁴⁴ *EH*, pp. 118-119.

come to these self-realizations on their own, otherwise, they are merely and inauthentically replacing one ensnarement for another. Finally, it further emphasizes that, for Serequeberhan, all philosophy at its core is hermeneutical, and all hermeneutics are inherently activist: just as one cannot overcome Eurocentrism's ensnarement from on high, one cannot interpret from on high either. Thus, whether one realizes it or not, they are actuating either a resistance to or a reinforcement of the concrete, lived reality whence they contemplate.

Pulling back and looking at my larger project, this chapter will set our future discussion concerning Bergsonian 'orthogenesis' (a creative evolution) and the notion that humanity holds within it an inventive, vital force, which Bergson calls the '*elan vital*'. The upshot of this eventual discussion between the two is realizing how temporality and becoming are creative events narrativized within one's history. It does not come from outside but within ourselves – both personally and communally – in relation to the physical-temporal space in which we exist. Consequently, we find a sight of activism or, to paraphrase Serequeberhan, a place for a lived existence that challenges and changes the dominating, ensnaring forces that shape our understanding of the world around us. We do this through a self-realization of one's place within history alongside one's existence and the co-creative relationship between self, community, and their world(s).

Returning to this chapter, I detailed Serequeberhan's notion of historical, hermeneutical awareness through engaging his shaping of Gadamerian concepts in pursuit of his own philosophy. Along with his unique appropriation of Heidegger, what emerges from this shaping is his tandem notions of existence and heritage, and how they are held in hermeneutic tension so as to clear a space for a lived existence to form from within oneself. The first section detailed this tension and why it is hermeneutically necessary.

The second section delved further by exploring the ways Serequeberhan appropriates Heidegger's critique of technology and his notion of *Ge-stell*. Through this appropriation, Serequeberhan articulates the ways in which our intellectual debates (African or otherwise) are always already en-framed within a Eurocentric model. Finally, I argued that Serequeberhan's hermeneutics critically engages this en-frament, risking that such an engagement would allow a lived existence to fully arise from within oneself, which

consequently emancipates said lived existence and, hopefully, is pressed into the service of emancipating others.

Yet still, we must recall that Serequeberhan's hermeneutics is activist and inherently prescriptive, which runs contrary to most Western hermeneutic models and is inherently descriptive. Consequently, this means that there needs to be a practical or pragmatic element to Serequeberhan's over-arching project. I cannot think of a better way to highlight this pragmatism than through his reading and use of Fanon: it at once gives a clear example of a lived existence for Serequeberhan (thus bringing together all the ideas discussed above) while also providing a model for others to follow. Therefore, I will close with a very brief look at how 'Serequeberhan's Fanon' embodies a lived existence.

Interestingly, Serequeberhan rarely, if ever, directly engages Fanon's existentialism through phenomenology.⁴⁵ Obviously, Serequeberhan knows and mentions these aspects, and the final chapters of *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy* detail the diagnostics given to us through Fanon, along with Marcién Towa and Amícal Cabral.⁴⁶ Notably, though, Serequeberhan continually stresses Fanon's critique while distancing it from any Sartrean influence or any other phenomenological inquiry.⁴⁷ To me, this furthers the notion that Serequeberhan is giving a hermeneutic reading of Fanon and his work – same as he did to Heidegger and Gadamer – and that Serequeberhan is more interested in Fanon as a 'lived existence who decolonizes' than Fanon as 'existential phenomenologist who conceptualizes decolonization.'

Serequeberhan employs Fanon's diagnostics but also highlights throughout his work that Fanon exemplifies a lived existence that knows itself and that this self-knowledge has been framed/shaped/molded through its historicity. Thus, it is not about the methods Fanon uses

⁴⁵ See, for example, *HAP*, pp. 6-9.

⁴⁶ Time and space prevents me from going too in-depth on Cabral and Towa's influence, here, but it is well worth noting for future research. See: *HAP*, pp. 105-110, 112, 118 for more on Cabral's influence. For Marcién Towa, note that Serequeberhan's Introduction to *HAP* employs Marcién Towa's critical examination of the current state of African philosophy during his time (p. 7) and Serequeberhan also ends his final chapter, "The Liberation Struggle," with a reflection upon Towa's overview of African philosophy's true commitments (p. 114). See also: *CM*, where Towa plays a major diagnostic-hermeneutic role in assessing Eurocentrism's effects on African philosophy (pp. 2, 16-17, and note that on Chapter 3, "The Idea as Colonizer," begins with an epigraph from Towa (p. 63). Again, Serequeberhan remains rather consistent in his appropriation of sources; see also: *OH*, p. 2.

⁴⁷ For example, see: *OH*, pp. 19-20.

when engaging postcolonialism; it is about how, from within himself, he comes to fully realize his own existence and heritage. This can be seen in Serequeberhan's presentation of heritage as an ongoing question (and opportunity) in the opening chapter of *Our Heritage*, entitled "Heritage and Its Transmission, A Reading of Frantz Fanon:"

...this lost possibility – defeated through and in victory – that defines postcolonial Africa is the ground from which arises the anguished question of heritage. Towa points out, in synchrony with Fanon, this '*zone de non être*:' "The anguished conscience of our identity is in reality the consciousness of the lost of identity under the dissolving action of external forces which we have not succeeded in controlling." Thus, to properly respond to Fanon's call is to overcome the ground of this malaise – in effect, to reclaim and solidate that fleeting moment in modern African history, when the enigma of our heritage was momentarily dissolved, to reclaim and anew consolidate that moment in modern African history – defeated in and through victory – which makes us worthy of questioning the question of our heritage. *This is what Fanon calls us to.*⁴⁸ (Emphasis mine)

He continues from this to lay out how Fanon's self-reflection upon him being "an 'ex-native'" and its resulting effects on his own personhood shows that he wrote "from the lived horizon of the African liberation struggle."⁴⁹ Furthering his point, he notes how Fanon calls out directly to all 'ex-natives,' *as well as to their former colonizers and those who even today indirectly benefit from this colonization*. He calls upon them to refuse to accept this history as arbitrarily unchangeable. Serequeberhan notes that, in choosing to refute this historical imperialization and to confront this heritage, one begins to emancipate oneself from its ensnaring and all-encompassing constriction of possibilities, its "constricting horizon."⁵⁰ As he summarizes: "in this choice he or she becomes open to the 'effects' of a different 'effective-history.' In refusing, such a person negates – for whatever reason – his or her self-understanding, *within the colonial horizon*, in terms of which he or she had lived life up to that point."⁵¹

⁴⁸ *OH*, p. 8. He is quoting from: Marcien Towa, "Propositions sur l'identité culturelle," *Presence Africaine* 109 (1st

Quarter, 1979), p. 83.

⁴⁹ *OH*, p. 9. He is quoting from: Frantz Fanon, *The Wretched of the Earth*, Constance Farrington, trans. (New York: Grove Press, 1963), p. 106.

⁵⁰ *OH*, p. 10.

⁵¹ *OH*, p. 10. He is referencing Hans-Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, (New York: Crossroad Publishing Co.,

Note what is going on in this reading of Fanon: through Fanon's work – primarily *Wretched of the Earth*, but also his articles (Serequeberhan rarely quotes from *Black Skin, White Masks*) – Serequeberhan is employing Fanon's autoethnographic style and approach to decolonization to emphasize its historicity and how it compliments Gadamer's 'effective-historical consciousness.' He does something similar in *Existence and Heritage*, wherein the last chapter, simply entitled "Frantz Fanon: Thinking as Openness," Serequeberhan brings the two together. After a brief discourse on Gadamer's notion that historicity opens us to "*the truth that we are*" – meaning both that we exist and who we are – Serequeberhan states: "For, indeed, the formerly subjugated – and not historically and culturally hybridized – have become interlocutors who have to be taken seriously in mutual dialogical interaction" with the West.⁵² In the very next sentence and paragraph, he continues: "it is in this context that Fanon, in concluding *Les damnés de la terre*, calls us to invention."⁵³

Although *The Hermeneutics of African Philosophy's* final chapters explore Fanon's thoughts on revolution and violence, Serequeberhan's later work continually stresses the call coming from within Fanon's life and thought and how that call emanates from a demand for justice and emancipation from Western domination.⁵⁴ As he sees it, "Fanon calls from *within a lived fracture, an open wound*; his call ... does not rest on given and established normative structures. *His call originates from a lived experience of fracture, a concrete absence, a 'gap between actuality and ideality.'*"⁵⁵ As mentioned above, the self-realization of this absence and how it reflects upon one's personhood (or selfhood, *Dasein* even) and the effective-historical situation whence crafted that selfhood is the pathway toward a lived existence.

In closing, what we can gather from Serequeberhan's reading of Fanon is that 'his Fanon,' if you will, embodies what it means to be a lived existence and to hold oneself in hermeneutic tension between the concrete reality of their existence and the heritage that one inherits. This heritage, whether one wants it or not, must be confronted through this concrete reality.

1982), pp. 264-266 and then cross-referencing that with Frantz Fanon, *Dying Colonialism* (New York: Monthly Review Press), Appendixes 1 and 2, the testimonials of C. Geromini and B. Yvon, and Fanon's reading of 'truth' on p. 87. See footnote 62 of *OH*, p. 81.

⁵² *EH*, p. 118. He is quoting from Hans-Georg Gadamer, "The Universality of the Hermeneutical Problem," in *Philosophical Hermeneutics*, David Linge, ed. and trans. (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1976), p. 16, emphasis Serequeberhan's. Note that this is a reprisal, or theme, which runs throughout the book.

⁵³ *EH*, p. 118

⁵⁴ *HAP*, pp. 72-78; *OH*, pp. 7.

⁵⁵ *OH*, p. 8, emphasis mine. Here, he quotes himself from *HAP*, p. 9.

Though Fanon's wound may never have healed, and others may not ever as well, Fanon's wound is a calling out to others to recognize the destruction that caused these wounds. In so doing, one confronts one's heritage – both its positives and negatives – and risks that this confrontation may open oneself to new horizons of possibilities. Horizons are seen through a lived existence that authentically knows itself.

These possibilities, these new horizons, may never heal past wounds, but they may prevent future ones. They may reopen oneself to a future-past whereby new vantage points, new horizons, arise from that past. They may disclose horizons or regions of truth heretofore disclosed. If the risk toward openness – toward the Other, toward one's past, toward one's cultural past, toward the history presently being written – pays off, then Serequeberhan's dream for African philosophy (and all of philosophy) may just be set in motion. It is a risk worth taking.

CHAPTER EIGHT:
SURVIVAL IS A CREATIVE ACT:
BERGSON'S *ELAN VITAL* WITHIN EVOLUTION AND SOCIETY

1. Introduction

As mentioned before, Bergson's ultimate concern is the creative mobility of life. His first major works, *Time and Free Will* and *Matter and Memory*, sought to undo the ways in which analysis and its metaphorical-spatial categorization overwrote the issues in question. Whether it was determinism, monism, or their counterparts, Bergson's critique essentially argues that each side was debating the wrong thing: rather than picking the right categories and/or correct rational frameworks to understand their issues, all sides should have been looking at the mobility of life and how our perceptions of it seek an understanding from our own experiences. From this critique, he arrives at the concept of *duration* as a means through which we sense the mobility (i.e., temporality) of life, how we create through this mobility (i.e., qualitative multiplicity), and how this informs our understanding (i.e., empiricism). Concerning this last point, through his exploration, he develops his method of intuition, which, in tandem with analysis, allows us to sense the flow and qualitative multiplicity of life as we perceive, remember, and comprehend it.

His later writings press further: how does the vivacity of life expand and thrive in worlds hostile to it? This led to what many call his masterwork, *Creative Evolution*, which was extremely well received, with some even hailing Bergson as a genius, especially William James.¹ Its genius, if one accepts the praise, is that it widens the scope of Bergson's philosophical insights by articulating the durative, creative survival and adaptation of life from the point of view of one's consciousness, instinct, and intellect. Out of this, *Creative Evolution*

¹ See: *CE*, p. x; William James, "Bergson and His Critique of Intellectualism," in *A Pluralistic Universe* (New York: Longmans, Green and Company, 1909), pp. 223-73.

sought to explain how the qualitative multiplicities of life are ever ongoing and not a production of mere perception. Rather, it is a matter of life adapting and changing in order to exist: life's survival is a creative act.

Unfortunately, due to several reasons, Bergson's *Two Sources of Morality and Religion* had a different reception. As Alexandre Lefebvre notes, "the debate and controversy that surrounded its immediate reception were characterized by misunderstanding and polemic. On top of that, the book was soon afterward nearly forgotten."² Interestingly, throughout my research, I have found that many scholars either focus on *Time and Free Will* and *Matter and Memory*, or on *Creative Evolution*, *Two Sources*, and ancillary essays such as those within *Mind-Energy*. Yes, there are some nods to all the books from one camp to the other, but the focal points are nearly always the same: the first group seeks to explore *duration* and intuition from within a phenomenological or metaphysical range, and the second group seeks to explore Bergson's *elan vital* and his political philosophy. However, both acknowledge a linkage between the works – albeit some stronger than others – such as Bergson maintaining his empirical approach and notions of intuition and *duration*.³ So, it is really a matter of interest in what each scholar seeks within Bergson, given the array of subjects which his work touches.

For our purposes, this chapter's aim is to explore *Creative Evolution* and then *Two Sources* to gather an ecological understanding of the mobility of all life in all its interconnectivity and its moral implications. This interconnectivity is manifold in that I am not speaking merely of a shared ecosystem, but a shared impulse to live which is expressed through evolutionary acts such as adaptation, environmental modification, or the expansion of an organism's capabilities.⁴ In showing this, I will illustrate how Bergson holds all of these possibilities through his notion of the *elan vital* and how he employs it to describe the drive for survival and the creative means through which organisms succeed in their survival.⁵ Then, through a

² Alexandre Lefebvre, *Human Rights as a Way of Life: On Bergson's Political Philosophy* (Stanford: Stanford UP, 2013), p. xiii.

³ Idella J. Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution: The Moral Philosophy of Henri Bergson* (Dordrecht: Springer Science & Business Media, 1970) p. 15.

⁴ Alexandre Lefebvre, Melanie White, "Introduction: Bergson, Politics, and Religion," in *Bergson, Politics, and Religion*, Alexandre Lefebvre and Melanie White, eds. (Durham: Duke UP, 2012), p. 7; *CE*, p. xi.

⁵ Note that some authors use the original spelling, *élan vital*, and others translate it to vital impulse. Unless I directly quote an author, I will use *elan vital* for simplicity.

reading of *Two Sources*, I will show how this *elan vital* is the undercurrent within Bergson's political philosophy, especially within his argument for an open society.

To accomplish this task, I will have to give a very focused and selective reading of *Creative Evolution* and *Two Sources*. This means that I cannot cover Bergson's continued critique of Kantianism nor an expansive reading of his critique against Durkheim. Furthermore, to streamline my argument, I have decided to focus solely on these texts and touch upon *Mind-Energy* and other works only where necessary. Thus, this will not be a *reportage* of the *elan vital*, but an argumentative engagement with its ecological and moral implications.

Therefore, in what follows, I will lay some groundwork by describing the connection between *duration* and the *elan vital* as concepts that describe and express our sense of life. In these next two sections, which will be based on *Creative Evolution*, I will show that they are comprehensive operations for sensing the qualitative modality of life. This will allow us to revisit the concept of lived existence (and its adequation to Bergson's mystic/hero) in the following chapter. Recall that the ensuing conversation between Bergson and Serequeberhan will be about the concept of place; this section will foreshadow this by establishing an ecological understanding of life's energy – its '*vital*' – and the creative means of expressing that energy through its survival – its '*elan*'. This expression, as I will detail below and in the following chapter, is both an evolutionary and moral act.

In the penultimate section, I will examine Bergson's understanding of the intellect, particularly within humanity. This will be the relationship that brings *Creative Evolution* and *Two Sources* together since the latter speaks of an open society and the need for its openness so that the human intellect can thrive or, in Wiredu's parlance, further its *intellectual* evolution. This, I find, emphasizes how humanity's continuation is itself a moral and political act since what society chooses to do – whether opening or closing itself from others and/or the world – has consequences for its own living continuation.⁶ Although Wiredu may not have foreseen this, I will argue that this intellectual evolution begins with Bergsonian instinct, through which he argues we gather our sympathy. By being open to sympathetic relations

⁶ *CE*, p. ix.

with others, we not only find ourselves in a more peaceful society, but we will eventually evolve as a species to be more in tune with our environment through sensing *duration*.

I will further examine the moral and political philosophical implications of these findings in my final analysis of open societies and their relationship to Bergson's ecology. It holds an evolutionary component, similar to Wiredu's impetus, where we need to develop society for the intellectual evolution of our species. Bergson would agree, here, and I argue that his notion of *elan vital* supplies us with the recognition that this is not a mere anthropocentric evolution; it is communal with a much wider horizon. It compels us to see how our acts influence our environment and it teases out the morality underlying the creativity of life's survival in given spaces. Thus, this chapter will advance the argument that we experience a living history extended throughout our environment; the memorial, sedimented layering of history onto space is an ecological event whereby we create a sense of place for ourselves and our communities.

2. From Duration to Elan Vital: Bergson's Reframing of Evolution

Similar to his prior works, Bergson begins with an ongoing debate and he proclaims that both sides have missed the entire point in question. Here, Bergson's focus is on the so-called finalists and mechanists and how each falls into the trap of mistaking *the organization and analysis of evolution as evolution itself rather than seeing evolution as an unpredictably creative, ecological event*.⁷ Concerning finalism, Idella Gallagher summarizes that it "signifies the working out of a program already planned or the realization of an idea conceived in advance."⁸ Similarly, mechanists view each change through a hierarchal lens, as if an organism's evolution of having eyes was a technical achievement rather than one for survival.⁹

The problem with these rationalities is that they either causally explain evolution or describe it as having a predetermined, teleological course. They are reasoning *backwardly*, similar to the determinists and liberationists who sought to articulate human will by what has happened, not how happenings are a successive flow of experience. Concerning evolution,

⁷ CE, pp. 36-40.

⁸ Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, p. 40.

⁹ CE, pp. 41-43.

Bergson argues that neither side is truly open to its creative movement of energy given that their causal and positivist teleological rationality ‘reasons away’ the actual life of the organism in question and looks at it only through the lens of sterile organization.¹⁰ It is as if intellect alone can *define* and *articulate* evolution rather than the organism that is actually undertaking an always-evolving moment of life.

Conversely, Bergson argues that if one views evolution and creation through the lens of *duration*, then our understanding of life moves beyond our attempt to organize it and allows us to see the creative mobility through which we engage the world:

But *duration* is something different from [radical mechanism] for our consciousness, that is to say, for that which is most indisputable in our experience. We perceive *duration* as a stream against which we cannot go. It is the foundation of our being and, as we feel, the very substance of the world in which we live. It is of no use to hold up before our eyes the dazzling prospect of a universal mathematic; we cannot sacrifice experience to the requirements of a system. That is why we reject radical mechanism.¹¹

Importantly, evolution is not *duration*, it is merely through *duration* that one finds oneself intuiting the vitality of the world. Nor is life’s creative survival evolution *per se*; yet Bergson calls this survival evolution so that we can empirically understand these creative movements.¹² Again, we need to intertwine our analysis of these experiences with intuition. Sure, we need to understand and analytically sort our experiences to move throughout the world, but it is through intuition that we hold a possibility of sensing these movements as more than utilities. As such, Bergson asserts that “in vain ... does life evolve before our eyes as a continuous creation of unforeseeable form: the idea always persists that form, foreseeability and continuity are mere appearance – the outward reflection of our own ignorance.”¹³ Appearance (and, to a degree, ignorance) speaks to how we analytically rationalize creation, breaking up its continuity to organize and systematize creation so that it is comprehensible to us.

This, again, is similar to Bergson’s critique of segmenting time and events to gather a mere representation of reality when what we should do is pull further back and sense the creative

¹⁰ Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, pp. 40-42.

¹¹ *CE*, p. 45.

¹² *CE*, pp. 33-35.

¹³ *CE*, p. 35

flow of these events. Here, one can sense the underlying notion of how *duration* becomes a pathway to understanding the creative, qualitative multiplicity of life. “Real *duration*,” Bergson states, “is that *duration* which gnaws on things and leaves on them the mark of its tooth.”¹⁴ Continuing, he notes that “we do not *think* real-time. But we *live it* because it transcends intellect. The feeling we have of our evolution and of the evolution of all things in pure *duration* is there, *forming around the intellectual concept properly so called an indistinct fringe that fades off into darkness.*”¹⁵

We will revisit Bergson’s concept of intellect in the next section. For now, notice how fundamental this ‘indistinct fringe’ and ‘fading of *duration*’ is since one must remember that thinking comes too easily for us. That is why intuition, and accordingly *duration*, requires the deep introspection Lawler spoke about within Bergson’s earlier work.¹⁶ Consequently, if one were to ask Bergson, ‘Why examine evolution?’ I imagine his reply would be to illuminate what too easily fades away, to elucidate the *duration* which is within all of life. In order to do so, he must examine what life is and how life carries forth throughout the universe in its abundant, myriads of ways. This is the point of *Creative Evolution* and is why he structures the work throughout its *duration*. It is also why we must revisit *duration* to gather a sense of the *elan vital*.

Using mechanism and finalism as our foils, neither see movement beyond its causality or calculative procedures. They are trying to organize evolution rather than truly seeking comprehension of what is going on through what we call evolution. One cannot think of evolution as merely a scientific concept; one must see that these creative events are always ongoing. Therefore, the concept of evolution is simply there to help us empirically grasp this event’s becoming. If we only focus on analyzing the concept, we reify and neuter our experience of and participation within evolution. Clarifying his argument further, he summarizes:

Just as we separate in space, we fix in time. The intellect is not made to think *evolution*, in the proper sense of the word – that is to say, the continuity of a change that is pure mobility. ... Suffice it to say that the intellect represents *becoming* as a series of states, each of which is homogeneous with itself and consequently does not change. Is our

¹⁴ *CE*, p. 52.

¹⁵ *CE*, p. 53, emphasis mine.

¹⁶ Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, p. 62.

attention called to the internal change of one of these states? At once we decompose it into another series of states which, reunited, will be supposed to make up this internal modification. Each of these new states must be invariable, or else their internal change, if we are forced to notice it, must be resolved again into a fresh series of invariable states, and so on into infinity. Here again, thinking consists in reconstituting, and, naturally, it is with given elements, and consequently with *stable* elements, that we reconstitute. So that, though we may do our best to imitate the mobility of becoming by an addition that is ever going on, becoming itself slips through our fingers just when we think we are holding it tight.¹⁷

We will revisit the notion of the intellect's role in evolution in the next section. For now, one can see Bergson's expansive account of life and why he structures the work to first dispel problematic explanations of life and evolution, and then he works toward understanding the vitalism of life.¹⁸ Our intellect, to put it succinctly, *is a participation within evolution*; it helps us notice change and the flow of adaptation within life. However, we fail to see the vitalism as always ongoing once we fixate our intellect onto stable concepts. Here again, the metaphor overtakes the event: by only employing rational analysis and thus segmenting and breaking apart change and adaptation of life into stable concepts (i.e., elements), we are able to make evolution intelligible for us. However, in so doing, we render out the vitalism or energetic flow of/within evolution.¹⁹

Importantly, Bergson employs the term vitalism much differently than his peers who, according to James Difrisko, used it as a distinction between "life and matter at the level of substance, such that life bears a different substratum than nonliving matter, or that it is the seat of different kinds of forces and different laws."²⁰ In other words, the vitalism used by his peers becomes too abstract, too psychologistic, and fashions a faulty metaphysics rather than an empirical analysis of life and the world. Although Bergson does hold a distinction between life and matter, it is not a reductionist metaphysics between organism and inert material, nor is it a dualistic interpretation of how life comes from matter. As Difrisko clarifies:

"[This] dualism is just one moment of the method, which is followed by a moment where the terms of the dualism are shown to be two sides of a more primary term [i.e.,

¹⁷ *CE*, pp. 179-180, emphasis Bergson's.

¹⁸ *CE*, pp. 48-49.

¹⁹ See: Chapter Five, pp. 100-101, 110, 117, where I point out this is the same issue Bergson has with spatialized metaphors of temporality.

²⁰ James Difrisko, "Elan Vital Revisited: Bergson and the Thermodynamic Paradigm," *The Southern Journal of Philosophy* (53:1, 2015), p. 56.

elan vital]. ... Bergson is led to reconfigure the distinction between matter and life in nonsubstantialist terms, such that they do not get distinguished as different types of things, with the *elan vital* representing a special type of ‘vital force.’”²¹

In summary, the vitalism articulated by Bergson is an initial distinction between life and inorganic matter and is employed so that we can recognize each’s interconnection beyond category. Although Bergson will initially accept the differences in kind between life and inert matter rather than a difference in degree, he does this so that he can eventually show that each, in their own way, possesses stored energy or vitality.²² For Difrisko, amongst others, this is why Bergson’s *elan vital* offers a thermodynamic account of life where energy – either sought by the organism or stored by matter – is a relational event between accruing energy or dissipating energy.²³

This often moves Bergson closer to scientific discussions concerning the second law of thermodynamics and related issues within physics, but for us, it is an access point to understanding the *elan vital*, or vital impulse, as it is often translated.²⁴ Bergson is essentially describing the relationality between living and inorganic matter: both hold energy and, throughout the universe, they either seek it to live – such as plants who gather resources through the soil and sun – or their energy is dissipated and transferred through others – such as animals eating said plants.²⁵

²¹ Difrisko, “*Elan Vital Revisited*,” p. 56.

²² Bergson touches upon this in the final chapter, see: *CE*, pp. 288-293.

For an example of matter’s stored energy, consider how nutrients – which are inert matter – are necessary for life’s survival; we may not eat minerals, but our food does, it is through plants (for example) that these nutrients allow the plant to gather its energy alongside photosynthesis. We then eat the plant for its energy. We then die, and fall into the soil to decompose, we deposit new nutrients along the way, which plants will invariably use to continue the cycle.

²³ Difrisko, “*Elan Vital Revisited*,” p. 67. See also: *CE*, pp. 13-15, 221-228, 235-237, 257-258.

²⁴ Difrisko, “*Elan Vital Revisited*” is an excellent resource to review these ongoing discussions. For our purposes, it is beyond our scope to go into Bergson’s emerging role in the philosophy of science, but it is worth exploring in future research.

²⁵ *CE*, p. 57-58, 126-128.

Note that Bergsonian vitalism is different than the ‘vital force’ as understood within African Traditional Thought, and importantly as it is translated into other languages. As Bruce Janz points out, Placide Tempels was influenced by Bergson and, in *Bantu Philosophy*, one can see how Tempels translates certain, more spiritual meanings of living force into vitalism’s various synonymous iterations. See: Bruce Janz, *African Philosophy and Enactivist Cognition* (London: Bloomsbury, 2022), pp. 46-62. Janz’ articulation of vitalism within this chapter is especially interesting when comparing it to Bergson’s original intent with the term. Unfortunately, due to our focus and scope, we cannot engage Janz here, but it is well worth future exploration.

Bergson argues in his first two chapters that, rather than discussing the organization of evolved matter, we should be focusing on the *raison d'être* for evolution: how organisms acquire energy for living.²⁶ As Difrisko and others point out, Bergson's vital impulse is a description of the force by which living things *seek to live*; they have the desiring impulse (*elan*) to live (*vital*). To merely describe it as a dualistic structure ignores how these movements relate to one another through the carrying, dissemination, and reception of energy necessary for life.

I argue that this account is an ecological description of becoming: it literally begins with why life happens and how life seeks growth to carry on living. Evolution is the adaptive process through which life endures; each development or adaptation (which we call an evolutionary event) is one that is necessary for survival.²⁷ Contrary to a finalist or mechanist position, Bergson's *elan vital* describes the relational logic between the desire for survival and the need for adaptation in the pursuit of survival. In a word, this adaptation has a singular purpose: energy. It is either in accruing or maintaining the energy that drives the impulse for survival. Interestingly, the translation of *elan vital* into 'vital impulse' offers a clarification here: whether translated as a vital impulse – which follows a more energetic description (i.e., vitalism) – or expressed in the original French as an *elan vital* – which emphasizes the creativity in this act of survival (i.e., *elan*) – what Bergson is describing is the relational, energetic movement between inert matter and living entities.²⁸

We, therefore, can see the connections between Bergson's earlier and later works beyond empiricism and terminology: the energetic mobility and vitalist flow of life, which we sense through our own duration, is the same flow which carries throughout all life and all becoming. Although it requires both our analysis and intuition to understand this mobility, when we do,

²⁶ *CE*, pp. 263-267, 277.

²⁷ Throughout Chapter Two of *CE*, Bergson illustrates this through the development of the eye. The organization of the eye, in all species, is a remarkable event in its complexity, but why have eyes in the first place? He argues (see: *CE*, pp. 106-108) that it became necessary and, although we can analyze and compare eyes across organisms, each organism came to developing eyes through their own process of survival; in short, it was a necessary act, and each development is an individuated, creative expression of that organism's development. As a creative expression (*CE*, p. 107), no development of the eye was predetermined, as if (à la finalism) eyes are part of a 'developmental tree' through which life can be hierarchically categorized. Sure, we can rank and file organisms, but their 'ranking' is of our own analysis and not their own. Also, some organisms fail to develop, which was not a predetermined event, and finalism would present this failure some sort of destiny or predetermination.

²⁸ *CE*, pp. 97-102, 108.

we can sense an interconnectivity of becoming: an ecological embeddedness of our *duration* and that of all other things.

Concerning living organisms, that *duration* is embodied in our living environment; concerning inert matter, that *duration* is expressed in our need for matter and its ability to produce and disperse its energy. The key is that one cannot live life alone: one participates within an environment through which energy is carried from one entity to another. Widening our aperture, this argument points out that the environment is not merely a situatedness of where we find ourselves; it is a living, ecological habitat, and we humans play our own small roles in its directional flow and change.

Although early Bergson describes *duration* through consciousness – and especially focusing on an individual’s consciousness – one can see that, in his later works, he is trying to avoid both an individualistic and an anthropocentric metaphysics or cosmology. Yes, his requirements for deep introspection to sense *duration* have a Cartesian-like inwardness, but its relational logic extends beyond one’s mental operations of intuition and analysis. It is a description of how humans can sense their relationship *with becoming tout court*, not merely their own becoming but that of everything that surrounds them, including inert matter, which contains stored energy. This sensation of *duration* can be co-effective or co-generative, or it can be one’s own self-realization of the becoming already happening around/within them.

However, for this ecological event of becoming to happen in the first place, the environment needs to be open to life. Not every species survives, not every adaptation is successful, and some environments are simply closed off to life.²⁹ In short, there needs to be an openness for this vitality to express its creative mobility. In our next section, I will further elaborate on this by emphasizing Bergson’s account of consciousness and the birth of instinct and intellect. From this, we can better grasp the need for an openness within the environment for life to develop, and in Section Four, I will show how this relates to morality and the intellectual evolution of humanity.

3. *Elan* as the Will to Live: Understanding’s Evolution and Its Intellectual Implications

²⁹ *CE*, pp. 116- 117, 142-148.

The difficulty with Bergson is that his works rarely have a linear path. For example, one can see his use of intuition within *Time and Free Will*, but it is only within *Introduction to Metaphysics* – written after *Time and Free Will* and *Matter and Memory* – where he describes the mechanics and necessity of intuition as a method. Similarly, although Bergson often speaks of consciousness sensing *duration*, it is only until *Creative Evolution* that he articulates how consciousness comes into being. This means that Bergson cannot be read linearly but rather as if he is in conversation with himself. Remarkably, I find that this runs similar to *duration* in that it requires a constant revisitation of what has been read with what one is currently reading to fully gather a sense of Bergson’s philosophy. If I can be somewhat daft about the matter, I feel like I am *living with Bergson* while writing about him!

To my mind, this digression is one of the best ways to grasp Bergson’s articulation of consciousness, instinct, and intellect: for living organisms who possess all three, there is no linear progression but rather an ongoing interplay between them all as an organism engages/perceives their environment. Although Bergson places humanity at the top of the hierarchy of life, which may be anthropocentrically problematic for some, in *Two Sources*, he seeks a further evolution of humanity.³⁰ Similar to Wiredu’s concept of intellectual evolution, Bergson’s concept of *human* evolution is aligned to morality and furthers our understanding and relationship to each other and the world(s) we share.³¹

We will further explore the moral implications of these interactions later. For now, to describe this interplay between an organism’s faculties, I will begin with Bergson’s fundamental rank for life: consciousness. Bergson describes consciousness as:

...the name for the rocket whose extinguished fragments fall back as matter; consciousness, again, is the name for that which subsists of the rocket itself, passing through the fragments and lighting them up into organisms. But this consciousness, which is a *need of creation*, is made manifest to itself only where creation is possible. It lies dormant when life is condemned to automatism [i.e., in operative, unable to happen]; it awakens as soon as the possibility of a choice is restored.³² (Emphasis Bergson’s)

³⁰ See: Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, “The Goal of Evolution,” pp. 52-56.

³¹ See: Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, “The Evolution of Morality,” pp. 88-91.

³² *CE*, pp. 282-283.

Returning to Difrisco's thermodynamic model and his astute differentiation between life and inert material, this quote demonstrates the interchange between inert matter and the birth of the organism. Consciousness is the initial drive of life which is produced out of matter. As the 'need of creation,' consciousness is the awakening of life. Here, one can read 'need' and 'impulse' synonymously, as if life begs to become. Finally, and to the heart of life, whatever is created needs to be able to choose or, in other words, have some autonomy over its existence. This is the primary distinction between the inert and the living: the consciousness of choice.³³

Critically, what we may think of choice is not Bergson's description. We may think of humans choosing to have oatmeal or cereal for breakfast – something like free will – but, for Bergson, the entire *mobility of life requires choice*. When a plant repositions itself for more direct sunlight, has it not made a choice, or did some invisible hand do it? When an amoeba changes its shape in reaction to its environment, has it not done so on its own?³⁴ For Bergson, the capability to choose to act is foundational for life and for how it expands or evolves; it is an initial step but a critical one. As Bergson states, "consciousness corresponds exactly to the living being's power of choice ... [it] is synonymous with invention and freedom."³⁵

This requires us to reframe our notion of consciousness: whereas 'we' see it in ourselves as a psychological faculty, Bergson argues that all living creatures possess it.³⁶ This deepens the ecological aspect of Bergson's philosophy in that it compels us to recognize that aspects of our mental capacity are shared across the spectrum of life; everything that possesses consciousness possesses the creative need to live, *which they express through their will*.³⁷ As Bergson states:

When we put back our being into our will, and our will itself into the impulsion it prolongs, we understand, we feel that reality is a perpetual growth, a creation pursued without end. Our will already performs this miracle. Every Human work in which there is invention, every voluntary act in which there is freedom, every movement of an organism that manifests spontaneity, brings something new into the world.³⁸

³³ CE, p. 288.

³⁴ CE, pp. 38-42. Note that Bergson uses the amoeba as an illustration of faulty notions of evolution.

³⁵ CE, p. 287.

³⁶ See Bergson's critique of ordering creation: CE, pp. 236-240.

³⁷ CE, p. 245.

³⁸ CE, p. 261.

The manifestation of will (and the choice of what to will) is consciousness. Importantly, Bergson does not proceed with, say, higher planes of consciousness where some organisms are 'smarter' than others because they have an elevated consciousness. Rather, he moves on to describe how instinct is derived through consciousness as a necessary innovation that manifests itself through this impulse to live, this *elan vital* which is within all conscious entities.³⁹ It is necessary precisely to allow the organism to survive by adapting to its environment. Again, survival is a creative act, and instinct is an innovation to propel survival.

At the risk of oversimplification, but to get further to my point, instincts develop similarly to an organism's physical development. Instinct is built from the need for adaptation, but what makes it distinct for a particular organism is that it is the product of accrued habitual knowledge, which is then shared and developed through ancestry.⁴⁰ Instinct, thus, is a development from consciousness or, more precisely, an extension of consciousness' expression to live.⁴¹ Yet there is not a clean separation between instinct and consciousness: one does not move up and down from consciousness to instinct; there is a covalency at play where the conscious will to act is further expressed in the instinctive actions of an organism.⁴² As such, it is not a matter of jumping from one plane to another – leveling up from consciousness to instinct – it is a co-generated spectrum of engaging the world and adapting to that world.⁴³

Moreover, instinct and its development are a response to one's environment. At first blush, this can be seen as a mere biological description, yet Bergson pushes further. One of the key issues Bergson critiques throughout *Creative Evolution* is how positivist science and other rationalities define the characteristics of intelligence. He is arguing that these categories are not so neatly separated, nor are they as individuated as we think. An essential result of this argument is that organisms develop sympathy through instinct, which arises through consciousness' will to live. Initially, this may sound somewhat absurd but consider the plant which bends to the sunlight; is that plant not sympathetically reacting to its environment? It

³⁹ *CE*, pp. 293-294.

⁴⁰ *CE*, pp. 163-164; 188-191.

⁴¹ *CE*, pp. 150-160, 183-185, 204.

⁴² *CE*, p. 182: "Instinct ... is molded on the very form of life. ... The most essential of the primary instincts are really, therefore, vital processes. The potential consciousness that accompanies them is general actualized only at the outset of the act, and leaves the rest of the process to go on by itself."

⁴³ Note that Bergson repeats this notion when discussing intellect on *CE*, p. 211.

is sensing where the sun's energy is and responds to it through its 'will.' Its consciousness wills it toward survival whilst that will is carried through the plant's instinct to bend toward the light. This may be considered a 'primitive' act by some, but for Bergson, who argues that the intellect arises through instinct yet never leaves it behind, this act is an indispensable development of evolutionary growth. As he argues:

Instinct is sympathy. If this sympathy could extend its object and also reflect upon itself, it would give us the key to vital operations – just as intelligence, developed and disciplined, guides us into matter. For – we cannot too often repeat it – intelligence and instinct are turned in opposite directions, the former toward inert matter, the latter toward life. Intelligence, by means of science, which is its work, will deliver up to us more and more completely the secret of physical operations; of life it brings us and moreover only claims to bring us, a translation in terms of inertia. It goes all round life, taking from outside the great possible number of views of it, drawing it into itself instead of entering into it.⁴⁴

Recall that sympathy towards matter is fundamental to intuition. And yet sympathy is instinct. What Bergson is pointing out is that we often neglect essential aspects of our capacity to live. Instinct and its sympathy are typically seen as inferior to intellect and, therefore, discarded in rational thought. This is why we often only acquire mere representations of life rather than an understanding of life as a whole. Without this sympathetic operation one can only observe life – go all around it, analyzing it and translating this analysis into information – and not sense nor feel the life or potentiality of life throughout the universe. Science, or the intellect writ large, can do many great things, but it accomplishes a deeper sensation of life when it employs its sympathetic faculties when doing so.

For Bergson, intellect often absconds from sympathy, but instinct as sympathy is crucial to the development of intellect. If the former is focused on the outside world, and the latter is focused on life itself (and its inner vitality), how much more could we learn if we enfold these movements together? For him, this is the relationality between analysis and intuition, and it is the core principle of *duration* and our sensation of it.⁴⁵ This is important since it shows that there is not a clear-cut expression of instinct that does not express consciousness.⁴⁶ This means that the *elan vital* is not something life gains as it evolves – contrary to the mechanized

⁴⁴ CE, p. 194.

⁴⁵ ME, pp. 32-35.

⁴⁶ CE, p. 132.

and mathematized principles Bergson critiques – it is the very foundation of life. It is furthermore expressed through consciousness which carries it forth through instinct and, eventually, through intellect.

Regarding intellect, Bergson argues that this is a pivotal moment within evolution where the organism recognizes the wider array of possibilities as it also acquires the capacity to act in more innovative ways. Here, the mobility of the organism greatly increases, but notice how it is intertwined with the recognition of that mobility. Intellect, then, is not neatly separated from instinct and consciousness: the same coextension and spectrum between consciousness and instinct is carried through to the intellect. Although one may now choose to act against their instincts, they still have those instincts to act against. Furthermore, they possess the same faculty of consciousness, which is their life, it is just now they have a greater capacity to express the *elan vital* within their consciousness. We sever these relationships between consciousness, instinct, and intellect at our own peril, diminishing our own faculties:

But, on the other hand, intelligence has even more need of instinct than instinct has of intelligence; for the power to give shape to crude matter involves already a superior degree of organization, a degree to which the animal could not have risen, save on the wings of instinct. So, while nature has frankly evolved in the direction of instinct in the arthropods, we observe in almost all the vertebrates the striving after rather than the expansion of intelligence. It is instinct still which forms the basis of their psychical activity; but intelligence is there, and would fain [i.e., strive to] supersede it.⁴⁷

I will give a more detailed description of Bergson's understanding of intellect in the next section since it opens his philosophy to morality. For now, recall that Bergson's distinctions are aimed at a specific point: there is an interconnectivity between all life that is expressed through the *elan vital* and, regardless of an organism's ability, they share the same ecological will to life even if they do not express it in the same way or with the same capacity.⁴⁸ As Bergson states, this arises from *the need for consciousness*, meaning that there is a willful desire for life to spring forth.⁴⁹

⁴⁷ *CE*, p. 157. See also: *CE*, pp. 292-294, where he speaks about the loss of intuition within philosophy.

⁴⁸ For a more comprehensive account, see: Elena Fell, *Duration, Temporality, Self: Prospects for the Future of Bergsonism* (New York: Peter Lang, 2012), Chapter Four, "Consciousness, Life and the Universe in *Creative Evolution*," pp. 59-85.

⁴⁹ *CE*, p. 210.

In a sense, one can see a ‘cone of life’ that is similar to Bergson’s ‘cone of memory’ in that consciousness, as one of the three faculties of the *elan vital* and not as described in *Matter and Memory*, functions at the base/widest part of the cone and wills this *vital*. The creative expression of the will – its *elan* – is an interplay between an organism’s instinct and its intellect. The organism expresses all three through their engagements with the world and, in turn, living organisms express their capabilities in response to other organisms. These build habit-based memories (and perhaps innovate new instincts), and it builds true memories (and perhaps develops intellect) in the event of living in one’s environment. Taken further, all of this happens through the creative mobility of life itself, and one can sense these interplays through their expression within *duration*.

Stepping further back, though, something often overlooked is the *engagement* aspect of this interweaving of *elan vital* and *duration*. As the next section articulates, it is a morally political act in that all engagements have responses or consequences of some kind. Bergson touches upon this in *Creative Evolution* when he speaks about the need for an environment to be open to life, and he later articulates this through the need for an open society. Accordingly, in what follows, I will examine this need for openness and its moral and political implications for Bergson’s ecology.

4. Being Open to Life: The Social and Moral Implications of the *Elan Vital*’s Intellect

As shown above, Bergson’s description of the intellect is intertwined with instinct. Additionally, through the *elan vital* within evolution, the intellect is a desire to surpass mere instinct in pursuit of further engaging the world. Its concern is with one’s environment and, eventually, how one can understand that environment in pursuit of using it (or, at worst, exploiting it). It is thus no surprise that Bergson sees the creation of tools built from the environment (or matter) as a hallmark of the intellect.⁵⁰

Yet in order to create these tools, one must first seek an organization of one’s environment. This is where, at least for humanity, reason emerges as a process to develop an ordered account of matter which then leads to knowledge production. Consider the following scenario: Humans discover that certain types of matter can be burned as a heat source. When

⁵⁰ *CE*, pp. 152-156

figuring out why, humans realize that heat is just released energy. They then realize that they can harness this energy and create forges to melt other materials. They then discover how this smelting/forging can create better tools to which they can better manipulate other kinds of matter, and so on.⁵¹

Notice, however, that we have moved beyond the need of consciousness for life and the creative innovation of instinct and other faculties for life's survival. Here, we have moved to an outward expression of one's gaze upon matter.⁵² Bergson agrees and accepts that there is still a need for survival within the intellect, but he sees a "vicious circle" where intelligence, "harnessed, like yoked oxen," adaptively responds to this need while also trying to transcend it and move from survival to introspection.⁵³

In broad and general terms, the intellect is born out of the need for further creative innovation to survive but, as it progresses in its successful organization of the outside world, it seeks to transform this world toward its own needs. Its ordering and categorization of the world serve a bifurcated purpose: once survival is secured, it then proceeds to address other wants and needs, which often are self-serving.⁵⁴ Out of this, intellectual projects such as philosophy and science are born. Now, Bergson does not have any particular quarrel with these projects as they stand and sees them as natural evolutions of the intellect.⁵⁵ The problem is that many of these projects forsake their prior evolutionary operations, such as the beginnings of consciousness and how it binds us to all of life, or instinct, and how it literally is our sympathetic reception or adaptation to living and to life itself. They begin to believe that intellect alone is all that is needed.⁵⁶

⁵¹ In broad terms, this is my reading of *CE's* section on 'Intellect and Materiality,' pp. 219-228. I have left out his Kantian critique for simplicity.

⁵² Gallagher points this out as well on pp. 47-48 of *Morality in Evolution*: "Had the intellect been created primarily for theorizing, it would seek its place within the fluid and mobile where true reality is to be found [i.e., in the ecological mobility of life], but the intellect always starts from the solid and immobile since its natural operation is directed toward utility."

⁵³ *CE*, p. 210. See also: John Mullarkey, "Equally Circular: Bergson and the Vague Inventions of Politics," in *Bergson, Politics, and Religion*, Alexandre Lefebvre and Melanie White, eds. (Durham: Duke UP, 2012), pp. 62-64.

⁵⁴ This is revisited throughout, but see especially: *CE*, pp. 176-178. Also, Bergson gives critiques against synthetically organizing life *CE*, pp. 237-238, 244-247, 258; however, one can read within these critiques and in his responses to them, the process I summarized above.

⁵⁵ Recall Bergson is an empiricist and engages these disciplines, as well as psychology.

⁵⁶ Gallagher points this out as well on pp. 47-48 of *Morality in Evolution*: "Had the intellect been created primarily for theorizing, it would seek its place within the fluid and mobile where true reality is to be found

As Gallagher states, for Bergson, humanity's best understood not as *homo sapiens* but as *homo faber*, "for the human intellect appears to be essentially the faculty of manufacturing artificial objects, particularly the tools for making other tools ... the intellect never appears to be in its element unless it is working on inert matter..."⁵⁷ For a hypothetical example, knowing that an element gives off energy may be trivial, but once I or others recognize that this energy can be harnessed, it becomes knowledge. Then, either myself or others set out to organize and then harness that energy, typically by fabricating tools to do so. Finally, once that energy is fully understood and perhaps harvested, it becomes the foundation for further development, which progresses its organization into the realm of facticity: it is unquestioned that this element that gives off heat actually produces radiated energy; now what are we going to do with it, and can we find other elements that do the same?

This example points toward the startling progress humanity has made through its intellect, but there is a question of at what cost?⁵⁸ Furthermore, the intellect's focus on matter – or the outside world – pushes it away from the rest of life. Its abstractions of the world cease to consider the world in which it observes:

In short, all that goes on in nature as in the works of human genius, where, though the result may be trifling, there is at least perfect adequacy between the object made and the work of making it. ¶ Nothing of the kind in the evolution of life. There, the disproportion is striking between the work and the result. From the bottom to the top of the organized world we do indeed find one great effort; but most often this effort turns short, sometimes paralyzed by contrary forces, sometimes diverted from what it should do by what it does, absorbed by the form it is engaged in taking, hypnotized by it as by a mirror. ¶ Our freedom, in the very movements by which it is affirmed, creates the growing habits [i.e., instrumental reasonings] that will stifle it if it fails to renew itself by a constant effort: *it is dogged by automatism*. The most living thought becomes frigid in the formula that expresses it. *The word turns against the idea*. ¶ *The letter kills the spirit*.⁵⁹ (Emphasis mine)

Once again, this is why Bergson champions intuition as a necessary method intertwined with analysis. When one begins to gaze upon the world without sympathy or intuition, then one's creative impulse is stifled. They only rely upon analytical tools to categorize or order things to

[i.e., in the ecological mobility of life], but the intellect always starts from the solid and immobile since its natural operation is directed toward utility."

⁵⁷ Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, p. 47.

⁵⁸ Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, pp. 49-51.

⁵⁹ *CE*, pp. 140-141.

their sensibilities and needs. They merely focus on matters at hand and not about the interconnectivity of life expressed through *duration* or otherwise. True empiricism can only happen if one sympathizes as being ecologically related to the thing one is observing; the interiority of intuition is just as important as the exteriority of analysis, both are experiential and thus empirical.⁶⁰

Bergson sees instinct and intellect as creative innovations by organisms to address different needs. One could argue that instinct's interiority focuses on self-preservation whereas intellect is about self-exertion and, yet although in opposition, they are not so clearly separated as we think. By pulling back and sensing the *duration* within a given moment, one can sense the interrelation between the two: one needs instinct's sympathy for thinking intuitively and one needs the intellect's analytic faculties to think rationally. They are relationally necessary because we cannot sense *duration* without the other. Thus, whereas intellect alone may create a vicious circle for Bergson, I argue that he proffers a virtuous circle through *duration*.

Furthermore, I argue that this virtuous circle is ecological given that one must not merely see inert matter as an outward appearance of a thing; one must dig into one's instinctive, sympathetic nature to recognize the shared moment between oneself and what they are currently perceiving. It is not just the inert matter that one experiences, it is in concert with *everything one has experienced (memories), the experiences of said matter (how it came to oneself), and the entire environment in which one experiences said matter*. Returning to the 'cone of life' metaphor, all three living faculties – consciousness, instinct, and intellect – are involved in the telescopic reception of a perceptive experience, and one's faculties of memory – pure, true, and habit – open oneself to being co-penetrated within one's perception of this experience. Both cones, if you will, are necessary for a true sensation of the *duration* happening all around the perceiver and the perceived.

Going even deeper, this reading of Bergson's *elan vital* is also a moral event. Pivoting toward *Two Sources*, Bergson's political philosophy carries within it his ecological position on life and the need for openness to life for it to continue. However, he locates within creation a need

⁶⁰ CE, pp. 258-260.

for social cohesion, which is essential to survival for many species. For humanity, which is a communal species, this is expressed as the social obligation or duty one has to society to maintain its existence.⁶¹

One example he gives is that ants need to cooperate to build their home, find food, and ward off dangers. In this sense, there is a social element to their survival, not unlike Wiredu's argument that humans, as featherless bipeds strewn across the earth, likewise need each other to survive.⁶² In the case of the ants, Bergson notes that if they are not organized or do not fulfill their individual responsibilities, then the colony dies.⁶³ Extrapolating from this, Bergson likewise notes that human societies follow a similar structure in that there are duties and responsibilities for each individual in order to maintain social cohesion. These duties help maintain the society's existence and give that society a specified politics and moral code, but often at the expense of closure: they sense the need to enclose themselves within their own social fiefdom to ward off others.⁶⁴ This need often comes at a great expense: war.⁶⁵

It is here that we arrive at Bergson's delineation between closed and open societies. For Bergson, a closed society is one where "members hold together, caring nothing for the rest of humanity, on the alert for attack or defence, bound in fact, to a readiness for battle. ... Man was made for this society, as the ant was made for the ant-heap."⁶⁶ As Susan Guerlac summarizes:

Sociability, he argues, is a natural tendency, one at work in communities of ants and bees as well as humans. This social instinct, which operates on behalf of the conservation of the species, "always implies [*vise toujours*] . . . a closed society" (TS32/1001). Nature, in other words, requires a closed society where moral obligation, a function of habit and adaptation, occurs through various pressures imposed by natural necessity in accordance with evolutionary forces and constraints. Bergson introduces this perspective in his first chapter of *Two Sources* and returns to it in his discussion of war in the concluding chapter of his study: humans are designed for war, an inevitable

⁶¹ See: *CE*, pp. 266-268.

⁶² See: Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," p. 215.

⁶³ *TSMR*, pp. 28, 55, 82. Bergson recalls this ant analogy, often implicitly throughout the first two chapters of *TSMR*.

⁶⁴ *TSMR*, pp. 64-66; see also: Gallaher, *Morality in Evolution*, p. 73.

⁶⁵ *TSMR*, p. 67.

⁶⁶ *TSMR*, p. 266.

consequence of the closed structure of human society, itself required by nature for purposes of survival.⁶⁷

One's duty or morality is designed for maintaining social order and only this order. An individual will or desire is subsumed into the collective cohesion of things, where duty supersedes personal well-being. Or, as Bergson states, "obligation is to necessity what habit is to nature."⁶⁸ In this closed society, everyone must "play their part" lest they be punished, and in more extremely closed societies, they must not question the parts given to them.⁶⁹

It is important to note that there is an ecological need for such closure: social cohesion allows people to survive, and these types of societies did not arise from nowhere. This makes closed societies part of our created nature, similar to other social creatures like ants.⁷⁰ However, and this is the turn within human intelligence, the survival impetus of this morality only constitutes half of our possibilities:

I grant that the organic tendencies do not stand out clearly to our consciousness. They constitute, nevertheless, the strongest element of obligation. However complex our morality has grown and though it has become coupled with tendencies which are not mere modifications of natural tendencies, and whose trend is not in the direction of nature, it is to these natural tendencies that we come in the end, when we want to obtain a precipitate of the pure obligation contained in this fluid mass. Such then is the first half of morality.⁷¹

Clarifying his point, Bergson continues by stating that perhaps intelligence's expansion in humanity far exceeded its natural or organic intentions of survival.⁷² Nature, he postulates, "could not have intended that this should go on so far as to endanger the original structure," by which he means the ecological balance of life in general.⁷³ Though discussing it in a different context, this is akin to what Leonard Lawler describes as humanity's "cheating nature."⁷⁴ Lawler is speaking of the same chapter cited above, but he is focusing on a different

⁶⁷ Susan Guerlac, "Bergson, The Void, and The Politics of Life" in *Bergson, Politics, and Religion*, Alexandre Lefebvre and Melanie White, eds. (Durham: Duke UP, 2012), p. 46.

⁶⁸ *TSMR*, p. 14.

⁶⁹ *TSMR*, p. 19.

⁷⁰ Susan Guerlac adroitly summarizes this

⁷¹ *TSMR*, p. 56.

⁷² *TSMR*, pp. 56-64.

⁷³ *TSMR*, p. 56.

⁷⁴ Leonard Lawler, "Asceticism and Sexuality: 'Cheating Nature' in *The Two Sources of Morality and Religion*," in *Bergson, Politics, and Religion*, Alexandre Lefebvre and Melanie White, eds. (Durham: Duke UP, 2012), pp. 153-155.

aspect of the chapter, namely reproduction. It is beyond our scope to explore this, but I think his analysis dovetails into my point: In the chapter “Moral Obligation” of *Two Sources*, Bergson goes on at length about the different ways in which the human intellect far exceeded the need for survival to the point where it can separate itself from the world, build its own social orders outside of ‘nature,’ and proceed as if it is somehow above or separate from all other creatures.

This puts humanity in a problematic disposition: on the one hand, it thinks that it has superseded nature through its intelligence and how humanity’s magnificent tools, knowledge production, and even its creation of art has shown humanity that it is above its biological origins. On the other hand, it still behaves like ants and other social creatures, attacking its own kind in pursuit of land, power (however imagined), and other resources. Humanity has, in a very blunt sense, fooled itself into thinking it is beyond nature when its own natural instincts and intellect still function because humanity is still a creature of the soil.⁷⁵

This is where Bergson presents the ‘other half,’ if you will, of morality from the quote above. Although our social behaviors do carry with them the same instinctive impulse to protect the community, just like ants or the beehive, humanity’s intellect allows it to reject this instinctive impulse. We have the ability to reshape our morality beyond duty or obligation to society; we can reject our communities and their enclosures. This rejection is not what creates an open society, but the act of questioning morality itself reveals to Bergson that we have a pathway to reconcile our desires to intellectually innovate and our desires to appreciate the interconnectedness we possess with our surrounding world(s).

In our final analysis below, I will present Bergson’s open society, its limits and its possible reconciliation between humanity’s intellect and instinctual natures. Importantly, I draw my conclusions about this reconciliation through Melanie White’s notion of “natural” and “complete” sympathies and how they complement each other.⁷⁶ From this, I will conclude by arguing how these sympathies, embedded within Bergson’s ecological philosophy and its *elan*

⁷⁵ I find that this, in broad strokes, summarizes Bergson’s notion of “Static Religion,” pp. 102-209 in *TSMR*. Unfortunately, due to our thesis, scope, and length, we cannot delve further into his reading of stasis, which is sadly often overlooked in the literature on *TSMR*.

⁷⁶ Melanie White, “The Politics of Sympathy in Bergson’s *The Two Sources of Morality and Religion*,” in *Beyond Bergson: Examining Race and Colonialism through The Writings of Henri Bergson*, Andrea J. Pitts and William Mark Westmoreland, eds. (Albany: SUNY, 2018), p. 59.

vital, furthers our understanding of the relationship between morality and the will that persists throughout all of life.

5. Final Analysis: Sympathy and the Ecology of *Duration*

Although it may seem easy enough to present an open society as the next generation or evolution of humanity, it too has its limitations. For one, as Bergson notes, open societies do not tend to be open for long: “But after each occasion the circle that has momentarily opened closes again.”⁷⁷ It is not as if we can discover a new, open morality and then evolutionarily adopt it. If it were that easy, then there would not have been a reason to even have moral philosophy; we would have already done it as part of our evolutionary course.

This is why Bergson proffers for a dynamic society: one that recognizes its nature as a social creature which needs cohesion and order to survive but also recognizes that it needs to critique and question this cohesion – especially at pivotal moments of exclusion which may cause oppression and war – so that it can further intellectually evolve. For Bergson, this dynamism is often carried by the mystic or hero who rises to critique their community’s moral order to pursue a more just, more open society.⁷⁸ We will briefly cover Bergson’s notion of the mystic and hero below and give a more in-depth analysis in the next chapter when we bring Bergson into conversation with Serequeberhan’s notion of a lived existence. For now, though, what is important is to gather the larger picture that societies close and open; they are dynamic, and this is not merely a rational picture of society; it is an ecological and evolutionary movement.

As Gallagher points out, a closed society represents “a halt in the evolutionary process” as it closes itself to change so it can preserve its ordered and routinized cohesion.⁷⁹ It is closed to development and seeks to preserve what it already holds dear. The inbreaking of this society to open itself to change thus represents an evolutionary development. It is important to note, though, like all evolutionary possibilities, there is a danger that what it opens may destroy said society.⁸⁰ Some evolutionary adaptations advance an organism’s life, some adaptations

⁷⁷ *CE*, p. 267.

⁷⁸ *TSMR*, pp. 212-221; note that this argument is made throughout most of Chapter Three.

⁷⁹ Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, p. 71.

⁸⁰ *TSMR*, pp.80-81.

stagnate, and some create weaknesses that may lead to extinction. This is why open societies are momentary: they do not presume progress, they presume adaptation and availability to change. The creaturely desire to survive prevails, and if we presume that a pure, ongoingly open society is a better society, then we similarly neglect our own creatureliness as those I critiqued above who gaze upon the utility of the world rather than sensing its *duration*.

I believe that this is why Bergson ultimately places the burden of opening society on the mystic or hero who emerges from within a society to change it: these individuals exert pressure against social norms, and by questioning them eventually they push society to momentarily open itself to new ideas, morals, and possibilities.⁸¹ Ultimately, though, the society will persist and continue long after ‘the mystical hero’ has passed. However, there is a dynamism at play between the halting of evolution within the closed society and the potentiality of evolution within the open society. There is a relational logic between the closed and the open society. Just as there is a relational logic between intuition and analysis, different forms of memory, and the rise of consciousness, instinct and intellect within the *elan vital*. All these relationalities present different aspects of becoming; they are creative evolutions, if you will, of how we come to better know ourselves, our societies, and our environments.

I find that Melanie White’s analysis of the sympathy involved within closed and open societies further illustrates this. White argues that Bergson challenges us to reconsider the notion of sympathy and its potential role in exclusion.⁸² This challenge places sympathy – and I would extend it to intuition – on the same problematic range we have placed analysis in that sympathy is not inherently good.⁸³ One could read all the critiques of reason and misunderstand sympathy and intuition as the antidote to reason, as if all sympathy is intrinsically great and intuition is superior to analysis. Yet remember that these are relational concepts, and they, like their counterparts, are inherent parts of our evolutionary being. In short, they are neither divine nor pure. They are human, all too human.

⁸¹ *TSMR*, pp. 52-53, 63-64; note that this argument is carried throughout *TSMR*.

⁸² White, “The Politics of Sympathy,” p. 59.

⁸³ *Ibid.*, pp. 61-63.

White shows this through the interrelation of ‘natural sympathy’ and ‘complete sympathy.’ From her reading of *Two Sources*, she notes that natural sympathy exists in the unity of a society, yet “to be united ... at once [means] to be both intimate and confined. It is this double meaning that ... grafts the idea of sympathy onto Bergson’s conception of a closed society.”⁸⁴ Recall that sympathy is instinctive, and for social creatures, instinct unites their pack, their pride, or their tribe.⁸⁵ Furthermore, instinct is interrelated to habit – as seen in habit memory and unreflective action – and it can function as an instrumental reasoning or presupposed ideology whose purpose is to maintain order/cohesion at all costs. Therefore, although Bergson argues that we must engage our sympathetic nature, we must never forget that it is a part of instinct, that it too comes with survival as its *modus operandi*, which is why bypassing the intellect to access pure sympathy ultimately solves nothing. As White notes, it may provide unity, but at what cost?⁸⁶ As she summarizes, “the presence of a natural sympathy with its inclusions and exclusions helps to explain why it is not possible for our sympathies to broaden out in an unbroken progression from family to city to country to humanity.”⁸⁷

On the other hand, White finds within an open society a sense of complete sympathy, which the mystic or hero (or mystical hero, for brevity) possesses and presses upon their community. Quoting Bergson, White states that what sets these people apart is that they sense the “‘vital impetus’ of life, an impetus that Bergson describes variously as ‘joy of joy’ or ‘love of love.’”⁸⁸ The dynamism of sympathy is like the sensation felt within *duration* and how it opens the qualitative multiplicities of life.

Foreshadowing our conversation between Bergson and Serequeberhan, the mystical hero can break through the mundane, workaday life and see new possibilities, a broad fusion of horizons, which they then put into service of their community. Note that service is important for Bergson, as White shows, and Serequeberhan would agree, since it is not merely an experience; it is a call to action. Furthermore, the mystical hero or lived existence – whichever locution one prefers – never sees themselves as above society or absconds from society.

⁸⁴ Ibid., p. 62.

⁸⁵ Ibid., p. 63.

⁸⁶ Ibid., p. 63-65.

⁸⁷ Ibid., p. 64. Note how this clearly echoes and deepens Bergson’s remarks (*CE*, p. 267) highlighted above.

⁸⁸ Ibid., p. 69. She quotes from: Henri Bergson, *The Meaning of the War: Life and Matter in Conflict* (London: T. Fisher Unwin, 1915), pp. 212, 255.

Rather, they are drawn to it, and, in Bergson's case, that impetus is for the love of their fellow people.⁸⁹

A complete sympathy, in succinct terms, is a social sympathy that recognizes its relationality to humanity in general and to its ecological world. It is a social sympathy that seeks transformation through the same evolutionary process that brought humanity to its present situation. In Wiredu's philosophy, this could be an intellectual evolution. In Bergsonian terms, it is the cognizance of one's participation in life through *duration* and how that cognizance compels one to a deeper love of life beyond scientific and social enclosure.⁹⁰ Or, in my own words, it is an evolution of humanity's appreciation for life, for the love of being, which entails a more complete morality in sympathy with all of life.

However, returning closer to the issue at hand, the notion of the mystical hero and the evolutionary openness of society leads many scholars to argue that what Bergson is describing is humanity progressively moving towards the divine, and indeed Bergson does allude to this.⁹¹ Yet, from White's description of a natural and complete sympathy, I find that these sympathies mutually operate within the cohesion and transformative evolution of humanity; they are less divine and more creaturely than Bergson may intend. Accordingly, I think it is fair to conclude that these sympathetic notions operate similarly to instinct and intellect: natural sympathy follows an inwardness with a desire for unity and cohesion, a desire for homemaking and community; complete sympathy follows an outwardness and an appreciation of the unforeseen, a desire for connection and upbuilding. Does this not follow the inwardness of instinct and the outwardness of intellect?

Furthermore, they reveal the relational tension between the pressure for humanity to dynamically unify while also expanding further than their own gaze. Recall that Bergson argues in *Creative Evolution* that life must be open to development and that evolution is a creative process of survival. If we look at how humanity's intellect has surpassed the need for survival, then that survival instinct turns toward humanity itself. War, as Bergson emphasizes in *Two Sources*, is the greatest threat to humanity – humanity's extinction is now most likely

⁸⁹ Ibid., p. 70.

⁹⁰ Ibid., p. 71.

⁹¹ See: Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, pp. 52-55, 75-77; *TSMR*, pp. 267-268, 293-300.

to happen due to its own self-destruction. Of course, there is perhaps more destructive than war such as climate change, which Bergson did not anticipate, but this too is an extension of the same extinction threat: humanity causes its own destruction, its own dissolution.

To conclude we must return to the *elan vital* and creation's will to live. What we have covered is how Bergson describes this impulse within creation to will itself into action, where an organism bursts to life through matter. This will to life – both in capability of action and desire for action – is the core component of consciousness. In furthering this will in a world often hostile to it, organisms creatively adapt both physically and instinctively, evolving their nature to attenuate to this possibly hostile environment. This instinct is sympathetic in the sense that it is an internally conscious act; its aim is to be responsive to the environment and to adapt accordingly. However, as organisms further evolve, their responses turn further outward to further understanding their environment, thereby instantiating intellect. Countervailing to instinct and its sympathy, intellect seeks to organize and utilize the environment to its advantage, furthering its survival capabilities. Intellectual organisms thus begin developing strong communicational functions and create tools to utilize their environment.

In the case of humanity, this process has surpassed the 'natural' impulse for survival and has adapted its intellect to develop knowledge, belief systems, ideologies, and so forth. However, just like all evolved organisms, regardless of their hierarchy or level of evolutionary 'progression,' humanity still maintains within itself the same consciousness, the same instinct, and the same impulse to intellect; humanity may have surpassed the need to survive, but it has not surpassed its own biology. Within the human, then, there is a consciousness, there are instincts, there are intellectual evolutions which are shared across the spectrum of life.

The human is therefore not a special being, somehow above its own nature. According to Bergson, it fools itself when it thinks this, and often, he situates himself within these foolish arguments – reorienting and deconstructing them – to show how human intelligence forgets about its other faculties. The ultimate consequence of this foolishness, though, is that while there is no existential threat against humanity, it has created one for itself through war, oppression, and other acts of violence against its own kind. Humanity has become humanity's greatest enemy, which is the core critique within *Two Sources*. Bergson again situates himself amongst this foolishness by noting how closed societies are not as different from other social

organisms; humans have the same impulse for cohesion, order, and obligation as one sees in ant colonies. White notes this as the natural sympathy that humanity still holds, born out of its instinct and its vital impulse to survive.

Yet still, the *elan* – the creativity – within this vitalism remains. This is where Bergson highlights the mystical hero who sees beyond the order, finds the love of life, feels the ecological relationships which surrounds them, senses the *duration* of not just its own being, but that which passes through all of life. The mystical hero then is compelled to serve this life which it so loves, they seek to end the halting of human evolution (or development) by showing their society the qualitative multiplicities of life and, in so doing, shows society that their order and unity may be holding them back more than it maintains their needs and desires.

This opens society, if only for a moment, to sense greater possibilities, to a communal love of life, if only for a moment. I have spoken before of a *communal duration*, and I will further integrate this argument in the next chapter. But, for now at least, one can sense within an open society the *elan vital* which all conscious life shares: a creativity, a will, a love for life, and an ecology of creation seeking further becomings, further developments, a future which it may not know but senses and is compelled to seek.

CHAPTER NINE:
PLACING POLITICS:
SEREQUEBERHAN AND BERGSON IN CONVERSATION ON THINKING-WITH-PLACE

1. Introduction

Given the importance of the following conversation, I find it vital to recall that my thesis within this book is that a human becomes a person by engaging its community over time, and this engagement manifests itself in space and, through their historical-memorial negotiations, they transform this space into particular places. Our first and second conversations covered the relationship between personhood and community, as well as the relationship between communality and becoming within time and space. What is left for us to explore is how place manifests itself amongst personhood and community; we have focused specifically how this happens through a relational logic of becoming in the latter conversations, and now here we seek understanding of how this becoming happens within active, dynamic places.

Significantly and from the outset, I do not think of place as merely a site of creation or memory but as a co-generative entity which becomes imbued with meaning through negotiations with persons and communities. This is why it is neither just the contextual location of thinking nor the perception of human existence. Calling space 'a place' where thinking happens is too subjective for me, given that places influence thinking and typically are always already ecologically conscious (as we have seen in Bergson's *elan vital* and his cosmology). I will investigate this notion throughout our conversation and what it means for my thesis and its consequences on hermeneutic phenomenology.

However, prior to this conversation, we must engage the ongoing developments of 'placial thinking.' Thinking of place goes back to the works of Heidegger, Sartre, Merleau-Ponty, and Schulz. However, I have chosen Jeff Malpas, Bruce Janz, and Abraham Olivier as my interlocutors because they are currently the foremost thinkers on the philosophy of place,

especially within non-Western contexts. As such, they will provide us with a baseline moving forward. In short, Janz builds off Malpas and sees 'placial thinking' as doing "philosophy-in-place," which entails that African philosophy, amongst other historically marginalized traditions, should carve out a space for itself to think on its own terms.¹ In so doing, it should emphasize the particularity of that space; its 'placiality.' Olivier, who is likewise indebted to Malpas, appreciates this latter aspect but proposes that, rather than doing "philosophy-in-place," one should perform "philosophy-through-place" given the contextual interconnectivity of all the aspects that go into philosophizing.² This requires one to think of a multitude of 'placialities,' including (but not limited to): the author's place, the place of the ideas one engages (be it a historical-contextual place, or a place amongst other philosophies and concepts), and the relationship between experiencing a given place while thinking about other places, contexts, and/or cultures. It is up to the thinker to discern which of these placialities are the most relevant for their work, and Olivier encapsulates this into his concept of "exterophenomenology," which we will discuss below.³

After having situated the conversation, I then will proceed to exploring the interplay between Serequeberhan's hermeneutics and Bergson's cosmologic ecology. Fusions of horizons need landscapes, and although Serequeberhan's sense of worldhood is hermeneutic, it does not preclude sympathy/intuition, nor does it preclude that all living matter is conscious. On this last point, obviously Serequeberhan and Bergson have different notions of consciousness, but I find that they are not mutually exclusive. Resultantly, Serequeberhan's notions of Gadamerian prejudice and effective-historical consciousness provides a better connection between memory, history, and place which enhances Bergsonian *duration* by bridging the gap between internal (i.e., individual) and external (i.e., social) memory through their interrelation. Although Bergsonian *duration* and its memory is conceptually clear, Serequeberhan further emphasizes the politicization of memory and history, something I also covered in Conversation Two between Bergson and Wiredu and *communal duration*. Furthermore, these middle sections return to David Addyman's critique that Bergson lacks a

¹ Bruce Janz, *Philosophy in an African Place* (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2009), p. 12.

² Abraham Olivier, "The Place of Philosophy in Africa," *Southern Journal of Philosophy* 54:4 (December 2016), pp. 502-520. This argument runs throughout the article.

³ Abraham Olivier, "Understanding Place," in *Place, Space, and Hermeneutics*, Bruce Janz, ed. (Gewerbstrasse: Springer, 2017), p. 12.

definition of “good space.”⁴ I will argue that this can be reconciled through the relationship between good space and place: although Bergsonian analysis requires spatiality, and intuition somewhat negates the representative nature of this intellectual event, Serequeberhan’s activist hermeneutics opens our understanding of the qualitative multiplicities of *duration* and its impetus for both life and morality. Hence, good space becomes a placial, hermeneutic concept whereby life is open to expansion and creativity through its actions which are always already moral and political.

The fifth section addresses an issue that I see within Serequeberhan and Bergson, and that is the individuated way in which they articulate human morality through the lived existence or the mystical hero. This problem is typically called the ‘Great Man Theory,’ which is a fallacy whereby paradigm shifting events in human history are thought to be caused by so-called ‘Great Men’ like John Cecil Rhodes, whom I will address. As others have pointed out, this fallacy ignores the collective, communal, and placial interactions which led up to these major events.⁵ For us, though, it needs to be addressed because it is an outlier to the ecological network of place: it is as if these men (and its nearly always men) stand outside of history – outside of both world and cosmology – and not only see the future but actually shape it in their own image. This problematic hinders both Serequeberhan’s effective-historical consciousness and Bergson’s ecological cosmology. Although I will not rewrite their works, I will show how each’s use of relational logic addresses this issue since great moral, political change requestions communities and historical conditions to further humanity’s ‘intellectual evolution,’ to reprise Wiredu’s moral anthropology.

Moreover, this contributes to this chapter’s argument since morality, as I will present it, comes from a communal place, indicating that the community of place is equally (if not more) important than the lived existence or the mystical hero. What this emphasizes is that neither lived existences, mystical heroes, nor their communities come from nowhere. They exist in space, and they make place their home which I will show by reframing placial thinking within a communal logic. Liberators and mystics require community since both seek to open the community to further humanity’s intellectual evolution via morality. This evolution is

⁴ See: Chapter Six, pp. 145-149; Addyman, “Bergson’s Matter and Memory: From Time to Space,” pp. 24-25.

⁵ Peter Novick, *That Noble Dream: The “Objectivity Question” and the American Historical Profession*. (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005), p. 8.

'effected-historically' (*pace* Serequeberhan) since the extant, changing morality comes from a place of community, thereby proving that the community of place is equally important. Again, this reiterates how neither liberating heroes or mystics, nor their communities, come from nowhere: they exist in politically laden, temporal spaces, and they mutually cooperate with this already conscious space (either ecologically or through lived memory) to establish dynamic, relational places.

I will argue that the issues above reveal two problems: First, there is a problem of individualism and subjectivity; meaning that not just Serequeberhan and Bergson but also the placial approach to thinking about life overemphasizes the perspective of a singular consciousness. Yes, I have argued that Serequeberhan and Bergson hold a relational logic which emphasizes the person and community (as well as the ecological cosmos, for Bergson), but their work still retains the classical phenomenological starting point of the individual consciousness. This dovetails into Bergson's problem with lacking a definition of 'good space' as well as the issues within placial thinking: whether it is good space or philosophizing of/through place, these notions are always from a singular subject's perception. My analysis argues that the fact that persons and communities imbue space with living, historical meaning does not exclude places from having their own existence or their own lifeworld. Sure, persons help create this history and placial designation, thereby making places dependent upon personal-communal engagements but, as we have seen within this entire book, each entity is co-dependent and therefore co-generative. Places are no different: they require engagement just like persons and communities.

This is what makes my emphasis on relational logic and the notion of place so important to the future of hermeneutic phenomenology: we thinkers have typically reckoned with space/place as if it were merely a product of mind and experience, but they were always already there before we gazed upon them. A relational logic allows hermeneutic phenomenologists to analytically and intuitively understand this relationship, and a moral anthropology allows us to take responsibility for our co-development and co-generation of spaces into places. Thus, we arrive at more vigorous insights of persons, communities, and places. Moreover, we arrive at a stronger hermeneutic phenomenological method where place is not context, and engagements are not dialectical nor subjective; they work within a triadic event and a hermeneutic phenomenologist must consider the place unto itself rather

than rendering it as context or pretext to interpersonal interactions. All three are matter, all three are living, all three matter for our philosophies.

2. Conceptual Considerations: Philosophy in Place, through Place, or with Place?

Just like philosophical considerations of space are nothing new, neither are philosophies which engage the concept of place. “Placial thinking,” has primarily arisen as a site of philosophical inquiry due to Jeff Malpas’ work on Heideggerian topology, which heavily influenced Bruce Janz’ and Abraham Olivier’s work on the concept of place within African philosophy and phenomenology writ large.⁶

Malpas’ focus on topology spans much of his career, especially within two important books. The first is *Place and Experience: A Philosophical Topography*, which focuses on the relationship between events and space to arrive at the concept of place and argues that topology is a phenomenological touchstone for further analysis. Later, in *Heidegger’s Topology: Being, Place, World*, Malpas introduces the notion that place holds an underserved but important role throughout Heidegger’s work, especially his later period, which not only gives more depth to Heideggerian scholarship but also presents an application of topology as a method.⁷ Topology, for Malpas, is a process whereby one does not render the structure of a thing or event to its particular parts, but rather looks for the intersections and conjoining (even if contradictory) ideas or processes which helped produce the event in question. As he summarizes it:

The idea of topology suggests that it is a mistake to look for simple, reductive accounts – whether we are exploring a concept, or problem, or the meaning of a term, the point is always to look to a larger field of relations in which the matter at issue can be placed. This means, however, that it will seldom be possible to arrive at simple, univocal definitions. Significant terms will generally connect up with other terms in multiple ways and carry a range of connotations and meanings that cannot always be easily or precisely separated out.⁸

⁶ Olivier, “The Place of Philosophy in Africa,” p. 511; see also: Bruce Janz, *Philosophy in an African Place*, p. 6; Jeff Malpas, *Place and Experience: A Philosophical Topography* (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1999).

⁷ Jeff Malpas, *Heidegger’s Topology: Being, Place, World* (Cambridge: MIT Press, 2006); for an overview of how his work coalesces around the notions of place and topology, see: pp. 2-6. See also: Jeff Malpas, “Heidegger’s Topology of Being,” in *Transcendental Heidegger*, Seven Crowell, Jeff Malpas, eds. (Stanford: Stanford UP, 2007), pp. 119-134.

⁸ Malpas, *Heidegger’s Topology*, p. 35.

Continuing through Heidegger's use of language as a key example where topology is relevant, he states:

Almost all of Heidegger's language, especially the language of his later writings, is "iridescent" in the sense of constantly shining and showing different facets. The attempt to delineate the topology of thinking and the topology of being will always carry a certain "iridescence" of this sort. It is an iridescence that may also be compared to the "backwards or forwards" relatedness that is to be found in hermeneutical thinking and that is also tied to the nature of the topological. It is a reflection of the iridescent, the multiple, shifting character of place as such.⁹

While Malpas' project appears to make headway into the spatial character of the lifeworld and events which unfold within it, the crucial point carried throughout most of his work is that place is not just where we find ourselves but it is also where we begin to philosophize.¹⁰ This is because all of our ideas are situated within history (*pace* Gadamer), and even within a clearing or at a remove (*pace* Heidegger), we cannot see the world beyond our own region within it. Thus, a topology allows us to view the connections which create this situatedness, and the concept of place allows us to recognize the hermeneutical to-and-fro of our reasoning which is not linear, nor progressive, nor regressive; it moves as we think.

Janz follows this in his philosophy of place. In an early and aptly titled article, "The Territory is Not the Map," Janz sets the trajectory of his project by stating his aim is "to consider ways in which we might think of African philosophy outside the metaphors of maps both modernist and some postmodern writers use, the first to delineate and define area and establish ownership and citizenship, the second to clear space and allow for possibilities."¹¹ At this stage, Janz argues that Deleuze and Guattari's "geophilosophy" sheds light on "the milieus that act and interact. These milieus become territory, which itself is deterritorialized through the creative power of refrain. There is no essence to place; it cannot be used ... to assert

⁹ Ibid., p. 37; note that these quotes come from a conversation Malpas had with Marcelo Stamm (Fn. 102).

¹⁰ Ibid., pp 39. See also p. 306: "The place," Malpas summarizes, "at issue here (which appears in various guises as the 'Da' of Dasein, as the clearing, *die Lichtung*, that is the happening of the truth of being, as the gathering of the fourfold in the *Ereignis*) is itself constituted only through the interrelations between the originary and mutually dependent ('equiprimordial') elements that themselves appear within it." What Malpas is pointing out, here, is that all of these technical elements of Heidegger's phenomenological analysis of being and the event of being are brought together topologically. Meaning, in a place where they cohere and illuminate what being is there, how it is there, why it is there, and what it is doing there.

¹¹ Bruce Janz, "The Territory is Not the Map: Place, Deleuze, Guattari, and African Philosophy," *Philosophia Africana*, 5:1 (2002), p. 2. Janz brings Deleuze and Guattari into conversation concerning mapping philosophy, and it is important to keep in mind Deleuze's connection to Bergson even though we cannot delve further into it here.

ownership and entitlement.”¹² Here, we see Janz locating something like Charles Mills’ geopolitics and chronopolitics which I highlighted in Chapter Four, namely that those who control the land – i.e., place – also dictate the rationality of those who reside within that land.¹³ Furthermore, this aligns with Bergson’s argument that a society, which occupies space/land, dictates morality and what is reasonable.¹⁴ Space, then, is not philosophically nor morally innocent. It too has sedimented layers of history and memory which can be exerted onto others, or, through a refrain and deterritorialization, it can be reclaimed or claimed anew even though the history of said space remains (but perhaps reinterpreted).

In Janz’ case, he will expand upon this geopolitical aspect of philosophizing to articulate not just that Africans carve out a space for their philosophy but that, in so doing, they are de/re-territorializing the designations where they do philosophy; it becomes a place of regionality for thought to arise. As he argues, “rather than asking, ‘What is the identity of African philosophy?’ one might ask ‘What is it to do philosophy in this (African) place?’”¹⁵ This is where he begins developing his notion of “philosophy-in-place,” which “brings the positionality out of our investigative mechanisms ... [and] bring[s] them to light;” the latter meaning that we have to leave room for the unexpected, and uncover (or shed light upon) ideas and concepts which heretofore were hidden.¹⁶ Doing so necessitates recognizing that their effected-historical context is also a placial context which influences and, to a degree, controls one’s thinking.

Importantly, though, philosophy-in-place is not trying to ‘liberate’ oneself from their placiality or positionality since that would be impossible (we all exist in one place or another). Rather, it seeks to open possibilities for conversational thought where “both parties have a certain degree of vulnerability.”¹⁷ In other words, where the control of the space is freely open to both parties and where the placial designation – the living contextuality within the

¹² Ibid., p. 4.

¹³ See: Chapter Four, p. 115-119.

¹⁴ It is important to note that, throughout his work, Janz engages Bergson’s *elan vital* as a reference point for a critique of spatiality, but Janz often maintains a Heideggerian or Deleuzeian approach to his overarching philosophy. Malpas does this as well and likewise continues with a Heideggerian phenomenological approach. Although it is worthwhile to review their usage of Bergson, given the scope and thesis of this chapter, I cannot address it here.

¹⁵ Bruce Janz, *Philosophy in an African Place* (New York: Rowman & Littlefield, 2009), p. 7.

¹⁶ Ibid., p. 110.

¹⁷ Ibid., p. 111.

conversation partners' positionality – is shared. Janz summarizes this concept of philosophy-in-place as his “term for this whole creative process” of rethinking how we engage others and different concepts, and this rethinking “is a philosophy of dynamical and emergent systems rather than [debates or philosophizing about] first principles or models.”¹⁸

Placial thinking, then, holds a certain type of ‘*d’où parlez vous?*’ Although, unlike Ricoeur’s intention of acknowledging one’s historicity within the question, Janz presses further by asking from what place do you speak? From what land and from what rationality upon which that land is located?¹⁹ Once these places of thinking are established, a genuine conversation may open within the place where one and another are situated, a place to share ideas and disagreements on equal footing.²⁰

Returning to Malpas, one can see how a topology produces placial thinking by highlighting the intersections and conversions of thought. Placial, in this way, is the grounded land upon which these ideas were generated through reflection about one’s situatedness within the world, but how does reflection and situatedness interact without overdetermining the other? In a sense, focusing too much on place – in the abstract and literal sense – can silo thought into a locality rather than opening it up to collective reflection, thereby preventing it from engaging other ideas because they are ‘too African’ or ‘too American,’ or what have you. One may argue that we are back to where we started: with a fixated notion of thinking that is unmovable and untranslatable since there is little universal connection of experience and ideas between two thinkers because each is so entrenched into their own places.²¹

Later, in *African Philosophy and Enactivist Cognition*, Janz seeks to resolve this problematic by “rehabilitat[ing] the notion of the spatial” within his placial philosophy.²² The attempt, in

¹⁸ Bruce Janz, *African Philosophy and Enactivist Cognition: The Space of Thought*, (London: Bloomsbury, 2022), p. 9; see also: Bruce Janz, “The Location(s) of Philosophy: Generating and Questioning New Concepts in African Philosophy,” *Philosophia Africana* 16:1 (2014), pp. 11-24.

¹⁹ Janz, *Philosophy in an African Place*, pp. 8-12.

²⁰ Bruce Janz, “Conversation in Place and About Place: Response to Chimakonam, ‘Conversational Philosophy as a New School of Thought in African Philosophy: A Conversation with Bruce Janz on the Concept of ‘Philosophical Space,’” *Journal of World Philosophies*, 1 (2016), p. 42-46. Note that Janz is not a part of the Conversational School, nor does he completely subscribe to its method, he does however, appreciate the distinction it makes concerning the politics of dialogue and the critique that dialogues often become dialectical or adversarial.

²¹ Olivier, “The Place of Philosophy in Africa,” p. 506.

²² Janz, *African Philosophy and Enactivist Cognition*, p. 5.

short, is one where placial thinking does not dominate the entire 'space' of thought or philosophizing; where 'thinking-in-place' becomes stuck, if you will, and cannot move forward.²³ This spatial register, then, is a way in which Janz seeks to recognize "the cognitive space" or the abstract since the physical, placial positioning of thought needs to convey ideas through a cognitive spatiality from one person to another.²⁴ Here, as Olivier describes it, "Janz explains *space* in terms of a 'field' of thought, one that addresses a particular problematic that is typically expressed by asking particular sets of questions."²⁵ Space, then, becomes the mediation between ideas which are generated through thinkers landed in placiality with all its contexts, histories, and logics. The enactivist nature of this exchange articulates the agency and activity of the embodied persons engaging in these exchanges, whether self-reflective or conversational with other persons.²⁶

Olivier is critical of this tenuous connection, querying whether philosophy-in-place delimits the possibility of philosophizing. For Olivier, "if the relation between philosophy and place remains of a reflective nature, then the philosopher seems to have no compelling reason as to why place should be more interesting than any of the [other] topics that have currency and induces philosophy to undertake self-reflection."²⁷ What he means by this is that philosophers are interested in various important issues and processes of thinking and/or understanding. If philosophy-in-place is to be a reflective exercise to understanding the contextual and positional nature of thinking itself, then – even with cognitive spatiality – how could it possibly engage in concepts other than place? At its core, Olivier's critique is that philosophy, and especially phenomenology, must have some type of universals to be both translatable and comprehensible: one must have a means of thinking beyond one's own situatedness (whether positional or effected-historical) to engage meaningfully with other ideas.²⁸

Olivier further critiques placial thinking by questioning if topologies accept "distopology," where placial "displacement has the features of repositioning and juxtaposing which makes

²³ Ibid., pp. 219-220.

²⁴ Ibid., pp. 11; see also: pp. 26-27, 222.

²⁵ Olivier, "Enactivist African Philosophy: A Response," *Philosophia Africana*, 22:1 (2023), p. 13.

²⁶ Janz, *African Philosophy and Enactivist Cognition*, pp. 8-9.

²⁷ Olivier, "The Place of African Philosophy," p. 506.

²⁸ Ibid., p. 506-508.

it a force of a movement that makes it possible for anyone to take one's place and *have a place of one's choice*, although in a way that is never settled and remains unsettling."²⁹ In short, Olivier questions the fixated nature of placial thinking, both literally and figuratively. On the one hand, the positionality of the thinker in-place ignores the universal and translatability of their experiences and rationalities. On the other hand, this topological positionality does not adequately address the unsettled nature of being in a place; whether that is being placed somewhere by force or by choice.³⁰

Placial thinking and topology, for Olivier, are great concepts but they need access points for engagement, and they also need to recognize that distopologies go hand-in-hand with topologies. This emphasizes the to-and-fro of the movement of ideas, as mentioned above. Continuing, he argues that "the challenge is to remain responsive to the dynamics of displacement in any place (field, situation) of philosophical practice, no matter what methods of enquiry one follows."³¹ Although cognitive enactivism addresses this issue, Olivier still is concerned that, given how spatiality and cognition typically are qualified through Western terminology and thus Western thought, the cognitive space which may bring about distopologies or reflections in-place may fall prey to neo-colonization. This harkens back to Paulin Hountondji's critique of "conceptual extraversion, the imposition of Western concepts on an African place."³² It also is in concert with Wiredu's arguments that we need translatable universals as a species, and the fact that many African communities, such as the Akan, do not think in immanent and transcendent terms, but rather think and reflect upon their lives solely through spatialized events.³³

In response to his own critique, Olivier first proposes "philosophy-through-place" and later an "exterophenomenology."³⁴ Overall, a philosophy-through-place accepts phenomenology's emphasis on conscious experiences and reflections thereof, but it imparts upon phenomenology that these experiences happen in a given place – not just a space and time, but a literal place with its own context – which thus changes/influences consciousness'

²⁹ Abraham Olivier, "Place and Displacement: Towards a Distopological Approach," *International Journal of Philosophical Studies*, 27:1 (2019), p. 46, emphasis mine.

³⁰ Olivier, "The Place of African Philosophy," p. 508; Olivier, "Place and Displacement," p. 47-48.

³¹ Olivier, "Place and Displacement," p. 48.

³² Olivier, "Enactivist African Philosophy," p. 19.

³³ See: Chapter Five, pp. 81-83, 85-87, 91.

³⁴ Olivier, "The Place of African Philosophy," p. 506.

reflection upon said experiences.³⁵ Or, in simpler terms, one's positionality influences their reflection upon their experiences, so philosophizing-*through*-place allows one to think about how experience in a particular, specific place changes the way that they understand or reflect upon said experience. This allows the philosopher to ask, "what is the relations between place and experience?" and reckon with the notion that "experience is constituted in place in its particularity."³⁶ The outcome of this is that each event (and reflection of the event) is novel since places are ever-changing.

Thus, a universality appears for intellectual exchanges given that phenomenology maintains an experiential character with its emphasis on consciousness rendering phenomena into meaning, thereby allowing placial thinking to engage with experiences. Olivier often illustrates this through how Heidegger might be received in South African townships, which at once are displacements – impoverished communities which are literally pushed aside from adjacent cities – but also are places where those who struggle find some type of meaning to their lives.³⁷ Topology and distopology overlap, here, where being displaced from home and being at home are constituted through experiences forced upon oneself, and that it is also the lens through which oneself understands the world.³⁸ The place, then, comes before the subject in that it is already constituted before the subject is there, and the subject's experiences come from being thrown into a given place by birth, by force, or by choice. Either way, an extero-phenomenology opens phenomenology to begin by thinking through the place in which the subject's experience is always already constituted.³⁹ This takes Malpas' topological method and employs it within an embedded and embodied subject.⁴⁰

Here, Olivier attempts to shift the focus "from the subject to the object by emphasizing the hermeneutical significance of the meaning of exteroconceptual objects."⁴¹ 'Exteroconceptual objects' means the relationship between the "mind-independent" object and the way in

³⁵ Ibid., pp. 507-511.

³⁶ Ibid., p. 511.

³⁷ See: Olivier, "The Place of African Philosophy," pp. 516-518 where he revisits his article, "Heidegger in the Township," *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 34 (2015), pp. 240-254.

³⁸ For an overview, see: Abraham Olivier, "Displacement and Decolonization: Mbembe and Decolonizing the University," in *Decolonization as Democratization*, Siseko H. Kumalo, ed. (Pretoria: HSRC Press, 2021) pp. 163-164.

³⁹ Olivier, "Understanding Place," pp. 15-16, 18-19.

⁴⁰ Ibid., p. 20.

⁴¹ Ibid., p. 12.

which they appear or become conceptualized through experience.⁴² The aim of this type of phenomenology basically is to recognize the difference between the independent object and the way in which it is perceived, understood, and then explained to others. Concerning placial thinking, Olivier finds that this way of understanding place puts the phenomenologist at a remove, separating their own analysis of the event from the event itself by recognizing the hermeneutical gesture always already within phenomenology. One cannot experience an event or object without mediacy, and one cannot think of a given thing or object without recognition of its positionality. Thus, a phenomenologist who is engaging how a given subject perceives a given object must perform a double recognition: the positionality, i.e., placiality, of the subject and object as well as the phenomenologist's own placiality and how this affects their analysis. This is true even if the phenomenologist is examining their own community since the overlapping positionality will change their analysis. In short, the object has a place, the perceiver has a place when perceiving said object, and the phenomenologist has a place as well. All three need to be considered since all three are subjected to the embodied event of experiencing, perceiving, and thinking.⁴³ Summarizing, Olivier states that:

Firstly, the exterophenomenological approach to meaning shifts the focus from the orientation toward universal structures of experience toward the exploration of the place-bound particularity of experience. The implication is that the understanding of place turns place itself into a methodological framework of understanding experience, in short, a hermeneutical key. Thus place is not just the site of the meaning of experience, but the way that we access its meaning. ¶ Secondly, the exterophenomenological focus on the constitution of experience in and by place qua contextual web of meanings opens experience to third-personal inquiry on a universal level, even though place trades in and relies on particularity and contingency. We can all understand place from within an objective third-person inquiry, but we shall understand it in its particularity as a place of living. This means, we can universally understand the way that experience is constituted by place as a particular kind of experience.⁴⁴

For Olivier, then, the answer to getting 'stuck in place' is first to think *through* placiality and not merely within it, and later he emphasizes the hermeneutical connectivity of experiences via placiality which can be shared and analyzed by others. In his more recent analysis, Olivier is integrating other posthumanist and ecological approaches into his exterophenomenology,

⁴² Ibid., p. 11.

⁴³ Ibid., p. 12-16.

⁴⁴ Ibid., p. 19.

particularly within understanding how ecology and posthumanist work emphasizes how places/habitats hold their own historical-cultural character independent of, but related to, the self and/or other.⁴⁵

Thus, we now have moved from a phenomenological topology to a philosophy-in-place, to a philosophy-through-place, and back to a form of phenomenology (exterophenomenology) which incorporates the topological and the distopological into an analysis of experiential hermeneutics. My apologies to the reader, and I give thanks for their patience, but there was a reason for this extensive review of placial thinking.

First, this is an emerging field of phenomenological research, and it is important to recognize these developments and how they enfold each other. I find that Olivier is intrigued by Janz' concept of place but is swayed by Malpas' reading of Heidegger's topology, and often his critique of Janz reflects this. I appreciate Olivier's movement into the hermeneutics of place but his emphasis on experience and universality gets in his own way: yes, we have a position in which we interpret an event or thing in question, and yes that place is in itself comported to its own world before we even experience it, but Olivier still maintains that this is a subjective experience. Meaning, the 'place' of placial thinking remains within the logic that takes subjectivity as its primary starting point; even exterophenomenology requires a network of subjects for understanding. Perhaps, I proffer, 'the understanding' is always already there in the place itself with persons and communities discovering it in different ways, adding to its life, history, and meaning for generations to come.

What I am getting at, here, is that while Malpas, Janz, and Olivier have made great headway into placial thinking, perhaps there is another pathway to understanding this notion through a relational logic between person, community, and place. My aim in what follows is therefore not to argue against these thinkers, but to contribute to the discussion by suggesting that a foundational relational logic – one that begins via relationality rather than expressing a web of relations as the situation of interaction – may may open hermeneutic phenomenology (or

⁴⁵ Abraham Olivier, "Out of the Dark Night of Necropolitics: Reflections on African Ecophenomenology," *South African Journal of Philosophy*, Forthcoming (as of January 2025). It is beyond our scope to engage the posthumanist and ecophilosophical approaches to placial thinking. This is especially true since a thorough engagement would require at least a chapter length treatment. However, it is a strong anchor point for further research. See: Chapter Ten: 260-261.

phenomenology writ large) to new perspectives. For some, I understand if they find Malpas, Janz, and/or Olivier already incorporate a relational logic. However, I think that it could be pressed further to articulate how persons and communities manifest themselves in time and space to create places which hold sedimented layers of meaning in negotiated tension between persons and communities. I accordingly seek a complimentary pathway to discovery – adding to the multiplicity of philosophizing – rather than the typical adversarial approach where all other ideas are ‘problematic.’

What I will argue is that what we call places have their own life and world before we gaze upon them. In an ecological register and following Bergson, there is already conscious life reacting to the worlds we enter – the clearing in the forest is alive and well with beings expressing their *elan vital*. From a hermeneutical register and following Serequeberhan, places have their own histories and, although it may take a web of experiences to hermeneutically express or articulate that history, it is a living and ongoing history that is not the domain of a subject or a set of subjects. Long after I have left a place, that place keeps on living, keeps on layering its histories, keeps on building memories. In what follows I will develop this argument and describe why we must *think with place* rather than render it to our own subjectivities.

3. *Ge-stell* and the *Elan Vital*: Serequeberhan and Bergson on Consciousness

Since Serequeberhan and Bergson have differing notions of consciousness, it is worth focusing on the overlap and hermeneutic tensions between their ideas. Furthermore, this will set up how they present the concept of place as a site of historical-memorial thinking which influences and changes a given place (Serequeberhan), and how this site is always already teeming with life-energy on its own and is worthy of hermeneutic phenomenological scrutiny unto itself (Bergson). What will emerge from this section is how consciousness and existence are relational, and how this articulates a type of placial thinking that is more than a constituted site of subjective interactions.

Although Serequeberhan’s notion of thinking is indebted to Heidegger, his notion of consciousness is found within his reading of Gadamer (and his contrast/critiques of

Gadamerian hermeneutics with African and decolonial thinkers).⁴⁶ Here, a lived existence recognizes its effected-historical consciousness and, now that it knows their *regionality* in relation to truth, they can see new possibilities (via a fusion of horizons heretofore unseen) for themselves and especially their community.⁴⁷

What I find interesting is that Gadamer's *wirkungsgeschichtliches Bewusstsein* is often translated as 'historical-effected consciousness.' However, from my reading of Serequeberhan, I think that his own translation of 'effected-historical consciousness' directly corresponds to his notion of a lived existence and its heritage:

- A lived existence recognizes the forces which *effected* and ensnares/en-frames one's situatedness.
- With this knowledge, a lived existence can reinterpret their *historical* situatedness, thereby retrieving and reinvigorating their heritage.
- Equipped with both, one can then reflect upon these aspects in pursuit of forming their own *consciousness*, or comportment and understanding of the world in which they live.⁴⁸

A lived existence, then, is one that recognizes the *Ge-stell* or en-framing of their existence and the rationalities which has forcibly and historically ensnared their thinking. Reprising Mills, knowing that 'who controls the land controls its rationality and temporality' allows one to recognize the ways in which they have been ensnared and, most importantly, who or what needs to be confronted regarding this ensnarement. A lived existence consequently recognizes how their own consciousness was shaped and molded by one's environment and their understanding of it but, with this newfound regionality of truth, the lived existence must forwardly press to new regions of truth to pursue personal and communal emancipation.⁴⁹

Returning to Serequeberhan's notion of consciousness, then, one could plausibly argue that it is a part of thinking (or the intellect), but it gets instrumentally buried as a person carries on about their everyday life. As mentioned in Chapter One, these existent persons think only within the terms and conditions which engulf them, and those conditions often are enforced

⁴⁶ See: Chapter Seven, p. 157-163.

⁴⁷ See: Chapter One, p. 9-14.

⁴⁸ This and the above paragraph come from: Justin Sands, "John D. Caputo and Tsenay Serequeberhan in Conversation: Can A Radical Theologian Be A Lived Existence?" in *Diversity and Exclusion in Religion and Politics*, Whitney Lynn Harper, ed. (Oxfordshire: Routledge, 2026), *forthcoming*.

⁴⁹ See: Chapter Seven, p. 161, 170, 175.

by an oppressive effective-historicity. This is why a *lived* existence is different: it recognizes these forces and how it has buried one's consciousness to only think through the oppressors' framework. This is why Serequeberhan concluded that both entho- and professional philosophers shared the same dilapidating, Eurocentric metaphysics.⁵⁰ They could not *consciously* recognize the Eurocentric situatedness of their own thinking.

Recall how Serequeberhan gathers his notions of existence (or *ek-sistence*) and its living enactment through Heidegger's work on thinking, and not on any existential notion seen within Heidegger's earlier or later work. From this, Serequeberhan argues that *ek-sistence* (which entails a "standing out") *and* consciousness can be nullified by the ideological forces that ensnare them.⁵¹ The emancipation, then, is a self-recognition of one's situatedness and one uses this realization to press toward emancipation of what ensnares oneself. Once one realizes the regionality of their sense of truth, one can then (and only then) begin to rediscover their heritage; one's collective and communal historicity and its cultural legacy which was heretofore buried under the oppressor's effective-historicity. For the oppressor, recognizing their own heritage's oppression allows them to confront how they have benefitted from this heritage – even if they themselves were not the original oppressors – and how they can utilize their region of truth to emancipate those oppressed while also opening themselves to a life which has reconciled itself with the legacy which fashioned it. Remember that Serequeberhan speaks about the oppressed, but his work emphasizes that all could be lived existences and that everyone has a heritage with which they must reckon or reclaim.

This is how oneself transforms beyond mere existing to a living existence; it is a self-recognition and then a communal recognition that is relational to each other, which is also relational to each's historical situatedness. This is where one transforms their effected-historicity into an emancipatory heritage:

In naming themselves, in the refusal and discipline of the movement, in every effort aimed at reclaiming humanity, the formerly enslaved carve out and reclaim, at each phase of the struggle, the heritage of their freedom. Each effort aimed at freedom or enacted within the ambient of a limited freedom and aimed at enhancing this already achieved freedom situates a specific or concrete engagement within one's heritage: *the*

⁵⁰ See: Chapter One, p. 16-20; Chapter Seven, p. 161-165; *HAP*, p. 32.

⁵¹ *EH*, p. 2, see also: Chapter One, p. 12-16, 22-23.

*"effective-history" of one's existence. The actuality of a heritage is, then, the lived sedimentation, the layering of the self-formation that constitutes a specific history.*⁵²

Existence, then, is an ontic state of being and, although this beingness requires thinking, it is not 'activated' or 'lived' until it ontico-ontologically rediscovers the way in which its consciousness has been ensnared or en-framed into a specific metaphysics. It is this rediscovery of one's heritage, through an effected-historical *consciousness*, that one begins the struggle towards liberation or, as I pointed out before, when one may begin to philosophize.⁵³ Consciousness therefore holds a specific nature or operation within Serequeberhan's hermeneutics, and I think that its operation could overlay onto (or reside within) Bergsonian consciousness.

Consciousness, for Bergson, is a creative burst or standing forth of life through its *elan vital*. It is the vital impulse to will energy from within inert matter into life. This means that consciousness is an internal reaction to external stimuli which begins to express itself by finding a way to exist within a given environment. Accordingly, Bergsonian consciousness readily and reflexively accepts the en-framing nature of these movements since consciousness is merely reacting to what surrounds it. This reaction is the impulse to live, and an organism's evolutionary response to its environment is the pursuit of thriving or gaining greater freedom to express its will to live.⁵⁴ Importantly, this response is a *choice*: "consciousness corresponds exactly to the living being's power of choice ... [it] is synonymous with invention and freedom."⁵⁵

As an organism evolves, it gains instinctual and intellectual faculties, and these are intertwined along with consciousness; one does not lose the other faculties as they evolve. Furthermore, Bergson states that "instinct is sympathy" since it is turned "toward life" with its primary function being the gathering of habitual knowledge which is solely focused on maintaining life. Contrariwise, the intellect or intelligence is turned outwardly toward "inert matter" where it "goes all around life, taking from outside the great possible number of views of it, drawing into itself instead of entering to it."⁵⁶

⁵² *OH*, p. 22. Emphasis mine.

⁵³ See: Chapter One.

⁵⁴ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 185-191.

⁵⁵ *CE*, pp. 287-288.

⁵⁶ *CE*, p. 194.

For our present purposes, what this means is that consciousness holds within itself the willful choice to live – the initiation of the *elan vital* – and instinct is the sympathetic response toward expressing this will: where to spawn, how to stay safe, how to thrive and multiply in a given environment. The intellect, then, is the faculty to analyze, engage, and otherwise use the outward environment to one’s advantage. It does so through the sciences as well as other intellectual pursuits, but it is a highly analytical faculty that often takes its circumstances (i.e., its everydayness) as a given.⁵⁷ What Bergson argues through his dual usage of intuition (via instinct) and analysis (via intellect) is that one can gather a greater sense of one’s situatedness within the world and see the multiplicity of possibilities of that world by sensing one’s *duration* within that world. This *duration* is at once a memorial recognition of one’s temporal situatedness and also one’s personal and species-wide evolution/adaptation to this situated world.⁵⁸

Bergson argues that, far too often, pure analysis and intellect win the day within human life, often at the expense of other life – be it human or otherwise.⁵⁹ I find that Bergson’s critique of this highly scientific-calculative way of human thinking resonates with Serequeberhan’s adaptation of Heidegger’s critique of everyday thinking and its inauthenticity.⁶⁰ Both recognize the rote matter in which thinking becomes employed not for the flourishing of life, broadly construed, but for other means such as the pursuit of financial gain or power over others. This is why Serequeberhan emphasizes an initial ‘letting go’ (*Gelassenheit*) of the world in which one lives so they can see its regionality or en-framement to better recognize where other possible truths or rationalities lay.⁶¹ Similarly, this is why Bergson heavily emphasizes the need for human rationality to rediscover its sympathetic reasoning, i.e., intuition, via its intertwined faculties of consciousness, instinct, and intellect.

Sympathy may begin as an inward process of recognition, but as intuition, it can be expressed outwardly to cognitively allow a co-penetration between the perceiver and what is being perceived.⁶² He proposes this against the modernist notion that we have ‘overcome nature’

⁵⁷ *CE*, pp. 194-196.

⁵⁸ *CE*, pp. 52-53. See also: Chapter Eight, pp. 182-185, 188, 192-195, 199, 202.

⁵⁹ *TSMR*, pp. 56-64; see also: Lawler, “Asceticism and Sexuality,” pp. 153-155.

⁶⁰ Remember that we are only describing Serequeberhan’s reading of Heidegger, not ongoing Bergson-Heidegger debates. See also: *CE*, pp. 152-156; Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, p. 47.

⁶¹ See: Chapter One, pp. 8-13; Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer,” p. 48.

⁶² See: Chapter Five, pp. 97-102, 109, 112-114, 129, 139; *MM*, p. 55.

via science and culture, that he critiques as a destructive concept which also denudes oneself of their full capacity to authentically think.⁶³ In short, once we think we are above nature through concepts like ‘culture,’ ‘civilization,’ or ‘scientific reasoning,’ then we have lost the plot of who we are and thus lost a crucial portion of our faculties of expressing our *elan vital* and sensing the *duration* happening within us and amongst others.

Although they have different operations, intuition and its outward sympathy functions similarly to this notion of one consciously ‘stepping back’ (*Schritt-zurück*) and releasing oneself (*Gelassenheit*) to see their world as it readily is.⁶⁴ The similarity does not necessarily lie within the concepts themselves, but how Bergson and Serequeberhan employ them. Remember that Bergson’s initial concerns are against the way in which we mistake differences between degree and kind because we merely use analysis – and its metaphors which tend to overtake the concept in question – and thus fail to see how intuition along with analysis allows us to sense the living force of things via *duration*. Covalently, for Serequeberhan, a lived existence and its heritage are brought about through a double recognition of recognizing one’s ensnarement within a specific worldview whose logic typically benefits a specific group, and then realizing how this logic is a product of effected-historical ideologies which subdue and/or dominate one’s consciousness.⁶⁵ Concerning the latter recognition, Serequeberhan accepts that one cannot live outside of an effected-historical consciousness, but realizing this in tandem with one’s ensnarement allows for oneself to become a lived existence through discovering one’s heritage, and how together they can be employed toward personal/collective emancipation.

In both cases, Bergson and Serequeberhan are arguing for a more complete, robust logic which is relational at its core. *Duration’s* use of intuition and analysis allows one to sense their interrelatedness with the thing(s) in question or the world at large, which gives one a greater sense of themselves and their world, and how they can creatively change that world or their own constitution within that world. A lived existence via its heritage allows one to activistically engage their historical situatedness to find a greater sense of the truth between

⁶³ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 191-193; *CE*, pp. 157, 292-294. Even though Bergson rarely employs the authenticity, I think it fits here.

⁶⁴ This has been pointed out in Heidegger-Bergson scholarship (see Backman, *Complicated Presence*), but it is beyond our scope to engage in this discourse.

⁶⁵ See: Chapter Seven, pp. 191-197; *EH*, pp. 40-44.

who they are and how their world has shaped their identity, which thus allows them to see a multiplicity of horizons to find pathways toward emancipation.

This emancipation is an openness toward new ideas, new truths, and new possibilities. Also, reprising Wiredu and following Bergson, it is a moral evolution whereby a person or an open society seeks to further life's flourishing by rethinking and reframing the way in which they understand life and the world in which they inhabit. This connects the two's notion of the functions of consciousness (along with Bergsonian instinct and intellect) to the site of these evolutions and their becomings. Neither Bergsonian *duration* nor *elan vital* happen from nowhere, and neither does Serequeberhan's lived existence and its heritage just 'emerge.' There is a relational transition in both their works which spirals outward towards the landscapes of horizons since both readily accept that the space in which one lives is always already imbued with lifeworld(s) unto its own. However, as we shall see below, both expand consciousness onto placial thinking in different yet interweaving ways.

4. Conscious Places: Bergson and Serequeberhan on Thinking-with-Place

I will begin with Bergson to establish how space becomes place through the *elan vital* of the living organisms which were always already there before a person engages it. This will concretize placial thinking as a physical site of life which hermeneutic phenomenologists need to appreciate prior to their analysis. From there, I will describe the way in which Serequeberhan's notion of life's historical-memorial heritage overlays onto Bergson's cosmology. At the foundation of both descriptions is the relational, co-generative disposition of the phenomenon that is life, and how this relational logic can be employed to gather a greater sense of events which co-affect persons, communities, and places.

As covered in Chapter Eight, Bergson's *Creative Evolution* describes the ways in which life comes to being through the *elan vital*. This is a process where inert matter's stored energy expresses itself in response to its environment and thus is able to make choices for itself, thereby becoming a living organism. As Difrisko argued, this is similar to the thermodynamic account of the origin of life, where there is a relational event between acquiring/storing energy and dissipating it.⁶⁶ The key is that this dissipation is not a mere explosion of energy

⁶⁶ Difrisko, "Elan Vital Revisited," pp. 57, 67. See also: *CE*, pp. 13-15, 221-228, 235-237, 257-258.

such as a bomb, but a development of organic life which now has the capacity to interact with its environment.⁶⁷ The inspiring move Bergson makes in his description of consciousness is that it is the primary instantiation of *all living organisms* whereas many associate consciousness – especially within phenomenology – as a product of *the human self's cognition*. As seen in the prior sections, there are overlaps which do not make these accounts mutually exclusive, but what Bergson provides us with is a description of energy, life, and consciousness happening throughout the cosmos; or, more specifically, that our lifeworld is teeming with the energy of non-living matter and life of other organisms before it is even ours.

This entails that Bergsonian intellect outwardly engages either inert material, which can be an energy source, or it engages other organic life, which is possessing and acquiring energy. This latter engagement is not an isolated event, it happens within a cohabited ecosystem of living consciousnesses that take the form of different organisms, all seeking to accrue energy for survival. In that process, some organisms in this ecosystem develop instincts and intellects to sustain and creatively develop their lives in accordance with environmental changes. Furthermore, this account includes the possibility of new species entering the ecosystem.

Designating all life as consciousness and conceptualizing all matter through energy (either using it or possessing it) allows us to greater sense our *durational* relationship to the environment.⁶⁸ We need the environment for energy, but also our cultural development is co-dependent upon this environment. It is co-dependent because our habitual and true memorial negotiations with this environment create associations where we accrue meaning and understanding of ourselves, our community, the environment which both inhabit, and the world created between these three relationships. This happens between engagements with other inorganic material, lifeforms (human or otherwise), our communities which cooperate in a shared living space, and places which hold memorial significance to us.

Furthermore, by designating the concepts of instinct and intellect as creative evolutionary processes available to all species, Bergson undercuts the notion that there are levels of cognition. This is especially fruitful because it hinders those who believe that certain creatures

⁶⁷ *CE*, pp. 288-293.

⁶⁸ See: Chapter Six, pp. 129, 140; Chapter Eight, pp. 198-203; *CE*, pp. 258-260.

or persons lack the level of cognition to do philosophy or think rationally.⁶⁹ Undercutting our descriptions of cognition as levels also presents our relationality to all conscious life within the world, not just to 'other selves.' This is where I think that the 'self-other' phenomenological paradigm is found wanting: though it does take the self and others' historical and situational context into account, it rarely sees this environment as a living entity which co-effects 'the self' and 'the other' and in turn is co-effected by both.

In a similar fashion, when Wiredu discusses in his notion of culture, he notes that a person and community's language, beliefs, practices, and artefacts are products of their environment.⁷⁰ It is first an account of survival, but once this is secured then communication and moral order further develop into a culture which is positionally bound to said person and community's environment or place. Therefore, the environment is just as important to personhood as community is, and the environment is also just as important to the community as the person is. All three are co-generative and co-effected and therefore are co-relational to each other. Finally, all three are equally important to hermeneutic phenomenology.

For Bergson, the intellect's outward engagement with the environment allows persons and communities to fashion their creations. Seeing humanity as *homo faber*, as Gallagher describes it, has the double effect of indicating humans as creators fabricating from their environment but also reveals their relationship to the environment as one of usage.⁷¹ Again, this lends itself to the temptation to analytically see trees as timber and mountains as stores of minerals to be mined. However, as Serequeberhan notes via Heidegger's concept of thinking, one can realize this onto-theological rendering of the world by stepping back, letting go of the mind's race from one idea to another, and thus seeing the world as it is unto itself.

Moreover, though, Bergson likewise helps us realize that it is not just about the fabrication of the world to render it to our wills and wants, but that we need to realize our relationship to the environment is deeper than our own perception of things or entities. Importantly, it is not mere recognition of other conscious beings within that environment but also that the energy stored within inert matter has the potential for life via the *elan vital*. This is why I have

⁶⁹ See: Chapter One, pp. 4-5, 15-16.

⁷⁰ See: Wiredu, "Empiricism," pp. 22, 33; Wiredu, "Identity as an Intellectual Problem," p. 214; Wiredu, "Social Philosophy in Postcolonial Africa," p. 338; *CUP* pp. 9, 19, 21, 28, 41.

⁷¹ Gallagher, *Morality in Evolution*, pp. 47-49.

emphasized the thermodynamic nature of Bergson's work. We are related and relational to those living beings and energetic matter because all life has consciousness, and all life needs to find energy to sustain itself. From the nutrients which empower plants, to the insects which eat those plants, to the animals which eat those insects, to the animals which eat those animals, to the insects which eat those decomposing animals, to the nutrients left behind to enrich the soil that empowers plants to grow.

If we humans accept this, then the self-other paradigm delimits us to only an intellectual and analytical description of a single species – our species – and it finds meaning and understanding only within a worldhood of this singular species. 'Other species' have typically been bracketed out via the phenomenological reduction, severing the myriad ways in which they too influence how humans find meaning within their lives and environment(s). However, if we incorporate these other species and inert materials (i.e., energy, or potential species) into our phenomenology via their relationship to humanity, then we can find a pathway to broader understandings of human meaning-making and its dependence not just on the other selves, but also on one's environment.

What I am doing through Bergson is emphasizing the relationality of these aspects of place and how conscious beings – be they human or otherwise – first react to their environment via consciousness and then progress to changing their environment through instinct and, finally, through intellect. There are panoplies of consciousnesses – or extero-subjects – which may not be human but nonetheless have made this space their home, their ecosystem, their place of being. With their instincts, they do so by inwardly and sympathetically developing habitual, memorial acts which allow them to flourish in said environment; with their intellects, they do so by outwardly, analytically engaging the environment to further their understanding of it, to use it, and to develop a culture or society within it.

Yet if we employ an outward sympathy through intuition alongside our analytical intellect, we can gather a *durational* sense of how we humans *belong to this environment*; how we have changed it as it has in turn changed us. We can also outwardly sympathize with non-human consciousnesses which cohabituate this environment. Doing so requires us to relate to other organisms through the concept of consciousness, which all life has and thereby is a universal access point for hermeneutic phenomenology.

This is why I find 'thinking-with-place' is a better concept for hermeneutic phenomenology since it emphasizes the relationality between matter, organisms, and the human species. All three relationally create an environment or ecosystem which not only positions them in place, but this place becomes a site of meaning for them.⁷² Neither could a person, a community, nor a place do this by itself; all three are required for this creation of placial being and its meaning-making.

Furthermore, I find that Wiredu is correct by designating communication as the "cultural universal *par excellence*," but I think this can be extended beyond human culture. I think that how species relate to their environment – especially via consciousness – broadens this cultural universal. All species must engage their environment to find energy, safety, and to propagate. In so doing, they interact with their own kind but also with other species, which makes the pursuit of life – the *elan vital* – a cultural universal which spans beyond humanity to encapsulate all life, everywhere, and all inert matter, everywhere.

The pursuit of life is thus universal to all life, it is therefore translatable between organisms which cooperate and even those which compete against each other for energy (and perhaps safety). If we do not consider this cosmological cultural universal within our hermeneutic phenomenological analysis, then we only see the other and the world as it affects us or 'the self' – the philosopher's abstract vicar of consciousness – and not the larger picture of becoming which is being painted around us.

Bergson's description of ants and bees as having societies unto themselves is an example of 'lower' species having a sense of order, duty, and rank, all of which one could construe as a basic culture.⁷³ The 'higher' we go up the 'chain' of species – to say, wolves, elephants, or primates – the more this cultural comportment to the world is thought by 'speciesists' to

⁷² Some may object as to whether 'lower' forms of life such as amoebae have meaning, to which I argue that meaning can take on various forms and perhaps we need to reframe what we mean by meaning. Amoebae seek to reproduce, for example, and the ability to reproduce and the success of reproduction consequently is meaningful to them, even if it is at a basic, conscious level of survival. Perhaps meaning increases in importance for an organism as it evolves, but, as seen through the sympathy developed through instinct, perhaps meaning is part of creative evolution's process of surviving and adapting where organisms must find meaning in relation to their environmental circumstances so that they can process how they can live and thrive within it.

⁷³ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 195-197; *TSMR*, pp. 14, 19, 56-64; Susan Guerlac, "Bergson, The Void, and The Politics of Life," p. 46.

exert through instinct and intellect. However, all these examples indicate that cooperation and adaptation to the environment are necessary for survival in their own species-specific terms. Wiredu expounded the same point with communication between what is thought to be the 'simplest' of creatures. Translatability, here, also comes into play given that species are able to interact with other species to cooperate/compete for survival and also through similar adaptations/evolutions which various species go through.

It is important to recall, though, that Bergson is not creating a hierarchy of evolution where the development of certain faculties indicates a 'higher' functioning species, which would reductively disassociate evolution to the environment and present a predetermined or mechanistic view of life rendered by human industrialization.⁷⁴ Or, in simpler terms, it would present life as 'the more they are like us, the more advanced they are,' which misses the crucial point that all life is interrelated and co-generative.

Bergson thus provides a sound conceptualization of the relationality between life and environment. Furthering this, I have expanded upon his notion of the *elan vital* to identify how it broadens our notion of culture and society through the ways in which species cooperate/compete with each other to live and flourish.

However, recall that Bergson's earlier philosophy on *duration* has two distinct problems or disconnects with this idea of culture which must be addressed. First is his lack of a concept of 'good space,' as Addyman states it. The second is the Cartesian-like inwardness of *duration*, as Lawler points out.⁷⁵ I find that these two issues are intertwined and that Serequeberhan's hermeneutics addresses them while advancing the importance of culture's transference onto space to create places.

To address these concerns, let us quickly turn to Serequeberhan. Although Serequeberhan's concept of how an effective-historical consciousness transforms into a heritage is one of his best philosophical advances, I think his reading of Gadamerian prejudice is often overlooked but is essential for understanding why heritage matters. Prejudice is the mechanics behind

⁷⁴ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 227-229; Olivier, "The Place of African Philosophy," pp. 516-518; Olivier, "Heidegger in the Township."

⁷⁵ See: David Addyman, "Bergson's Matter and Memory," pp. 24-25; Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, pp. 62, 68-70. See also: Chapter Six, pp. 150-153.

effective-historical thinking because prejudice is the most fundamental engagement with outside matter/life. It is therefore also an integral intellectual operation within the concept of heritage. As mentioned in Chapter Seven, Gadamerian prejudice is the foundational “pre-judgement” of events happening and becoming around a person.⁷⁶ They are the core of underlying concepts which are given to a person through their community and are therefore the first movement of interpreting life as it happens.

For example, one knows the difference between a court room and a classroom when they walk into them because one has been historically conditioned to know their differences. One shares these conditions with their community whereby they collectively negotiate the meaning within these conditions.⁷⁷ These prejudices literally and figuratively allow persons to navigate their environments; in the literal sense they instrumentally indicate to persons how to get from points A to B, and in the figurative sense they instrumentally indicate the reasons why one should go from points A to B. Interpretation, for Serequeberhan via Gadamer, begins with pre-judging what one perceives and, following Wiredu’s empiricism to a degree, these pre-judgments allow one to recognize and communicate areas of harm, where food might be, where one can take shelter, whom to trust, and so forth. They instantiate a hermeneutics which is always already historically saturated with meaning, needing no Kantian transcendentals or *a priori* knowledge to comprehend them. Rather, they convey meaning from one person to another; they are the building blocks of interpretation.⁷⁸

Therefore, human perceptual pre-judgements are biological responses to one’s environment, and the key for unlocking the potential of this concept is to recognize how prejudice develops within a historicity. By so doing, one can genealogically trace how instrumental reasonings appear throughout one’s own consciousness and the collective (un)consciousness of one’s community, the latter of which has historically conditioned/effected both the event and one’s interpretation of said event. It is an inward self-recognition of one’s situatedness, which then allows one to critically engage their environment and what they perceive within it. It then allows one to take up a critical disposition so that they can question preconceived

⁷⁶ See: Chapter Seven, pp. 157-163; Serequeberhan, “Heidegger and Gadamer,” pp. 55-56.

⁷⁷ *EH*, p. xii.

⁷⁸ See: *EH*, pp. 75-76, 84; *CM*, Serequeberhan, pp. 6-7; Tsenay Serequeberhan, “Eurocentrism in Philosophy, The Case for Immanuel Kant,” *The Philosophical Forum*, 27: 4 (1996), p. 336.

interpretations of events by interrogating the effected-historical conditions operating through or behind these occurrences.⁷⁹ This questioning frees oneself from the ensnaring historicity which instrumentally frames and guides one's life, allowing them the possibility of "actuating ... the 'fusion of horizons' in and through which the acuity of understanding occurs," which happens when one perceives an event and "sieves/sifts" through the historical layers which first instigated the event and which give the event meaning or significance.⁸⁰

As the basic mechanism of consciousness' interpretation, and therefore a product of an effected-historical consciousness, prejudice is therefore the instigation of interpretive perception. It is the lens through which we initially interpret space. It begins with an infant developing object permanence (i.e., self-taught pre-judgments) and continues through a child's indoctrination within their community's culture (i.e., historical-dependent pre-judgments). As such, it is the medium through which one first perceives spatiality and renders phenomena within space into meaning.

Recalling Wiredu's argument that the Akan people only think spatially – where even metaphorical concepts correspond to given, metaphorical spaces – one can begin to see how spatiality is not just a distance but a correspondence of meaning.⁸¹ Space only 'happens' if consciousness perceives a thing to be 'there' and another to be 'here,' and it is necessary for consciousness since it allows a thing to instigate itself – a 'standing forth' or *ek-sistence* – and thus be separated from other things.

Space is therefore an interpretive event of consciousness, something that I find Bergson would readily accept. Space is not a thing unto itself, it is an interpretive designation of where events happen. It is the differentiation between things in an environment, something which allows entities to accrue meaning and understanding unto themselves. The problem Bergson held with space and/or spatiality is that this differentiation became the *primary* means through which humans understood the world.⁸² The spatial metaphors overdetermined the world in which those metaphors sought to describe. Contrariwise, space as an interpretive

⁷⁹ *HAP*, p. 26.; *EH*, pp. xii, 75. See also: Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, p. 238.

⁸⁰ *EH*, p. 80. Serequeberhan quotes from Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, p. 252. Recall that Serequeberhan often employs the word 'authentic' but vaguely defines it.

⁸¹ See: Chapter Four, p. 81-83, 85-87, 91; Chapter Six, pp. 145-149; *CUP*, pp. 49-50.

⁸² *TFW*, pp. 221-222; *MM*, p. 74; Guerlac, *Thinking in Time*, pp. 50-60, 110-115.

extension of perception becomes a dialogue or an exchange between entities (physically or metaphorically) which inhabit said space.

This happens through the representation of entities within space, or better, as Bergson argues, through the 'picture' or 'image' of reality which these perceptions become when we experience them within the flow of perception. The spatial becoming of each entity is co-effected by the other and therefore maintains a temporal, relational logic between them.⁸³ I covered this in Chapter Five but, at the risk of oversimplification, Bergson basically engages this through the historical-memorial relationships as described through his concept of *duration* rather than by redefining spatiality as independent from one's perception of the world.

The reason he does so is to rebuff his colleagues' misunderstanding of spatiality and therefore their misunderstanding of perception and meaning-making. This is why I find Bergson to be a placial thinker in that each perceptive event is one of consciousness' extensive perception, which then places onto said perception a concept or meaning. Serequeberhan's prejudice-laden, effected-historical consciousness does the same thing, albeit in a hermeneutical register: his notion of interpretation is one of living with/through/by history, recognizing the 'baggage' or instrumental reasonings within this historical context, and then sifting through this baggage to rediscover heretofore unknown truths, voices, or meanings. The task implored by Bergson and Serequeberhan is to rediscover how one relates to what one perceives, and how that relation is temporal (i.e., historical, *durational*) and thus what stands forth is a product of becoming unto itself. Both the perception of the thing and the thing's own becoming or saturation of meaning are creative processes involving multiple events which co-constitute our worldhood(s). They also were becoming before we were born, even before the human species evolved into what it is today.

Taken together, this creates a relational understanding of place as an environmental event and as a meaning-making event: Bergsonian temporality takes this up as a modality of creative evolution which is an always ongoing process from the Big Bang up until now;

⁸³ See: Chapter Five, pp. 104-107, 109, 111, 114; This dialogue is created through Bergson's notion of the "image" of reality we perceive through engaging the world, see: *MM*, pp. 7, 23-28, 50, 68, 78-79, 139; Barnard, p. 10.

Serequeberhan's historicity explores the communicative meaning of the events which led up to the temporal present or the 'nowness' we always experience. Although Bergson recognizes this meaning through deep introspection, this Cartesian-like inwardness is just an initial and necessary step for one to employ their intuition alongside analysis to sense the *duration* of oneself and their environment. If we look at *duration* as a relational logic, then it follows a similar pattern seen in Serequeberhan's 'stepping back' and 'letting go' of everyday life to see the historical-memorial negotiations which are always already ongoing within one's life and within their community's.

Furthermore, 'space,' or spatialization, becomes a medium through which one accesses *duration* (via memory) and heritage (via historical scrutiny). As a medium, space is thus politicized by its personal-communal exchange of ideas perceived through events happening all around persons and communities. Perspectives of the same event or even space changes from person to person, and the memorial-historical relationship between these persons also changes these events. Just like with time, as discussed in Conversation Two, space is just as political in that it conveys certain historical-memorial meanings to all who cohabitate or perceive that space.⁸⁴ Therefore, overlaying these concepts of politicization and meaning-making overdetermines the concept of space, which makes it difficult to describe its operative notion of differentiating between the perception of things.

This politicization of space is why the concept of place is a better notion to use within philosophy. When discussing space, many Western thinkers presume it as neutral – as an area or field – where things happen, and that these happenings are the 'political' elements of the event. However, the concept of space is a *representation* of reality, and a bad one at that. *The reason why there is no 'good space' is because recognizing that space is always already political – and thus relational between entities and events within a given area – entails that one is not speaking of space at all, but rather is speaking of place.* They are speaking about a cognitive field or a positionality (*pace* Janz), which co-effects the events happening in that area. They are speaking about the topology (*pace* Malpas) and distopology (*pace* Olivier) that is being negotiated in that area. They are speaking about the ecological and cosmological relationship between matter and organisms (*pace* Bergson) in that area. Finally, they are

⁸⁴ See: Chapter Six, pp. 146-150.

speaking about the historical and memorial layering(s) of meaningful events (*pace* Serequeberhan) in that area. *Good space is place because placiality acknowledges that no space – even metaphorical space – is without the perception or creation of consciousness and, as such, it is always already political and consequently always already moral.*

The morality component to ‘space’ may need further unpacking, which is what the next section aims to do. It does so by articulating how the designation of places, of thinking-with-space, is co-relational and interdependent upon the person and community. It will use the so-called ‘Great Man Theory’ of history as a foil to further understand how personhood, community, and place are all responsible for each other since they all call or insist upon mutual interaction and engagement with events created by all three, even events created by which do not belong to our own species.

5. The Morality of Place: Responsibility, Personhood, and Community within Placial Thinking

In Bergson and Serequeberhan’s political philosophy, there is an underlying notion that society needs special persons to either break it open or emancipate it to further realize its possibilities. For Bergson, this is the mystic or hero (or mystical hero, as I previously called it). For Serequeberhan, this is what stands out as the lived existence of a person. As seen below, while they break open societies, they also may become overdetermined and thus mutate into the oppression that they seek to eliminate. I will problematize this through the aforementioned ‘Great Man Theory’ but will reconcile the tension through repositioning the mystical hero and the lived existence within a placial, relational register. The outcome of this is to solidify the co-effected and co-generative nature of personhood, community, and place: neither can exist without the other, and thus neither can be explored without the other. The goal for this section, then, is to explore how morality or the political binds all three together, and this morality makes them co-equal to the other.

In Bergson’s thinking, societies close themselves to survive since a perpetually open society negates the ‘social’ aspect of a society and no longer functions as a cohesive structure intended for survival.⁸⁵ However, when a society becomes too closed, it denudes its impulse

⁸⁵ Susan Guerlac, “Bergson, The Void, and The Politics of Life,” p. 46; *TSMR*, pp. 14, 19, 56-65, 266; Chapter Eight, pp. 195-203.

to thrive (its socially collective *elan vital*) and it may wither away from within. This is where the mystical hero enters and questions the duties or laws which close the society from other societies or environments and, in this questioning, the mystical hero sees beyond their society's structures to present new possibilities. This presentation opens society to reconsider its inward stance to outward ideas heretofore unacknowledged, unknown, or rejected. The mystical hero, then, is someone who furthers society's flourishing but, crucially, they come *from within that society* and not as a conquering force.⁸⁶ This is why so many mystical heroes are persecuted or misunderstood in their own era.

In Serequeberhan's thinking, a lived existence is one of duty and responsibility. As mentioned above, what makes an existence *lived* is that it presses further for truth and, in so doing, cannot stand back on the sidelines of society; it must press its newfound realizations onto society for personal and collective emancipation. This is what makes Serequeberhan's lived existence different than Heidegger's notion of an authentic self, where the latter entails a disengagement from the trappings of society with only a resolute duty to care rather than a compulsion to emancipate. In this way, Serequeberhan's lived existence functions similar to Bergson's mystical hero but, the critical divergence is that Serequeberhan envisions a society where all existences are lived.⁸⁷ I find that this is what he means by social emancipation: a society of persons, aware of their effected-historical consciousness (and I would add, their pliality), and who accordingly critically engage their situatedness to further discover and evolve their heritage as an act of personal and collective determination.

Yet becoming a lived existence is not easy. As Serequeberhan highlights throughout *Our Heritage*, there are a select few people who achieve this realization, and those people are guideposts for the rest of us. These persons are presented as heroes, if you will, of decolonial emancipation and thus are worthy of emulation for our own becoming into lived existences. The end result is that the difficulty of becoming a lived existence is similar to the difficulty of becoming a mystical hero: both require a great deal of introspection, both carry similar

⁸⁶ *TSMR*, pp. 52-53, 63-64, 212-221; White, "The Politics of Sympathy," p. 59.

⁸⁷ *EH*, pp. 118-119.

burdens to society, both are risky to the person who carries this burden since they lend themselves to social persecution.⁸⁸

I raise this to note that there is a liability with placing such burden on a singular person. It lends itself to a messianic notion where we wait for a hero to emerge, often haphazardly appointing heroes which reflect our own ideals. The latter point would lead us back to inauthentic thinking, for Serequeberhan, and its onto-theological gesture of approving the status quo.⁸⁹ This where I raise the 'Great Man Theory' theory as a foil to reveal the collective and relational character of mystical heroes and lived existences. This idea of a Great Man resides throughout Western thought but was crystalized within early Modernity by Thomas Carlyle who argued that heroes come to the fore to shape history, or one could argue, open and emancipate society. As he summarizes it:

For, as I take it, Universal History, the history of what man has accomplished in this world, is at the bottom the History of the Great Men who have worked here. They were the leaders of men, these great ones; the modelers, patterns, and in a wide sense creators, of whatsoever the general mass of men contrived to do or to attain; *all things that we see standing accomplished in the world are properly the outer material result, the practical realization and embodiment, of thoughts that dwelt in the Great Men sent into the world: the soul of the whole world's history, it may justly be considered, were the history of these [Great Men].*⁹⁰ (Emphasis mine)

At the risk of oversimplification but to narrow my point, does this not sound like a mystical hero or a lived existence? Someone who enters into the world and *molds and shapes it* to progress this history of 'men' in some way? In a sense, these 'creators' seemingly stand above history or the world to then shape it into their own image. Doing so at a remove (*Schritt-zurück*) and releasing themselves (*Gelassenheit*) from the world, or through deep introspection (*via duration*) away from the world. This notion of objectivity and the creation of history has been thoroughly debunked by numerous philosophers and historians, most notably by Peter

⁸⁸ Tsenay Serequeberhan, "Heidegger and Gadamer," p. 59; *CM*, p. 115; Lawler, *The Challenge of Bergsonism*, pp. 62-68.

⁸⁹ See: Chapter One, pp. 8-10, 19; Chapter Seven, pp. 155, 161-167; *HAP*, pp. 132; *EH*, pp. 92-93, 105-110.

⁹⁰ Thomas Carlyle, *On Heroes, Hero-Worship, and the Heroic in History*, Micheal K. Goldberg, Joel J. Brattin, Mark Engel, eds. (Berkeley: California UP, 1993), p. 3. See also: Paul .E Kerry, Marylu Hill, *Thomas Carlyle Resartus: Reappraising Carlyle's Contribution to the Philosophy of History, Political Theory, and Cultural Criticism* (Madison: Fairleigh Dickinson UP, 2010).

Novik. Yet its legacy remains, especially in discussions about leadership or concerning the objectivity of history and the hard sciences.⁹¹

For our purposes, this brief description cantilevers the utopic version one may have of the mystical hero or lived existence. *Utopic* being the operative word: a universal and thus univocal vision of the next region of truth, a singular decision of which path to take after seeing the possibilities set upon the horizons hereby fused. In short, there is nothing new about the idea of a messianic figure who opens or emancipates a community or society. This is obvious given the various messianic figures within religion, but philosophically, it is also present within the very effected-historicity which ensnares the oppressed. The oppressors too have their messiahs who approve and instigate oppression. Lest we forget that John Cecil Rhodes was once considered a paragon of the Great Man, the same very man whose colonial fist hammered Southern Africa through his British South African Company.⁹²

However, if we view the mystical hero or lived existence through a placial lens, what arises is their relationship to their own community, and therefore their becoming persons of that community. Returning to the notion that persons become persons through their social-political engagements with their community, the relational character of this becoming grounds a person to their historico-cultural situatedness. If this is the case, and as argued in Conversation One, then their personhood is qualitative; meaning that one's character rises and falls from the esteem one gathers in their communal engagements.⁹³ This makes a person responsible for their actions, thereby revealing how each action is always already moral given that it happens in a socio-political framework.

These social interactions and their implications are no different than a person's engagement with their habitat. They gather their sense of place through spatial-temporal interactions where they feel either welcomed and at home or unwelcomed and displaced depending on *where* these interactions take place. In Conversation Two, we noted the temporality of this politics and morality, emphasizing how chronopolitics influences our sense of *duration* and

⁹¹ There are obviously multiple examples of this, but for an overview, see: Chukwuemeka Nnachi Oko-Uto, Chukwudi Godwin Chidume; "Objectivity and the Great Man Theory in Historiography," *Cogito*, 13:3 (2021), pp. 124-138; Brian Wolfel, *Thomas Carlyle and the Political Universe: From American Transcendentalism to an Elusive Post-Liberalism* (New York: Lexington Books, 2024).

⁹² John Newsinger, "Why Rhodes Must Fall," *Race and Class*, 58:2 (2016), pp. 70-78.

⁹³ See: Chapter Three, pp. 54-59, 62-63, 68-69.

also our sense of historicity.⁹⁴ Concerning our present conversation, though, the pliality, the ‘where’ of these engagements reveals how we sense the spatial distance between the physical and abstract place of where we are and where we want to be. How we want to change society is just as much a plial matter as it a historico-temporal one.

For instance, and to return to John Cecil Rhodes, during the 2015 #feesmustfall movement in South Africa, a #rhodesmustfall offshoot developed where the University of Cape Town (UCT) students demanded the removal of a statue of Rhodes on campus.⁹⁵ They demanded this because, for many Black, Coloured, and Indian students, it was a haunting reminder of how their ancestors and heritage were oppressed or obliterated by Rhodes’ companies and the pro-colonial, anti-indigenous, racist ideologies he lionized.⁹⁶

I find that this shows how this ‘Great Man’ and his legacy was a miasma which was not merely an abstract plague upon UCT students, but also a concrete, plial one. The statue was a *memorial*, a reminder of the man and an honorific of his deeds, which signaled to many students that they were not welcomed or at home on campus. In Olivier’s framework, they were displaced or were living a distopological experience on campus.⁹⁷ In Malpas’ framework, their topology as the ‘free generation’ of South Africans of color (dis)conjoined with UCT. This created a clash between the university – as plial concept and what political ideologies are carried through its existence in that place – and these students whose effected-historical positionality called into question the worldhood in which they participated with UCT’s ideological-historical legacy.⁹⁸ For Janz, in concert with Olivier and Malpas, their pliality raised the question of what is it to be a student of color in this erstwhile colonial place which chose to ignore (and thus maintain) its colonial culture rather than reform it.⁹⁹ For all three, the entire situation is one of territorialization and what it means to inhabit a place, particularly

⁹⁴ See: Chapter Six, pp. 115-121, 123-126, 147.

⁹⁵ See: Justin Sands, “Why Read the West? Messianicity and Canonicity within a Postcolonial South African Context” in *Who Is an African? Race, Identity and Destiny in Post-apartheid South Africa*, Roderick R. Hewitt, Chammah J. Kaunda, eds. (Minneapolis: Fortress Academic Press), pp. 275-276, 280-284; Paul Maylam, *The Cult of Rhodes* (Cape Town: David Philip, 2005), p. 12.

⁹⁶ Antje Daniel, Josh Platzky Miller, “Imagination, Decolonization, and Intersectionality: The #RhodesMustFall Student Occupation in Cape Town, South Africa,” *Social Movement Studies* 23:4 (2024), pp. 495-516.

⁹⁷ See: Olivier, “Place and Displacement,” pp. 33, 35-39; 45-46.

⁹⁸ See: Malpas, *Heidegger’s Topology*, pp. 2, 35, 219, 297-301.

⁹⁹ See: Bruce Janz, “Philosophy as if Place Mattered,” in *What Philosophy Is*, Havi Carel, David Gomez, eds. (London: Continuum, 2004), pp. 111-115.

one that is at best indifferent to those who inhabit it (and at worst, oppressive to their mere presence).

Deploying Serequeberhan's and Bergson's thinking, I think that there is a communal and relational register that helps us explore how the students felt and then reacted through protest: they came together in solidarity to requestion the colonial historico-cultural politics of UCT and, in Janz' words, deterritorialized their campus. This required a community and was not the product of one 'man,' and it also required a passionate resistance to the distopological imposition placed upon the student body by actors who sought to keep Rhodes' statue for the sake of 'history,' or what have you. It was, therefore, a personal-communal act of negotiation (including both the protestors and those upholding the status quo) about what this given place is, what it should be, and whose heritage it represents.

To clarify, the demand for the removal of the statue was a political act, but it was also a placial one. It was a change in the environment, the place in which these students lived and worked, and importantly it was a personal-communal act. Individual persons demanded this removal, but in so doing they formed their own community of resistance which influenced the larger community. There was no singular mystic, hero, or lived existence which did this, it was a collective effort arising from a larger movement (#feesmustfall) which was addressing the colonial historico-cultural *place* that is the South African university.

Returning to Bergson's notion of the environment, the students changed the space in which they lived, turning it into a 'good space' via their placial imprint upon it. Furthermore, following Serequeberhan, they were not deleting history, but were rather rediscovering it, uncovering the silent voices crushed by Rhodes whilst also establishing their own place within their local communal heritage, as well as South Africa's writ large. They were not members of Steve Biko's South African Students' Organisation (SASO) of the 1960's, but they carried on his Black Consciousness and lived their heritage through protesting the statue's physical existence on campus.¹⁰⁰

This change in the environment reveals several phenomenological factors at play. It was personal and communal in that these persons engaged their community's historical norms

¹⁰⁰ Steve Biko, *I Write What I Like*, A Stubbs, ed. (London: Heinemann), pp. 4-5.

and associations, many of which were either instrumentally buried or just merely ignored. In so doing, they challenged and changed their communities while realizing that there may be a better UCT with new possibilities heretofore unseen now that the haunted haze of Rhodes' presence on campus no longer hovered. It was physical and spatial given that their perception of the statue was a social-memorial indicator that UCT's management either never thought about what his presence meant to their changing student body or, worse, they knew exactly what it meant and wanted to send a message to incoming students.

In more technical terms, this physical-spatial presence and its politically laden symbolism is best understood through a placial thinking which brings its presenting existence into a relational register between person and community. The space inhabited by the statue was topologically a conjunction of ideologies which forged the university, its campus, and the country. It was saturated with history – both good and bad – and the best access we have to understanding its significance is through the relationship between personhood and community.

Returning to this section's questioning of the Great Man problem, I think that what separates mystical heroes and lived existences from the Great Men of old is that the mystical heroes and lived existences now recognize that change requires conditions to happen. Those conditions are built up by persons challenging and questioning their community's beliefs and ideas, but they also challenge and question the environment in which their personhood is enacted. These tripartite negotiations are constantly ongoing – they either affirm, adapt, or reject established and institutionalized ideologies – and sometimes can open society to new ideas or reaffirm and close society to the ones they currently hold. In either case, the place in which these negotiations happen matters just as much as the persons/communities having them: whether it is on campus at UCT and what that signifies, or in parliament, or at a family gathering.

6. Final Analysis: Relational Hermeneutic Phenomenology as *Contra Ex Nihilo*

Persons and communities do not come from nowhere, and neither just exist without a place to exist. The same should be said about places: they do not happen from nowhere, they are built and changed just as persons and communities are. Their histories and meanings are socially taught to us, and we employ our prejudices to navigate through these political

instrumentations and those organisms which exist within their place of sovereignty or influence. These organisms include all species, not just humans. Our sense of historicity endows a place with meaning – sometimes sacred meaning – and our preservation of that meaning is a political act, and as our discontinuation is also a political act, as seen via #rhodesmustfall. What grounds our understanding of persons, communities, and places, is therefore our continual interaction through and with them. Neither is above the other nor is one without the other, they spiral out into the world – creating and innovating the possibilities of that world – as we live, as we act and interact with each of the other.

These actions have consequences, which is what makes them moral acts (or political acts, if you prefer). Therefore, and finally, all interactions are moral consequences and the world constituted by us, before us, and after us, is a sedimented layering of actions taken by species unforeseen and by persons we may never know. The task of discovering and living a heritage, as well as the task of sensing the *communal duration* between ourselves and environment in which we inhabit, is therefore a moral task of deciding what we want to create, what world will become in that creation, and taking responsibility for what we have helped create.

What I have found within this conversation between Serequeberhan and Bergson is how deeply interrelated these three concepts – person, community, place – are. As such they need to be equally considered when we perform a hermeneutic phenomenological analysis. I will detail this in the oncoming conclusion to this book, but from the above, this conversation elevates our understanding of meaning-making by detailing the interrelated nature between consciousness and placiality. Here, places are not historical facts, they are more like living legacies, legacies which include life before we even were there to designate and name the place. Life that spans species and histories.

Acknowledging this fact is important to arrive at a more thorough hermeneutic analysis, but it is also crucial to understanding our moral anthropology on personal-communal levels. Knowing that our acts within our habitat co-effect not just other persons, but also other societies (be they other species or other communities, or even past and future communities) deepens the responsibility of becoming a lived existence or a just a good person. Let alone the mystical hero!

It forces us to realize that the fusion of horizons of our own cultural-intellectual possibilities do not just metaphorically appear as regions of truth but rather are landscapes. Above and below the horizon-line exists life we may never know, and our acts in some way will reverberate through the *communal duration* that is the past, present, future-past, and future beyond our existence. Who we esteem, who we remember, who we forget, who we engage, all these acts change the very environment of our community. They influence the lives of other species and their societies, of how they co-exist and co-generate meaning for the entire ecosystem, for the entire cosmos.

This is because acts have moral consequence – however benign – so the way we treat the lives of others is the way in which we treat the source of that life, meaning the grounded land and its living, cosmological historicity. Knowing this concretizes the burden of the fusion of horizons and its future of possibilities. It is the burden of knowing that becoming must become from some-where, has to become from some-time; it is becoming here, is becoming now. How we adapt to creatively further, hinder, or otherwise change these becomings is a personal-communal act that manifests itself within the places we create to enact our responses to the environment given to us, created by others. As with all conscious beings and those yet to possess it, we are left to choose, to decide what our response will be.

**CONVERSATIONS IN CONFERENCE: ON PERSONHOOD, COMMUNITY,
AND PLACE**

CHAPTER TEN:
DISCOURSES *IN MEDIAS RES*:
TOWARDS A RELATIONAL HERMENEUTIC PHENOMENOLOGY

1. Introduction

This book set itself on arguing the thesis that a human becomes a person through their communal engagements over time, and this engagement manifests itself in space and, through their historical-memorial negotiations, both the person and their community transform space into particular places. In pursuit of arguing this thesis, I sought to press it further by asking, what are its implications if brought into conversation with Western philosophy, and specifically hermeneutic phenomenology?

Interestingly, I decided that bringing this into conversation with hermeneutic thinkers such as Richard Kearney and Paul Ricoeur – amongst others – would only lead to an adversarial-style engagement. One where the typical ‘crisis-and-answer’ approach is taken, such as when an author first presents a critique against some idea or person, thereby presenting a ‘crisis’ which can be solved by said author’s new approach or idea. I like to call this a ‘clear away and present’ approach, and it is often employed within Continental philosophy and particularly within phenomenology. One can see this approach within Heidegger, Levinas, and even the early work of Paul Ricoeur. It has even been a format for articles with much tighter scopes than mine, where the author critiques another’s reading of a great thinker to present or address a lacuna within extant scholarship. It has its place within philosophy, but I do not think that it should be the only means by which we do philosophy.

Rather than spending half of this work critiquing the ‘deficiencies’ or ‘problematics’ within hermeneutic phenomenology or Western philosophy in general, I decided that my aims would

prove more successful with a different, essayistic approach. That is, an approach where I examine another pathway to understanding subjectivity and personhood, and then detailing its possible implications for the future of hermeneutic phenomenology. This, I believe, presents an alternative foundation of premises from which to begin such an analysis.

This is why I chose the Conversational Method to be my organizing principle. By bringing thinkers like Serequeberhan, Wiredu, and Bergson into conversation, I was able to present my own reading of each author and then bring that reading into conversation with another author's ideas while avoiding synthesizing each thinker into an amalgam of contradictory ideas. The lack of synthesizing is important. To synthesize each author would mean domesticating their thinking. I would have to smooth out, clear away, or somehow resolve the tensions between each author and, in so doing, I would have missed the very valid points each author was making. Rather than doing this, I tried to allow these arising tensions to become sites of reflection and inspiration. There was no 'winner' in these conversations, nor was there a creation of a newer, better idea; the tensions exist because they give rise to thought. Within a conversational approach, I believed that the tensions may resonate and disclose stronger insights that resolving them could not – or would not – reveal.

As mentioned in my Introduction, this entails that each chapter 'speaks' on its own while building my argument for a relational hermeneutic phenomenology. This is why there are so many cross-references in my footnotes, which function similarly to an actual conversation where one makes points, circles back to them, revises them in conversation with others, and then reaches some form of mutual understanding with their conversation partners. This understanding does not have to be complete agreement; it is rather a consensual understanding which respects the others' point of view and their ideas.

Surprisingly, my use of the Conversation School of Philosophy's method yielded a surprising and exciting dynamic: one could possibly read these three conversations in any order that one chooses, which may give rise to new interpretations of the overall work. It presents my overarching argument quite well, given that one can begin their analysis from either personhood, community, or place and, in doing so, find new or at least slightly different insights. In what follows, I will more straightforwardly present and connect these conversations, showing how they both argue my thesis and its broader, hermeneutic phenomenological implications.

Accordingly, the ensuing section will review how each chapter contributes to arguing my primary thesis. The penultimate section will then explore the implications of this thesis and how it presents a possible relational hermeneutic phenomenology. In this section, I will provide a brief description of what I think this relational hermeneutic phenomenology is. However, I will save an in-depth description of this new method for future works since it needs to be more thoroughly described, more than one can do in a concluding essay. What I have offered within this book is the mechanics behind this different approach which I hope becomes a foundation for others to engage in a relational logic and thus a relational hermeneutics. As such, my final words will be areas for future research and where I see these developments going forward. In sum, I personally cannot create such a method on my own; it will have to be a communal effort, as all relational thought is, and it is my hope that I have provided an area of inquiry worthy of that effort.¹

2. Relationality: Becoming a Person, Community, and Place

As I covered in my Introduction, I chose Tsenay Serequeberhan, Kwasi Wiredu, and Henri Bergson because I saw a different, relational pathway to understanding becoming within their work.² I did not notice until I began outlining my argument that each thinker's primary ideas *are in tension with themselves*, which provides an intellectual force to their becoming. Or, in other words, that each thinker brought to the fore two interconnected ideas which emphasize their relationality. For Serequeberhan, it was a lived existence and heritage; for Wiredu, it was his cultural universals and how they craft particular social epistemologies and consequent cultures; for Bergson, it was his notions of *duration* and *elan vital*. It was then that I realized that I could bring these thinkers into a discussion by presenting one concept of each thinker in conversation with another's covalent concept. Through this framework, I was able to more coherently present the relational, becoming nature of these thinkers' ideas because it gave access points to their work while showing how they can inform and engage others' ideas in a fruitful manner.

I began with Serequeberhan to establish where one begins philosophizing. Knowing that we are always already thinking *in medias res*, I questioned, '*in whose medias res are we thinking?*'

¹ Since this is a summative, concluding essay, I will only mention the chapter from which my summaries come. Citing otherwise could possibly entail rewriting the entire work.

² See: Introduction, pp. ii-vii.

I did this by focusing on Serequeberhan's decolonial impetus and his notion of a lived existence. His response to the ways in which the West has historically and categorically denied the rationality of other cultures was the strongest access point for me to engage in how one begins to think philosophically (or beyond the everydayness of existing within a globalized world) and how this changes one's sense of personhood or, if you prefer, one's self-identity. His notion of a lived existence was one where the person became self-aware of the ways in which everyday life en-frames (*Ge-stell*) the ways in which one thinks, and therefore the epistemic enclosures delimiting one's thinking. Through Heidegger and Gadamer, Serequeberhan shows us how one can recognize this process, disclosing new regions of truth and therefore new horizons which can be fused together to disclose new possibilities for oneself and one's community. Importantly, though, this existence is *lived*. Meaning, it must not resolutely hold onto these possibilities, one's self-awareness compels one to engage their community in pursuit of these potential emancipatory, liberative possibilities.

After establishing this as a prospective foundation through which one could think about themselves, their community, and their worldhood at large, I then turned to Wiredu's communal logic. Wiredu argues that the human species has two communal universals which allows it to survive: the universal need to communicate and some form of the Golden Rule; the latter meaning some form of respectful engagement where one treats others as they want to be treated. These universals describe how humans co-exist as a social species and, eventually, how they develop particular epistemologies which lead to communally held languages and cultures. It is through these language-cultures that one obtains personhood through two things: First, these language-cultures are employed by the community to define what a person is. Second, these language-cultures are employed by the community to grant personhood to others through said person's interaction with others. Here, I argued that Wiredu is presenting was a moral anthropology. It was an anthropology since it described how the human species survived and then developed particular cultures, and it was moral since it described how these cultures employ social esteem – adjudicated through personal-communal interaction – to attribute personhood to others.

Note that 'moral,' here, is not about being 'good' or 'bad;' it is not moral in the typical sense of the word. Rather, it is an acknowledgement that all actions – even thinking – happen within a given world and is imbued with cultural and epistemic consequences. Nothing happens in a

silos or unto itself. Even if an act is done in private, the act is informed by the cultural conditions of possibility provided to the actant via their language-culture. For example, even sitting holds a moral component since this behavior is informed by how one sits and where one sits. Each language-culture has its own way of defining sitting: do you sit on the floor, lotus position, or do you sit in a chair, with legs crossed or uncrossed? Each language-culture has its own means of judging the places where one sits: do you take the front seat of the table, or is that reserved for the most esteemed person within the group? Do you sit behind the desk – indicating authority – or do you sit in front of the desk? Do you sit in front of the bus or in the back, and what does it mean to sit in the back of the bus? For the last question, this is especially pertinent to those marginalized within their communities, such as American Blacks in the Jim-Crow era South, or Blacks and Non-Whites in Apartheid-era South Africa.

One could argue that these are *political* acts and not moral ones, and I have pointed out that Wiredu is often murky about the demarcation of the moral and the political.³ However, from my reading of his cultural universals, the Golden Rule is a conceptually moral position which means that it, in tandem with communication, gives rise to a politics which is understood by the person and their community through their particular language-culture. In short, if we take Wiredu at his word, we see that morality helps establish the political negotiations that develop within a given culture. Therefore, Wiredu's sense of morality gets expressed and defined within the politics of a given culture. This is why he speaks of an ethics which is delineated through a culture's ethic. The ethic, in tandem with translation between languages, can only be compared with other cultures' ethic because each stem from the same universal need for an ethics, or the Golden Rule articulated through communication.

The question I sought to address when bringing Serequeberhan and Wiredu into conversation at this juncture was about the subjectivity and agency of a person within a communal framework. As I pointed out in Chapter Three, my first Conversation Chapter, an overriding concern by several Western thinkers is how one has agency within a communitarian framework. For me, the question itself was not the priority, but rather what presuppositions the question brought with it: what is the relationship between agency, subjectivity, and a communal logic? I read and presented Serequeberhan and Wiredu as relational thinkers who

³ See: Chapter Two, pp. 36-37.

emphasized the nature of becoming; whether that is becoming a lived existence or a person within one's community (and what type of person one is esteemed to be). Also, as Wiredu mentions, this relates to the intellectual evolution of our species as the collective becoming of communities in consensus with each other.⁴

Through a conversation between Serequeberhan and Wiredu, I argued that both speak about an intellectual and personal responsibility for oneself and to others. One must take responsibility for their truth claims and what they represent or justify, and one must take responsibility for actions and what they consequentially signify to others. Responsibility thus shows a linkage between Serequeberhan's lived existence and Wiredu's moral anthropology; each concept relies upon standing forth (*ek-sistence, pace* Serequeberhan) to be called into account for one's beliefs and actions. It is a relational accounting given that the person being reckoned with by their community is, in turn, challenging or upholding their community's epistemological, cultural beliefs and norms, especially concerning their community's sense of justice and law. This entails a personal-communal negotiation which influences a language-culture's belief system. As such, it influences what the person and the community see as true, just, and/or acceptable. It is a co-effected relationship since both the person and the community influence each other, establish the possibilities of the others' actions and beliefs, and furthers each other's understanding of ways in which to act and think.

The example I gave was the father's relationship to their child, and vice versa. This is a relationship that is culturally defined, and the father's treatment/relationship with their child is judged by the community.⁵ A father (or child) could challenge the community's notion of fatherhood or even who can be a 'father.' It could uphold the community's cultural understanding of fatherhood, challenge this understanding, or be accommodating by critiquing this understanding while upholding certain cultural values in a compromising, consensus-forming fashion. Regardless, this relationship is defined by the socio-culture in which it exists, and the subjective agency of the father within this relationship reveals or informs us of the father and their sense of personhood (and the same for the child in this relationship).

⁴ See: Chapter Three, pp. 60-63.

⁵ See: Chapter Two, pp. 37-38; Chapter Three, pp. 63-64; Chapter Five, pp. 101-102, 105, 112, 121-122.

What Serequeberhan's lived existence brings to this negotiation is the possibility to see how this language-culture, and its co-effected relationship between persons and community, defines possibilities. Again, what separates 'Serequeberhan's Heidegger,' if you will, is that it has a responsibility to push one's sense of self and one's community's collective sense of identity and culture to heretofore unforeseen possibilities.⁶ This push is in pursuit of a more emancipated, more liberative sense of truth and justice. Yet this emancipation is not between oneself and their community, it is an emancipation *of both oneself and their community* from harmful yet established cultural norms, rules, and the epistemologies which justify these norms and rules. It is an emancipation set on furthering both person and community toward new possibilities, which again returns to responsibility for each other and the ways in which that responsibility is enacted through a language-culture's epistemic truth claims and assumptions.

This led me to further examine the epistemic nature of personhood and community in the next conversation where I explored Wiredu's empiricism in relation to Bergson's *duration*. In Chapter Four, I explored the spatialized nature of Wiredu's empiricism and how it eschews an immanent/transcendent distinction.⁷ Importantly, it does so in the same way as Wiredu's notion of morality eschews the typical definition of morality within Western culture and languages. Wiredu's cultural universals provided us with an account of how each human has the *capability* to learn and understand the world, and his account of cultural particulars provided us with an account of how they learn about the world through the culture in which they inherit. In so doing, it also provided us with an account of how this capability is expressed through *encounter*. One does not know or cannot understand what one has yet to encounter, but one can gather experience of others' encounters to inform one's own understanding of the thing or event in question.⁸ However, in either case, one cannot learn or further their understanding of the world alone. They must either engage in the broader world or listen and learn from others who have. This describes encounter and its capacity to transfer understanding (or at least information) through a relational event, which opens persons and

⁶ See: Chapter One, pp. 12-16.

⁷ Chapter Four, pp. 75, 83, 85; Chapter Six, pp. 127-131.

⁸ See: Chapter Four, pp. 79-80, 83-86, 87-90.

communities to further conceptualize their worldhood. It also describes how a community can engage other communities to find further understanding and possible developments.⁹

I brought Bergson into this conversation since the event of these encounters must happen within time, and I thought his notion of *duration* could elucidate the relationality of these happenings. What was important to me was not merely adding a notion of temporality to these events, but to better understand the importance of memory (both personal and social) and, consequently, the political nature of these events. They happen in time, yes, but I found that Bergson's *duration* allowed us to further see how these events are always already politically laden. This would prove important later when I explore the sedimented layering of histories and events which comprises Serequeberhan's notion of heritage. For now, though, *duration* provided two important descriptions: first, his use of intuition as a methodological component to understanding what is being transferred or negotiated within these events. Second, how one employs memory via *duration* to comport the perception of these events into knowledge and/or understanding, and thus into new memories.

Bergson highlights how our notions of time are laden with the problematics of assuming we know what time is merely through analysis. This opens us to mistaking the metaphorical language used to describe time for the concept of time itself, and therefore, mistaking the degrees of temporality (a foundation to *duration*) by imposing analytical categories onto time which are built from these metaphorical mistakes. His notion of intuition allows one to sympathetically sense the relationality between oneself and what one is perceiving, which then opens one to sense the ways in which we memorially engage what we perceive. This allows us to see the co-effected nature of perception, where the perceiver employs a sympathetic intuition alongside empirical analysis to gather a notion of how temporality is a creative process of encountering the outside world. A process which perpetuates understanding through living with the world and of what one comprises that world to be made. Accordingly, *duration* describes how we live with prior events and experiences through memories and how this informs our current engagements with phenomena. As I mentioned in Chapter Five, the ways in which myself and my community have lived and continue to with the Vietnam war is a strong example of this.

⁹ Chapter Two, 38-42; Chapter Four, pp. 83-89.

From this, in Chapter Five and in conversation with Wiredu in Chapter Six, I proposed the idea of a *communal duration*, which describes the socio-political nature of memory and its perception of temporality. Temporality is not philosophically innocent, and I argued this through Charles Mills' chronopolitics as well as Keletso Atkins' recounting of the Zulu-British clash with conceptually understanding time.¹⁰ My overall point was that *communal duration* represents the temporal flow of a culture gathering its epistemology, justice, and other expressive forms of understanding through said culture's encounters. Those encounters could be within the culture's community, between other cultures, or the environment. They can be either internal engagements or outward ones.¹¹ Through a *communal duration*, I argued that we are more equipped to sympathetically understand the evolution of a person and their culture's sense of identity, justice, language, and interconnected beliefs. In short, a *communal duration* helps us describe and understand how a community manifests itself through temporal engagements and negotiations writ large and how past engagements inform present and future ones through socio-political memories taught through traditions, languages, and other aspects of culture. Furthermore, *communal duration* describes the ongoing, interpenetrating nature of this manifestation and how it happens in some given time, which implies it must happen in some given place which formed the basis of my third and final conversation.

To unpack how these temporal-memorial findings influence our individual and collective sense of identity, I turned to Serequeberhan's concept of heritage in my Seventh Chapter. Here, I analyzed how Serequeberhan's concept of heritage and its sense of activism, which links it to a lived existence, is based upon his reading of Gadamer's 'effected-historical consciousness' (*wirkungsgeschichtliches Bewusstsein*). To summarize, what I found was that Serequeberhan's reading of our historicity is born out of process: First, our prejudices, which are handed down to us via culture or procured by us through personal experiences, allow us to conceptualize what we are currently perceiving (similar to Bergson's notion of true and habit memory). Second, these prejudices inform our present actions and, by acknowledging this, we can gather a sense of how we are historically situated.¹² By knowing our historical situatedness, we can better understand the ways in which our thinking and doing have been

¹⁰ See: Chapter Five, pp 117-119.

¹¹ See: Chapter Six, pp. 121-124.

¹² See: Chapter Seven, pp. 157-159, 161, 164-166, 170.

shaped by the historical-memorial conditions in which we are situated. Finally, through this acknowledgement, we can step back and see the possibilities of other constructs heretofore hidden from us or generally unknown to us.

In this latter stage, we see Serequeberhan employing Gadamer's notion of a fusion of horizons as a site or regionality of truth and understanding, which may be more emancipatory or liberating than the horizons upon which we currently gaze.¹³ This is a process describing how a lived existence comes to be and furthers the reasons why such an existence needs to press its community toward these possibly more emancipatory horizons: If one is historically situated and one cannot live outside of historicity, then one brings along with them the conditionalities of the culture from whence they came. If that is so, then the more emancipatory gesture is in service of others, thereby bringing them to the vista to see the horizons of new possibilities.

Yet these horizons have landscapes. They are seen from a vantage point, from some *where* and, to return to Wiredu, from some point in space. To gather a sense of these landscapes and how they are just as pivotal to us as the horizons themselves, I turned to Bergson's *elan vital*. Through the *elan vital*, I was able to understand and articulate the ways in which the human species is still interconnected to its environment. By exploring how the vital impulse which wills energetic expression from matter – i.e., how life comes to be – I was able to argue how consciousness is not a product of the mind, but a product of the creative will to life. I articulated Bergson's tripartite notions of consciousness, instinct, and intellect to describe the ways in which creative evolution is a co-effected event whereby an organism engages its environment to establish a habitat or an area to live and survive. In so doing, these engagements necessitate developments (or evolutions) which allow an organism to either challenge, accept, or adapt to whatever is happening around them.

This exploration also informed me of the ways in which *duration* is a sensation not just of temporality, but also of life's expression of itself as it perceives and engages the environment which surrounds it. As such, once survival is reasonably secured, then an organism's creative expression of this life can further develop by intellectually engaging its surroundings.¹⁴ Here,

¹³ See: Chapter Seven, pp. 159-167.

¹⁴ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 178-179, 180-184, 186-191.

especially concerning humanity and other pack species, one can see how the intellect builds off collected habits or instincts to organize their life and give it order. For humans, at least, this order also becomes a pathway for establishing epistemologies and meaningfulness. This harkens back to Wiredu's cultural universals and their necessity for survival, out of which cultural particulars develop in pursuit of a more fruitful life past mere endurance.¹⁵

Yet Bergson cautions that humans seem to have gone too far in their intellectual pursuits; to the point that they often see themselves as above the creaturely environment from whence they came. They seek mastery and command over their surroundings, seeing things in the same way that Serequeberhan critiqued as scientific-calculative thinking, where one only acknowledges the use value of things rather than appreciating the things unto themselves.¹⁶ Bergson's concerning critique does not necessarily entail a 'return to nature,' for the *homo faber* within humanity is already way too entrenched, and even if it were possible to shed away, humanity is still historically and culturally situated in the present moment, which it has created. Rather, Bergson calls us to sense the *duration* within our relationship to all the life-energy which surrounds us. Similar to a lived existence, *duration* allows one to better sense the interconnected nature of things and the ways in which those things became themselves and are continuously becoming on their creatively evolving path.¹⁷ Although some scholars do not link this sense of *duration* to Bergson's *elan vital*, nor to his sense of the political and the moral, I found it a fruitful linkage to comprehend his broader argument.¹⁸ It also allowed an access point to bring him in conversation with Serequeberhan on how persons and communities manifest themselves in particular places.

Before delving into this conversation, I thought it was important to describe placial thinking as it is understood within contemporary philosophical discourses. Although many of my commentary on these discourses, especially within the West, were broad generalizations to give foils to my interlocutors, I thought it was essential to explore this emerging philosophy in depth to help connect my work to ongoing discussions. It is here, at placial thinking, where I believe my thesis holds its greatest contribution since it shows that placiality is necessary to understand how a person becomes a person through community, and why this understanding

¹⁵ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 195-197.

¹⁶ See: Chapter One, pp. 8-10, 19; Chapter Nine, pp. 219, 225, 230, 235, 248.

¹⁷ See: Chapter Five, pp. 95-100, 104-109; Chapter Eight, pp. 179-184, 188-190, 198-200.

¹⁸ See: Chapter Eight, pp. 177.

matters. It matters more than just a different means to describe identity or what we call the self. This description at once reveals the interconnectivity between persons and communities as one which transforms space into meaningful sites laden with history and memories while also describing the ways in which these becomings are part of a larger socio-historical context that involves other species within an ecosystem in which we proclaim to be our habitat. What this does is open us to consider the concept of 'place' as something beyond context, as an ongoing and living event which came before us and will persist after us. In so doing, it will carry with it the historical-memorial negotiations between organisms and the environment (or, pace Bergson, the creative evolutions which have happened at this site). This entails that we should consider the concept of place unto itself, as a third entity which is co-effected by persons and communities, which are in turn co-effected by place.

On the whole, the relational logic which I have described throughout this work is not one between just two persons, or a person and their community, it is a logic employed to understand the creative event of life – from person to amoeba – and how that creativity manifests itself in community – whether a community of persons or a community of organisms. Importantly, and harkening Bergson's warnings, we cannot mistake this logic as *the principle by which life happens and establishes meaning*; that would be mistaking the language employed for the principle itself. Rather, I merely find that a relational logic better hermeneutically describes these happenings while also being self-suspicious that it is mere description. It is not nature itself, it is a way to better understand how nature is happening, and how we are happening within it (both personally and collectively).

There are other ways to describe how a person becomes a person, especially within African philosophy. One could easily gather this from just a thorough reading of Wiredu. However, the means by which I described this becoming – and the interlocutors I chose – helped me better understand the relationality at play and why this relationality matters. As I often have said throughout this work, aspects such as historicity often become merely a framework for hermeneutics, therefore rendering into mere context the environments/places where understanding happens. This severs the historical-memorial meanings which are sedimented into the places where events happen, only to be recollected when necessary and not fully analyzed unto themselves.

If we rather see these three components as relational to each other – both internally through an intellectual mechanics by which we describe persons, communities, and place, and externally by the way in which all three engage each other – then we may possibly uncover new sites of truth or understanding. We may find more emancipator fusions of horizons that Serequeberhan advocates for seeking. A more open negotiation between persons and communities, as well as between different communities, which Wiredu sought to conceptualize. A stronger sense of the creative mobility of life and its possibilities, which Bergson sought to reveal through his *duration* and *elan vital*.

3. The Possibility of a Relational Hermeneutic Phenomenology

The development of what I call a relational hermeneutic phenomenology came to me as I was working on various decolonial and African philosophical projects. However, as mentioned in my Introduction to this work, this work is not a ‘decolonial’ nor ‘African philosophy’ project. Rather, it takes these philosophies seriously in pursuit of understanding meaning-making within one’s world. While employing the concepts from these philosophies, I came across multiple possibilities or ways in which they could contribute to the development of the hermeneutic phenomenological method. Rather than trying to ‘clear away and present’ a new hermeneutic phenomenology, which I think is both irresponsible and would be unwieldy, I settled upon the locution of a ‘relational hermeneutic phenomenology’ to give it some distinction while also showing its relationship to extant hermeneutic phenomenological methods. Doing this allowed me to articulate two core principles that I think may provide a conceptual foundation for future analysis: relational logic and the fact that a phenomenology’s schematic framework does not need to be binary or dialectical. Although there are hermeneutic phenomenologists who employ either concept within their work, I thought that presenting them together in a methodological process might yield new possibilities for the field. Therefore, in what follows, I will detail these two core principles, which shed light upon what a possible relational hermeneutic phenomenology might look like.

The core principle of my thesis is relational logic and its emphasis on becoming. Before moving forward, it is important to repeat that ‘becoming’ does not imply progress; becoming could be ‘good’ or ‘bad’ for a person, community, or place. As Bergson reiterates throughout *Creative Evolution*, some species die due to their adaptations, and evolution is not a

mechanistic or finalist process. As such, I found that a relational logic allows us to better analyze how meaning/understanding is created through the relational event between the perceiver and what they are perceiving. Whether that perceptual event is between persons, the environment, or a collective experiential event, I found that it is crucial to recognize that the perceiver is participating in the event in which they perceive, and thus effecting the event just as much as the event is affecting the perceiver's perception and understanding of what is happening.

Even if this perception is done at a distance, say by reading a historical account of a past event, the perceiver's interpretation of that event comes with the effected-historical consciousness of the perceiver, and the perceiver's reckoning with this past event changes the historical-memorial meaning which is carried through this event. Via *duration*, a perceiver can change – even if it for oneself and privately held – the perception of events past, present, future-present, and in the future.¹⁹

For example, as I am writing this, Jimmy Carter, the former President of the USA, passed away. Jimmy Carter is often known more as a 'failed president' and as the best 'former president' due to his extensive charitable works. However, as I am writing this, journalists, communities, and individual persons are reconsidering the achievements of Carter's presidency with the hindsight of history. The fact that he installed solar panels on the roof of the White House is now more relevant to the world's climate crisis. The same goes for other acts of legislation and governance that he implemented. Now, many are stating that Carter was '*ahead of his time*' and was 'right' about many things that were covered and ignored by future presidents and within USA politics at large. For instance, Ronald Reagan immediately removed those solar panels when moving into the White House, which likewise informs (or, in some cases, re-affirms) persons' and communities' esteem of Reagan's character and his presidency.

This example underscores the importance of relationality, particularly when it comes to memory and perception. This, I find, may be fruitful to hermeneutic phenomenology since it further entrenches the method within a historical-memorial awareness. Furthermore, this relationality (as seen within my reading of Wiredu) opens hermeneutic phenomenology to critically questioning who defines this awareness; again, *in whose in medias res are we*

¹⁹ See: Chapter Five, pp. 101-103, 109, 113, 121.

thinking? Obviously, this can be done with a healthy dose of a hermeneutics of suspicion by the phenomenologist, a Ricoeurian *d'où parlez vous?* However, I think that a relational logic presses further than an acknowledgement of one's biases created by one's historical-cultural situatedness. It does so by recognizing that *analysis is participation within the event being analyzed.*

As seen in the conversation between Serequeberhan and Bergson, analysis brings the memory of the event to the fore, into the phenomenologist's own *duration* and its memory, and the way in which that analysis is done is culturally and epistemologically en-framed.²⁰ Whatever the outcome is, the phenomenologist's study highlights, emphasizes, ignores, contextualizes, and/or reveals certain ideas or concepts which link to existing studies of what is being analyzed. Or, what one is analyzing reveals these aspects which are then linked to concepts which have been analyzed by others, perhaps showing how they are interrelated or how the phenomenologist's analysis addresses a lacuna within their field's body of scholarship. Either way, it is a historical-memorial recounting of the event that heralds participation with the event in question, its reception, its abstract conceptualization performed by others, and the analysis performed by the phenomenologist in question. This puts the phenomenologist in the *accusative*, or under scrutiny, just as much as the phenomenologist scrutinizes the event in question. This is because the phenomenologist is inserting themselves into a relationship between the event as it happened, was received, was previously analyzed, and is currently being analyzed by said phenomenologist along with their historical-memorial situatedness.

As such, many binary paradigms used within phenomenology may become overdetermined – meaning, overburdened – when taking up this relationality. This is where I think that the second core principle of this study becomes important: the acknowledgement that not every hermeneutic phenomenological analysis can be done through dualistic or binary constructs. Constructs such as 'the self and other,' 'immanent and transcendent,' or 'thesis and antithesis' have their place within phenomenology – I am in no way trying to rid us of them – it is just that *they are not the only way to do phenomenology.* This is especially true with non-Western cultures and their metaphysics, which I showed through Wiredu's empiricism and

²⁰ See: Chapter Nine, pp. 218-221.

its metaphysics.²¹ The phenomenologist may lose critical aspects of the event in question or the given perceiver within the study by trying to shoe-horn their study into a typical hermeneutic phenomenological method.

Yet this is not germane to just only non-Western perspectives and employing a relational logic through a tripartite schema of person, community, and place may yield strong results for Western culturally laden events as well. Acknowledging the relationality between the perceiver becoming a 'person' – with all the complexities that the term denotes, which may get missed by the abstracted concept of 'the self' – and how this influences their perception of an event happening within a place and amongst a community (or another person) may disclose new understandings within Western culture and its epistemological meaningfulness. 'New,' here, may not mean better, but these differences could prove crucial to further analysis.

Finally, this co-effected relationality still requires concepts to be analyzed. This is why I have presented the tripartite concepts of person, community, and place: each concept is complex on its own, but exploring their interrelated and developmental relationship with the other corresponding concepts can unpack or establish a presuppositional baseline for analysis. By seeing each concept *in circumincession* with each other – that is, in co-existence and interrelation to each other – the phenomenologist may better understand what they wish to study, thereby creating better research questions and thus better theses to address these questions. Or perhaps 'different' is more appropriate since there is a Serequeberhanian or Gadamerian risk involved here: a new horizon of possibilities does not entail a better horizon, merely a new vantage point and region to investigate.

We will not know if it is a viable alternative until it has been investigated, though. This is why I propose that my thesis contributes to the development of a relational hermeneutics: by exploring this tripartite relationship, I sought to understand how becoming happens through interactions within time and space, and how the memory of past events (or 'becomings') influences this happening. Furthermore, how this happening's eventual remembrance will influence future becomings as they happen (i.e., a future-past which intellectually influences and furthers development).

²¹ See: Chapter Four, pp. 81-83, 85-87, 91.

It is, at this stage, merely a gesture towards a new means of hermeneutic phenomenological analysis. I have sought to understand the mechanics of this new approach through this work by, interestingly, not describing it but performing it throughout arguing my intended thesis. I did not want to define its operation; I wanted to see its performance through interweaving conversations between disparate thinkers. In a way, I did not fully recognize what type of phenomenology a relational hermeneutic phenomenology would be until I began undertaking these conversations, and in so doing, realizing the core principles of relationality and paradigmatic frameworks described above. It has a way to go in its becoming, and I hope that this work inspires others to take up this project and critically analyze the possibilities and limitations of a relational hermeneutic phenomenology.

4. An Open Conclusion: The Future of Relational Hermeneutic Phenomenology

This work presents both a thesis and the implications of that thesis towards an entire methodology (or field of research, even). It, therefore, raises multiple questions for future research. As I have pointed out throughout this work, there are various possible avenues for future research. In what follows, I will highlight two broader research themes which may guide our understanding of the relationship between persons, communities, and places, as well as a possible relational hermeneutic phenomenology. Those themes are the creation of places and the role of the analyst.

Concerning the creation of places, Malpas, Janz, and Olivier may query whether my ‘another pathway’ to understanding placiality is actually another pathway. I might be taking different steps along that pathway, they may argue, but it is still the same route. I completely understand this when considering placiality as a concept unto itself. However, my contribution was primarily linking ‘placehood’ to the persons and communities which engage or create places. My main goal was to establish placiality as co-effected and relational to persons and communities. Yet still, the question remains about whether placiality – or places, in general – have any agency; they may not be thinking things with their own subjectivity, but do they have any sense of influence that is created by the place itself? If not, then does that consequently mean that places are context within the person-community or self-other paradigm? In short, if they have no agency, then why give placiality such a crucial role within my phenomenological schematic?

My answer to this possible critique is that places are continually becoming or developing as species – human and otherwise – along with the environment influences them. They are the bedrock of what Serequeberhan calls the historical sedimented layering of meaning.²² They carry with them meanings and possibilities before species even enter these places, and they will carry meaning long after said species leaves those places. This is what makes geology, geography, and anthropology (meaning, the academic field, not the concept) important to humanity's growing body of knowledge. These sciences, along with theoretical physics and other scientific explorations of matter and life, disclose to us the creation of these places and also the events which created their particular characteristics.²³ One can think of these events and their creation of characteristics as 'impressions' onto the place – such as glaciers impressing upon the ground to create mountains, plains, or rivers – which happen long before and during life living in this place. Furthermore, the life which has lived, is currently living, or will live in a given place leaves further impressions – both physical and memorial – since this life engages and changes this environment.

Although humans are the best examples of this, one can think of how the development of photosynthesis allowed organisms like algae to bloom within bodies of water, and how this impressed upon this body of water a host of environmental changes. From this, other species may have developed in concert with this body of water (and other bodies of water) to feed off of this algae, further impressing upon the identity of this body and also creating future conditions for others to engage it.

However, this is still a body of water reacting to life as it engages it. This may call into question whether the body of water, as a place, is still a 'non-agent.' This may be because it does not consent to these changes; it merely is changed. Perhaps this is where Bergson's articulation of the relationship between life and matter could play a role, where matter is considered stored or potential energy with which living organisms engage in procuring said energy.²⁴ This might be the answer to the agency question, or it may yield new perspectives to the question itself. Furthermore, engaging posthumanist and ecophilosophical approaches will be

²² See: Chapter Nine, pp. 210, 217-220, 240.

²³ See: Chapter Nine, pp. 223-226.

²⁴ See: Chapter Five, pp. 111-112; Chapter Eight, pp. 183-185, 191-193; Chapter Nine, pp. 223-227.

necessary to fully flesh out the agency of place within its relationship to persons and communities.

That being said, I think that Bergson's *elan vital* and its engagement with Serequeberhan's concept of heritage is a very strong starting point to being this engagement with other approaches and methods. Bergson and Serequeberhan, as I have shown, establish a foundational relationship between places, persons, and communities, and one should note from Chapter Three that agency (and therefore responsibility, duty, morality, or other forms of compelling choice) is relationally dependent. Within Chapter Three, I discussed this dependency between persons and communities. Even though I find that Chapters Seven through Nine lay a foundation for discussing this relationally dependent agency when it comes to place, I think that further research might build off of this foundation to solidify placial thinking within the tripartite network of personhood, community, and placiality.

The possible outcome of exploring Bergson's *elan vital* and his understanding of life and matter may push us to reconsider the primacy of agency, thereby taking philosophy into further dialogue with physics.²⁵ Similarly, it could reveal to us that placiality does not need agency to 'justify' its co-effected and relational place amongst personhood and community; given that places have such a historical, memorial, and concrete impact on our understanding of personhood and community, they must be hermeneutically considered as an entity unto itself in the meaning-making process which phenomenology seeks to analyze. It could also be a dead-end and perhaps another thinker not mentioned in this work has a stronger sense of the notion of placiality and its importance to meaning-making. Regardless, it is an open question that invites exploration.

The second broad theme that I see as an avenue for future research is the role of the researcher or analyst. For if the analyst – here, the phenomenologist – brings their own historical-memorial situatedness to their research, are they not a 'fourth' part of this relational hermeneutic phenomenology? As I covered, Olivier's 'exterophenomenology' takes this into account, and his findings need further scrutiny of my thesis and my proposed

²⁵ I think that James Difrisco's work may be a good entry point for this research, see: "*Elan Vital Revisited*."

method. Olivier recognizes that observation and critical reflection thereof changes the meaning of a given place, community, and the persons within them.²⁶

Although I think that this analysis does change the meaning of these entities – either internally if they are received by the community and persons or externally by both those reading about these entities without contact with them – I think that analysis inserts the phenomenologist into the community. Perhaps this insertion is welcomed, perhaps not, but I think that it is an engagement made possible through what Wiredu calls the translatability between particular cultures, which allows for engagement. The phenomenologist may also insert themselves as the ‘person’ within this relational paradigm, thereby giving a somewhat ethnographic phenomenological account within their analysis.

Either way, the role that the phenomenologist plays within a communal understanding cannot be ignored. This is especially the case for historically marginalized communities, as seen by the historic denial of Africans’ capacity to reason and do philosophy, which I covered throughout this work. In this scenario, European philosophers such as Kant, Hegel, and even Levinas (!) delegitimize non-Western thought, and there is an ongoing concern that further Western engagements with African philosophy (or any non-European philosophy) may give rise to neo-colonialism. I covered this in my Introduction and through exploring what Etieyibo calls “Western Universalism,” and it remains an ongoing concern.²⁷ I can only address this question given that the matter is not only unsettled but remains a massive threat to the future of philosophy writ large. I find that further decolonial research may yield the best answers to this question of the role of the analyst, but I think that we limit ourselves if we place this onus just on decolonial thinking. Rather, it will take the entire philosophical community – with all its fields, subfields, and adjacent niches – to completely reckon with the impacting legacies of prior analysis – especially colonial and racist analysis on non-European cultures – while also shaping the future meaning of what it means to be an analyst. In this shaping, the philosophical community will have to address what is the analyst’s purpose to meaning-making and understanding.

²⁶ See: Chapter Nine, pp. 216.

²⁷ See: Introduction, pp. viii-ix; Chapter Two, pp. 30-32; Chapter Three, pp. 50-52; Chapter Four, p. 73.

I do not anticipate a comprehensive answer to this question. In fact, I think one could argue that it traces its genealogy throughout what we call philosophy's history – however philosophy is defined or culturally construed – and it is one of the persistent questions insisting upon thinkers to take responsibility for their findings and arguments. It is my hope that this book has contributed to this development in some way. Its particular description of the relational becoming of persons, communities, and places contributes to the meaning of these concepts while, in turn, questions how the definitions of these meanings which I have made might influence these entities' future development. I must take responsibility and be held accountable as much as others in this degree. And it is also my hope that my proposal for a relational hermeneutic phenomenology may allow us to help take responsibility for our claims while also crafting possible accounts to meaning-making heretofore covered, undisclosed, or unacknowledged.

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